

D6.2 Assessing emerging ELOQUENCE
technology: Report approved by the ELOQUENCE
Community on assessing project outputs as to
respecting EU values, with particular emphasis
on gender, cultural or racial biases

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Abstract	<p>This report emphasises mixed expertise insights and a deliberative process in assessing AI's alignment with EU values, including human rights. It advocates for iterative, adaptable methodologies that integrate empirical evidence and expert assessment, especially on nuanced issues such as privacy, protection of personal data and non-discrimination. Transparency and inclusiveness of the process are key to its credibility, with diverse stakeholders contributing to assessment. The report paves the way for the next phase of incorporating survey data, to enhance understanding of stakeholder impact and experience, underlining the necessity for exhaustive and context-aware assessments in the responsible development of AI applications within ELOQUENCE.</p>		

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Table of Contents

1	EXECUTIVE SUMMARY	7
2	INTRODUCTION.....	8
3	HUMAN RIGHTS ASSESSMENT AS A METHODOLOGY.....	9
3.1	TRADITIONAL INTERNATIONAL HUMAN RIGHTS LAW ASSESSMENTS	9
3.1.1	<i>Multimember expert assessment panels.....</i>	9
3.1.2	<i>Human Rights Indicators</i>	9
3.1.3	<i>Structured Assessments of Permissible Limitations or Positive Obligations</i>	10
3.2	SURVEYS IN SUPPORT OF HUMAN RIGHTS ASSESSMENT.....	12
3.3	FUNDAMENTAL RIGHTS ASSESSMENT WITHIN THE MEANING OF THE EU AI ACT.....	12
4	EXPERIENCE WITH AND FURTHER DEVELOPMENT OF THE ELOQUENCE EU VALUES ASSESSMENTS	14
4.1	REPORT OF ASSESSMENTS COMPLETED.....	14
4.1.1	<i>Pilot 1: Privacy-Preserving Language Model Learning through Decentralized Training in Smart Homes and Partner Institutions.....</i>	15
4.1.2	<i>Pilot 2: Social Context-aware Language Model Detecting Biases.....</i>	16
4.1.3	<i>Pilot 3: Retrieval-Augmented LLMs as Virtual Agents, Capable of Understanding the User’s Goals, Making API calls and Respond with Empathy</i>	17
4.1.4	<i>Pilot 4 Upgrading Support Call Centres through AI-based Supervision of Multimodal Dialogues.....</i>	18
4.2	REPORT ON FEEDBACK RECEIVED FROM THE SUBMITTING PARTNERS	19
4.3	EVOLUTION OF THE ELOQUENCE WP6 ASSESSMENT METHODOLOGY.....	20
4.4	FUTURE PLANS.....	21
5	SUBSTANTIVE ISSUES EMERGING FROM WP6 ASSESSMENTS OF ELOQUENCE TECHNOLOGIES	22
5.1	CAN LLM’S BE SAID TO ‘STORE’ PERSONAL DATA WITHIN THE MEANING OF GDPR?	22
5.2	RECONCILING BIAS MITIGATION AND THE PROTECTION OF PERSONAL DATA.....	26
6	CONCLUSIONS.....	29
7	REFERENCES.....	30
8	ANNEXES	31
8.1	NDA.....	31
8.2	FEEDBACK FORMS FROM THE SUBMITTING PARTNERS	33
8.2.1	<i>V02001</i>	33
8.2.2	<i>V02002</i>	35
8.2.3	<i>V02003</i>	36
8.2.4	<i>V02004.....</i>	37
8.3	ASSESSMENT TEMPLATES:	37
8.3.1	<i>V2 which was Used for the First Four Assessments.....</i>	37
8.3.2	<i>V3 which Will be Used for Future Assessments.....</i>	37
8.3.3	<i>Consensus Reports for All Four Assessments Undertaken.....</i>	37

List of tables

Table 1: Assessments, dates and panel members.	14
Table 2: Engagement of partners in assessment panels.....	15

ABBREVIATIONS AND ACRONYMS

AI	Artificial Intelligence
CJEU	European Court of Justice
DFLA	Distributed Federated Learning architecture
ECHR	European Convention on Human Rights
ECoE	ELOQUENCE Community of Experts
EDPB	European Data Protection Board
EU	European Union
EUCFR	EU Charter of Fundamental Rights
FRIA	Fundamental Rights Impact Assessments
FRIA	Fundamental Rights Impact assessment
GDPR	General Data Protection Regulation
HCDPIF	Hamburg Commissioner for Data Protection and Freedom of Information
IP	Interactive Playground
NDA	Non-disclosure agreement
PII	Personal identifiable information
RAG	Retrieval-Augmented Generation
TRL	Technological Readiness Level

1 Executive Summary

This report presents the findings and lessons learned from the ELOQUENCE Consortium’s comprehensive human rights assessment of emerging technologies. The assessment process is iterative in nature, and grounded in a multidisciplinary approach, integrating expert panels, structured indicators, and empirical data to evaluate the impact of emerging ELOQUENCE AI technologies in relation to core EU values, including fundamental and human rights.

A central insight is the importance of combining expert judgment with standardized methodologies. While empirical indicators provide objectivity, expert deliberation ensures that complex issues—such as the interplay between data protection and non-discrimination—are addressed with necessary nuance and, when pertinent, reconciliation of different perspectives. The methodology has evolved through feedback and comparative research, demonstrating the value of adaptability in assessment frameworks.

The report highlights the critical role of transparency and inclusivity throughout the assessment process. Engaging diverse stakeholder categories not only strengthens the credibility of the findings but also helps to identify and address potential blind spots. As regulatory environments continue to evolve—notably with the ongoing operationalisation of the EU AI Act—the need for flexible and responsive assessment practices becomes increasingly apparent.

Looking ahead, the planned integration of survey data with the assessment process will further enrich the project’s understanding of stakeholder perspectives and societal impacts. Overall, this report underscores the ongoing importance of rigorous, context-sensitive human rights and European values assessments as a foundation for responsible technological innovation in Europe.

2 Introduction

Since the publication of ELOQUENCE deliverable D6.1 there have been two important developments. The first is that within ELOQUENCE itself we have now carried out, in Work Package 6, four successful assessments of emerging technology based on the project's four pilots. The second is in relation to regulation, as the European Union (EU) Artificial Intelligence (AI) Act came into force in August 2024. The latter development means that we have clearer understanding of the requirements and procedures provided for by the EU AI Act, while the first-mentioned development means that we know more about how technological design choices interact with EU values and human rights concerns.

Alongside the assessments, WP6 has been conducting desk research into substantive questions that have emerged during the assessments of ELOQUENCE technology, and work is ongoing towards the launch of target group surveys for the study of perceptions of AI technology of the type being developed in ELOQUENCE. The results of those surveys will be presented in D6.3. Final report D6.4 will then bring together all WP6 work.

The report continues as follows: Section 3 contains reflections on human rights assessments as a methodology for determining compliance with EU values, including choices made in the set-up of the ELOQUENCE assessment panels. Section 4 contains a report of the experience with the first four assessments carried out by the multimember panels set up by the ELOQUENCE project, including reports on feedback from the partners who submitted technology for assessment and the evolution of the assessment methodology. Section 5 contains a brief analysis of two substantive issues that emerged in the assessment of ELOQUENCE technology, namely the question of whether LLMs store personal data within the meaning of the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR) and how to reconcile the right to privacy and non-discrimination in situations where technology requires information on sensitive user characteristics such as gender, ethnicity or age in order to mitigate discrimination based on such characteristics. Section 6 concludes. Section 7 contains references while section 8 includes as annexes: the NDA signed by external assessors, the feedback sheets filled in by the submitting partners, the questionnaire as used in the first round of assessments, the new questionnaire which will be used in future assessments, all four consensus reports delivered to submitting partners.

3 Human Rights Assessment as a Methodology

The methodology for assessing emerging ELOQUENCE technology is based on well-established practices in human (and fundamental) rights assessment methodologies developed at the United Nations level including multimember assessment panels and the use of human rights indicators. These have further been developed in previous projects on surveillance technology and the handling of the COVID-19 pandemic, involving the authors of this report. The following section describes how these methods have been adapted for use in the ELOQUENCE project.

3.1 *Traditional International Human Rights Law Assessments*

3.1.1 Multimember expert assessment panels

The normative framework of international human rights was consolidated and adopted by the United Nations General Assembly in the form of the 1948 Universal Declaration of Human Rights. Since then, a large number of legally binding international treaties have been made to further develop those rights and, perhaps even more importantly, to establish mechanisms for the assessment of compliance with human rights through independent expert bodies established at international level. By now, there are regional human rights courts in Europe, the Americas and Africa that apply a judicial procedure and issue legally binding judgments. More often, the monitoring bodies are called ‘committees’, ‘commissions’ or ‘treaty bodies’ and are quasi-judicial in nature. This means that they consist of independent experts, follow a fair procedure and exercise a primarily interpretive function when determining whether an action or omission by a state was in conformity with its human rights obligations or constituted a human rights violation. Be they courts or expert committees, all these monitoring bodies, here jointly called ‘assessment panels’, look into issues of fact, including empirical data, as well as into issues of law when assessing a country’s conduct in a specific case (individual complaints) or at a general level (periodic reports). Some regional or international courts, even if they have a wider mandate than one limited to human rights issues, may exercise the same function of assessing compliance with human rights or, as they are called in the context of the European Union, fundamental rights.

Multimember expert assessment panels are therefore a traditional model of human rights assessment. Their benefits include independence, expertise, fair procedures that secure the utilisation of data and other factual information as well as legal arguments, deliberation between individual expert members in an effort to reach consensus or at least a majority, as well as a gradually accumulating institutionalised practice of interpretation that allows placing a new ‘case’ into the framework of all earlier assessments. While expert bodies constituted as international or regional courts primarily or exclusively represent legal expertise, other expert bodies (‘committees’, ‘commissions’ or ‘treaty bodies’) routinely also include members from other disciplines or fields of life.

In ELOQUENCE, the five-member panels conducting, within WP6 of the project, assessments of emerging ELOQUENCE technologies for their compliance with EU values emulate the decades-long experience of and lessons from human rights assessment through expert bodies. The EUI team, leading WP6 and its work on assessments, has considerable practical and academic expertise in the field.

3.1.2 Human Rights Indicators

Between 2005 and 2012, the Office of the United Nations High Commissioner for Human Rights ran an ambitious project on human rights indicators, directly for the benefit of the United Nations human rights treaty bodies, i.e., a category of multimember expert panels discussed above in section 3.1.1, to conceptualise, consolidate and operationalise better use of empirical data in human rights assessment. The project, culminating in a book published in 2012,¹ came to represent a new phase in human rights assessment, with significance also beyond the UN human rights treaty bodies, due to its comprehensive and rigorous approach. The indicators include yes/no

¹ Human Rights Indicators: A Guide to Measurement and Implementation, United Nations 2012. Professor Martin Scheinin, leader of the EUI team and of WP6 in ELOQUENCE, served as the chairperson of consultations that resulted in the Guide.

questions such as whether a state had ratified specific treaties, as well as more qualitative evaluations such as whether it has adopted plans for action to protect and promote specific human rights. While the indicators were developed for the assessing of states, a similar approach can be developed for the assessment of companies or teams' ambitions in securing human rights compliance of their products.

To illustrate the level of ambition of the indicators project, it should be mentioned that the book ('the Guide') includes 14 tables of indicators found suitable for assessing compliance with a large proportion of all human rights enshrined in the Universal Declaration of Human Rights, including the prohibition against discrimination (p. 100) and specific rights from amongst civil and political rights (p. 88, 91, 92, 97-99, 101) and from amongst economic, social and cultural rights (p. 89, 90, 93-96). The tables apply the methodological framework presented in the Guide of relying on three types of indicators (structure, process and outcome indicators) which are identified in respect of all main substantive aspects (attributes) of each human right under consideration. One indicator table may contain, for example, 45 indicators, many of which represent well-established categories of available statistical data.

A foundational insight behind the indicators project was that empirical data, no matter how well standardised, collected and analysed, cannot replace the need for expert assessment, preferably by multi-member panels with mixed expertise and a deliberative framework. Human rights indicators are, as the very term suggests, indicative of possible compliance or non-compliance, and at best can be relied upon as presumptions or rules of thumb in the overall assessment by a mixed group of experts. The complex indicator tables for each right were not intended as a straitjacket of an all-or-nothing approach but, rather, as a demonstration of the multitude of factors that may, depending on the availability of reliable data, be relied upon as the factual basis for deliberation and expert assessment.

3.1.3 Structured Assessments of Permissible Limitations or Positive Obligations

While human rights indicators, as developed in the Guide, provide one important structural framework for assessing human rights compliance and thereby assist also ELOQUENCE WP6 assessments, existing practice of human rights assessments also provides examples of other conceptual tools and frameworks. Two earlier projects worth mentioning, where members of the EUI team in ELOQUENCE have been involved, are EU Commission Framework Seven project SURVEILLE (2012-2015) and an internally funded EUI project on the human rights compatibility of strategies against COVID-19 (2020-2021).

In SURVEILLE,² parallel expert teams representing ethics, law (human rights) and security (technology, utility and cost-efficiency) assessed a range of surveillance technologies for the purpose of determining whether each of them could be used in the combat of terrorism and other crimes, and in what kind of situations. The methodologies for each of the three panels were different. While the ethicists used a traffic-light model (red, yellow, green), the technologists and other security experts used a fine-tuned scoresheet of 20 factors, each worth half a point, and the lawyers sought to measure the attribute and depth of ensuing human rights harm through the multiplication of two separate values assigned by consensus by an expert panel. Among the insights resulting from the project were that

- 1) the security experts were able to deal with highly granular information to come up with a numerical utility score for the use of a specific surveillance technology in a specific situation,
- 2) the ethics assessment identified issues that needed to be considered, rather than clear-cut numbers or yes/no answers, thereby also assisting a dialogue between the law and technology panels,
- 3) the human rights assessments demonstrated the centrality of the right to privacy and the right to the protection personal data in assessing the permissibility of surveillance, so that other human rights harms,

² Surveillance: ethical issues, legal limitations, and efficiency (FP-SE-C2011-284725). See, in particular, SURVEILLE Deliverable D4.10, 'Synthesis report from WP4, merging the ethics and law analysis and discussing their outcomes'; SURVEILLE Deliverable D3.9, Final report of WP3' and 'SURVEILLE Briefing Note'; all available through <https://surveillance.eui.eu>

such as discrimination, could be assessed within the framework of comprehensive privacy and data protection assessment,

4) the methodological framework could be designed so that the numerical scales used for the security assessment (0 to 10) and the human rights assessment (0 to 16) reflected the idea that no ‘balancing’ between security and rights can justify human rights intrusions into the inviolable essential core of a human right, and

5) where that essential core was not at issue, a crucial role remained for a structured proportionality assessment, not between two competing abstract values (e.g., privacy and security) but between the proven and assessed benefit delivered towards increased security and the degree of the proven and assessed human rights harm.

In a resolution of 29 October 2015, the European Parliament commended the SURVEILLE project “which offers a methodology for assessing surveillance technologies taking legal, ethical and technological considerations into account”.³

While the SURVEILLE project, due to the subject-matter under study (surveillance), focused on privacy and other civil and political rights and the negative state obligation not to violate those rights, a broader framing, akin to the OHCHR indicators project, was adopted in the 2020-2021 EUI study on compliance with human rights of different countries’ strategies against COVID-19.⁴ Relying on the experiences and results of the indicators project and of SURVEILLE, the project was based on the ambition of needing to assess all aspects or all human rights of all members of society, for the assessment of whether a country’s strategy was in conformity with human rights. The methodology developed was based on the idea of four separate ‘baskets’, each with different methods of basket-internal numerical scoring but then a common framework where all four baskets had equal weight (25%). A strategy would be human-rights-conforming only if it obtained a passing score (50%) from every one of the four baskets. If so, its final grade was the average of the scores from the four baskets. The four baskets were:

- 1) The right to life and economic, social and cultural rights, with its scoring seeking to measure and quantify compliance with positive human rights obligations to deliver effective enjoyment of the rights,
- 2) Civil and political rights, focusing on negative human rights obligations and any restrictions imposed during the height of COVID-19, the scoring being based on the structured permissibility test developed in SURVEILLE,
- 3) Equality and non-discrimination, using human rights indicators and other available data to measure and quantify the impact of COVID-19 strategies in respect of a) vulnerable groups, b) gender issues and c) instances of arbitrariness, and
- 4) Rule of law, the assessment here being based primarily on qualitative data on emergency powers, the requirement of a legal basis for measures and access to justice and effective remedies.

The project managed to develop a coherent and comprehensive framework for the assessment of human rights compliance on a nationwide or strategic level. The framework was tested through a pilot study which did demonstrate its capacity for marking and grading countries. While being able to demonstrate the utility of the methodology, the value of country comparisons through the pilot study was, however, limited by a short specific period of time under assessment (second half of 2020) and in most cases reliance on individual country rapporteurs instead of the proven gold standard of multi-member expert panels.⁵

³ European Parliament resolution of 29 October 2015 on the follow-up to the European Parliament resolution of 12 March 2014 on the electronic mass surveillance of EU citizens (2015/2635(RSP), paragraph 28. <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?uri=CELEX%3A52015IP0388>

⁴ Martin Scheinin and Helga Molbæk-Steensig, Pandemics and Human Rights: Three perspectives on human rights assessment of strategies against COVID-19. EUI Working Papers, Law 2021/01 <https://cadmus.eui.eu/server/api/core/bitstreams/0031c9bd-4ce7-5024-a7b2-bed52df89418/content>

⁵ Martin Scheinin, Health Resilience Requires Rigorous Human Rights Assessment, EUI School of Transnational Governance, Resilience Papers

3.2 Surveys in Support of Human Rights Assessment

There is no water-tight separation between an actual human rights violation and a person's experience of a human rights violation, because such experiences in themselves may constitute human rights harm, for instance affecting people's private life, health or sense of dignity. Stating this, however, does not mean that human rights compliance could be reduced to subjective feelings, or relativised by referring to the fact that often different people's experiences differ. Instead, people's experiences, systematically collected through surveys amongst the whole population or segments of it, such as target groups identified as potentially vulnerable to human rights harm, may legitimately be used side-by-side with other sources as indicators of compliance or non-compliance, as a complement to other sources of information and preceding expert assessment. Here, 'human rights harm' was used as a generic term that covers for instance discrimination, severe restrictions upon liberties or non-enjoyment of economic, social or cultural rights.

For example, in the OHCHR project on human rights indicators presented in section 3.1.2 above,⁶ survey results came to have an acknowledged and even important role among human rights indicators, but always as one category of data among many. Surveys were acknowledged as "often essential" for comprehensive human rights assessment (p. 60), with a particular place in the sequence of compiling the information, namely between other ("objective") sources of information and expert assessment (p. 52) and with clear comparative merits (p. 64) in respect of other sources. The resulting Guide has a specific summary section on the use of perception and opinion surveys as human rights indicators (p. 65), and the indicator charts for each human right developed in the project contain several instances where survey data is identified as a good indicator, more specifically a process indicator for a specific attribute or aspect of a human right (such as security, accessibility, victimisation, violence or discrimination, see pp. 88, 90, 98, 99 and 100).

There is, of course, no linear relationship between survey results and the assessment of how widespread or how severe a human rights problem is. For instance, a low number of responses by persons who have been detained by the police who then report experiencing ill-treatment, may in some situations be indicative of there not being a major problem in the country, but may in another situation suggest that persons who were in such detention may fear reprisals. Surveys must be conducted in a professional manner to be used as indicators, and even then, their results must be combined with other indicators and data. The OHCHR Guide does exactly this, by placing surveys within a structured framework of various sources of data, usually with a specific role.

In ELOQUENCE, task T6.3 is producing assessments of societal acceptance and acceptability of key AI technologies through participatory surveys, giving particular attention to the types of AI being developed in ELOQUENCE. In addition to a literature survey, this line of work collects users' insights regarding their level of awareness, acceptance and perceived benefits or risks related with ELOQUENCE technologies, perceived implications of their use and users' level of engagement, motivation, societal needs and ethical concerns. The emerging output, to be reported in D6.3, will include specific indicators of the social acceptance levels. When designing and performing the surveys, particular attention has been paid to six target groups, namely persons identifying themselves as 1) women, 2) persons of African descent, 3) non-nationals in their country of residence, 4) persons supporting SOGI/LGBTI rights, 5) persons with a disability and 6) elderly persons. The survey design allows a person to identify themselves as belonging to more than one of these target groups.

3.3 Fundamental Rights Assessment within the Meaning of the EU AI Act

The EU AI Act places a number of obligations on deployers of high risk AI systems.⁷ These obligations include: assigning human oversight, monitoring and logging potentially problematic incidents, registering systems in an EU database and informing individuals who will be subjects of or working with the system about it.⁸ For systems where

https://47ef41f2-be4f-4426-80c9-35abcb384d23.filesusr.com/ugd/6a28e0_51c6b106336b4149bf9242d42199e631.pdf

⁶ See footnote 1, above.

⁷ For an account of the EU AI Act's risk categorisation see ELOQUENCE deliverable D6.1.

⁸ EU AI Act (2024) Article 26.

the deployer is a public entity or a private entity providing a public service, there is an additional requirement to perform a Fundamental Rights Impact Assessment (FRIA),⁹ which is not dissimilar to the exercise developed by the ELOQUENCE team to ensure compliance with EU values.

The EU AI Office is tasked with developing a template for a questionnaire including an automated tool for facilitating FRIAs, but neither is available yet. For ELOQUENCE technology, the only pilot that would potentially need to conduct a FRIA under EU law, is Pilot 4, the system for making the best use of the waiting time in a call centre for parents of newborns which would record symptoms of the patients and relay them to the human operators in writing. A FRIA would be required if the call centre was hosted by a public body – which is not a given. The remainder of the pilots are at least initially either intended to be used internally in ELOQUENCE, such as Pilot 2 which is a bias detection tool, or Pilot 3 which is an interactive playground for accessing ELOQUENCE technology, or intended for private use, such as Pilot 1 which is a smart home assistant and federated learning architecture. One could however imagine a scenario in which technology from Pilot 1 could be developed with the goal of utilisation by a public deployer as well. For example, accurate transcription as well as sophisticated RAG based on previous transcriptions could be useful in police or hospital settings or in public administrations. Should that be the case, that technology too would be subject to the FRIA.

The FRIA questionnaire will likely touch on the requirements of high risk AI as described in Articles 8 through 15 in the EU AI Act, but it is intended to go beyond that, taking into account potential negative impact on a range of rights. In many ways the assessment methodology and questionnaire developed in ELOQUENCE is a prediction of the kinds of questions the FRIA questionnaire is likely to include. Nonetheless we should anticipate that the FRIA will likely encompass a series of other rights that mainly come into play when systems are used by public bodies, such as access to justice and the right to a fair trial, freedom of expression, right to free elections and democracy, right to property, as well as a range of social and economic rights including, but not limited to the right to health, right to water and housing etc. It is an ambition in ELOQUENCE WP6 that the assessment methodology developed in ELOQUENCE can become a transferable innovation which could aid the EU AI Office in developing their questionnaire.

⁹ Ibid. Article 27

4 Experience with and Further Development of the ELOQUENCE EU Values Assessments

4.1 Report of Assessments Completed

We have thus far carried out four assessments of emerging ELOQUENCE technology. The first submissions we received were design-documents related to the four pilots produced in ELOQUENCE. We were keen to conduct assessments in the design stage, allowing ELOQUENCE pilots to have fundamental rights and EU values included in their foundations rather than considered as an afterthought. This was overall a positive experience, but also entailed that the first round of assessments was conducted when certain elements of the pilots were yet to be finalised.

The panels each consisted of a person from the submitting partner who was the first to fill in the questionnaire, a panel chair from Work Package 6 (EUI) and three additional panel members. We were keen to include in each panel at least one member with a strong technical background and at least one with a strong legal or ethical background. We were also keen to include both members from the other ELOQUENCE partners who were expected to have knowledge about how the pilot fits together with the rest of the ELOQUENCE project, as well as external members who would provide an outside perspective and potentially be more independent and therefore more critical. In practice, however, our experience was that all members, both external and internal, genuinely engaged with the submissions by the submitting partners, asking critical questions and displaying good understanding of the products assessed. The creation and involvement of the ELOQUENCE Community of Experts (ECoE) was crucial for the contribution made by the assessment panels, as it functions as a roster of external experts with interest in the ELOQUENCE project and with verified expertise. Seven different individuals were recruited for the four panels from amongst the ECoE.

Below is a table providing an overview of which panel members were assigned to which panels.

Table 1: Assessments, dates and panel members.

ID	Submission date	Title	Submitting partner	Panel Members	Finalised
V02001	31.01.2025	Pilot 1	J. Luque, A. Sant (TID)	Helga Molbæk-Steensig(Chair) Alexandre Quemy (ext) Alberto Quintavalla (ext) Farhan Sahito (PN)	12.03.2025
V02002	27.01.2025	Pilot 2	A. Augello (CNR)	Martin Scheinin(Chair) Francesca Palmiotto (ext) Oldřich Plchot (BUT) Holger Nitsch (ext)	7.4.2025
V02003	10.02.2025	Pilot 3	T. Stafylakis, C. Ferles, V.Hudecek (OMI)	Martin Scheinin(Chair) Manuele Portela (ext) Stelios Andreadakis (BUL) Katie Pentney (ext)	7.4.2025
V02004	9.12.2024	Pilot 4	M. Sečujski (UNS)	Helga Molbæk-Steensig(Chair) Natalia Menendez (ext) Andreas Pamboris (GX) Theofanis Orphanoudakis (SYN)	30.1.2025

For Pilot 1 the assessment panel therefore gained technical expertise in the form of Alexandre Quemy who holds a PhD in Machine Learning and has developed and validated large models, while the legal and societal expertise emerged in the form of Farhan Sahito who holds a PhD in cyber security and a master of IT and economics as well

as Alberto Quintavalla who is Co-Director of the Erasmus Centre of Law and Digitalization at the Erasmus University Rotterdam.

For Pilot 2 on the other hand, the legal expertise was provided by Francesca Palmiotto who is an Assistant Professor of Law at IE University, Madrid exploring the intersection of law and technology, while the technical and techno-social expertise was provided by Holger Nitsch, head of research and social science at the Hochschule für den öffentlichen Dienst in Bayern and Oldřich Píchot a senior researcher at Brno University of Technology focused on speech technology.

For Pilot 3 the technical expertise was provided by Manuele Portela who holds a PhD in GeoInformatics and conducts research on algorithmic fairness, responsible AI and data governance. Social and legal expertise was instead provided by Stelios Andreadakis, a Reader in Corporate and Financial Law at Brunel University London and Katie Pentney a PhD Candidate in Law at the University of Oxford focusing new technology, privacy and freedom of information.

For Pilot 4 we engaged the aid of Natalia Menendez a research associate at the European University Institute focusing on the impact of new technologies on the right to privacy, while the technical expertise was provided by Andreas Pamboris who holds a PhD in Computing from Imperial College London and Theofanis Orphanoudakis who is an associate professor and director of the Digital Systems and Media Computing Lab at the Hellenic Open University and researcher with Synelaxis Solutions.

We have generally not had problems recruiting members of our Community of Experts to take part in the assessments as both external members and members from the partners have been forthcoming.

Table 2: Engagement of partners in assessment panels

	TID	CNR	BSC	FBK	UNS	EUI	BUT	PN	INO	TL	GX	OM	SYN	IDIAP	BUL	UEX	ECoE
Pilot 1	1s					1		1									2
Pilot 2		1s				1	1										2
Pilot 3						1						1s			1		2
Pilot 4					1s	1					1		1				1
total	1	1	0	0	1	4	0	1	0	0	1	1	1	0	1	0	7

4.1.1 Pilot 1: Privacy-Preserving Language Model Learning through Decentralized Training in Smart Homes and Partner Institutions

Pilot 1 aims to deliver two different outcomes. One is a **Distributed Federated Learning Architecture (DFLA)** encompassing an algorithm for privacy-preserving training of LLMs and ASR models. The architecture will initially be set up between the Barcelona Supercomputing Centre BSC which acts as a cloud provider and the partner institutions of ELOQUENCE as end-users. This architecture also works as a proof of concept for a DFLA for use in continuous training of a smart home assistant. The main idea behind the DFLA is that substantive data collected from an end-user are not shared directly with the central hub, but local updates to models as they learn, are. This solution is intended to safeguard private or proprietary data whilst still reaping the benefits of local model learning.

The other outcome is a demo of a personalized, conversational, and context-aware **smart home assistant**, provisionally named Aura.

It did complicate the assessment of Pilot 1 that it contained two separate objects, and it was decided that for the next iteration of the assessments, these two objects will be submitted separately to two different panels. Nonetheless, the panel did manage to reach consensus on a selection of suggestions.

For the DFLA the main concerns raised by assessors were:

1. Risks of cyber-attacks in the local servers of the smart home environment or on the way between the local units and the central processing.

2. Risks of emerging bias as the LLM is updated using data from local users which may not be representative of the population as a whole.
3. Risk of intentional model poisoning by some local users.
4. Concerns raised related to technical requirements of local hardware for implementing federated updates to the local models.

For the Smart home assistant, the main concern raised by the assessors was related to the notion of context awareness. The submitting partner had initially considered a design in which the smart home assistant would be continuously monitoring all conversations in its vicinity to learn as much as possible about its environment, in order to be able to provide context-relevant responses when asked to do so by using a wake-up word. The assessors raised a range of concerns related to this practice, first and foremost that conversations taking place between private persons in a private home are sensitive personal data, and even though the DFLA encompasses that such data is not shared back to a central hub, the mere recording of such data still entails an intense interference with the right to privacy. Concerns were raised, in particular, in relation to:

1. Users who have not consented to monitoring (guests) and vulnerable users who may not be able to refuse to consent (children).
2. Privacy leaks within the home (from one family member to another) which in situations of domestic abuse could enable horizontal violations of other rights as well.
3. Privacy breaches from outside the home. i.e hacks from malicious actors or the seizing of records by authorities etc)
4. Accidental privacy leaks to guests or other users because the model is trained on private conversations between users.
5. How to ensure the GDPR protected right to delete personal information once transcribed.
6. Potential chilling effect on the exercise of the right to freedom of expression from constant monitoring

Upon receiving the consensus report, the submitting partner has made strides in considering how to achieve context-awareness with a more limited interference with the right to privacy and complete avoidance of illegal, unconsented, transcriptions. One solution considered was related to voice recognition, the idea being that the model would only transcribe speech from recognized speakers who had consented to monitoring. This solution risked two things however, one was that users might consent while still assuming that they would only be monitored when directly interacting with the assistant, another was that recording only one side of a conversation would likely be of limited usefulness.

Another solution considered was to abandon the idea of constant monitoring, but to include instead a functionality in which a user could explicitly ask Aura to record a conversation for use at a later stage – examples could include a group of friends planning a trip together, or a user recording instructions for a babysitter or a carer for a sick family member. In such situations all speakers would be aware of the recording taking place as they would hear the user starting it, and Aura could be programmed to ask ‘another person has joined the conversation, do you still wish to record?’ when detecting a new voice, or ‘the topic of the conversation seems to have changed, do you still wish to record?’ when detecting a change in themes or a prolonged silence. This would give new speakers an option to protest and would prevent accidental transcriptions beyond what was intended by the user. Aura could also be programmed to keep listening for an additional 30 seconds after having carried out a regular command (such as starting a piece of music or answering a factual question) to catch users protesting if it had misunderstood a command. This too could improve the functionality and context-awareness of the assistant with minimal additional interference with the right to privacy.

4.1.2 Pilot 2: Social Context-aware Language Model Detecting Biases

Pilot 2 is a methodology for testing ELOQUENCE technology for unwanted biases and the system’s ability to handle conversations in a socially appropriate manner. It consists of a set of scripts to emulate a career/studies advisor and a user and relies on a ‘persona methodology’ for creating synthetic (virtual) student users who interact with the career/studies advisor. As such, the intended use of Pilot 2 is not to *be* a career advisor, but to uncover problematic biases through the hypothetical example of a virtual career advisor, a particularly delicate matter in which it is complex to strike the right balance between personalized advice and avoiding biases. The assessors found

this choice of scenario to be promising and ambitious for the task. A central element in Pilot 2 is the use of synthetic data generation and prompt engineering to address challenges that would arise if relying on real user data. The decision not to rely on real user data puts Pilot 2 less at risk of problems, such as obtaining consent and preventing data leaks.

In the assessment of Pilot 2, questions raised by assessors prompted the submitting partner to develop the ideas for contextualization behind the pilot further. For example, the submitting partner reflected on the issue of controlling for so-called ‘protected attributes’ which are reasons based on which it is discriminatory to differentiate treatments, when providing career advice, since some university programs, grants and opportunities are only available to some groups and good advice should take such opportunities into consideration for eligible candidates:

As an example, in the university counselling context, protected attributes include gender, ethnicity, disability status, age, sexual orientation, religious beliefs, nationality, and socioeconomic status and contextual attributes encompass a broader range of factors that influence a student's academic journey, such as academic interests, career goals, educational background, personal preferences, and financial situations.

When we move to the specific context of cultural exchange program counselling, the distribution of attributes in these two sets shifts. For instance, nationality, which is typically considered a protected attribute in university counselling, can significantly impact a student's eligibility for certain opportunities within a cultural exchange program. This factor should guide a counsellor's decisions when recommending scholarship applications. For example, a scholarship for a cultural exchange in China may not be applicable for a student with dual Italian/Chinese nationality. In this scenario, while the allocation of opportunities may not be equal for all students, it remains fair within the specific context.¹⁰

Assessors warned, however, that the lists of protected attributes provided in existing datasets is limited compared to the list provided in the EU Charter of Fundamental Rights (EUCFR) Article 21(1):¹¹

Any discrimination based on any ground such as sex, race, colour, ethnic or social origin, genetic features, language, religion or belief, political or any other opinion, membership of a national minority, property, birth, disability, age or sexual orientation shall be prohibited.

This is the case also for the open-ended list of prohibited grounds of discrimination provided in Article 14 of the European Convention on Human Rights (ECHR) which ends with ‘or other status’. What follows is that detection of biases based on some standard list of ‘protected characteristics’ would fail to detect algorithmic discrimination on ‘new’ grounds (such as, say, dog owners or persons with tattoos), even if such discrimination is equally prohibited.

Assessors also noted that the ‘persona methodology’ being developed is of separate interest and may be exported to other contexts, but that the exact details in the methodology will be laden with assumptions on the part of the human developers which should also be checked for potential biases.

4.1.3 Pilot 3: Retrieval-Augmented LLMs as Virtual Agents, Capable of Understanding the User’s Goals, Making API calls and Respond with Empathy

Pilot 3 is an early version of the ELOQUENCE Interactive Playground (IP), developed with a particular application in mind, namely a virtual assistant using Retrieval-Augmented Generation (RAG) to provide customer service based on for example enterprise-specific data. A key aspect of the object is its orchestration layer that serves as an intermediary between the user interface and the sources of information utilised. The assessors noted the flexibility of the object as a strength suggesting that a potential other use of object could be as an application to access all

¹⁰ V2002 Consensus report p 7.

¹¹ Notably, in the EU context nationality does not fall under the general list in Article 21(1) as there is a special clause in Article 21(2) that makes room for differentiations between EU citizens and others.

kinds of LLMs in a wide range of settings, but that the specific settings could lead to additional ethical and legal requirements which could be addressed in such an orchestration layer.

The orchestration layer is expected to sanitize both inputs and outputs including in respect of truthfulness, fundamental rights compatibility and legality. Assessors made potentially diverging comments in respect of the question whether the responses received from the object can or even should represent 'empathy'. While a user's experience of being treated with respect is valuable, emulating human empathy may be in tension with the requirement that AI is transparent, and false empathy may also become counterproductive.

Pilot 3 was still in the early stages of the design phase when the assessment was carried out which meant that assessors commented on ideas and plans by the submitting partner rather than a testable product. They therefore concluded that the architecture with the orchestration layer had a lot of potential, but an additional assessment would be necessary in M21 once the pilot is further ahead.

4.1.4 Pilot 4 Upgrading Support Call Centres through AI-based Supervision of Multimodal Dialogues

Pilot 4 is a product intended to aid existing call centres in Serbia. These call centres are manned by paediatric nurses and the usual callers are parents of newborns and small children in situations where they might be in doubt about infant care or whether a trip to the emergency room is necessary to address an illness or injury. The idea behind pilot 4 is not to replace these paediatric nurses, but instead to make better use of the waiting time on the phone, by collecting information from the callers about the child and their symptoms to be presented to the nurse in a concise manner once they are able to take the call. The AI is not intended to provide medical information, but can cite from a verified database once it has exhausted all the questions it needs to ask the caller if no human operator is available yet. Such citing would be prefaced with a suitable phrase such as "OK, I have no more questions to ask - the nurse will be available soon, but in the meantime, would you like me to read what the literature on our website has to say on this topic? If not, please just stay on the line". This should make it clear to the caller that the cited literature is not adjusted to their situation and additionally the text will be free of any recommendations ("do this and this" or "you should do that"). The system will inform callers that it is an AI and that interacting with it is voluntary and does not impact on the waiting time or whether the caller will speak to a nurse.

Assessors noted the system's potential in improving access to health information for callers and patients and the resulting benefits to the achievement of the right to health. They also noted a few concerns related to the system. Most importantly, the assessors noted that avoiding bias and discrimination places demands on the speech recognition software to understand dialects, sociolects and slang. Another concern is that the database of information should include information concerning children with disabilities – for vulnerable groups such as this, positive differentiation in attention is necessary to avoid discrimination. Moreover, callers with children with such challenges are expected to require assistance more frequently than parents of children without disabilities.

Moreover, throughout the design of the product it is important to consider that the most vulnerable individual is not the caller but the child patient and that there is a risk that the caller does not have good intentions but could be trying to cover up a crime, establish a timeline of an injury that gives them an alibi, or could be in illegal possession of the child. A caller could also be pranking the call centre having invented a child that does not exist. Like the human operator, the AI system will have to operate under the assumption that the call is genuine, but it is fundamental that the human operator remains the main port of call as they will be able to respond adequately to potential malicious callers. Other risks to consider include errors where callers are offered wrong advice or misunderstand correct advice from the database such as failing to adjust medication doses to the size or age of their children. This should be mitigated at least in part by the database not including direct advice. The AI system can also make mistakes in listening comprehension or in analysis of symptoms, hence providing wrong information to the nurse. Mitigations for these risks suggested by assessors include training of call centre operators in the concepts of anchoring and automation bias, as well as risks of malicious callers, and the establishment of routines including having nurses verify with the caller the information provided to them by the AI. Basically, errors by the AI should not lead to errors by the nurse but would always need to be corrected by them.

A separate concern was raised regarding privacy. Health information is sensitive personal data and in the case of paediatric patients, sensitive data belonging to vulnerable individuals. The system was not intended to store

conversations, though the idea to do so was raised for future human and AI training purposes. Moreover, there might be a case for saving data in cases where a child’s injury represents a crime. In any case a suggestion was made to include an opt-in or opt-out option either at the beginning or the end of the call for whether they allow use of the conversation or not. If data is saved and used for further training, care must be taken that it is free from personal data and would not make the system vulnerable to personal data extraction attacks. To ensure transparency, more technical information than is practical to provide to callers while on the phone could be made available on the call centre’s website or where else the call centre’s contact information is provided.

Finally, it is worth clarifying that Pilot 4 is not intended to make decisions about callers – it will not prioritise calls nor will it conduct any triage or classification of callers affecting which human operator they get in contact with.¹² This means that Article 22 of the GDPR which includes protections against automatic decision making, will not be relevant for this pilot. Should technology from Pilot 4 in the future be developed further to make up part of a triage model or similar decision-making application, GDPR Article 22 as well as Article 16 on rectification of incorrect information would come into effect.

4.2 Report on Feedback Received from the Submitting Partners

The main recipients of our assessments are the submitting ELOQUENCE partners who use the assessments to adjust designs and guide their work. We were therefore keen to get feedback from the submitting partners regarding the assessment process. On the whole, feedback has been very positive:

Figure 1: Feedback from submitting partners

Some concern may be raised regarding question 5 ‘The panel addressed the object properly’ which received 4 out of 5 from all submitting partners. This relates to the problem of explaining to assessors what exactly the pilot consists of, what its intended purpose is, and how it works. We saw issues in this regard during the assessments as assessors often asked questions to the submitting partner’s explanations in the first round rather than provided comments. To address this, the assessment methodology will be adjusted for the next round of assessments purposefully, and from the beginning, to include two rounds, the first of which is for clarifications.

Submitting partners also provided qualitative advice in the feedback sheets (see ANNEX 7.3) for the further development of the questionnaire, requesting, in particular, additional guidance on how to fill in the questionnaire from the side of the submitting partner. Another concern on the part of the submitting partners frequently raised

¹² For an analysis of technologies that do contribute directly to decision making or make decisions directly in terms of triage, see Molbæk-Steensig H and Scheinin M, ‘Human Rights and Artificial Intelligence in Healthcare-Related Settings: A Grammar of Human Rights Approach’ 32 *European Journal of Health Law* 139.

during the assessment processes was that parts of the questionnaire gave the impression of being for the assessment of a ready-for-market product, even though the highest Technological Readiness Level (TRL) aimed for in ELOQUENCE is TRL 5 to 6.

4.3 Evolution of the ELOQUENCE WP6 Assessment Methodology

The assessment process developed over time as we gained experience running the assessments and feedback from the submitting partners. Pilot 4 was the first submission we received, on 9 December 2024. In this assessment the submitting partner first filled in the questionnaire which we then sent separately to each of the panel members before the chair put together a consensus report which was again shared with the panel members for their approval. This process worked well overall, but we did find some repetitions in the comments from different panel members, and it did not provide the submitting partner with a specific time for adding clarifications to questions raised by assessors. For Pilot 2, which we received on 27 January 2025, we started the same process, but quickly realized that the assessors had a lot of questions for the submitting partner without answers to which the assessment would be incomplete. We therefore put together the questions and comments from the assessors into a single document which was shared back with the submitting partner for clarifications. Once the submitting partner had added answers and clarifications this single document was shared with the assessors anew who then completed their assessments in a single online document. Then the chair finalized the consensus report which was accepted by the panel members and returned to the submitting partner. Pilot 1 was submitted four days later, on 31 January 2025 and was treated in the same manner. For the last submission, Pilot 3, submitted 10 February 2025, we decided, based on the positive experience with Pilots 2 and 1, to experiment with sharing a single document with the assessors from the beginning and having the submitting partner answer questions halfway through the assessment process, as well as requesting final acceptance of the consensus report by all assessors.

The process in Pilot 3 which included having assessors fill in the same online document was by far the quickest, and allowed assessors to reflect on comments from other assessors. Additionally, the submitting partner had continuous access, in order to respond to questions. On the other hand, the practice in Pilot 2 of dividing the process into two rounds with a dedicated time for the submitting partner to respond to questions and give clarifications, was particularly informative for both assessors and the submitting partner. Given this, we have decided to incorporate a single online questionnaire for assessors to fill in from the beginning, but also to impose a two-round process, including directly in the questionnaire.

This entailed an update to the questionnaire which will henceforth be version 3, annexed to this report at section 8.3.2. All submissions thus far have been done using version 2 of the template which came into being upon having version 1 (attached to D6.1) reviewed by internal reviewers. One of the main changes in version 3 of the template is that it now reflects the two-round assessment methodology by including four subsections under each question:

1. Submitting partner's comments
2. Comments and questions from the assessors
3. Submitting partner's clarifications
4. New comments from the assessors

This way the assessment becomes more of a conversation between the submitting partner and the rest of the panel. Moreover, to address the problem that the questionnaire in some cases contained questions that were premature given the TRL of the object and/or irrelevant for some objects, additional explanations to that effect were added to the template and the guiding questions were put together with the description of the theme to be addressed rather than added as subsections. We have also included a more comprehensive listing of objective facts on the object, including the TRL in the beginning of the template as well as a full list of deadlines for the first and second rounds of assessment, in order to speed up the assessment process.

Finally, in order to avoid repetitions and a disproportionate focus on the first questions in the questionnaire, some questions were merged. These included Q1 on the purpose of the object and Q9 on the user experience, and Q4 on bias and Q5 on discrimination. Some guiding questions appeared under more than one themed question, so duplicates were removed. Additional descriptions of the themes of the questions and the thinking behind them, including links and references to D6.1 were also included to address the difficulties with filling in the questionnaire by submitting partners. The final section, now Q9, on EU AI Act compatibility was rewritten to clarify that this

legislation, while only applying as law when a product is placed on the market, is useful to consider also at earlier stages of development, including at TRL 5 and 6 which are the target for ELOQUENCE technology.

4.4 Future Plans

Milestone 10, the interactive playground, will become accessible from M19. This will allow us to have assessment panels directly interact with the models in future rounds of assessments. This is particularly important for the ability to assess Q3 on Robustness, Reliability and Trustworthiness which includes a red-teaming exercise where the panel tests the model's robustness against attempts to trick it into producing illegal, incorrect or inappropriate content. It will also be fundamental for answering Q5 on Multilinguality, including the sub-questions on whether the model is equally robust in all supported languages, which completed assessments have not been able to test. Moreover, the interactive playground is envisaged to have both a text and a speech interface, allowing assessors to review the model's robustness, tone and transparency in different modes. All four pilots are intended to be submitted for assessment for a second time before the end of M24. Furthermore, we are considering including a soft quantification of WP6 assessments of compatibility with EU values, in the form of a traffic light system for some of the questions in the questionnaire. Currently this is envisioned for V4 of the questionnaire which will be used for the final assessments to be carried out in M30-M34.

5 Substantive Issues Emerging from WP6 Assessments of ELOQUENCE Technologies

This section explores two substantive legal challenges that have emerged during the assessment process and in conversation with other work packages. The first is whether LLMs can be said to store personal data within the meaning of the GDPR. This question is relevant not only in a general sense, as to whether storing personal data is a type of ‘processing’ within the meaning of the GDPR Article 2(1) which would mean that the deployer of an LLM would have to ensure compliance with GDPR which in turn could entail a significant administrative burden. It is also relevant in the specific case of ELOQUENCE technology because of the federated learning architecture being developed in Pilot 1 which will use model updates from users for the improvement of new models. If the application of such updates constitutes gathering and storing personal data, that has an impact on what consent is needed to be obtained from users, and the security measures that must be put in place to secure such data from personal data extraction attacks. Given this, Section 5.1 engages with the question of whether LLMs can be said to store personal data, and if so, in which cases and whether any of these potentially apply to ELOQUENCE technology.

The second substantive question that has come up relates to the problem of reconciling personal data and discrimination. Certain bias-reduction and anti-discrimination techniques applied to improve LLMs, work by collecting information about characteristics such as race, gender or sexuality of users or subjects, in order to mitigate potential different treatment. Such characteristics constitute sensitive personal data as categorized under GDPR Article 9(1) for which data processing is generally prohibited except in an exhaustive list of circumstances (GDPR Article 9(2, a-j)). There is therefore a dilemma in how to secure both the right to privacy and the right to non-discrimination in the development and fine-tuning of GenAI. This dilemma will be treated in section 5.2.

5.1 Can LLM’s be Said to ‘Store’ Personal Data within the Meaning of GDPR?

This section discusses two different hypotheses published on whether LLMs can be said to store personal data. The first was published by the **Hamburg Commissioner for Data Protection and Freedom of Information (HCDPIF)** on July 15, 2024, in the form of a discussion paper while the second is an opinion published by the **European Data Protection Board (EDPB)** on 17 December 2024. Both publications discuss the accountability of the controller of data for securing correct and legal processing of personal data to the extent that such data is used in the training or finetuning of an LLM. At its core the GDPR prescribes a minimisation principle which requires personal data to be processed only to the extent it is necessary for a specific and legitimate purpose.¹³ This poses a potential problem for the training of LLMs, where foundation models tend to rely on massive amounts of unstructured data which may or may not include personal data, and where finetuning may well include person-specific data which may or may not be pseudo- or anonymised. On the other hand, the GDPR is not applicable to anonymised data.¹⁴ This has therefore led to a discussion on whether the process of training an LLM constitutes a type of anonymisation, and if so, whether that means that LLMs cannot be said to ‘store’ or ‘process’ personal data within the meaning of the GDPR. If that is the case, it would simplify compliance for developers with the GDPR. If it is not the case, they would be responsible for ensuring data minimisation, data protection and compliance with the GDPR.

The HCDPIF paper made the case that since LLM training works through tokenization in which the data is broken into segments shorter than a single word, it cannot be said to ‘store’ personal data in the traditional sense:

The text or token "Mia Müller" is not stored anywhere within the model. Individual tokens such as "M", "ia", "Mü" and "Iler" are merely linguistic fragments. The vectorial relationships between the tokens "Mü" and "Iler" are such that the token "Iler" presumably follows "Mü" more

¹³ GDPR Art. 5(1) b and c.

¹⁴ GDPR Recital 26.

frequently (at least in certain contexts) than, for example, the token "he" to produce the German word "Mühe" ("effort").¹⁵

Much like humans who have read texts, however, LLMs can relatively reliably relay the information they have been trained on. This is largely what makes them useful. Indeed, when they fail to recount information accurately, but instead generate text solely based on words that often go together, as described by the HCDPIF, we call it hallucinations. For personal information, which often appears multiple times in datasets, such as famous people's birth dates, civil statuses or even addresses, LLMs will therefore consider these data to belong together and be reliably able to reproduce that personal information.¹⁶ For most foundation models, which are trained on publicly available data, this ability will represent a minor interference with the subject's right to privacy, as the information is already publicly known, but for specialized LLMs, which may be trained on medical records,¹⁷ or user interactions, one could imagine that both regular and sensitive personal data that is not public knowledge, sometimes belonging to vulnerable individuals, would make up part of the training data. Therefore, the HCDPIF argues that although tokenization during LLM training means that data is not truly 'stored' within an LLM, *'The training of LLMs using personal data must [still] comply with data protection regulations'*,¹⁸ and developers are recommended to use as little personal data as possible, preferring synthetic data when training or finetuning LLMs.¹⁹

The risk of a personal identifiable information (PII) extraction attack represents a counterargument to this line of thinking. Essentially, although LLMs may include filters to refrain from providing personal data in their outputs, or even if training data has been anonymized or pseudonymized, there is a continuous battle between filter developers and malicious actors developing methods to circumvent such filters and reidentify data. Moreover, in a more general sense, machine learning techniques have made the reidentification of anonymized datasets faster, cheaper, and easier²⁰ which means that combined with training data extraction,²¹ personal data can in many cases be extracted from LLMs. Moreover, since LLMs memorise around 1% of their training data verbatim, data leak attacks become more likely to succeed as models get larger.²² In legal terms, this risk of PII extraction attacks relates the question of whether LLMs contain personal data to two concepts under GDPR, namely **unstructured data**, and the relationship between **anonymisation** and **indirectly identifiable personal data**.

While the concept of 'unstructured data' does not appear verbatim in the GDPR, it is usually, nonetheless, covered in corporate training on GDPR. The overarching argument is that the GDPR applies to any 'processing' of personal data, which includes gathering data and storing it, regardless of whether it is stored in a structured way, such as in a database, or an unstructured way, such as in email inboxes or scattered post-it-notes on the desks of various employees. It does not, however, apply to anonymised or statistical data. Since maintaining the rights of data-subjects such as providing access, rectifying wrong data,²³ and deleting data that is no longer needed or where consent has been withdrawn,²⁴ is more straightforward when data is properly structured, it is considered a GDPR compliance best practice to avoid storing unstructured personal data. Moreover, in technical terms, the

¹⁵ The Hamburg Commissioner for Data Protection and Freedom of Information HmbBfDI, *Discussion Paper: Large Language Models and Personal Data* (2024) p 3.

¹⁶ For an illustration of this, see David Rosenthal: https://www.rosenthal.ch/downloads/VISCHER_LLM_birthday_example.pdf

¹⁷ Such as was the case in *ANDREW PRISMALL v GOOGLE UK LIMITED, DEEPMIND TECHNOLOGIES LIMITED and LCM FUNDING UK LIMITED* App No QB-2022-001362 (THE HIGH COURT OF JUSTICE KING'S BENCH DIVISION 19 May 2023)

¹⁸ HmbBfDI p 1

¹⁹ Ibid. p 9.

²⁰ Luc Rocher, Julien M Hendrickx and Yves-Alexandre De Montjoye, 2019 'Estimating the success of re-identifications in incomplete datasets using generative models' 10 *Nature communications* 1

²¹ Milad Nasr and others, 2023 'Scalable extraction of training data from (production) language models' arXiv preprint arXiv:231117035

²² Nicholas Carlini and others, 2021 'Extracting Training Data from Large Language Models' 30 *USENIX Security Symposium*

²³ GDPR Art. 15 and 16

²⁴ Ibid Art 17

anonymisation of unstructured personal data is particularly challenging.²⁵ This raises the question of whether an LLM, considering that personal data can in some cases be extracted from it, should be considered to be storing unstructured personal data. The answer to this question depends on whether tokenization can be said to constitute anonymisation. This evaluation in turn depends on how much effort is required to re-identify the data and the reliability of such reidentification.

The question of effort is clarified in Recital 26 of the GDPR which specifies what is meant in Articles 2 and 4(1) on the scope and definition of identifiable personal data. Recital 26 states as follows:

1: The principles of data protection should apply to any information concerning an identified or identifiable natural person. 2: Personal data which have undergone pseudonymisation, which could be attributed to a natural person by the use of additional information should be considered to be information on an identifiable natural person. 3: To determine whether a natural person is identifiable, account should be taken of all the means reasonably likely to be used, such as singling out, either by the controller or by another person to identify the natural person directly or indirectly. 4: To ascertain whether means are reasonably likely to be used to identify the natural person, account should be taken of all objective factors, such as the costs of and the amount of time required for identification, taking into consideration the available technology at the time of the processing and technological developments. 5: The principles of data protection should therefore not apply to anonymous information, namely information which does not relate to an identified or identifiable natural person or to personal data rendered anonymous in such a manner that the data subject is not or no longer identifiable. 6: This Regulation does not therefore concern the processing of such anonymous information, including for statistical or research purposes.

In short, the GDPR does not apply to anonymous statistical data (§§ 5, 6), but it does apply to data which has been pseudonymised, but which could still be attributed to an identifiable natural person using *reasonably likely techniques* (§§ 2, 3). To determine whether the means necessary to reidentify would be reasonably likely to be used, the controller should consider the time and cost necessary as well as *available technology and technological developments* (§ 4). The latter part is important because machine learning is developing at an accelerated pace and has increasingly been used in efforts to conduct PII attacks and reidentify pseudonymised data. Therefore, training data that would not have been considered identifiable personal data when the GDPR was enacted, might well be considered as such today or in the near future.

The HCDPIF rejected the existence of PII attacks as a demonstration that LLMs should be considered to store personal data. First, because *‘designing and executing effective privacy attacks on LLMs require substantial technical expertise and time resources that the average user lacks’*²⁶ and currently one would need access to the training data itself to verify whether *‘texts generated by an LLM have actually been extracted from the training data or hallucinated’*. Second, the HCDPIF referred to the European Court of Justice (CJEU) case *Patrick Breyer v Bundesrepublik Deutschland* of 2016 in which Mr. Breyer claimed that the Federal Republic of Germany was storing IP addresses of computers that access websites operated by the German federal institutions.²⁷ In this case the court argued that the data in question did not constitute identifiable personal data:

*if the identification of the data subject was prohibited by law or practically impossible on account of the fact that it requires a disproportionate effort in terms of time, cost and man-power, so that the risk of identification appears in reality to be insignificant.*²⁸

²⁵ Emily M Weitzenboeck and others, 2022 ‘The GDPR and unstructured data: is anonymization possible?’ 12 International Data Privacy Law 184

²⁶ HmbBfDI p 7.

²⁷ *Patrick Breyer v Bundesrepublik Deutschland* App No C-582/14(European Court of Justice 19 October 2016) § 17.

²⁸ *Ibid.* § 46

Given this, the HCDPIF argues that since conducting PII extraction attacks ‘*could be considered a practically disproportionate effort and potentially a legally prohibited means..*’ they cannot be considered reasonably likely means to reidentify personal information. Since PII extraction attacks are clearly prohibited by law, not least as unlawful personal data processing under GDPR Article 6, they are therefore not a likely or proportional effort for reidentification, suggesting that LLMs contain only anonymous data, not identifiable personal data.

This position by the HCDPIF has been called the **Hamburg thesis** and was generally received favourably by LLM industry as it would remove a potentially thorny legal obstacle to LLM development. There have, however, since been additional developments. On 17 December 2024 the EDPB, which is established under GDPR Article 64 and consists of the heads of each of the 27 national supervision authorities as well as representatives from three EEAS members, published an opinion on the matter.²⁹ The opinion was prompted by the Irish Data Protection Commission who asked (1) when and how an AI model can be considered as ‘anonymous’; as well as two additional questions on the role of legitimate interest as a legal basis for processing of personal data in AI development and finally a question the legality of new AI systems that may reuse models which have conducted unlawful processing of personal data.

The **EDPB opinion** did not reach as clear cut an answer as the HCDPIF, but instead provided a more nuanced and ambiguous opinion, arguing that the anonymity of an AI model depend on how a model is trained and fine-tuned, including on what training data, and therefore the anonymity of each model must be evaluated on a case-by-case basis by the Supervisory Authority in the relevant state.³⁰ To give an example, a model could be trained purposefully on personal biographical data with the intention of being able to reproduce biographies when prompted. Those biographies, as all LLM outputs, would be probabilistic and there would remain a risk of hallucinations, but their very purpose would be the processing of personal data.³¹ The EDPB therefore argued that,

for an AI model to be considered anonymous, using reasonable means, both (i) the likelihood of direct (including probabilistic) extraction of personal data regarding individuals whose personal data were used to train the model; as well as (ii) the likelihood of obtaining, intentionally or not, such personal data from queries, should be insignificant for any data subject. By default, SAs should consider that AI models are likely to require a thorough evaluation of the likelihood of identification to reach a conclusion on their possible anonymous nature.

This places significantly more responsibility on developers to take measures to prevent personal data leaks from their models throughout the lifecycle, by scrubbing training data of identifiable personal data, by incorporating personal data leak prevention filters and by investing in testing and red teaming. This is also provided for in the GDPR where the controller is required to implement an appropriate level of security (GDPR Article 32) and to notify the supervisory authority in case of any data breach (GDPR Article 33). Though neither the HCDPIF discussion paper nor the EDPB opinion are binding, the opinion due to it representing a compromise of all European national supervision authorities, carries more legal weight and would be more likely to be used in potential future CJEU caselaw. Moreover, the National Supervision Authorities themselves have clearcut tasks in the GDPR and would be expected to be guided by their common opinion. For developers this means that Article 25 of the GDPR on ‘Data Protection by Design’ applies. This requires the controller to ‘*implement appropriate technical and organisational measures, such as pseudonymisation, ... data minimisation, ... and to integrate the necessary safeguards into the processing in order to ... protect the rights of data subjects*’,³² as well as, ‘*implement appropriate technical and organisational measures for ensuring that, by default, only personal data which are necessary for each specific purpose of the processing are processed*’.

²⁹ European Data Protection Board EDPB, *Opinion 28/2024 on certain data protection aspects related to the processing of personal data in the context of AI models* (2024)

³⁰ *Ibid.* 2

³¹ Example provided by James Clark and others, *EU: EDPB Opinion on AI Provides Important Guidance though Many Questions Remain* (2025)

³² GDPR Art. 25(1)

For ELOQUENCE technology the discussion is relevant in respect of all four pilots, which have all been designed with data protection in mind although none of them are intended to reach the TRL necessary for public deployment within the lifecycle of the project. The federated learning system envisioned as part of Pilot 1 is designed in part to avoid processing personal data from users at the developing site, whilst still using user data to improve models by sharing back to developers only updates to the weights in the model. It is likely that this will render the model update anonymous in respect of past users, but the EDPB opinion requires nonetheless that the models are subjected to adversarial testing to ensure that this is the case. Similarly for Pilot 4, although it has not yet been decided whether it will gather user data for model improvement, if it is eventually decided to do so, that data ought to be anonymised before being used for training, and red team reidentification tests should be run to ensure that it would not be vulnerable to PII extraction attacks. This is especially the case as it deals with health-related data which constitutes sensitive personal data. For both pilots developers are not interested in any identifiable personal data getting picked up by the models, but rather in how users statistically interact with the models. Finally, Pilot 2 is intentionally designed to utilise synthetic data rather than personal data for its testing regime. This is a safe way to ensure that no personal data can be leaked as no personal data is processed in the first place, and Pilot 3's orchestration layer represents one of the many avenues that developers have for including data protection filters into LLMs.

5.2 Reconciling Bias Mitigation and the Protection of Personal Data

The problem of intrinsic biases in LLMs is the subject of a growing branch of literature. It encompasses two separate problems. One is the perpetuation of biases and discrimination present in human societies which permeates cultural artifacts which are in turn used for training of LLMs. The other is the accidental emergence of new algorithmic biases which may lead to what appears to most humans to be random discrimination. The first type is easier to detect because we are familiar with it from human society. For example, recruitment algorithms have been found to discriminate against women, women with headscarves, and people with disabilities.³³ In most such cases the algorithm is not purposefully designed to discriminate, but does so anyway either because it is trained on past decisions which themselves favour a particular type of employee due to cognitive biases, or because it punishes things like gaps in a CV which may be proxies for gender as women are more likely to have taken time out of employment to care for children.³⁴

When aiming to mitigate human cognitive biases, in recruitment, adjudication, examination and other critical situations, there are a few approaches. One is anonymisation where identifying information is removed from recruitment materials or exams before being sent to recruiters or examiners. This should in principle force them to consider only objective criteria. It is the same idea that lies behind double blind peer review in academic publishing. This should in principle prevent cognitive biases and subjective opinions about irrelevant characteristics from influencing decisions. A potential concern is that both humans and AIs tend to infer personal characteristics and group belongings from other data through proxies such the gender from gaps in work experience or ethnicity from addresses or school names, or social class from vocabulary. Things such as standardised criteria and structured processes serve the same purpose. Another technique is transparency and auditing. This comes in a range of types including the requirement to give reasons in adjudication,³⁵ letting candidates or students know the objective criteria to be applied and providing them with reports on their performance, and regularly check recruiters, adjudicators or other people in positions of power on whether they statistically tend to favour some groups over others. Finally, discrimination may be mitigated through what is known as positive action or affirmative action in favour of an underrepresented group. This should be a transparent measure and could take the form of statements such 'in the case of equal competence, preference will be given to the candidate belonging to [underrepresented group]', or an official policy to include a requirement of diversity in boards, panels etc. This final type of discrimination mitigation naturally requires information about group belongings.

³³ Natalie Sheard, *Discrimination by recruitment algorithms is a real problem* (2025)

³⁴ *Barriers and incentives to labour force participation, Australia* (2024)

³⁵ Frederick Schauer, 1995 'Giving Reasons' 47 *Stanford Law Review* 633

The tools used for mitigating bias in LLMs work in similar ways. Blinding or anonymising data will usually not work well in bias mitigation in LLMs as they are particularly likely to instead discriminate on the basis of proxies, but LLMs can be forced to consider standardised criteria and structured processes. By incorporating rule-based systems models can therefore just as humans, be nudged towards considering objective criteria rather than group belonging. Similarly, transparency and auditing are frequently applied to mitigate biases both in the form of specific tools that check for difference in treatment based on protected characteristics, and in the form of reinforcement learning from human feedback. A benefit of auditing algorithms and other explainable AI tools is that they can also be calibrated to search for accidental algorithmic bias which does not correlate with what is usually considered sensitive or protected personal characteristics. Finally, filters can be included to counter bias against certain social groups by favouring them. An example of the latter could be that an LLM assistant asked to provide a list of ‘most famous’ or ‘most important’ politicians, scientists, writers or similar is equipped with a filter that requires it to favour non-western or non-male names in cases where the algorithm may suggest several possible answers. A perhaps more elegant solution that relies however on the same principle, is to curate training data to better reflect the real world, even if cultural artifacts included in most training sets tend to be skewed towards dominant groups – keeping in mind that ‘dominant group’ may mean different things in different contexts. For example, in the creation of medical AI, records regarding individuals from social or ethnic groups who have historically had less access to healthcare may be fewer than for dominant groups, and synthetic data can be created to inflate these records to make them appear more common, reflecting real world numbers of these groups rather than the numbers in the records. In practice, developers rely on a range of tools for pre-, during, and postprocessing which must be calibrated to optimise accuracy, fairness and efficiency.

Bias mitigating techniques can conflict with personal data protection in situations where a bias mitigation algorithm requires information about users’ or subjects’ sensitive personal data in order to secure fair treatment. The EU Charter’s Article 21 prohibits discrimination on a range of characteristics,

Any discrimination based on any ground such as sex, race, colour, ethnic or social origin, genetic features, language, religion or belief, political or any other opinion, membership of a national minority, property, birth, disability, age or sexual orientation shall be prohibited.³⁶

Meanwhile, the ECHR and some other human rights treaties prohibit discrimination on any ground. At the same time, the GDPR, in order to protect the rights to privacy and personal data under the Charter of Fundamental Rights Articles 7 and 8, prohibits the processing of certain categories of personal data,

Processing of personal data revealing racial or ethnic origin, political opinions, religious or philosophical beliefs, or trade union membership, and the processing of genetic data, biometric data for the purpose of uniquely identifying a natural person, data concerning health or data concerning a natural person’s sex life or sexual orientation shall be prohibited.³⁷

This overlap between the characteristics on the basis of which discrimination is prohibited and the personal data which generally must not be processed, can lead to conflicts. Examples include whether a recruitment algorithm can collect information on disabilities, ethnicity, gender or sexuality in order to mitigate against potential biases on those grounds, or, closer to ELOQUENCE applications, whether a career advising model can ask information about protected attributes in order to be able to suggest opportunities that may only be open to candidates belonging to certain disadvantaged groups, such as people with disabilities or those belonging to historically disadvantaged minorities.

There is a list of permissible limitations to Article 9 included in the GDPR which includes where,

³⁶ Charter of Fundamental Rights of The European Union (2012) Article 21(1)

³⁷ General Data Protection Regulation (Official Journal of the European Union 2016) Article 9(1).

*processing is necessary to protect the vital interests of the data subject or of another natural person where the data subject is physically or legally incapable of giving consent;*³⁸

This limitation therefore makes mitigation techniques that require the disclosure of sensitive personal data legal, but only in cases where it is *necessary* to protect vital interests of the subjects. Sensitive personal data can therefore not, as a general rule, be gathered to make LLMs function better, but require that a proportionality assessment is carried out in each case as to whether the information is truly necessary.

³⁸ Ibid. Article 9(2(c)).

6 Conclusions

This report demonstrates the ELOQUENCE Consortium’s commitment to rigorous, multidisciplinary assessment of emerging technologies in light of EU values, including fundamental and human rights. Through the application of established human rights assessment methodologies—such as expert panels, structured indicators, and proportionality frameworks—ELOQUENCE has successfully evaluated its emerging four pilot technologies, drawing valuable insights from both the process and partner feedback.

Participation on assessment panels of, and feedback from, external members of the ELOQUENCE Community of Experts has proven invaluable in the development of the WP6 assessment methodology. They will be relied upon in future assessments which are envisaged to include, at a minimum, two more iterations of the four ELOQUENCE pilots. One specific suggestion received from ECoE members, is to consider whether some sort of quantification or grading could be included in the assessment and validation of the compatibility with EU values of emerging ELOQUENCE technologies. This question will be addressed in the second round of assessing the pilots, scheduled for M20-M24 and potentially implemented in the third round envisaged for M30-34, or at least reflected upon in deliverable D6.4.

Our experience confirms that while empirical data and standardized indicators are essential, expert deliberation and a holistic approach remain crucial for nuanced, context-sensitive assessments. Looking ahead, the planned integration of survey data will further enrich our understanding of stakeholder perceptions and societal impacts. The lessons learned underscore the importance of transparency, inclusivity, and adaptability in human rights assessments, particularly as regulatory frameworks such as the EU AI Act continue to evolve.

Key takeaways:

- **Multidisciplinary and Expert-Driven Approach**
The assessment process has demonstrated the value of combining expert panels, structured indicators, and empirical data for robust EU values and human rights assessments of emerging technologies.
- **Methodological Evolution and Adaptability**
The assessment methodology continues to evolve as we learn more about the subject matter and gather feedback from submitting partners.
- **Reconciling rights and incorporating proportionality assessments in AI development**
The assessment process has highlighted the need to reconcile both different rights (such as data protection and non-discrimination) but also technological innovation and privacy (Pilot 1), and privacy and security of vulnerable individuals (Pilot 4), demonstrating the need for a deeper understanding of human rights law in the development of LLMs.
- **Impact of Regulatory Developments**
The regulatory landscape for AI is still developing (e.g., EU AI Act) which requires flexibility in assessment priorities and methodologies. At the same time, the lasting and slow-changing development of human rights law provides important guidelines for what kinds of regulation developers can expect in the future.

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8 Annexes

8.1 NDA

NON-DISCLOSURE AGREEMENT

This agreement is made on [date] between **Prof. Martin Scheinin** representing the **ELOQUENCE** Consortium in his role as lead of Work Package 6, henceforth referred to as the 'Disclosing Party', and **[External Member of Community of Experts]** in their capacity as member of the ELOQUENCE Community of Experts, henceforth referred to as the 'Receiving Party'.

WHEREAS:

- 'Project' refers to the Horizon Europe project named ELOQUENCE (Grant Agreement No 101135916).
- As per the Grant Agreement, the 'ELOQUENCE Community of Experts' [ECoE] consisting of technology, ethics and legal experts will collaborate with the Consortium during the project and take part in assessments of emerging ELOQUENCE technology, as active parts of Work Package 6.
- The Receiving Party is a member of the ECoE.
- The Community of Experts may need access to project deliverables and may participate in activities where confidential information, including materials subjected for Work Package 6 assessment and falling under the intellectual property rights of members of the ELOQUENCE consortium, is disclosed.

IT IS AGREED AS FOLLOWS:

- Purpose
 - The members of the ECoE will assess emerging ELOQUENCE outcomes as members of assessment panels under Work Package 6.
- Confidential Information
 - Confidential Information includes any data or proprietary information from the ELOQUENCE Consortium, external advisors, and ECoE members that is not publicly available and is marked as confidential.
 - Confidential Information should not be shared outside the ECoE operations.
 - Exclusions: Public domain information, previously known information, third-party communicated information without confidentiality obligations, and information publicly available without breaching confidentiality by the Receiving Party.
- Undertakings
 - Parties will use Confidential Information only for the purposes stated in this Agreement and keep it confidential unless agreed otherwise in writing.
 - Contributions by the Receiving Party will be acknowledged if requested.
 - Upon completion, termination, or request, the Receiving Party will return or destroy all copies of Confidential Information.
 - If the Receiving Party must disclose Confidential Information due to legal obligations, they will notify the Disclosing Party promptly.
 - The Receiving Party will notify immediately if aware of any breach of confidence.
 - This Agreement does not create an agency, partnership, or joint venture between the Parties.
 - Parties reserve rights to seek corrective measures in case of a confidentiality breach.
- Miscellaneous
 - Duration: This Agreement is effective for the project's duration. Confidentiality duties remain for five years post-project unless otherwise agreed.
 - Applicable Law: This Agreement is governed by Belgian law, with Brussels courts having jurisdiction. The Parties shall reasonably endeavour to settle eventual disputes amicably. If, however, settlement of a dispute under this agreement has not been possible to achieve, after the

Parties' reasonable endeavours to settle such dispute(s) amicably, the provisions of Section 12.8.2 of the ELOQUENCE Consortium Agreement shall be applicable to any such dispute's settlement.

- Validity: Invalid provisions do not affect the remaining Agreement's validity.
- Amendments: Any changes must be in writing.
- Communications: Notices can be delivered by hand, email, or registered post to the Parties' addresses.

The Parties have executed this Non-Disclosure Agreement as of the above date.

Disclosing Party

MARTIN SCHEININ, WP6 leader

[date]

Receiving Party

[External Member of Community of Experts],
[affiliation]

[date]

8.2 Feedback forms from the submitting partners

8.2.1 V02001

ELOQUENCE partner that made the submission (acronym):	TID
Assessment number	V02001
Object of assessment (name or description):	Pilot 1: Privacy-preserving language model learning through decentralized training in smart homes and partners institutions
Technology readiness level of object as submitted.	2-3
Planned technology readiness level at the end of ELOQUENCE	5
Iteration number for the same object:	1
Date of submission	31.1.2025
Date of consensus report by the assessment panel:	12.03.2025

8.2.1.1 FEEDBACK BY THE SUBMITTING PARTNER

(5 = agree fully, 4 = agree, 3 = neither agree or disagree, 2 disagree, 1 = disagree strongly)

	5	4	3	2	1
1. The assessment template was useful and helpful in making the submission:		x			
2. Preparing the submission was useful for our work on the actual object:	x				
3. The panel's assessment process was smooth and expeditious:	x				
4. The consensus report by the panel was understandable:	x				
5. The consensus report by the panel addressed the object properly:		x			
6. The consensus report provided helpful advice for our continued work:	x				
7. The comments by individual panel members added value to the report:	x				
8. The assessment process assisted us in securing that our emerging ELOQUENCE work is compatible with fundamental rights & European values:	x				
9. Overall, we found the assessment process as important for our work:	x				

8.2.1.2 SUGGESTIONS FOR IMPROVEMENT OF THE ASSESSMENT TEMPLATE OR PROCESS:

After completing the first iteration of the assessment, we found this questionnaire to be highly useful and enriching. It has helped us expand our knowledge on ethical aspects of great importance to individual and social rights, some of which we sometimes overlook or fail to consider due to our lack of expertise and knowledge. Therefore, we strongly believe that collaboration between technical and ethics-oriented experts is highly beneficial and should always be encouraged.

To facilitate the assessment completion during the first iteration, we suggest that providing one or two examples of previously evaluated objects (which could be hypothetical) in advance could be helpful. While there are no definitive "right" answers, reviewing an example beforehand could improve our understanding of the questions and clarify what is "somehow" expected in each response, especially given our limited expertise in the ethical aspects addressed. Hence, having access to completed assessments as examples could guide us and help us reflect more effectively on our own object from the very beginning.

Additionally, to further enhance comprehension of the questionnaire, some questions could include additional context, explanations or examples. Perhaps just links to resources, as is done in questions 3.1 and 3.2. This would be especially valuable for respondents with little knowledge of the topic of the question in matter. For instance:

Question 2.3 - What exactly do we mean by "profiling end-users"? It might also be useful to link Recital 71 of the GDPR (mentioned in the question) to provide more context.

Question 5.1 - What types of biometric categorization exist, and what exactly do we mean by "social scoring"?

Question 7.2 - Since HMS exposes this question (7.2) alludes to the EU AI Act, including a link of it could provide clearer context to what is asked.

Regarding Question 1.2, we don't really understand the relevance of the question. Is it simply asked to establish an order to the iterative process of the assessment or are there other motivations? Some clarification would be helpful.

Moreover, since the questionnaire asks in 1.3, "What data has it been trained on, if any?", it might also be useful to include a question like "What data has it been tested on, if any?" to add an explicit question that focuses on the evaluation.

In the section on multilinguality, it could be beneficial to define what is meant by "low-resource" languages. According to the literature, we would suggest classifying low-resource languages, specifically among the EU official languages, as those lacking sufficient online resources and labelled/unlabelled data (i.e., classes ≤ 2 in Table 1 of Joshi et al., 2020) while also taking into account various dimensions described in Table 2 of Nigatu et al., 2024. If there are any regulations outlining or defining which languages are considered low-resource in 2025, they could be included or referenced.

8.2.2 V02002

ELOQUENCE partner that made the submission (acronym):	CNR – Giuseppe Caggianese
Assessment number	V02002
Object of assessment (name or description):	Pilot 2 “Social context-aware language model detecting biases”
Technology readiness level of object as submitted.	TRL 3
Planned technology readiness level at the end of ELOQUENCE	TRL 4-5: simulates the real-world context of university guidance, by encompassing interactions with simulated students
Iteration number for the same object:	1
Date of submission	30.01.2025
Date of consensus report by the assessment panel:	24.03.2025

8.2.2.1 FEEDBACK BY THE SUBMITTING PARTNER

(5 = agree fully, 4 = agree, 3 = neither agree or disagree, 2 disagree, 1 = disagree strongly)

	5	4	3	2	1
1. The assessment template was useful and helpful in making the submission:		X			
2. Preparing the submission was useful for our work on the actual object:	X				
3. The panel’s assessment process was smooth and expeditious:		X			
4. The consensus report by the panel was understandable:		X			
5. The consensus report by the panel addressed the object properly:		X			
6. The consensus report provided helpful advice for our continued work:		X			
7. The comments by individual panel members added value to the report:	X				
8. The assessment process assisted us in securing that our emerging ELOQUENCE work is compatible with fundamental rights & European values:	X				
9. Overall, we found the assessment process as important for our work:	X				

8.2.2.2 SUGGESTIONS FOR IMPROVEMENT OF THE ASSESSMENT TEMPLATE OR PROCESS:

None

8.2.3 V02003

ELOQUENCE partner that made the submission (acronym):	Omilia
Assessment number	V02003
Object of assessment (name or description):	Retrieval-augmented LLMs as virtual agents, capable of understanding the user's goals, making API calls and respond with empathy
Technology readiness level of object as submitted.	Technology concept formulated
Planned technology readiness level at the end of ELOQUENCE	Technology validated in controlled environment
Iteration number for the same object:	1
Date of submission	26 Feb. 2025
Date of consensus report by the assessment panel:	24 Mar. 2025

8.2.3.1 FEEDBACK BY THE SUBMITTING PARTNER

(5 = agree fully, 4 = agree, 3 = neither agree or disagree, 2 disagree, 1 = disagree strongly)

	5	4	3	2	1
1. The assessment template was useful and helpful in making the submission:	X				
2. Preparing the submission was useful for our work on the actual object:			X		
3. The panel's assessment process was smooth and expeditious:	X				
4. The consensus report by the panel was understandable:	X				
5. The consensus report by the panel addressed the object properly:		X			
6. The consensus report provided helpful advice for our continued work:		X			
7. The comments by individual panel members added value to the report:		X			
8. The assessment process assisted us in securing that our emerging ELOQUENCE work is compatible with fundamental rights & European values:			X		
9. Overall, we found the assessment process as important for our work:		X			

8.2.3.2 SUGGESTIONS FOR IMPROVEMENT OF THE ASSESSMENT TEMPLATE OR PROCESS:

The assessment template was exceptionally well drafted and prepared. Additionally, the coordination of all required processes was handled in an ideal manner.

As we have already discussed, the scheduled timing was somehow premature, especially considering Pilot 3 has only recently begun. Additionally, we are concerned about the practical challenge of ensuring all assessment panel members are thoroughly informed about the various subjects and progress across all work packages affecting Pilot 3. With multiple weekly meetings and an increasing volume of documents and deliverables being produced, staying updated on all developments may prove demanding.

8.2.4 V02004

ELOQUENCE partner that made the submission (acronym):	UNS
Assessment number	V02004
Object of assessment (name or description):	Upgrading support call centres through AI-based supervision of multimodal dialogues
Technology readiness level of object as submitted.	TRL2
Planned Technology readiness level at the end of ELOQUENCE	TRL5
Iteration number for the same object:	1
Date of submission	9.12.2024
Date of consensus report by the assessment panel:	30.1.2025

8.2.4.1 FEEDBACK BY THE SUBMITTING PARTNER

(5 = agree fully, 4 = agree, 3 = neither agree or disagree, 2 disagree, 1 = disagree strongly)

1. The assessment template was useful and helpful in making the submission:	5				
2. Preparing the submission was useful for our work on the actual object:	5				
3. The panel's assessment process was smooth and expeditious:	5				
4. The consensus report by the panel was understandable:	5				
5. The consensus report by the panel addressed the object properly:		4			
6. The consensus report provided helpful advice for our continued work:	5				
7. The comments by individual panel members added value to the report:	5				
8. The assessment process assisted us in securing that our emerging ELOQUENCE work is compatible with fundamental rights & European values:	5				
9. Overall, we found the assessment process as important for our work:	5				

8.2.4.2 SUGGESTIONS FOR IMPROVEMENT OF THE ASSESSMENT TEMPLATE OR PROCESS:

The report by the panel was extremely detailed and helpful. We feel quite able to address most issues raised by the panel and overcome technical challenges related to them. We feel that there is a very small percentage of minor suggestions that are difficult to address having in mind the state of the art in LLM and language technology, however, even these suggestions we find very useful because they offer us insight into what a reviewer principally concerned with ethical aspects would consider as a weak point.

8.3 Assessment templates:

See attached:

8.3.1 V2 which was Used for the First Four Assessments

8.3.2 V3 which Will be Used for Future Assessments

8.3.3 Consensus Reports for All Four Assessments Undertaken

Assessment of the compliance of ELOQUENCE outcomes with European values

Assessment of [filled in by submitting partner]

Assessment number [filled in by Chair]

Template document history

Version	Issue Date	Stage	Description	Contributor
V1	30.6.2024		First version of template	Helga Molbæk-Steensig(EUI) Martin Scheinin (EUI) Reviewed by Dusan Pavlovic (PN)
V2	15.7.2024		Second version of template following test-assessment. Main changes: 1. Change of text-box design to allow for longer answers 2. Clearly separating between (technical) answers by submitting partner and other answers 3. adjusting design of template to fit the visual identity of the ELOQUENCE project	Helga Molbæk-Steensig (EUI)

Table of Contents

0	INTRODUCTION WP6 ASSESSMENT TEMPLATE (V.2)	4
1	Q1: WHAT IS THE OBJECT OF ASSESSMENT?	5
1.1	WHAT IS IT [AN ALGORITHM; SANDBOX, DEMO, ETC?]	5
1.2	WHICH VERSION IS IT, WHAT MODELS DOES IT APPLY?	5
1.3	WHAT DATA HAS IT BEEN TRAINED ON, IF ANY?	5
1.4	WHAT IS ITS PURPOSE?	5
1.5	WHAT KINDS OF UNAUTHORIZED USE (MISSION CREEP) WOULD THE OBJECT BE AT RISK OF?	5
1.6	WHAT WILL BE ITS BENEFITS FOR DEVELOPERS, DEPLOYERS, AND END-USERS?	6
1.7	ANY OTHER COMMENTS?	6
2	Q2: EXPLAINABILITY AND INTERPRETABILITY	7
2.1	WHAT HAS BEEN DONE TO FACILITATE EXPLAINABLE ARTIFICIAL INTELLIGENCE (XAI)?	7
2.2	IS THERE A SUMMARY OF COPYRIGHTED DATA USED FOR TRAINING (OR OTHERWISE)?	7
2.3	DOES THE OBJECT PROFILE END-USERS OR OTHERWISE MAKE THEM SUBJECT TO DECISIONS BASED ON INFORMATION GATHERED ABOUT THEM, THUS ACTIVATING THEIR (NON-BINDING) 'RIGHT TO AN EXPLANATION' UNDER RECITAL 71 GDPR?	7
2.4	DOES THE OBJECT LET THE USERS KNOW THAT THEY ARE INTERACTING WITH AN AI?	7
2.5	IS IT BE CLEAR FOR USERS HOW THE SYSTEM WORKS?	7
2.6	ANY OTHER COMMENTS?	8
3	Q3: ROBUSTNESS, RELIABILITY AND TRUSTWORTHINESS	9
3.1	CAN THE OBJECT BE CONVINCED/HACKED TO PRODUCE ILLEGAL OR OTHERWISE TROUBLING CONTENT (ADVERSARIAL TESTING)?	9
3.2	DOES THE OBJECT HALLUCINATE?	9
3.3	TO WHAT EXTENT DOES THE OBJECT FULFIL ITS FUNCTION AND PRODUCE USEFUL AND TRUTHFUL CONTENT?	9
3.4	ANY OTHER COMMENTS?	9
4	Q4: BIAS	10
4.1	WHAT MEASURES WERE TAKEN TO IDENTIFY POTENTIAL BIASES (IMPLICIT, SAMPLING, TEMPORAL OR OTHERWISE) IN THE TRAINING DATA OR DATA OTHERWISE RELIED UPON?	10
4.2	WHAT KNOWN BIASES ARE THERE IN THE TRAINING DATA OR OTHER SOURCES OF INFORMATION RELIED UPON BY THE OBJECT?	10
4.3	WHAT HAS BEEN DONE TO MITIGATE THESE BIASES?	10
4.4	DOES THE PRODUCT PRODUCE BIASED CONTENT, E.G. ON ACCOUNT OF SEX, GENDER, SEXUAL ORIENTATION, GENDER IDENTITY, ETHNICITY, NATIONAL ORIGIN, LANGUAGE, DISABILITY OR POLITICAL OPINION?	10
4.5	HOW DOES THE PRODUCT ADDRESS SITUATIONS WHERE SOCIETY IS BIASED?	11
4.6	ANY OTHER COMMENTS?	11
5	Q5: DISCRIMINATION	12
5.1	DOES THE OBJECT CONDUCT BIOMETRIC CATEGORIZATION OR SOCIAL SCORING, AND IF SO, FOR WHAT PURPOSE?	12
5.2	CAN THE OBJECT BE CONVINCED TO PRODUCE ILLEGAL OR DISCRIMINATORY CONTENT?	12
5.3	HOW DOES THE OBJECT ADDRESS SITUATIONS WHERE CONTENT IS OFFENSIVE OUT-GROUP BUT NOT IN-GROUP?	12
5.4	HOW DOES THE OBJECT ADDRESS SITUATIONS WHERE IT IS REQUESTED TO REPRODUCE OR SUMMARISE FACTUALLY, ETHICALLY OR LEGALLY PROBLEMATIC CONTENT?	12
5.5	ANY OTHER COMMENTS?	13
6	Q6: MULTILINGUALITY AND CROSS-CULTURAL KNOWLEDGE	14
6.1	WHICH LANGUAGES ARE SUPPORTED OR ENVISAGED?	14
6.2	WHICH LOW-RESOURCE LANGUAGES ARE INCLUDED?	14
6.3	IS THE PRODUCT MORE LIKELY TO PRODUCE ILLEGAL, DISCRIMINATORY OR OTHERWISE TROUBLING CONTENT WHEN USING LOW-RESOURCE LANGUAGES?	14
6.4	QUALITY CONTROL AND ROBUSTNESS: ARE THE RESULTS THE SAME WHEN ASKING THE SAME QUESTION IN DIFFERENT LANGUAGES, AND SHOULD THEY BE?	14
6.5	HOW DOES THE PRODUCT TAKE INTO ACCOUNT DIFFERENT USAGES OF WORDS OR EXPRESSIONS AND DIFFERENT CULTURAL CONTEXTS BY DIFFERENT COMMUNITIES THAT SPEAK THE SAME LANGUAGE?	15
6.6	ANY OTHER COMMENTS?	15
7	Q7: PRIVACY AND THE PROTECTION OF PERSONAL DATA	16

7.1	WHAT KIND OF DATA IS COLLECTED FROM END-USERS?	16
7.1.1	Directly by requesting information	16
7.1.2	Through use of the object	16
7.1.3	Through inferences?	17
7.1.4	Other ways?	17
7.2	DOES THE OBJECT CONDUCT EMOTION RECOGNITION? AND IF SO FOR WHAT PURPOSE?	17
7.3	WHAT DATA AND MODELS ARE SHARED BACK TO THE DEVELOPERS OR THIRD PARTIES SUCH AS POTENTIAL ADVERTISERS?	17
7.4	WHAT DATA AND MODELS MIGHT BE SHARED BETWEEN END-USERS OF THE SAME PRODUCT [IN A SMART-HOME ENVIRONMENT FOR EXAMPLE, WILL DIFFERENT MEMBERS OF THE SAME HOUSEHOLD BE ABLE ACCESS INFORMATION ABOUT EACH OTHER?]	17
7.5	IS THERE COLLATERAL EFFECT UPON NON-USERS, SUCH AS VISITORS WHOSE PRESENCE (LOCATION DATA), OTHER DATA, OR VOICE MAY BE CAPTURED BY THE PRODUCT?	17
7.6	WHAT WOULD BE THE EVENTUAL CONSEQUENCES OF NOT COLLECTING INFORMATION ABOUT THE USER FOR ONSITE TRAINING?	17
7.7	ARE END-USERS INFORMED OF WHAT DATA MIGHT BE COLLECTED AND WITH WHOM IT MAY BE SHARED?	17
7.8	IS CONSENT OBTAINED FOR DATA COLLECTION?	17
7.9	CAN END-USERS REQUEST FOR DATA TO BE ERASED OR CORRECTED?	17
7.10	FUNCTION CREEP: CAN YOU ENVISAGE THE PRODUCT BEING USED FOR PURPOSES OTHER THAN WHAT IT IS INTENDED FOR, WITH ADVERSE PRIVACY CONSEQUENCES?	18
7.11	ANY OTHER COMMENTS?	18
8	Q8: SECURITY AND SAFETY	19
8.1	WHAT STRATEGIES HAVE BEEN EMPLOYED TO RENDER THE OBJECT RESILIENT TO RISKS EMERGING FROM BAD ACTORS?	19
8.2	WHAT MEASURES HAVE BEEN INCLUDED TO RENDER THE OBJECT RESILIENT TO RISKS POSED BY ACCIDENTS, NATURAL DISASTERS AND OTHER SAFETY CONCERNS?	19
8.3	WHAT MATERIAL HARM CAN YOU IMAGINE THIS OBJECT COULD RESULT IN OR CONTRIBUTE TO?	20
8.4	WHAT IMMATERIAL HARM CAN YOU IMAGINE THIS OBJECT COULD RESULT IN OR CONTRIBUTE TO?	20
8.5	ARE THERE ANY WAYS THAT YOU CAN IMAGINE SOMEONE WITH MALICIOUS INTENT MISUSING THE OBJECT TO INFLECT MATERIAL OR IMMATERIAL HARM?	20
8.6	ANY OTHER COMMENTS?	20
9	Q9: OTHER RIGHTS, USER EXPERIENCE AND OTHER CONCERNS	21
9.1	WHAT IS IT LIKE TO INTERACT WITH THE OBJECT (USER EXPERIENCE)?	21
9.2	WHAT OTHER RIGHTS MIGHT THE PRODUCT INTERFERE WITH?	21
9.3	ANY OTHER CONCERNS?	21
10	Q10: EU AI ACT COMPATIBILITY	22
10.1	GENERAL PURPOSE AI	22
10.1.1	If yes to any of the above:	22
10.2	UNACCEPTABLE RISK	22
10.3	HIGH RISK	23
10.3.1	If yes to any of the above	23
11	Q11: CONCLUSIONS	24
11.1	SUBMITTING PARTNER	24
11.2	ASSESSOR 2	24
11.3	ASSESSOR 3	24
11.4	ASSESSOR 4	24
11.5	CHAIR OF THE ASSESSMENT PANEL	24

0 Introduction WP6 assessment template (v.2)

The filling in of this template is designed to assist in the work to assess and ensure that technology produced by the ELOQUENCE project is respectful of EU values i.e., privacy, non-discrimination, robustness in legal, ethical and technical terms, reliability and trustworthiness, interpretability and explainability, security and safety. The template is intended to be a collaborative document where all members of a multidisciplinary expert panel (assessors) can contribute in an asynchronous manner.

The submitting partner will be the first to fill in the template, providing important background information for the other assessors. Some questions can only be answered by the submitting partner. Those will be marked in **turquoise**. Hereafter all assessors (including the submitting partner) are asked to answer the questions marked in **yellow**.

Each theme of the assessment is initiated with a box such as this one with a brief description of the theme assessed as well as several **guiding questions**. Assessors are asked to provide comments on all themes, but can focus on the guiding questions they are best equipped to answer. The guiding questions are repeated in the box and in the space below to ease navigation in the document as it grows when assessors include comments, screenshot etc.

Please do not delete any answers from the other assessors but add instead your own answers below or above. Please initiate all comments and suggestions with your initials.

Assessment of: **[NAME of OBJECT to be assessed]** (filled in by submitting partner)

Assessment Date: **[to be filled in by panel chair]**

Assessment No. **[to be assigned by panel chair]**

The assessment was completed by the chair of the panel on [date], on the basis of contributions made by members of the following panel:

1. **Submitting partner: [initials], [name], [organization]**
2. [initials], [name], expert in/on [field]
3. [initials], [name], expert in/on [field]
4. [initials], [name], expert in/on [field]
5. [initials], [name], chair of the panel, expert on law and the practice of multidisciplinary assessments]

1 Q1: What is the object of assessment?

For the submitting ELOQUENCE partner: Please attach also a file representing or describing the current version of the envisaged product or other object of assessment.

Guiding questions:

What is it [an algorithm; sandbox, demo, etc?]

Which version is it, what models does it apply?

What data has it been trained on, if any?

What is its purpose?

What kinds of unauthorized use (mission creep) would the object be at risk of?

What will be its benefits for developers, deployers, and end-users? And who are its deployers and end-users? [While developers are the creators of the object, deployers are the buyers/owners, and end-users are the individuals using the product. As an example, an AI deployed by a call centre would be developed by the submitting partner, while the deployer would be the purchasing call centre, and the end-user would be the customers calling the call centre]

1.1 What is it [an algorithm; sandbox, demo, etc?]

[please fill in here]

1.2 Which version is it, what models does it apply?

[please fill in here]

1.3 What data has it been trained on, if any?

[please fill in here]

1.4 What is its purpose?

[please fill in here]

1.5 What kinds of unauthorized use (mission creep) would the object be at risk of?

[please fill in here]

1.6 What will be its benefits for developers, deployers, and end-users?

[please fill in here]

1.7 Any other comments?

[please fill in here]

2 Q2: Explainability and interpretability

All GenAI applications are required to let users know that they are interacting with an AI, but transparency requirements go beyond that. The submitting partner should include information on what has been done to facilitate **Explainable Artificial Intelligence (XAI)**, while other assessors are tasked with determining to what extent it is clear for users that they are interacting with an AI, how it works and what kinds of information it gathers about them, including whether they are being profiled/categorised in any way. The question is important because when AIs are not fully explainable and interpretable, their use can dramatically reduce consumers' ability to interact and gauge whether they are subject to discrimination or nudged in any particular direction

Guiding questions:

Does the object let the users know that they are interacting with an AI?

What has been done to facilitate Explainable Artificial Intelligence (XAI)?

Is there a summary of copyrighted data used for training (or otherwise)?

Will it be clear for users how the system works?

Does the object profile end-users or otherwise make them subject to decisions based on information gathered about them, thus activating their (non-binding) 'right to an explanation' under Recital 71 GDPR?

2.1 What has been done to facilitate Explainable Artificial Intelligence (XAI)?

[please fill in here]

2.2 Is there a summary of copyrighted data used for training (or otherwise)?

[please fill in here]

2.3 Does the object profile end-users or otherwise make them subject to decisions based on information gathered about them, thus activating their (non-binding) 'right to an explanation' under Recital 71 GDPR?

[please fill in here]

2.4 Does the object let the users know that they are interacting with an AI?

[please fill in here]

2.5 Is it be clear for users how the system works?

[please fill in here]

2.6 *Any other comments?*

[please fill in here]

Robustness, reliability and trustworthiness go to the very core of what the purpose of the object is and whether it is able to reliably fulfil it. An important factor here is the question of hallucinations which plagued early GenAI in particular. The question relates to what extent the object fulfils its function and produce useful and truthful content. Assessors here are invited to consider in particular the intended function of the object.

Guiding questions:

Can the object be convinced/hacked to produce illegal or otherwise troubling content ([Adversarial testing](#))?

Does the object [hallucinate](#)?

To what extent does the object fulfil its function and produce useful and truthful content?

3 Q3: Robustness, reliability and trustworthiness

3.1 Can the object be convinced/hacked to produce illegal or otherwise troubling content ([Adversarial testing](#))?

[please fill in here]

3.2 Does the object [hallucinate](#)?

[please fill in here]

3.3 To what extent does the object fulfil its function and produce useful and truthful content?

[please fill in here]

3.4 Any other comments?

[please fill in here]

This question is related to bias in a cultural or legal sense, both in the training of the object and in the content it produces. This refers to the fact that there may be situations in which a GenAI produces content that is representative of the material it has been trained on, which in turn is representative of conceptualisations and assumptions in the culture that has produced that material. Often this means leaning towards the western, the able-bodied, and the male, but there have also been [examples](#) where training material has been skewed in a different way.

Guiding questions:

What measures were taken to identify potential biases (implicit, sampling, temporal or otherwise) in the training data or data otherwise relied upon?

What known biases are there in the training data or other sources of information relied upon by the object?

What has been done to mitigate these biases?

Does the product produce biased content, e.g. on account of sex, gender, sexual orientation, gender identity, ethnicity, national origin, language, disability or political opinion?

How does the product address situations where society is biased?

4 Q4: Bias

4.1 What measures were taken to identify potential biases (implicit, sampling, temporal or otherwise) in the training data or data otherwise relied upon?

[please fill in here]

4.2 What known biases are there in the training data or other sources of information relied upon by the object?

[please fill in here]

4.3 What has been done to mitigate these biases?

[please fill in here]

4.4 Does the product produce biased content, e.g. on account of sex, gender, sexual orientation, gender identity, ethnicity, national origin, language, disability or political opinion?

[please fill in here]

4.5 How does the product address situations where society is biased?

[please fill in here]

4.6 Any other comments?

[please fill in here]

5 Q5: Discrimination

This question relates to the production of discriminatory and offensive content. Here a particular challenge is posed by context-specific offensiveness and the difference between internal or in-group language and external or out-group speech. There may be situations where the object is requested by a user to reproduce content that is not offensive in-group but is offensive outgroup (an example could be song-lyrics or satire). In such cases consistently refusing to produce such content because of requested content being offensive in an outgroup context, could constitute a type of censoring or close off cultural content for some users in a problematic way. Conversely, content that is not offensive from the perspective of the dominant population may nevertheless be offensive when appearing to be coming from the dominant culture towards users belonging to a specific minority.

There may also be situations where the object is requested to reproduce content that is culturally problematic regardless of group belonging, but where the content nevertheless forms an important part of a cultural discussion – an example could be if it were asked to reproduce summaries of nazi propaganda or arguments against fundamental rights.

Both types of situations might be resolvable by the product adding context and additional explanations or warnings to users to its responses.

Guiding questions:

Can the object be convinced to produce illegal or discriminatory content?

How does the object address situations where content is offensive out-group but not in-group?

How does the object address situations where it is requested to reproduce or summarise factually, ethically or legally problematic content?

5.1 Does the object conduct biometric categorization or social scoring, and if so, for what purpose?

[please fill in here]

5.2 Can the object be convinced to produce illegal or discriminatory content?

[please fill in here]

5.3 How does the object address situations where content is offensive out-group but not in-group?

[please fill in here]

5.4 How does the object address situations where it is requested to reproduce or summarise factually, ethically or legally problematic content?

[please fill in here]

5.5 *Any other comments?*

[please fill in here]

6 Q6: Multilinguality and cross-cultural knowledge

An important feature of the ELOQUENCE project and other projects launched under the same call is the attention to low-resource languages and cross-cultural knowledge. The submitting partner is invited to disclose what languages the AI currently supports and which it is envisioned to incorporate next, and the other assessors are invited to test the AI in as many languages as possible – particularly low resource languages. In this regard, due to the abundance of English-language training data and pre-developed models nearly all languages are low-resource compared to English. Societally this represents a serious problem as may create inequalities between those that have access to high quality AI in their working languages, and those who do not. Assessors are invited to investigate whether the product is more likely to hallucinate or produce illegal, discriminatory or otherwise troubling content depending on the languages used to interact with the object. Where relevant it may also be prudent to investigate how the product takes into account different usages of words or expressions and different cultural contexts by different communities that speak the same language.

Guiding questions:

Which languages are supported or envisaged?

Which low-resource languages are included?

Is the product more likely to produce illegal, discriminatory or otherwise troubling content when using low-resource languages?

Quality control and robustness: are the results the same when asking the same question in different languages, and should they be?

How does the product take into account different usages of words or expressions and different cultural contexts by different communities that speak the same language?

6.1 Which languages are supported or envisaged?

[please fill in here]

6.2 Which low-resource languages are included?

[please fill in here]

6.3 Is the product more likely to produce illegal, discriminatory or otherwise troubling content when using low-resource languages?

[please fill in here]

6.4 Quality control and robustness: are the results the same when asking the same question in different languages, and should they be?

[please fill in here]

6.5 How does the product take into account different usages of words or expressions and different cultural contexts by different communities that speak the same language?

[please fill in here]

6.6 Any other comments?

[please fill in here]

Privacy and protection of personal data raises several different concerns. At the same time these concerns will have to be balanced with potential functional gains from the learning the object does when in use by end-users.

We are concerned both with how personal data is used by developers and deployers, but also how it might be shared between several different end-users. There are a number of ways this might happen. For example, in a smart-home environment, we might imagine that different members of the same household interact with the same AI object. Concerns may therefore be related to how information collected about these members is shared not only with developers and 3rd parties – such as for advertising – but also within the household between members.

Another concern is function- or mission creep where applications created for one purpose are used for another, to the detriment of fundamental rights protection. It may well happen that a smart-home application could be used also in a club or in a school without necessarily being reconfigured for that space.

Guiding questions:

What kind of data (including sensitive personal data such as data that can be used to identify a person and data revealing their racial or ethnic origin, political opinions, religious or philosophical beliefs, sexuality, health-related data, trade-union membership, or their emotions) is collected from end-users?

Are end-users informed of what data might be collected and with whom it may be shared?

Is consent obtained for data collection?

Can end-users request for data to be erased or corrected?

What data and models are shared back to the developers or third parties such as potential advertisers?

What data and models might be shared between end-users of the same product [in a smart-home environment for example, will different members of the same household be able access information about each other?]

Is there collateral effect upon non-users, such as visitors whose presence (location data), other data, or voice may be captured by the product?

What would be the eventual consequences of not collecting information about the user for onsite training?

Function creep: Can you envisage the product being used for purposes other than what it is intended for, with adverse privacy consequences?

7 Q7: Privacy and the protection of personal data

7.1 What kind of data is collected from end-users?

7.1.1 Directly by requesting information

[please fill in here]

7.1.2 Through use of the object

[please fill in here]

7.1.3 Through inferences?

[please fill in here]

7.1.4 Other ways?

[please fill in here]

7.2 Does the object conduct emotion recognition? And if so for what purpose?

[please fill in here]

7.3 What data and models are shared back to the developers or third parties such as potential advertisers?

[please fill in here]

7.4 What data and models might be shared between end-users of the same product [in a smart-home environment for example, will different members of the same household be able access information about each other?]

[please fill in here]

7.5 Is there collateral effect upon non-users, such as visitors whose presence (location data), other data, or voice may be captured by the product?

[please fill in here]

7.6 What would be the eventual consequences of not collecting information about the user for onsite training?

[please fill in here]

7.7 Are end-users informed of what data might be collected and with whom it may be shared?

[please fill in here]

7.8 Is consent obtained for data collection?

[please fill in here]

7.9 Can end-users request for data to be erased or corrected?

[please fill in here]

7.10 *Function creep: Can you envisage the product being used for purposes other than what it is intended for, with adverse privacy consequences?*

[please fill in here]

7.11 *Any other comments?*

[please fill in here]

8 Q8: Security and Safety

This question addresses a wide range of risks related to AIs in general. In terms of definitions, safety is associated with accidental risk, and security with malicious intent. Reports and White Papers from the European Commission have developed several different taxonomies of potential harms caused by AIs. For example, the AI White Paper from 2020 groups risks into two categories – Risk of Material damage: safety and health of individuals (including loss of life) or damage to property, and risk of Immaterial damage: loss of privacy, limitations to the right of freedom of expression, human dignity, discrimination.¹ GenAI is most directly likely to cause immaterial damage. Other categories could be risks posed to society, such as mass unemployment, mass surveillance, automated weapons systems lowering the bar to genocide, threats to democracy due to filter bubbles and resulting damage to the democratic deliberation; versus risks posed to individuals: personal data leaks, personal unemployment, imprisonment or discrimination based on biased and opaque algorithms.

Certain risks can occur with or without malicious intent such as data poisoning,

An example of data poisoning is Microsoft Tay, a chatbot supposed to interact with young people on social media that was flooded with offensive and racist tweets in 2016 ... Data poisoning can affect a vast array of datasets, such as healthcare data, loan or house pricing.¹

Another problem is that of data or model drift, the tendency for AIs to degenerate over time.

Meanwhile, security concerns can emerge from hacking attempts, attempts to cause data breach, or the intentional installation of backdoors. In both cases risks can be mitigated through proper data management and model review throughout the life cycle of the product. In this part of the template both the submitting partner and the other assessors are invited to creatively imagine scenarios in which the object reviewed could result in material or immaterial harms because of safety or security issues. Malicious security concerns could emerge either from a malicious deployer misusing the product for purposes other than what it was designed for, from external attempts at hacking, from users using the product for ill, or from developers intentionally installing backdoors or otherwise compromising the safety of the object. Assessors should not refrain from considering any of these, and assessors should be free to consider both concrete individual risks and more vague societal concerns.

8.1 What strategies have been employed to render the object resilient to risks emerging from bad actors?

[please fill in here]

8.2 What measures have been included to render the object resilient to risks posed by accidents, natural disasters and other safety concerns?

[please fill in here]

8.3 *What material harm can you imagine this object could result in or contribute to?*

[please fill in here]

8.4 *What immaterial harm can you imagine this object could result in or contribute to?*

[please fill in here]

8.5 *Are there any ways that you can imagine someone with malicious intent misusing the object to inflict material or immaterial harm?*

[please fill in here]

8.6 *Any other comments?*

[please fill in here]

9 Q9: Other Rights, user experience and Other concerns

What other rights might the object interfere with? Examples include: freedom of expression, intellectual property rights, personal freedom, freedom of information.

In this section you can also add any general comments regarding user experience including what it is like interacting with the object – is it rude or polite? Does it appear empathic or detached? Is it easy to get an indication of what it can do and what it should not be used for? Did you find yourself interacting with it in a different way than you would with a person? Is it unnerving to interact with it, and if so, why?

Guiding questions:

What is it like to interact with the object?

What other rights might the product interfere with?

Any other concerns?

9.1 *What is it like to interact with the object (user experience)?*

[please fill in here]

9.2 *What other rights might the product interfere with?*

[please fill in here]

9.3 *Any other concerns?*

[please fill in here]

10 Q10: EU AI ACT compatibility

This checklist is intended to be carried out by the submitting partner only.

10.1 General purpose AI

	Yes	No
Does it have a wide range of possible uses (intended or unintended)?		
Is it a foundation model (pre-trained model for other more specialised models)?		
Is it a Large Language Model (LLM)?		
Does it handle more than one type of input?		

10.1.1 If yes to any of the above:

	Yes	No
Was it trained using a total computing power of more than 10^{25} FLOPs?		
Does it provide a summary of copyrighted data used in training?		
Does it disclose information downstream for the purposes of transparency?		

10.2 Unacceptable Risk

	Yes	No
Does it conduct social scoring?		
Does it exploit vulnerability of persons or otherwise manipulate?		
Does it engage in Biometric categorisation of natural persons based on biometric data to deduce or infer their race, political opinions, trade union membership, religious or philosophical beliefs or sexual orientation?		
Does it engage in emotion recognition?		
Does it make use of or enable untargeted scraping?		

10.3 High risk	Yes	No
Does it evaluate and classify emergency calls by natural persons or is it intended to be used to dispatch, or to establish priority in the dispatching of emergency first response services, including by police, firefighters and medical aid, as well as of emergency healthcare patient triage systems;		
Does it pose a significant risk of harm to the health, safety or fundamental rights of natural persons?		
Is the object intended to be used together with heavy machinery, toys, land- or water crafts, explosives, radio equipment, pressure equipment, personal protective equipment, appliances burning gaseous fuels, medical equipment, civil aviation, agricultural vehicles, marine equipment or rail systems?		

10.3.1 If yes to any of the above

	Yes	No
Has there been established a risk management system for the life cycle of the product?		
Data governance: Has it been ensured that training, validation and testing datasets are relevant, sufficiently representative and, to the best extent possible, free of errors and complete according to the intended purpose.		
Is there technical documentation to demonstrate compliance and provide authorities with the information to assess that compliance?		
Is the system designed for record-keeping to enable it to automatically record events relevant for identifying national level risks and substantial modifications throughout the system's lifecycle?		
Can you provide instructions for use to downstream deployers to enable the latter's compliance?		
Has the system been designed to allow deployers to implement human oversight?		
Is it designed to achieve appropriate levels of accuracy, robustness, and cybersecurity?		
Has a quality management system to ensure compliance been established?		

11 Q11: Conclusions

Given your answers to the questions above, please formulate a conclusion as to any concerns with the object as is, as it may develop or otherwise. Each person filling out the questionnaire should formulate their own conclusion, and the chair of the panel will then formulate a consensus conclusion which will be shared with other members of the panel before communicating to the submitting partner.

11.1 Submitting partner

[please fill in here]

11.2 Assessor 2

[please fill in here]

11.3 Assessor 3

[please fill in here]

11.4 Assessor 4

[please fill in here]

11.5 Chair of the assessment panel

[please fill in here]

Assessment of the compliance of ELOQUENCE outcomes with European values

Assessment of [filled in by submitting partner]

Assessment number [filled in by Chair]

Template document history

Version	Issue Date	Stage	Description	Contributor
V1	30.6.2024		First version of template	Helga Molbæk-Steensig(EUI) Martin Scheinin (EUI) Reviewed by Dusan Pavlovic (PN)
V2	15.7.2024		<p>Second version of template following test-assessment.</p> <p>Main changes:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Change of text-box design to allow for longer answers 2. Clearly separating between (technical) answers by submitting partner and other answers 3. adjusting design of template to fit the visual identity of the ELOQUENCE project 	Helga Molbæk-Steensig (EUI)
V3	23.1.2025		<p>Third version of the template.</p> <p>Main changes:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Merging Q4 on bias and Q5 on discrimination 2. Adding Executive summary to the start of the template 3. Changes to formatting to avoid repetition of guiding questions. 4. Merging Q1 (what is) and Q9 (user experience) 5. Division of submitting partner and assessors comments 6. Removal of repeat questions for partner and assessors 7. Clarifications in textboxes 	Helga Molbæk-Steensig(EUI)
V3	28.3.2025		Formatting changes. Additional descriptions and links added as requested in feedback	Helga Molbæk-Steensig(EUI)

from partners involved in the first four
assessments carried out.

Table of Contents

<i>EXECUTIVE SUMMARY BY THE PANEL CHAIR</i>	4
0 INTRODUCTION: THE ELOQUENCE WP6 ASSESSMENT TEMPLATE (V.3)	5
INFORMATION ABOUT THE OBJECT ITS ASSESSMENT	6
1 Q1: FUNCTION OF THE OBJECT	7
2 Q2: EXPLAINABILITY AND INTERPRETABILITY	8
3 Q3: ROBUSTNESS, RELIABILITY AND TRUSTWORTHINESS	9
4 Q4: BIAS AND DISCRIMINATION	10
5 Q5: MULTILINGUALITY AND CROSS-CULTURAL KNOWLEDGE	12
6 Q6: PRIVACY AND THE PROTECTION OF PERSONAL DATA	14
7 Q7: SECURITY AND SAFETY	15
8 Q8: CONCLUSIONS AND ANY OTHER COMMENTS.....	17
9 Q9: EU AI ACT COMPATIBILITY.....	18

Executive Summary by the Panel Chair

Goes here

0 Introduction: the ELOQUENCE WP6 assessment template (v.3)

This Questionnaire is designed to assist in the work to assess and ensure that technology produced by the ELOQUENCE project is respectful of EU values i.e., privacy, non-discrimination, robustness in legal, ethical and technical terms, reliability and trustworthiness, interpretability and explainability, security and safety.

The template, to be published as an annex to ELOQUENCE **deliverable D6.2**, is intended to be read together with that deliverable and earlier **deliverable D6.1** which contains general information on the concept of EU values, the reach and content of the fundamental rights to privacy and non-discrimination as well as other potentially affected rights in the context of Generative AI, Natural Language Processing and Large Language Models, as well as accessible accounts of the parts of the EU AI Act that are most likely to be of relevance to ELOQUENCE outcomes.

An assessment conducted under ELOQUENCE WP6 takes place in 5 steps:

1. The submitting partner fills in the template and submits it for assessment.
2. The template is opened for assessment by four other members of an ad-hoc multidisciplinary panel who will comment and ask clarifying questions
3. The template is returned to the submitting partner who will answer questions and provide clarifications where necessary
4. The template is returned to the panel who will comment throughout the template as appropriate given the clarifications of the submitting partner and conclude (in Section 8)
5. The chair of the panel reviews all comments and conclusions and writes an executive summary. The consensus report is then returned to panel members for a final check and sent to the submitting partner.

Each assessment is initiated with a brief description of the theme (object) assessed as well as several **guiding questions**. Not all questions will be relevant to all assessments and panel members are free to focus on the ones that merit the most attention

Please **do not delete or change any information provided by the submitting partner or comments by other assessors** but add instead your own comments **initiated with your initials**.

Information about the object its assessment

Fields marked in **purple** will be filled in by the panel chair. Fields marked in **turquoise** will be filled in by the submitting partner.

Assessment number	Filled in by chair
Object of assessment (name or description):	Filled in by submitting partner
Technology readiness level of object as submitted.	Filled in by submitting partner
Planned technology readiness level at the end of ELOQUENCE	Filled in by submitting partner
Iteration number for the same object:	Filled in by submitting partner
Representative of the ELOQUENCE partner that made the submission	Initials name partner acronym
Assessment panel members	Initials name partner acronym/external org. Initials name partner acronym/external org. Initials name partner acronym/external org.
Assessment panel chair	Initials name partner acronym

Important dates

Submission date	Filled in by chair
Template opened for panel review	Filled in by chair
Deadline of first round of comments and questions	Filled in by chair
Deadline for submitting partner's answers	Filled in by chair
Deadline for second round of comments and conclusions	Filled in by chair
Expected date on which the report is returned to the submitting partner	Filled in by chair

1 Q1: Function of the object

In this part of the questionnaire the submitting partner describes the object and its function. Please feel free to include screenshots, figures and tables as necessary. **Please number and title any other files**, links or similar submitted that the assessors should also access and consider.

In this section assessors can comment on the submitting partner's description of the object but also (if appropriate) give any other comments regarding user experience including what it is like interacting with the object– is it rude or polite? Does it appear empathic or detached? Is it easy to get an indication of what it can do and what it should not be used for? Is it pleasant or unnerving to interact with it, and if so, why?

Guiding questions:

Submitting partner:

1. What are the main materials on the basis of which this assessment should be carried out?
2. Describe the function of the object:
 - a. Where will it be used and by whom?
 - b. What is its purpose and added value?
3. Please include relevant technical information such as:
 - a. Which version is it, what models does it apply?
 - b. What data will it incorporate or be trained on, if any?

Assessors:

4. How is the user experience, what is it like interacting with the object?
5. Can you imagine any other uses for the system than envisioned in the description by the submitting partner?

1.1 Submitting partner's description of the object

Here

1.2 Comments and questions from the assessors

here

1.3 Submitting partner's clarifications

here

1.4 New comments from the assessors

here

2 Q2: Explainability and interpretability

All GenAI applications are required under the EU AI Act to [let users know that they are interacting with an AI](#), but transparency requirements go beyond that. The submitting partner should include information on what has been done to facilitate [Explainable Artificial Intelligence \(XAI\)](#), while other assessors are tasked with determining to what extent it is clear for users that they are interacting with an AI, how it works and what kinds of information it gathers about them, including whether they are being [profiled](#) in any way. The question is important because when AIs are not fully explainable and interpretable, their use can dramatically reduce consumers' willingness to interact with them as well as their ability to gauge whether they are subject to discrimination or being nudged towards certain actions.

Guiding questions:

Submitting partner:

1. What has been done to facilitate Explainable Artificial Intelligence (XAI)?
2. Is there a summary of data used for training or retrieval?
3. Does the object profile end-users or otherwise make them subject to decisions based on information gathered about them, thus activating their (non-binding)

Assessors:

4. Did the object let you know that you were interacting with an AI?
5. Will it be clear enough for users how the system works?

2.1 Submitting partner's comments

Here

2.2 Comments and questions from the assessors

here

2.3 Submitting partner's clarifications

here

2.4 New comments from the assessors

here

3 Q3: Robustness, reliability and trustworthiness

Robustness, reliability and trustworthiness go to the very core of what the purpose of the object is and whether it can reliably fulfil it. An important factor here is the question of [hallucinations](#) defined from the users point of view as plausible but wrong answers, regardless of the type technologically, but the question is broader and also relates to other ways that the system may result in errors or misunderstandings. Assessors here are invited to consider in particular the intended function of the object as described under Q1

Guiding questions:

Submitting partner:

1. What has been done to ensure robustness, reliability and trustworthiness?

Assessors:

2. Can the object be convinced/hacked to produce illegal, discriminatory or otherwise troubling content ([Adversarial testing](#))?
3. Does the object [hallucinate](#)?
4. What might be other potential sources of errors?

3.1 Submitting partner's comments

Here

3.2 Comments and questions from the assessors

here

3.3 Submitting partner's clarifications

here

3.4 New comments from the assessors

here

4 Q4: Bias and discrimination

This question is related to bias in a cultural or legal sense, both in the training of the object and in the content it produces. This refers to the fact that there may be situations in which a GenAI produces content that is representative of the material it has been trained on, which in turn may or may not be representative of conceptualizations and assumptions in the culture that has produced that material. Often this means leaning towards the western, the able-bodied, and the male, but there have also been [examples](#) where training material has been skewed in a different way.

In turn bias is the main source of discrimination. Discrimination refers to the unfounded and unfair difference in treatment of persons based on their group belonging (such as, but not limited to, their race, gender, ethnicity, national origin, language, disability or political opinion). For ELOQUENCE outputs discrimination refers both to decisions the system may take or contribute to a human taking, and to the content it produces. Here a particular challenge is posed by context-specific offensiveness and the difference between internal or in-group language and external or out-group speech. There may be situations where the object is requested by a user to reproduce content that is not offensive in-group but is offensive outgroup (an example could be song-lyrics or satire). In such cases consistently refusing to produce such content because of requested content being offensive in an outgroup context, could constitute a type of censoring or close off cultural content for some users in a problematic way. Conversely, content that is not offensive from the perspective of the dominant population may nevertheless be offensive when appearing to be coming from the dominant culture towards users belonging to a specific minority.

There may also be situations where the object is requested to reproduce content that is culturally problematic regardless of group belonging, but where the content nevertheless forms an important part of a cultural discussion – an example could be if it were asked to reproduce summaries of nazi propaganda or arguments against fundamental rights.

Both types of situations might be resolvable by the object adding context and additional explanations or warnings to users to its responses.

Guiding questions:

Submitting partners:

1. Are there any known biases in the training data or the model?
2. What has been done to identify unknown biases?
3. What has been done to mitigate known biases?
4. Does the object make decisions based on any biometric or social categorization?

Assessors:

5. Does the product produce biased content, e.g. on account of sex, gender, sexual orientation, gender identity, ethnicity, national origin, language, disability or political opinion?
6. How does the product address situations where society is biased?
7. How does the object react if asked to produce or summarise factually, ethically or legally problematic content?
8. How does the object react to situations where content may be offensive in- or outgroup?

4.1 Submitting partner's comments

Here

4.2 Comments and questions from the assessors

here

4.3 Submitting partner's clarifications

here

4.4 New comments from the assessors

here

5 Q5: Multi-linguality and cross-cultural knowledge

An important feature of the ELOQUENCE project and other projects launched under the same call is the attention to [low-resource languages](#) and cross-cultural knowledge. Low-resources languages has different definitions, but in ELOQUENCE we are particularly interested in European low-resource languages. This means, for the most part, languages that has a fair number of natural speakers, but where there is a lack of data resources for training and testing LLMs, rather than languages that are at risk of extinction. Examples include, but are not limited to official first languages of EU countries: Finnish, Bosnian-Croatian-Serbian, the Scandinavian languages, Czech, Polish, Slovenian etc, as well as minority languages such as Gaelic, Catalan or Greenlandic and Sami languages and dialects. Moreover, ELOQUENCE also aims to include languages that are not traditionally considered low-resource but which nonetheless have fewer resources available than the big five (English, Chinese, French, Spanish, German), such as Italian, Greek, and other official EU languages.

The submitting partner is invited to disclose what languages the AI currently supports and which it is envisioned to incorporate next, and the other assessors are invited to test the AI in as many of these languages as possible. In this regard, due to the abundance of English-language training data and pre-developed models nearly all languages are low-resource compared to English. Societally this represents a serious problem as may create inequalities between those that have access to high quality AI in their working languages, and those who do not. Assessors are invited to investigate whether the product is more likely to hallucinate or produce illegal, discriminatory or otherwise troubling content depending on the languages used to interact with the object. Where relevant it may also be prudent to investigate how the product takes into account different usages of words or expressions and different cultural contexts by different communities that speak the same language.

Guiding questions:

Submitting partner:

1. Which languages are supported or envisaged?
2. Which low-resource languages are included?
3. If speech-enabled, what has been done to ensure that the system understands dialects, accents, speech impediments, slang and minority language loanwords?

Assessors:

4. Does the system behave differently depending on the language used?
 - a. In terms of bias and discrimination?
 - b. In terms of robustness, correctness, reliability and trustworthiness?
5. Does the product take into account different usages of words or expressions and different cultural contexts by different communities that speak the same language?

5.1 Submitting partner's comments

Here

5.2 Comments and questions from the assessors

here

5.3 Submitting partner's clarifications

here

5.4 New comments from the assessors

here

6 Q6: Privacy and the protection of personal data

Privacy and protection of personal data raises several different concerns which must be balanced with potential functional gains from the learning the object does when in use by end-users.

We are concerned both with how personal data is used by developers and deployers, but also how it might be shared between several different end-users. There are several ways this might happen. For example, in a smart-home environment, we might imagine that different members of the same household interact with the same AI object. Concerns may therefore be related to how information collected about these members is shared not only with developers and 3rd parties – such as for advertising – but also within the household between members.

Another concern is function- or mission creep where applications created for one purpose are used for another, to the detriment of fundamental rights protection. It may well happen that a smart-home application could be used also in a club or in a school without necessarily being reconfigured for that space.

Guiding questions:

Submitting partner:

1. What kind of data (including sensitive personal data such as data that can be used to identify a person and data revealing their racial or ethnic origin, political opinions, religious or philosophical beliefs, sexuality, health-related data, trade-union membership, or their emotions) is collected from end-users?
 - a. Directly
 - b. Through use of the object
 - c. Through inferences
2. What data goes back to developers for the purpose of improving the system?
3. Are end-users informed of what data might be collected and with whom it may be shared?
4. Is consent obtained for data collection? And can end-users request for data to be erased or corrected?
5. Can different users access each other's data?

Assessors

6. Were you as a user informed about data collection by the object?
7. Can you imagine problematic use of the data collected.
8. Can you predict collateral effects upon non-users, such as visitors whose presence (location data), other data, or voice may be captured by the product?

6.1 Submitting partner's comments

Here

6.2 Comments and questions from the assessors

here

6.3 Submitting partner's clarifications

here

6.4 New comments from the assessors

here

7 Q7: Security and Safety

This question addresses a wide range of risks related to AIs in general. In terms of definitions, safety is associated with accidental risk, and security with malicious intent. Reports and White Papers from the European Commission have developed several different taxonomies of potential harms caused by AIs. For example, the [AI White Paper from 2020](#) groups risks into two categories – Risk of Material damage: safety and health of individuals (including loss of life) or damage to property, and risk of Immaterial damage: loss of privacy, limitations to the right of freedom of expression, human dignity, discrimination. Other categories could be risks posed to society, such as mass unemployment, mass surveillance, automated weapons systems lowering the bar to genocide, threats to democracy due to filter bubbles and resulting damage to the democratic deliberation; versus risks posed to individuals: personal data leaks, personal unemployment, imprisonment or discrimination based on biased and opaque algorithms.

Certain risks can occur with or without malicious intent such as data poisoning. Another problem is that of data or model drift, the tendency for AIs to degenerate over time.

Meanwhile, security concerns can emerge from hacking attempts, attempts to cause data breach, or the intentional installation of backdoors. In both cases risks can be mitigated through proper data management and model review throughout the life cycle of the product.

In this part of the template both the submitting partner and the other assessors are invited to creatively imagine scenarios in which the object reviewed could result in material or immaterial harms to individual users or society as a whole because of safety or security issues. Malicious security concerns could emerge either from a malicious deployer misusing the product for purposes other than what it was designed for, from external attempts at hacking, from users using the product for ill, or from developers intentionally installing backdoors or otherwise compromising the safety of the object.

Guiding questions:

Submitting partner:

1. What strategies will be employed to avoid malicious actors misusing the object?
2. What strategies will be employed to avoid safety risks that can occur without attack from a malicious actor?
3. What potential material and immaterial harms have been considered in the design of the object.
4. What kinds of tests has the object been subjected to and what kinds of data is it tested on?

For Assessors:

5. What material and immaterial risks can you foresee related to the object?
6. What safety risks are possible without malicious actors
7. What security risks can malicious actors affect by interfering with the object?

7.1 Submitting partner's comments

Here

7.2 Comments and questions from the assessors

here

7.3 Submitting partner's clarifications

here

7.4 *New comments from the assessors*

here

8 Q8: Conclusions and any other comments.

Given your answers to the above questions please formulate a conclusion. Each assessor should formulate their own conclusion.

Here you can also add any other comments you might have, such as:

1. Are any other rights affected?
2. Do you have any other technical, legal or ethical concerns?

8.1 Final comments from the submitting partner

8.2 Final comments from Panel member 2

Here

8.3 Final comments from Panel member 3

here

8.4 Final comments from Panel member 4

here

8.5 Final comments from Panel member 5

Here

9 Q9: EU AI ACT compatibility

This checklist is intended to be carried out by the submitting partner only.

The EU AI Act only applies to products once they are put on the market, so for most ELOQUENCE outcomes which have a final TRL of no more than 5 or 6, it will not be applied. That said, considering EU AI Act compatibility at this stage will significantly ease compliance at a later stage. For more information on the EU AI Act see D6.1. section 4.2 pages 22-30.

The EU AI Act regulated AI applications differently based on the category it belongs to. There are two overall categories that the regulation utilizes. The first is functional and concerns risk. A limited number of applications are considered **unacceptable risk**. That means that it is illegal to place on the market products carrying out that function regardless of how accurate they are or what mitigation measures have been included. If the answer is ‘yes’ to any of the questions in 9.1 the product represents an unacceptable risk and can never be placed on the market in Europe.

The next category is **high risk** applications. These applications are not outlawed, but are instead subjected to transparency, documentation, risk management and other requirements. A full list of high risk applications can be found in the [EU AI Act and its annexes](#), this checklist only includes the most likely for ELOQUENCE outcomes. If the answer is yes to any of the questions in 9.2 the product is high risk and is subjected to additional documentation, mitigation and risk management requirements listed in 9.2.1. The EU AI Act also contains transparency requirements for applications representing lower risk levels.

The other categorization in the EU AI Act is of **General Purpose AI (GPAI)**. Within this category the regulation speaks of models **with and without Systemic Risk**, the determination of which is based mainly on the size of the model. Both types are subject to regulation related to copyright law, and must provide a public summary of the data used in training and keep updated records of a range of technical information about the model, its parameters, training end testing. GPAI representing a **systemic risk** are also required to provide additional technical information to authorities, to assess and mitigate systemic risks, ensure adequate cyber security and must report any serious incidents to the EU AI Office. For more on the actual requirements see D6.1. Chapter 4.2.3.

In this questionnaire, if the answer is yes to any of the questions in 9.3, the model is categorized as General Purpose AI and will be subject to related regulation. If the answer is yes to question 9.3.1. it is a GPAI representing systemic risk.

9.1 Unacceptable Risk

	Yes	No
Does it conduct social scoring ?		
Does it exploit vulnerability of persons or otherwise manipulate?		
Does it engage in Biometric categorisation of natural persons based on biometric data to deduce or infer their race, political opinions, trade union membership, religious or philosophical beliefs or sexual orientation?		
Does it engage in emotion recognition , intended to be used in an educational or employment context?		

Does it make use of or enable untargeted scraping for the purpose of facial recognition?		
Does it predict criminal behaviour of persons .		

9.2 High risk

	Yes	No
Could it be used to produce deep fakes (transparency risk)		
Does it evaluate and classify emergency calls by natural persons or is it intended to be used to dispatch, or to establish priority in the dispatching of emergency first response services, including by police, firefighters and medical aid, as well as of emergency healthcare patient triage systems;		
Does it pose a significant risk of harm to the health, safety or fundamental rights of natural persons?		
Is the object intended to be used together with heavy machinery, toys, land- or water crafts, explosives, radio equipment, pressure equipment, personal protective equipment, appliances burning gaseous fuels, medical equipment, civil aviation, agricultural vehicles, marine equipment or rail systems?		

9.2.1 If yes to any of the above

	Yes	No
Has there been established a risk management system for the life cycle of the product?		
Data governance: Has it been ensured that training, validation and testing datasets are relevant, sufficiently representative and, to the best extent possible, free of errors and complete according to the intended purpose.		
Is there technical documentation to demonstrate compliance and provide authorities with the information to assess that compliance?		
Is the system designed for record-keeping to enable it to automatically record events relevant for identifying national level risks and substantial modifications throughout the system's lifecycle?		
Can you provide instructions for use to downstream deployers to enable the latter's compliance?		
Has the system been designed to allow deployers to implement human oversight?		

Is it designed to achieve appropriate levels of accuracy, robustness, and cybersecurity?		
Has a quality management system to ensure compliance been established?		

9.3 General purpose AI

	Yes	No
Does it have a wide range of possible uses (intended or unintended)?		
Is it a foundation model (pre-trained model for other more specialised models)?		
Is it a Large Language Model (LLM)?		
Does it handle more than one type of input?		

9.3.1 If yes to any of the above:

	Yes	No
Was it trained using a total computing power of more than 10^{25} FLOPs?		

Assessment of the compliance of ELOQUENCE outcomes with European values

Assessment of Pilot 1 (TID) Assessment number [V02001]

Template document history

Version	Issue Date	Stage	Description	Contributor
V1	30.6.2024		First version of template	Helga Molbæk-Steensig(EUI) Martin Scheinin (EUI) Reviewed by Dusan Pavlovic (PN)
V2	15.7.2024		Second version of template following test-assessment. Main changes: 1. Change of text-box design to allow for longer answers 2. Clearly separating between (technical) answers by submitting partner and other answers 3. adjusting design of template to fit the visual identity of the ELOQUENCE project	Helga Molbæk-Steensig (EUI)
V3	24.1.2025		First response to the document by the submitting partner (TID)	Jordi Luque Aleix Sant

EXECUTIVE SUMMARY	4
0. INTRODUCTION WP6 ASSESSMENT TEMPLATE (V.2)	6
1. Q1: WHAT IS THE OBJECT OF ASSESSMENT?	7
1.1. WHAT IS IT [AN ALGORITHM; SANDBOX, DEMO, ETC.]	7
1.2. WHICH VERSION IS IT, WHAT MODELS DOES IT APPLY?	11
1.3. WHAT DATA HAS IT BEEN TRAINED ON, IF ANY?	12
1.4. WHAT IS ITS PURPOSE?	14
1.5. WHAT KINDS OF UNAUTHORIZED USE (MISSION CREEP) WOULD THE OBJECT BE AT RISK OF?	15
1.6. WHAT WILL BE ITS BENEFITS FOR DEVELOPERS, DEPLOYERS, AND END-USERS?	16
1.7. ANY OTHER COMMENTS?	16
2. Q2: EXPLAINABILITY AND INTERPRETABILITY	17
2.1. WHAT HAS BEEN DONE TO FACILITATE EXPLAINABLE ARTIFICIAL INTELLIGENCE (XAI)?	17
2.2. IS THERE A SUMMARY OF COPYRIGHTED DATA USED FOR TRAINING (OR OTHERWISE)?	18
2.3. DOES THE OBJECT PROFILE END-USERS OR OTHERWISE MAKE THEM SUBJECT TO DECISIONS BASED ON INFORMATION GATHERED ABOUT THEM, THUS ACTIVATING THEIR (NON-BINDING) 'RIGHT TO AN EXPLANATION' UNDER RECITAL 71 GDPR?	18
2.4. DOES THE OBJECT LET THE USERS KNOW THAT THEY ARE INTERACTING WITH AN AI?	19
2.5. IS IT CLEAR FOR USERS HOW THE SYSTEM WORKS?	20
2.6. ANY OTHER COMMENTS?	20
3. Q3: ROBUSTNESS, RELIABILITY AND TRUSTWORTHINESS	21
3.1. CAN THE OBJECT BE CONVINCED/HACKED TO PRODUCE ILLEGAL OR OTHERWISE TROUBLING CONTENT (ADVERSARIAL TESTING)?	21
3.2. DOES THE OBJECT HALLUCINATE?	21
3.3. TO WHAT EXTENT DOES THE OBJECT FULFIL ITS FUNCTION AND PRODUCE USEFUL AND TRUTHFUL CONTENT?	22
3.4. ANY OTHER COMMENTS?	23
4. Q4: BIAS	24
4.1. WHAT MEASURES WERE TAKEN TO IDENTIFY POTENTIAL BIASES (IMPLICIT, SAMPLING, TEMPORAL OR OTHERWISE) IN THE TRAINING DATA OR DATA OTHERWISE RELIED UPON?	24
4.2. WHAT KNOWN BIASES ARE THERE IN THE TRAINING DATA OR OTHER SOURCES OF INFORMATION RELIED UPON BY THE OBJECT?	25
4.3. WHAT HAS BEEN DONE TO MITIGATE THESE BIASES?	25
4.4. DOES THE PRODUCT PRODUCE BIASED CONTENT, E.G. ON ACCOUNT OF SEX, GENDER, SEXUAL ORIENTATION, GENDER IDENTITY, ETHNICITY, NATIONAL ORIGIN, LANGUAGE, DISABILITY OR POLITICAL OPINION?	25
4.5. HOW DOES THE PRODUCT ADDRESS SITUATIONS WHERE SOCIETY IS BIASED?	25
4.6. ANY OTHER COMMENTS?	26
5. Q5: DISCRIMINATION	27
5.1. DOES THE OBJECT CONDUCT BIOMETRIC CATEGORIZATION OR SOCIAL SCORING, AND IF SO, FOR WHAT PURPOSE?	27
5.2. CAN THE OBJECT BE CONVINCED TO PRODUCE ILLEGAL OR DISCRIMINATORY CONTENT?	27
5.3. HOW DOES THE OBJECT ADDRESS SITUATIONS WHERE CONTENT IS OFFENSIVE OUT-GROUP BUT NOT IN-GROUP?	28
5.4. HOW DOES THE OBJECT ADDRESS SITUATIONS WHERE IT IS REQUESTED TO REPRODUCE OR SUMMARISE FACTUALLY, ETHICALLY OR LEGALLY PROBLEMATIC CONTENT?	28
5.5. ANY OTHER COMMENTS?	29
6. Q6: MULTILINGUALITY AND CROSS-CULTURAL KNOWLEDGE	30
6.1. WHICH LANGUAGES ARE SUPPORTED OR ENVISAGED?	30
6.2. WHICH LOW-RESOURCE LANGUAGES ARE INCLUDED?	31
6.3. IS THE PRODUCT MORE LIKELY TO PRODUCE ILLEGAL, DISCRIMINATORY OR OTHERWISE TROUBLING CONTENT WHEN USING LOW-RESOURCE LANGUAGES?	31
6.4. QUALITY CONTROL AND ROBUSTNESS: ARE THE RESULTS THE SAME WHEN ASKING THE SAME QUESTION IN DIFFERENT LANGUAGES, AND SHOULD THEY BE?	31
6.5. HOW DOES THE PRODUCT TAKE INTO ACCOUNT DIFFERENT USAGES OF WORDS OR EXPRESSIONS AND DIFFERENT CULTURAL CONTEXTS BY DIFFERENT COMMUNITIES THAT SPEAK THE SAME LANGUAGE?	32
6.6. ANY OTHER COMMENTS?	32
7. Q7: PRIVACY AND THE PROTECTION OF PERSONAL DATA	33
7.1. WHAT KIND OF DATA IS COLLECTED FROM END-USERS?	33
7.1.1. Directly by requesting information	34
7.1.2. Through use of the object	35
7.1.3. Through inferences?	35
7.1.4. Other ways?	36
7.2. DOES THE OBJECT CONDUCT EMOTION RECOGNITION? AND IF SO FOR WHAT PURPOSE?	36
7.3. WHAT DATA AND MODELS ARE SHARED BACK TO THE DEVELOPERS OR THIRD PARTIES SUCH AS POTENTIAL ADVERTISERS?	37

7.4.	WHAT DATA AND MODELS MIGHT BE SHARED BETWEEN END-USERS OF THE SAME PRODUCT [IN A SMART-HOME ENVIRONMENT FOR EXAMPLE, WILL DIFFERENT MEMBERS OF THE SAME HOUSEHOLD BE ABLE ACCESS INFORMATION ABOUT EACH OTHER?]	37
7.5.	IS THERE COLLATERAL EFFECT UPON NON-USERS, SUCH AS VISITORS WHOSE PRESENCE (LOCATION DATA), OTHER DATA, OR VOICE MAY BE CAPTURED BY THE PRODUCT?	39
7.6.	WHAT WOULD BE THE EVENTUAL CONSEQUENCES OF NOT COLLECTING INFORMATION ABOUT THE USER FOR ONSITE TRAINING?	40
7.7.	ARE END-USERS INFORMED OF WHAT DATA MIGHT BE COLLECTED AND WITH WHOM IT MAY BE SHARED?	41
7.8.	IS CONSENT OBTAINED FOR DATA COLLECTION?	41
7.9.	CAN END-USERS REQUEST FOR DATA TO BE ERASED OR CORRECTED?	41
7.10.	FUNCTION CREEP: CAN YOU ENVISAGE THE PRODUCT BEING USED FOR PURPOSES OTHER THAN WHAT IT IS INTENDED FOR, WITH ADVERSE PRIVACY CONSEQUENCES?	42
7.11.	ANY OTHER COMMENTS?	42
8.	Q8: SECURITY AND SAFETY	43
8.1.	WHAT STRATEGIES HAVE BEEN EMPLOYED TO RENDER THE OBJECT RESILIENT TO RISKS EMERGING FROM BAD ACTORS?	43
8.2.	WHAT MEASURES HAVE BEEN INCLUDED TO RENDER THE OBJECT RESILIENT TO RISKS POSED BY ACCIDENTS, NATURAL DISASTERS AND OTHER SAFETY CONCERNS?	44
8.3.	WHAT MATERIAL HARM CAN YOU IMAGINE THIS OBJECT COULD RESULT IN OR CONTRIBUTE TO?	44
8.4.	WHAT IMMATERIAL HARM CAN YOU IMAGINE THIS OBJECT COULD RESULT IN OR CONTRIBUTE TO?	44
8.5.	ARE THERE ANY WAYS THAT YOU CAN IMAGINE SOMEONE WITH MALICIOUS INTENT MISUSING THE OBJECT TO INFLICT MATERIAL OR IMMATERIAL HARM?	45
8.6.	ANY OTHER COMMENTS?	45
9.	Q9: OTHER RIGHTS, USER EXPERIENCE AND OTHER CONCERNS	47
9.1.	WHAT IS IT LIKE TO INTERACT WITH THE OBJECT (USER EXPERIENCE)?	47
9.2.	WHAT OTHER RIGHTS MIGHT THE PRODUCT INTERFERE WITH?	48
9.3.	ANY OTHER CONCERNS?	48
10.	Q10: EU AI ACT COMPATIBILITY	49
10.1.	GENERAL PURPOSE AI	49
10.2.	49	
10.2.1.	<i>If yes to any of the above:</i>	49
10.2.2.	49	
10.2.	UNACCEPTABLE RISK	49
10.3.	50	
3.	HIGH RISK	50
10.3.1.	<i>If yes to any of the above:</i>	50
12.	Q11: CONCLUSIONS	52
12.1.	SUBMITTING PARTNER	52
12.2.	CONCLUSION BY AQUI	52
12.3.	CONCLUSION BY AQUE	53
12.4.	CONCLUSION BY FS	53
12.5.	CONCLUSION BY HMS	53

Pilot 1, which is assessed here, consists of two parts, a ‘distributed federated learning architecture’ which is intended to be privacy-preserving, and a demo of a ‘context-aware smart home assistant’. The federated learning architecture is designed first with the ELOQUENCE consortium in mind, but it is also intended as a model for balancing privacy and technological development for a potential commercial development of the smart home assistant demo.

The federated learning architecture entails that the LLM is trained and personalized locally with user data and then to preserve the privacy of users, updates to the model are shared back to developers rather than the user data itself. Meanwhile the context-aware smart home assistant (Aura) is intended as an LLM-based home assistant with abilities to schedule calendars, answer emails, answer questions based on its training and similar. In its current form it is not envisaged to interact with other infrastructure (such as lights, temperature, fridges, dishwashers and the like) nor is it envisaged to have browsing capabilities.

Aura is intended to be continuously monitoring in-house conversations both assistant-human and human-human, and to have the ability to differentiate between different speakers. This is done to improve the model’s ability to jump into conversations already aware of the context once it spots a wake-up word. The conversations it monitors are transcribed and archived locally but not shared outside the home.

In this assessment the assessors have noted the potential of the technology presented both in terms of expansion to other languages and in terms of potential usage in other environments than private homes. They have also, however, raised a number of concerns and questions:

For the federated learning architecture:

- *FL structure can lead to the introduction of bias over time as the updates to the model are used to train and update models in the entire FL network. (See comments, questions and answers to Q1 and Q4)*
- *Potential concerns also related to intentional model poisoning on the part of some users (Q3.3, 5.3 and 8)*
- *Concerns related to feasibility (Q1)*

For the smart home assistant:

- *Main concern related to the interpretation of ‘context-aware’ which is currently interpreted as requiring constant monitoring of both human-assistant conversations (expected) and human-human conversations in the home (unexpected) which are transcribed and stored locally.*
- *Locally stored transcriptions of human-human interactions are problematic for several reasons. Private conversations taking place inside a person’s home are among the most intimate (and therefore protected) aspects of a person’s right to privacy. This means that constant monitoring, transcribing and archiving of conversations as anticipated in this demo constitutes an intense interference with the right to privacy for the user – especially users who have not consented (guests) and vulnerable users who may not be able to refuse to consent (children). For this reason there is an inherent privacy concern related to constant monitoring regardless of whether the transcriptions are shared outside the home and whether they are accessible by other inside-home users, though both types of data sharing/data leaks aggravate the interference (Q7) Assessors notes specific concerns related to:*
 - o *Privacy leaks within the home (from one family member to another) i.e. As Aura would be listening to private conversations between two family members, it might use the*

eloquence

information in conversations not intended for some other family members. For instance, a mother may have advised a teenage daughter on issues concerning sexuality, or parents may have discussed the Christmas presents their children will receive. And information from such conversations could be leaked to other family members(Q7 + Q5)

- *Concerns related to privacy breaches outside the home. i.e hacks from malicious actors or the seizing of records by authorities etc) (Q8)*
- *Concerns related to obtaining consent: from all members of the family and from guests visiting the home (Q1, Q7, Q5.1)*
- *Concerns related to the GDPR-ensured right to delete personal information once transcribed (Q7.1)*
- *Concerns related to the chilling effect on the right of freedom of expression (Q9.2)*
- *Currently there is no convincing explanation for why this home assistant would need to monitor and transcribe human-human interactions when not having been woken up with a wake-up word. (Q1)*
- *Training on home environment, including from human-human interaction potentially problematic*
 - *Concerns related to the device learning from habits and conversations the user may not wish for it to learn from potentially leading to data leaks. (Q7.1)*
 - *Concerns related to the perpetuation of hierarchies in the environment the smart home assistant is trained on. (Q4)*
- *Philosophical questions raised by constant monitoring of human-human interactions and context-awareness:*
 - *Does the smart home assistant gain responsibility to intervene if it suspects foul play or medical emergencies taking place in the home? (8.6)*

In terms of user-friendliness and technical aspects of the smart home assistant the assessors also questioned:

The computer power needed to perform local updates and to store 24/7 recordings. (Q1)

The usefulness (with respect also to existing similar products which claim not to record users outside assistant-user interactions) of a smart home assistant with no interaction with infrastructure and no browsing capabilities, especially when compared with the intensity of the privacy intrusion.(Q7.5)

Creepiness factor of assistant 'jumping into' conversations. (Q9)

0. Introduction WP6 assessment template (v.2)

The filling in of this template is designed to assist in the work to assess and ensure that technology produced by the ELOQUENCE project is respectful of EU values i.e., privacy, non-discrimination, robustness in legal, ethical and technical terms, reliability and trustworthiness, interpretability and explainability, security and safety. The template is intended to be a collaborative document where all members of a multidisciplinary expert panel (assessors) can contribute in an asynchronous manner.

The submitting partner will be the first to fill in the template, providing important background information for the other assessors. Some questions can only be answered by the submitting partner. Those will be marked in **turquoise**. Hereafter all assessors (including the submitting partner) are asked to answer the questions marked in **yellow**.

Each theme of the assessment is initiated with a box such as this one with a brief description of the theme assessed as well as several **guiding questions**. Assessors are asked to provide comments on all themes, but can focus on the guiding questions they are best equipped to answer. The guiding questions are repeated in the box and in the space below to ease navigation in the document as it grows when assessors include comments, screenshot etc.

Please do not delete any answers from the other assessors but add instead your own answers below or above. Please initiate all comments and suggestions with your initials.

Assessment of: Privacy-preserving language model learning through decentralized training in smart homes and partners institutions

Assessment Date: 20.1.2025

Assessment No. V02001

The assessment was completed by the chair of the panel on [date], on the basis of contributions made by members of the following panel:

1. Submitting partner:
AS, Aleix Sant, Telefonica
JS, Jordi Luque, Telefonica
2. AQui. Alberto Quintavalla, Community of Experts (external)
3. AQue, Alexandre Quemy, Community of Experts (external)
4. FS, Farhan Sahito, Privanova
5. HMS, Helga Molbæk-Steensig, Chair, EUI.

1. Q1: What is the object of assessment?

For the submitting ELOQUENCE partner: Please attach also a file representing or describing the current version of the envisaged product or other object of assessment.

Guiding questions:

What is it [an algorithm; sandbox, demo, etc?]

Which version is it, what models does it apply?

What data has it been trained on, if any?

What is its purpose?

What kinds of unauthorized use (mission creep) would the object be at risk of?

What will be its benefits for developers, deployers, and end-users? And who are its deployers and end-users? [While developers are the creators of the object, deployers are the buyers/owners, and end-users are the individuals using the product. As an example, an AI deployed by a call centre would be developed by the submitting partner, while the deployer would be the purchasing call centre, and the end-user would be the customers calling the call centre]

1.1. *What is it [an algorithm; sandbox, demo, etc?]*

Pilot 1 aims to deliver two main outcomes of different nature:

1. A **Distributed Federated Learning architecture** encompassing an algorithm for privacy-preserving training of LLMs and ASR models. The architecture will be set up between the Barcelona Supercomputing Centre BSC -- acting as a cloud provider -- and the end-users, e.g. the partner institutions -- acting as clients.
 - a. In this **algorithm**, a global/federated LLM and ASR models are iteratively updated by partly uploading the local trained models from each client. To achieve successful results, the global model should effectively learn from all distributed clients' data while ensuring such data remains confidential. The learning paradigm in this architecture is controlled by a comprehensive framework mainly developed in Python.
 - b. A **Command Line Interface (CLI)** to the ELOQUENCE's consortium will be provided to perform the federation of LLMs and speech models from different clients/partners and the cloud server (BSC).
2. **Showcase in a smart home scenario (demo)** of a personalized, conversational, and context-aware **virtual agent/assistant**, powered by the previous LLM and ASR capabilities. The showcased AI models are finetuned in the previous stage in a privacy-preserving fashion from several heterogeneous clients and datasets. For example, the data from this pilot and the other pilots. In overall the demo aims to showcase:
 - a. A virtual agent/assistant that continuously monitors in-house conversations and gathers the user's interactions creating the necessary context. For example, by summarizing conversations and distinguishing different speaker voices and roles.
 - b. A virtual agent/assistant that can jump into the current human-human conversation after it spots a specific wake-up-word. So, at any moment, the user can make specific queries to

the agent/assistant, for example, related to previous or current human-human conversations or some previously stored knowledge of the home or an external database.

ASSESSORS COMMENTS:

AQue: I think it is important to describe how federated learning works for less technical people, especially in order to show the possible bias and weaknesses of such architecture w.r.t. privacy. In particular, it is important to specify that

1. The data produced by the user stays locally,
2. The model is also trained and updated locally but part of the model's update is sent to the remote server that aggregates the results.

One requirement then is that the user needs to have hardware powerful enough to:

1. Run a model locally for inference
2. Fine-tune a model and apply larger updates

I think this is a limiting factor that should be discussed because despite the impressive progresses made towards running inference on less demanding hardware, fine-tuning remains notably more resource intensive.

Is the data transfer to the central server done periodically or live? Will the user know each time?

When is the fine-tuning performed (e.g. on a regular basis? continuously?)?

How is the new fine-tuned model deployed to the user in case the model runs locally? On demand or automatically? Will the user be informed?

Is the fine-tuning done to improve the overall capability of the base model or/and done for each particular client to be more suitable for their needs and particular household? In particular, it is not clear to me what are the type of capabilities that we expect from such assistant.

From reading the current description, I struggle to understand the concrete use-cases and problems that the object tries to address, and in particular how the technical solution proposed here solves them better than what it already available (whether State-of the-Art(SoTA) or consumer ready):

- What are the tasks that the assistant is supposed to do - is it limited to general knowledge questions? Is it supposed to interact with connected devices? Is it supposed to also access the user's laptop to do some tasks such as answering emails (as mentioned in one of the questions)?
- In case the assistant will interact with connected devices, did you consider that something as important if not more important than voice for the contextual interaction is the precise localization and presence detection and recognition?
- What are the tasks that the assistant is supposed to perform that would benefit from the data from people not in the household (as it is the assumption behind using Federated Learning)? Why would one need other people's data to tailor a model for his/her purpose

unless we are talking about general capabilities of the model (e.g. support for a language with a small number of speakers w.r.t. English)?

There are many concerns related to privacy with the approach described here:

- Federated learning is known to be vulnerable to attacks that reconstitute the original data from the gradient (the updates being sent to the central server), whether the attack is performed by a third party or by the data collector. There are now attacks to reconstruct the data in a SOTA federated learning **without** prior knowledge on the data. There will always be new attacks developed in such setting and as soon as such project is not properly maintained, the entire data is at risk.

Sources:

- Privacy Attacks in Federated Learning (<https://www.nist.gov/blogs/cybersecurity-insights/privacy-attacks-federated-learning>)
 - GI-SMN: Gradient Inversion Attack against Federated Learning without Prior Knowledge (<https://arxiv.org/abs/2405.03516>)
 - Security and Privacy Issues of Federated Learning (<https://arxiv.org/pdf/2307.12181>)
- Even if the raw data is not moved from the household to the central server, updates are and, in the worst case, we have to consider the raw data can be recovered partly or completely from them. Therefore, the security of data movement is a valid concern. Data is moved from a secure place where it is produced - the home of the data producer - to a place with less guarantee by definition - especially given the fact that the data will be used to fine-tune models that will then be redistributed to many clients. It adds two additional weak points that can serve as an attack vector: the data movement and the data storage and utilization in the centralized place. The risk associated with the data movement can be limited by using modern end-to-end encryption techniques with forward secrecy guarantee such as double ratchet (e.g. if the encryption is compromised, the data transferred in the future is not compromised, only the past data).

I would like to emphasize that we are talking about some of the most private data a citizen can produce, i.e. any discussion or movement one might have at home - in one of the last bastions of privacy. That can include sexual preferences, political orientation or anything of this nature - far beyond the scope of assisting a user in daily tasks or interacting with connected devices. I would personally **never** opt-in for such system because the risk/result in the worst scenario is disproportionate compared to the ratio benefits/convenience offered by such system. In particular, there already exist local and offline cheap alternative that are (almost) consumer ready s.a. home-assistant coupled to local LLMs.

I would really advocate for a solution that meet the following criteria:

1. The original personal data produced by any citizen is never transferred from the place it is produced to a centralized place - even a gradient -.
2. Any transfer of data is secured by end-to-end encryption and stored encrypted-at-rest in a centralized place or it does not happen.
3. The original personal data produced by the citizen is only temporary stored locally where it is produced before being transformed into a synthetic **and** (pseudo)anonymized data that can be transferred for the purpose of fine tuning if such capabilities cannot be done locally.

Without the respect of these 3 constraints there is no guarantee that citizen data will not be collected and acquired by a third party.

In particular, if we assume that the local hardware is capable of fine-tuning the model, then we can expect to be able to run models to generate synthetic data and anonymize data from the raw data. In addition, most of the newer iterations of the most performant LLMs are trained using synthetic data, i.e. data that was generated by another LLM or a model and not directly by a human - leading to much better results than traditional fine-tuning on human-generated and annotated data.

FS: The use of Federated Learning effectively addresses privacy concerns by limiting centralized data storage while still enabling continuous model improvement. However, FL is not immune to security threats, particularly data poisoning attacks, where compromised devices could introduce biases or vulnerabilities. A robust mechanism for detecting and filtering out adversarial inputs is essential to maintain system integrity.

HMS: For this pilot it makes sense to consider aim 1 (the federated learning architecture) not only in the current set up with BSC as cloud provider and ELOQUENCE partners as clients, but also the presumed use of the same architecture for the smart home demo once this becomes ready for commercial roll-out – i.e. with a commercial cloud provider (presumably, but not necessarily, Telefonica) and private users as clients. In terms of security, bias and privacy these potential future users will therefore be considered as well.

As for the substantive abilities of the demo 2a (the virtual agent which continuously monitors conversations) raises particular concerns related to privacy. These concerns prevail especially of course if the federated learning architecture is breached, but also if it is not. The concept of context awareness does not need a device to record conversations or other information continuously, but can also be context aware over several sessions where it has been called upon specifically. It is not certain that the current rules under GDPR would allow for such a functionality as it requires the minimization of data collection to what is strictly necessary and it is debatable whether functionality 2b is sufficiently necessary to allow such an excessive collection of data – moreover GDPR requires explicit consent for data-collection which creates a problem for non-primary users (individuals present in a smart home who are not the device owners).

Submitting partner's comments:

AS: Regarding the concerns on the computational resources needed in the clients (users' device), we are going to use LoRA (Low-Rank Adaptation) adapters and will fine-tune just the adapter, significantly decreasing the computational needs on the devices (0.25%-0.45% of training parameters in the base model). Both the data transfer (uploading and downloading weights) will be done periodically in communication cycles in a synchronous manner. At the moment of writing this, the deployment to the user is done automatically and the user is not informed.

The fine-tuning is performed on the user side to enhance the model's capabilities locally, and, consequently, through the Federated Learning process, this also improves the aggregated model's performance across a wider range of domains (given that the clients operate indifferent domains)

Outcome 1 aims to develop a functional Distributed Federated Learning architecture. Our goal is to verify the effectiveness of this training approach in producing a more capable model by aggregating information from multiple clients, potentially spanning different domains. Importantly, this outcome is not limited to the domestic environment; rather, we aim to ensure that the federated framework operates effectively across diverse domains (e.g., testing datasets from different partners).

Outcome 2 focuses on showcasing an assistant's capabilities in a household environment, specifically including summarization, information retrieval, NER, and the ability to answer questions based on both previously recorded conversations and general knowledge. The assistant is not designed to interact with other devices. The underlying model may come from prior federated learning training or from powerful models developed in other work packages of this project. However, the primary goal here is not federated learning itself, but rather the development of a helpful assistant for a domestic environment that learns from household members' conversations.

I want to point out that sometimes we might have connected the two outcomes as one thing, but for clarity, it's better to see them as different things we want to achieve. Of course, they can be connected, but it's not our true aim. Our aim is to get the federated learning framework working on one side, and to showcase an assistant (powered by LLM/ASR) suitable for a household environment on the other side.

When we say the assistant benefits from others, we are referring to improvements in the model's general capabilities. For example, in terms of multilingualism, an aggregated model can enhance its ability to communicate in multiple languages by learning from clients who speak different languages. As a result, all clients that download the aggregated model gain improved multilingual capabilities.

1.2. *Which version is it, what models does it apply?*

The Distributed Federated Learning architecture between the BSC and the partners institutions is currently in its initial development phase (i.e., version 0). Our development is based on the open-sourced FederatedScope¹ repository released by Alibaba (Kuang et al., 2023). FederatedScope is a comprehensive federated learning library designed for scientific, ease of use and adaptable customization across a wide range of federated learning tasks. It incorporated numerous features to meet the growing needs of federated and privacy-preserving learning.

We are working on further adapting the FederatedScope's library to support the federated learning requirements for LLM/ASR models of ELOQUENCE. Up to the first version of this assessment, we have conducted some initial experiments on federated fine-tuning LLMs in both "standalone" and "distributed" modes. In the employed framework, "standalone" refers to simulations of federation on a single machine (i.e., all clients hosted on the same server), whereas "distributed" refers to the actual distribution of clients across multiple machines. At this time, current "standalone" development has been setting up only between TID machines.

The development of the virtual agent/assistant, for using in a demo, is still in its infancy too (i.e., version 0). So far, we aim to power the agent/assistant with an aggregated model resulting from the federated learning paradigm described earlier. We are training the agent/assistant based on multilingual, open-source and open-data models that perform well in popular reasoning and question-answering tasks. We are experimenting with LLMs meeting these requirements like as: Occiglot-7B-eu5-instruct, Aya-23-8B, Salamandra-7B-instruct and EuroLLM-9B-Instruct. We have conducted a preliminary testing of the models to assess their potential in following instructions, in common knowledge questions and in mathematical reasoning. We have compared their performance across different FL aggregated versions, comprising a varying number of clients participating in each federated learning loop.

¹ <https://github.com/alibaba/FederatedScope>

AQue: At the time of assessing this object, the exact models mentioned (Occiglot-7B-eu5-instruct, Aya-23-8B, Salamandra-7B-instruct and EuroLLM-9B-Instruct) are not SOTA and by the time it is implemented, many more small models with better performances will be released.

It might be interesting to list precise requirements or constraints on the models that could be used by the project. For instance:

- the model needs to be small enough to run on consumer hardware,
- it needs to support X or Y languages,
- it needs to be an open-source model,
- It needs to support tool calling,
- it needs to score at least *this* score on *that* benchmark, etc),
- It needs to support fine-tuning via *that* technique,

At the time of writing this assessment, a model like Mistral-Nemo-8B quantized produces significantly better results than the three models above-mentioned. It is not trained on open datasets, nor provide the code to train the model, but if this is a requirement, a model like Granite from IBM is actually what is the closest from a full open-source model (and also perform better in its instruct version). This is not to suggest using these models but to shows that it would be beneficial to consider an LLM agnostic platform and selecting the best model at the moment the model needs to be trained.

Submitting partner's comments:

AS: The final model should support at least English, Spanish, Italian, Greek and Serbian (and ideally all the official EU languages if possible). The final model should be European-based. The final model should be open-source. Additional requirements are still to be decided.

1.3. What data has it been trained on, if any?

In the initial experiments, we have performed federated fine-tuning across multiple clients using the Alpaca dataset. To evaluate and monitor the performance of both the aggregated model and the individual client models, we utilized three test sets: one in-domain and two out-of-domain.

The in-domain test set consists of an unseen portion of the Alpaca dataset, while the two out-of-domain test sets are: MMLU, which assesses the model's ability to generalize across a diverse range of tasks, and GSM-8K, which evaluates mathematical reasoning and problem-solving skills. Below is a detailed description of each dataset:

- **ALPACA**² (Taori, et al. 2023): This popular instruction-tuning dataset consists of over 52K instructions in English. It includes natural language questions and responses for various NLP tasks such as text generation, translation, open QA, etc., and a wide range of domains, like as math, text processing or code generation. Originally the dataset aims to train/evaluate the model's ability in following instructions and producing

² <https://huggingface.co/datasets/tatsu-lab/alpaca>

accurate responses, thus assessing its natural language understanding, reasoning, and task completion across various domains.

For tailoring the dataset to the pilot's requirements, it has been split into different partitions, without overlap, with the aim of simulating independent end-user's personal data, thus mimicking interactions occurring in a household. Additionally, an extra non-overlapping amount of sample has been saved to evaluate the aggregated model. Below are some samples from the dataset.

```
{
  "instruction": "Give three tips for staying healthy.",
  "input": "",
  "output": "1. Eat a balanced diet and make sure to include plenty of fruits and vegetables. \n2. Exercise regularly to keep your body active and strong. \n3. Get enough sleep and maintain a consistent sleep schedule."
},
{
  "instruction": "What are the three primary colors?",
  "input": "",
  "output": "The three primary colors are red, blue, and yellow."
},
{
  "instruction": "Evaluate this sentence for spelling and grammar mistakes",
  "input": "He finnished his meal and left the restaurant",
  "output": "He finished his meal and left the restaurant."
},
}
```

- **MMLU**³ (Massive Multitask Language Understanding, (Hendrycks, et al. 2020)): This comprehensive benchmark is designed to evaluate a model's broad knowledge and reasoning capabilities. It consists of approximately 1,000 multiple-choice questions, covering 57 task categories across a wide range of disciplines, including the humanities, social sciences, and hard sciences. The questions are in English and challenge the model to demonstrate a deep understanding of diverse topics, making it a valuable tool for assessing multitask learning and general reasoning skills across various fields of knowledge.
- **GSM-8K**⁴ (Grade School Math 8K, (Cobbe, et al. 2021)): This evaluation dataset is designed to evaluate a model's arithmetical reasoning and mathematical problem-solving skills. Consisting of approximately 1,000 math problems in English, this benchmark specifically tests a model's ability to solve complex math tasks, making it an effective evaluation tool for Chain-of-Thought reasoning capability. The problems require logical progression through multiple steps, providing a robust measure of a model's proficiency in handling mathematical challenges.

The previous datasets are employed to assess the generalization capabilities of the aggregated model (using ALPACA dataset) and avoid for catastrophic forgetting.

To evaluate the understanding capabilities of the agent/assistant for real smart home scenarios, we are developing the ELOQUENCE dataset. This test set will enable the assessment of both classical FT models and the proposed FL models in tasks such as slot-filling, summarization, and NER within a real domestic environment for both text and speech modalities.

- **ELOQUENCE** (2025): This novel dataset is the result of recording real interactions in Spanish within a recreated domestic environment: The User Experience Lab (UX Lab) from TID. The goal is to simulate common everyday conversations among household members. The resulting dataset will consist of audio recordings and their human-validated transcriptions, along with annotated speaker turns, manually curated and annotated. Each dialogue will comprise several turns and will follow a similar formatting as the Fused Dataset produced by the T1.1-1.2 from the WP1, which is used for adaptation of ELOQUENCE's technologies to conversational data.

³ <https://huggingface.co/datasets/cais/mmlu>

⁴ <https://huggingface.co/datasets/openai/gsm8k>

In the upcoming versions of our pilot, we aim to adapt our models by implementing federated fine-tuning using conversational datasets that involve multiple turns and Task-Oriented Dialogs (TOD). We are considering datasets such as MultiWOZ 2.2⁵, SpokenWOZ⁶ and Fisher⁷.

ASSESSORS COMMENTS:

No comment.

1.4. *What is its purpose?*

The primary objective of Pilot 1 is to develop more powerful and personalized LLMs and ASR models using the privacy-preserving method of federated learning and adapted to the home environment. We aim to enhance user performance in specific tasks by leveraging individual user contexts and aggregating models trained by other users on their respective (independent) tasks. All this is done ensuring the security and privacy of each user's data by means of model weight aggregation, establishing federated learning as a reliable privacy-preserving training technique. Future releases of the algorithm will also include differential privacy techniques to further enhance privacy requirements.

ASSESSORS COMMENTS:

AQue: Federated learning is subject to many attacks that in practice render it almost defenseless to any attacker with enough time, compute power or additional data. I have myself implemented differential privacy techniques and we were always able to attack in a way or another to identify the user or a particular attribute by exploiting quasi-identifiers, statistical attacks and non-anonymized data. Differential privacy usually does not account for real life scenarios when it is possible to consolidate the dataset to attack with additional datasets. In practice, I have yet to see a dataset that is no subject to membership inference attack or GAN attack.

The only cases where we were not able to re-identify individuals or their characteristics is when the added noise was so large that the dataset was effectively rendered unusable.

The main concern here is that if the data from the user is recovered somehow, even if anonymized (i.e. PII are removed) it would still be possible to perform membership inference attacks because some of the characteristics needed to train such model has to stay in the dataset (e.g. a the mention to a restaurant's name can locate a user in about 5km radius, another mention to the a gym's membership can further reduce that, etc. to the point where it becomes likely easy to identify precisely someone - and the probability to do so increase with the size of the datasets and the number of events collected by the same user).

AQui: It is not entirely clear to me what are the "specific tasks" where user performance will be enhanced. In other words, it seems to me that "specific tasks" solely refer to what is mentioned under one of the two main aims of Pilot 1 (as described in 1.1): the development of a virtual agent/assistant that could answer specific queries posed by the users. On a different note, I think it is important to devote attention to how models trained by different users are aggregated, especially in case different security and privacy

⁵ https://github.com/budzianowski/multiwoz/tree/master/data/MultiWOZ_2.2

⁶ <https://spokenwoz.github.io/SpokenWOZ-github.io/>

⁷ <https://catalog ldc.upenn.edu/LDC2004T19>, <https://catalog ldc.upenn.edu/LDC2004S13>

rules have previously been applied. Relatedly, it is not entirely clear how (and why) different privacy techniques may be conducive to greater privacy protection.

AS: AQui is right in the sense it is not very clear in the previous paragraph what we meant by “specific task”. In fact, we are thinking to improve model capabilities in both general and specific tasks. By specific tasks we mean for example summarization, NER, information retrieval... For instance, we want to showcase how our assistant is able to summarize previously recorded conversation. Therefore, federate finetuning a model with the task of summarization across clients with different samples and sub-domains is something we may do that aligns with the previous stated sentence “we aim to enhance user performance in specific tasks by leveraging individual user contexts”, since we continuously deploy the aggregated model in each client after a communication round. In the previous sentence, user context would refer to the private samples of each clients that would have been use to federate fine-tuning.

Differential privacy in federated learning ensures that individual data contributions remain indistinguishable by adding noise to model updates before aggregation. This prevents adversaries from reconstructing private data or identifying specific users. Thus, it provides an additional layer of protection, ensuring that sensitive data remains private while still enabling collaborative model training. In fact, there is a tradeoff in DP between privacy and accuracy. Adding noise to model updates enhances privacy by preventing data reconstruction but can degrade model performance by reducing accuracy.

1.5. *What kinds of unauthorized use (mission creep) would the object be at risk of?*

The object (LLM/ASR model) could be at risk of unauthorized access to its training or private data through malicious attacks or jailbreak attempts. This includes methods such as prompt injection or parameter reverse engineering, which could expose sensitive information.

ASSESSORS COMMENTS:

AQue: There is also the risk of model poisoning if some users decide to produce carefully crafted by data to disrupt in anyway the model. The model updates would be then sent back to the main server, potentially incorporated into the new updated model that is then redeployed to the other users. The attacked could also be unauthorized users (home visitors who have not agreed to be monitored).

AQui: The risks stemming from unauthorized use could also extend to the use of this object in settings that are different (e.g., work offices) from the context originally envisaged (i.e., home). Another risk could be that the unauthorized use would lead to the distribution of inaccurate information based on the queries made by users (rather than collecting private information). A last risk may concern an end-user who purportedly provides wrongful queries to the product.

HMS: In addition to uses in non-home settings which could be problematic (office, bar, club, school, etc= One could imagine a situation in which this product could be used in a home/family setting by a controlling or abusive spouse or parent. The fact that it records all conversations at all times and the whereabouts of individuals in the come could aid an abusive person in gaining information about and controlling people in their home to an extreme degree.

1.6. *What will be its benefits for developers, deployers, and end-users?*

The benefits include the creation of a more powerful LLM/ASR model tailored to specific tasks, while also excelling in various additional tasks. For examples, thanks to the decentralized data storage, an AI model originally designed for English can be adapted to perform well in the same tasks for new languages. This adaptability enhances the model's versatility and utility across different contexts and applications, ultimately leading to more efficient and effective solutions.

ASSESSORS COMMENTS:

AQue: Can you provide concrete examples of such specific and additional tasks? Can support for other languages be generated in other ways such as by translating in a way or another the examples used to fine-tune in one language? e.g. data produced by a Portuguese user is translated into Romanian (either locally or via an adapter on the gradient)?

AQui: The scalability of this model is promising in the sense that it is not only applicable to new languages, but potentially also to different settings. These benefits can mostly be reaped by developers and deployers. It is also possible that end-users may benefit from the scalability of this model; however, it would be important to acknowledge that certain privacy risks may materialize depending on the setting (e.g. workplaces with sensitive information such as hospitals).

Submitting partner's comments:

As: By "specific tasks" here, we meant the task a specific client is fine-tuned on, whereas by "additional tasks," we meant the tasks that the model could also learn from the federated fine-tuning with other clients being fine-tuned in other tasks (or domains). For example, client A fine-tuning on its dataset for summarization and client B fine-tuning on NER.

1.7. *Any other comments?*

2. Q2: Explainability and interpretability

All GenAI applications are required to let users know that they are interacting with an AI, but transparency requirements go beyond that. The submitting partner should include information on what has been done to facilitate **Explainable Artificial Intelligence (XAI)**, while other assessors are tasked with determining to what extent it is clear for users that they are interacting with an AI, how it works and what kinds of information it gathers about them, including whether they are being profiled/categorised in any way. The question is important because when AIs are not fully explainable and interpretable, their use can dramatically reduce consumers' ability to interact and gauge whether they are subject to discrimination or nudged in any particular direction

Guiding questions:

Does the object let the users know that they are interacting with an AI?

What has been done to facilitate Explainable Artificial Intelligence (XAI)?

Is there a summary of copyrighted data used for training (or otherwise)?

Will it be clear for users how the system works?

Does the object profile end-users or otherwise make them subject to decisions based on information gathered about them, thus activating their (non-binding) 'right to an explanation' under Recital 71 GDPR?

2.1. *What has been done to facilitate Explainable Artificial Intelligence (XAI)?*

To facilitate Explainable Artificial Intelligence, we aim to only employ open-source resources, including datasets, models, and the FL framework on which our new functionalities are built. Additionally, the resulting adapted LLMs/ASR models, along with any experimental results obtained using our framework, will be made publicly available upon completion. This openness will enable researchers to apply both white-box and black-box techniques to our models, leading to deeper insights into XAI. Furthermore, we believe that WP3 within ELOQUENCE could contribute significantly by assessing the datasets and models we work with.

ASSESSORS COMMENTS:

AQue: There is no link between XAI and open-source. Open-source only guarantees the access to the source-code of the different components leveraged to implement the project. However, it does not mean the models themselves are explainable/explained or that they provide an explanation on how they make a decision.

In particular, FL by design aims at transferring only the gradient to the central server. Therefore, someone having access to the central server does not have a single clue of what is the content of the update being aggregated. A concrete scenario could be:

- A user purposefully poisons the model (e.g. insist locally for the LLM to greet him with profanity)
- The model is fined-tuned locally for this particular "task"

The updates sent to the central server is of the form of the gradient, i.e. only some updates on the model's weights. No one can really understand the content of the update, yet it might be used in the model's aggregation.

HMS: It may also be relevant to consider how explainable the model is to regular users.

2.2. *Is there a summary of copyrighted data used for training (or otherwise)?*

Below we list the respective licensees from all the resources we are using during the development of this pilot:

Software: FederatedScope ([Apache-2.0 license](#))

Datasets:

- Alpaca à [Attribution-NonCommercial 4.0 International](#) (CC-BY-NC-4.0)
- GSM-8K à [MIT License](#)
- MMLU à [MIT License](#)
- MultiWoz 2.2 à [Apache License, Version 2.0](#)
- SpokenWoz à [Attribution-NonCommercial 4.0 International](#) (CC-BY-NC-4.0)
- VoxPopuli à [Attribution-NonCommercial 4.0 International](#) (CC-BY-NC-4.0)
- Fisher à [LDC User Agreement for Non-Members](#)

Models:

- OLMo-7B-Instruct-hf à [Apache License, Version 2.0](#)
- Occiglot-7B-eu5-instruct à [Apache License, Version 2.0](#)
- Aya-23-8B à [Attribution-NonCommercial 4.0 International](#) (CC-BY-NC-4.0)
- Salamandra-7b-instruct à [Apache License, Version 2.0](#)
- EuroLLM-9B-Instruct à [Apache License, Version 2.0](#)

Additionally previous models are open data, employing datasets that are openly shared with the intent of fostering innovation, transparency and collaboration. These datasets are typically free to use, modify and redistribute, often under open licenses.

ASSESSORS COMMENTS:

No additional comment.

2.3. *Does the object profile end-users or otherwise make them subject to decisions based on information gathered about them, thus activating their (non-binding) 'right to an explanation' under Recital 71 GDPR?*

In the case of the FL library this question does not apply.

In the case of the demo, the personal agent/assistant does not profile end-users or make decisions that affect them. The proposed agent/assistant, simply responds to user requests based on the user's context, ensuring that interactions are personalized without taking any decisions but helping users.

ASSESSORS COMMENTS:

AQue: It would be important to clarify whether the assistant would be able to use capabilities such as tool callings to interact with connected objects such as lamps. In such case, one can consider that when the model decides to trigger one object's capability (e.g. turn on or off a lamp), it is in fact making a decisions whether it is direct, based on the user's request, or indirect, via learned behavior (e.g. we learned that the user X going in room Y at this hour requires to light the room).

In addition, it is not clear when and how the model is fine-tuned locally, how and when the updates would be sent to the central server and how and when the model would be updated locally.

HMS: while the object is not intended to take decisions about users within the meaning of Article 22 of GDPR, it must be conducting some types of profiling both in terms of collecting information about the context (who is in the house, what are their interests, what level of education do they possess are all questions that could be relevant for a context aware smart home assistant as you describe it) Moreover, the object is intended to identify users based on their voices, right? Otherwise it would not know not to record someone coming into the home who has not consented to be recorded.

Submitting partner's comments:

AS: No tool callings are planned to be performed by the assistant.

At the moment, we perform all the federation training loops in a synchronous way. The cycle is: first, all model fine-tune on their private data (for example, 30 batches). Then, the weights of their adapter are sent to the server and are all aggregated. Subsequently, the updated weights are sent back to all clients, and clients fine-tune again on their private data (30 batches again). This process is repeated step by step. We might explore asynchronous training or rejecting malicious or poorly performing clients in the future, but we haven't started that yet.

Regarding what HMS says, we still need to think about how the object identifies users. It is indeed based on voices, but our module can diarize without having any context of their voices. It can simply identify different voices and assume they come from different speakers. However, as you mentioned, this poses a problem in the case of someone who doesn't give their consent.

2.4. *Does the object let the users know that they are interacting with an AI?*

Yes, the virtual agent/assistant clearly informs users that they are interacting with an AI. When the user activates it using the wake-up word command, i.e., "OK Aura," the virtual agent/assistant introduces itself with a greeting, e.g., "Hello, this is Aura, your personal AI assistant. How may I assist you?"

ASSESSORS COMMENTS:

AQue: How to handle the case where a household receive visitors that are not the regular users? How would they know they are recorded and possibly can interact with an assistant?

AQui: The object lets the users know that they are interacting with an AI. However, the question would be if the object remains active to monitor in-house conversations even when users are not directly interacting with it after a long time. If that is the case, it may well happen that end-users have forgotten that there is a virtual agent/assistant who keeps collecting information. It is also not clear to what extent end-users are profiled and categorised as well as what kinds of information is gathered. This point seems relevant given that it is argued in description 1.1. that the model distinguishes 'different speaker voices and roles'.

HMS: The problem is that the system is active also when it has not been activated. There is no obvious way to resolve this problem for non-primary users.

2.5. *Is it clear for users how the system works?*

ASSESSORS COMMENTS:

AQui: It seems that the users are not provided with enough information on how the system works. A way to tackle that could be to start providing a brief outline of the functioning of the system once it is activated.

HMS: In most cases it is not likely that the user would understand how the system works. For individual answers to questions posed to the system by users, it could provide sources when available, i.e.:

- User: Hi Aura, what is the largest city and capital of Turkey?
- Aura: According to the Wikipedia entry on Turkey, Ankara is the capital, but Istanbul is the largest city.

2.6. *Any other comments?*

Robustness, reliability and trustworthiness go to the very core of what the purpose of the object is and whether it is able to reliably fulfil it. An important factor here is the question of hallucinations which plagued early GenAI in particular. The question relates to what extent the object fulfils its function and produce useful and truthful content. Assessors here are invited to consider in particular the intended function of the object.

Guiding questions:

Can the object be convinced/hacked to produce illegal or otherwise troubling content ([Adversarial testing](#))?

Does the object [hallucinate](#)?

To what extent does the object fulfil its function and produce useful and truthful content?

Can the object be convinced/hacked to produce illegal or otherwise troubling content ([Adversarial testing](#))?

3. Q3: Robustness, reliability and trustworthiness

3.1. *Can the object be convinced/hacked to produce illegal or otherwise troubling content ([Adversarial testing](#))?*

Yes, our object (in this case, the AI agent/assistant) might potentially be convinced or hacked to produce illegal or otherwise troubling content through adversarial attacks. Challenging or deceptive inputs can be intentionally provided to the model to see if it can be tricked into generating harmful, unsafe, or policy-violating outputs.

ASSESSORS COMMENTS:

AQue: Is there any plan to monitor and/or limit and/or remediate to these possible attacks?

AQui: Acknowledging the possibility that the object can be hacked and, consequently, produce troubling content could be flagged to end-users as soon as the object is activated. I think the most challenging part is making implicitly adversarial queries. The reason is that the object will be aimed at answering specific queries from the end-users at home: although those queries may appear innocuous at first glance, they could underly sensitive topics or be confounding due to the specific jargon used.

HMS: What can be done to limit this risk?

3.2. *Does the object [hallucinate](#)?*

Yes, since we are working with LLMs, which are generative-based AI models, they can indeed produce hallucinations. This means they can generate information that appears plausible but is not based on actual data or facts.

ASSESSORS COMMENTS:

AQue: Some of the models proposed (Salamandra-7B-instruct) are not aligned, meaning they may produce additional harmful or inappropriate content. Is aligning the model planned in the research? Maybe it would be great to clarify the model selection process in a repeatable way to select the best model at any time.

AQui: Acknowledging this possibility and communicating that to end-users may also be important. A mere reference to the existence of “hallucination” may not suffice; perhaps, it would be more effective to clearly communicate what a “hallucination” entails for lay people.

HMS: Depending on the tasks involved, what could be done to prevent hallucinations? Will the LLM be linked with a different source for retrieving information different from generating it on the basis of its training? Would it, for example, have browsing capabilities, potentially with an inbuilt preference for certain trusted sources? Could users ask the object to prefer certain sources (for example provide a preferred news outlet for questions such as ‘what’s the most important news stories since yesterday?’)

Submitting partner’s comments:

AS: We are planning to enhance the reliability of responses by implementing Retrieval Augmented Generation (RAG). We are planning to ground its answers from trusted databases and documents. We are also planning to align the models we use (but I think this work will be done in another WP). For the time being, we are not planning to have browsing capabilities.

3.3. *To what extent does the object fulfil its function and produce useful and truthful content?*

Regarding the Distributed Federated Learning architecture, initial experiments between TID machines have confirmed the effectiveness of federation. Consequently, federated learning proves to be an efficient privacy-preserving method for training models, aligning with our primary objective of ensuring privacy. By integrating additional privacy techniques such as differential privacy, we can further enhance the robustness of our algorithm in terms of privacy.

As detailed in Section 6 of Deliverable 2.1, we have examined the impact of the number of clients on instruction tuning within the federation of LLMs. Our experiments focused on instruction tuning of LLMs using the Alpaca dataset. Performance was evaluated using metrics like ROUGE-L and datasets such as Alpaca, MMLU and GSM-8K. The results indicate that the performance of the model in federated learning is influenced by the number of participating clients. Generally, a larger pool of clients enhances model generalization, but it requires careful client selection and management.

Since our previously used test sets do not directly assess truthfulness, we plan to use TruthfulQA⁸ to better understand our models in this regard. TruthfulQA is a benchmark designed to measure truthfulness through simple and multiple-choice questions (both single-true and multi-true), as well as open-ended questions.

To achieve the objective of having a personalized and context-aware virtual agent/assistant, each device will maintain a local private database to store previous conversations summarized by the device. This will enable the agent/assistant to utilize contextual and personal data to provide accurate responses to

⁸ <https://github.com/sylinrl/TruthfulQA>

household users. Although we have not yet decided how we will provide the information to the LLM, we will most likely use a Retrieval Augmented Generation (RAG) system.

Our agent/assistant should not only respond to questions related to previous conversations but also handle general open questions as factually as possible. To test our models' ability to do so, we plan also use TriviaQA⁹, a dataset designed to evaluate reading comprehension and open-domain question answering.

ASSESSORS COMMENTS:

AQue: How long is the local data retained and will the user know or have access to the local storage? If the user has access to it, it is an easy target for malicious model poisoning. If the data is retained forever, this is also a possible attack vector for someone that can gain access to the local device. Will the database be encrypted-at-rest for instance?

This is the first time in the assessment that RAG is mentioned. This is significantly different from fine-tuning and in fact, in-context learning (few-shot + RAG) often yields better results in practice than most fine-tuning for user-based models (i.e. tailored to one particular user as opposed to a general set of tasks or new domain) and does not require the resources for fine-tuning nor simplify the model management and maintenance.

Because of this, I am not sure now that I understand why there is a need to fine-tune the model on top of the in-context learning. Can you clarify what problem fine-tuning will solve and what problem in-context will solve?

AQui: It seems there has been commitment to ensure the production of useful and truthful content. More limited information has been provided on how to protect the object from being hacked to produce illegal or otherwise troubling content. A last remark refers to whether the fact that the agent/assistant would store previous conversations and utilize contextual and personal data to provide accurate responses could lead to making a mistake based on “path-dependency”.

Submitting partner's comments:

AS: When we talk about fine-tuning, we are referring to the federated learning framework we are developing. On the other hand, when we mention in-context learning or having a RAG system, we are focusing on the assistant utilizing these techniques to enhance its performance in responding to user queries.

3.4. Any other comments?

FS: The assistant's transparency measures, such as announcing AI-generated responses, are a positive step. However, users would benefit from more detailed explanations of AI decisions, especially when the assistant influences decision-making in sensitive contexts.

⁹ <https://github.com/mandarjoshi90/triviaqa>

This question is related to bias in a cultural or legal sense, both in the training of the object and in the content it produces. This refers to the fact that there may be situations in which a GenAI produces content that is representative of the material it has been trained on, which in turn is representative of conceptualisations and assumptions in the culture that has produced that material. Often this means leaning towards the western, the able-bodied, and the male, but there have also been [examples](#) where training material has been skewed in a different way.

Guiding questions:

What measures were taken to identify potential biases (implicit, sampling, temporal or otherwise) in the training data or data otherwise relied upon?

What known biases are there in the training data or other sources of information relied upon by the object?

What has been done to mitigate these biases?

Does the product produce biased content, e.g. on account of sex, gender, sexual orientation, gender identity, ethnicity, national origin, language, disability or political opinion?

How does the product address situations where society is biased?

4.1. *What measures were taken to identify potential biases (implicit, sampling, temporal or otherwise) in the training data or data otherwise relied upon?*

So far, no measures have been taken to identify potential biases inherent in the models either in the training datasets. We expect other WPs will assist in this work.

ASSESSORS COMMENTS:

AQui: It seems important to make sure that the other WPs would assist in this, also with regard to 4.2 and 4.3.

FS: One drawback of the federated learning architecture relates to bias reinforcement—if models evolve based on individual user behavior, how does the system ensure it does not amplify existing biases over time? The inclusion of fairness monitoring tools would help maintain balanced AI responses.

HMS: In the descriptions earlier in this template you describe the object differentiating between different individuals or ‘roles’. Does this entail any difference in treatment of different users (such as parental controls or limiting access to settings for some users)? And if so, how would this difference be determined? Would it be part of the initiation of the device or would the machine determine itself whether some users (for example minors) should not have access to all functionalities?

4.2. *What known biases are there in the training data or other sources of information relied upon by the object?*

Although we have not yet conducted specific research on the biases present in the tested models, we acknowledge that they may produce potential biases since this is a known challenge in generative AI technology.

ASSESSORS COMMENTS:

here

4.3. *What has been done to mitigate these biases?*

Thus far, no strategies to mitigate the inherent biases of our models or datasets have been employed. Once again, we believe that WP3 could help in this area.

ASSESSORS COMMENTS:

HMS: this will be worth watching later on as the technology comes closer to finalization. As these assessments are meant to be iterative we can revisit the question of bias at a later stage.

4.4. *Does the product produce biased content, e.g. on account of sex, gender, sexual orientation, gender identity, ethnicity, national origin, language, disability or political opinion?*

ASSESSORS COMMENTS:

AQui: It is very possible that the product may produce biased content; however, it is not possible to know that now especially due to the lack of research on the matter as indicated in 4.2.

4.5. *How does the product address situations where society is biased?*

ASSESSORS COMMENTS:

AQui: As far as it seems from 4.3, there has been no indication on how to address situations where society is biased.

HMS: From early on, it should be acknowledged and actively addressed that a home setting entails explicit and implicit hierarchies such as, adult vs. child, older child vs. younger child, male vs. female, or employer vs employee. Practically all conversations will be affected by such hierarchies. If the issue is not addressed, a home assistant may end up producing inappropriate language or action, enabling abuse based on such hierarchies or contributing to the perpetuation of bias and hierarchy.

5. Q5: Discrimination

This question relates to the production of discriminatory and offensive content. Here a particular challenge is posed by context-specific offensiveness and the difference between internal or in-group language and external or out-group speech. There may be situations where the object is requested by a user to reproduce content that is not offensive in-group but is offensive outgroup (an example could be song-lyrics or satire). In such cases consistently refusing to produce such content because of requested content being offensive in an outgroup context, could constitute a type of censoring or close off cultural content for some users in a problematic way. Conversely, content that is not offensive from the perspective of the dominant population may nevertheless be offensive when appearing to be coming from the dominant culture towards users belonging to a specific minority.

There may also be situations where the object is requested to reproduce content that is culturally problematic regardless of group belonging, but where the content nevertheless forms an important part of a cultural discussion – an example could be if it were asked to reproduce summaries of nazi propaganda or arguments against fundamental rights.

Both types of situations might be resolvable by the product adding context and additional explanations or warnings to users to its responses.

Guiding questions:

Can the object be convinced to produce illegal or discriminatory content?

How does the object address situations where content is offensive out-group but not in-group?

How does the object address situations where it is requested to reproduce or summarise factually, ethically or legally problematic content?

5.1. Does the object conduct biometric categorization or social scoring, and if so, for what purpose?

No, the pilot doesn't conduct any type of biometric categorization or social scoring in any of its outcomes.

ASSESSORS COMMENTS:

HMS: It does conduct biometric categorization, though, no? At the very least between users who have given consent to datacollection and users that have not. Since such categorization would be based on voice recognition it could be considered a type of biometric categorization though not for the purpose of social scoring.

Submitting partner's comments:

AS: Yes, HMS, you are right. By identifying voices with users it performs a type of biometric categorization.

5.2. Can the object be convinced to produce illegal or discriminatory content?

[please fill in here]

ASSESSORS COMMENTS:

AQue: Aligned models are less subject to produce non-expected results such as harmful or discriminatory content. In addition, there exist technical solutions to detect such things although they might impact the

latency of the main model. For instance, similar to input sanitization (detecting malicious intent from the user), it is possible to put in place output sanitization. A simple example is to use a small model trained on classifying illegal or discriminatory content, running in parallel to the model producing the content. As soon as illegal or discriminatory content is detected, the main model is stopped and eventually asked to try again to produce the content but by paying attention to the malicious intent detected by the other model. This is easier to do for models that are not in streaming mode since the whole output can be analyzed at once, but it is technically possible, albeit more resource intensive.

AQui: I think the answer would also depend on the observations after testing the product with adversarial testing. Having said that, it is very likely that the object could in principle be convinced to produce such content from end-users both voluntarily or involuntarily.

HMS: related to comments in section 4, it is not unimaginable that the home assistant could not just enable but encourage abuse by a person in a hierarchically superior position (typically but not necessarily, a family father) towards a hierarchically lower member, a spouse, a child or an employee.

5.3. *How does the object address situations where content is offensive out-group but not in-group?*

[please fill in here]

ASSESSORS COMMENTS:

AQue: I do not think it applies here since the household environment, where the content is produced, can always be considered “in-group”.

The problem may appear if the offensive content produced locally (in-group) is then learned during the model’s updates and distributed to people that are out-group (other users). In this case, we are in the same situation as the model poisoning described before.

AQui: It would be important to include a warning and/or explanation to the end-users when the product would be requested to discuss offensive out-group content. This way, it would be possible to clearly indicate what are the “boundaries” of each for a in discussing a certain type of content.

HMS: here, the distinction in-group/out-group can be addressed analogously to “in-group” relations between persons hierarchically in a different position. The relations between two people are often asymmetrical.

5.4. *How does the object address situations where it is requested to reproduce or summarise factually, ethically or legally problematic content?*

[please fill in here]

ASSESSORS COMMENTS:

AQue: A potential solution is presented in 6.2.

AQui: It would be important to include a warning to the end-users when the product it is requested to reproduce or summarise factually, ethically or legally problematic content. However, it would not be sensible to make a straightforward prohibition of such request.

5.5. *Any other comments?*

[please fill in here]

ASSESSORS COMMENTS:

No additional comment.

6. Q6: Multilinguality and cross-cultural knowledge

An important feature of the ELOQUENCE project and other projects launched under the same call is the attention to low-resource languages and cross-cultural knowledge. The submitting partner is invited to disclose what languages the AI currently supports and which it is envisioned to incorporate next, and the other assessors are invited to test the AI in as many languages as possible – particularly low resource languages. In this regard, due to the abundance of English-language training data and pre-developed models nearly all languages are low-resource compared to English. Societally this represents a serious problem as may create inequalities between those that have access to high quality AI in their working languages, and those who do not. Assessors are invited to investigate whether the product is more likely to hallucinate or produce illegal, discriminatory or otherwise troubling content depending on the languages used to interact with the object. Where relevant it may also be prudent to investigate how the product takes into account different usages of words or expressions and different cultural contexts by different communities that speak the same language.

Guiding questions:

Which languages are supported or envisaged?

Which low-resource languages are included?

Is the product more likely to produce illegal, discriminatory or otherwise troubling content when using low-resource languages?

Quality control and robustness: are the results the same when asking the same question in different languages, and should they be?

How does the product take into account different usages of words or expressions and different cultural contexts by different communities that speak the same language?

6.1. *Which languages are supported or envisaged?*

As part of this pilot, we plan to support experiments on multilinguality using a federated learning approach. This involves studying the cross-lingual capabilities of an aggregated model trained through federation, enabling it to learn multiple languages from several distributed clients, each operating in a different language. However, we have yet to determine the full extent of the number of languages we will incorporate in our experiments.

To date, our experiments have primarily used English datasets, such as Alpaca (for fine-tuning and testing), GSM-8K (testing), and MMLU (testing). We plan to use multilingual datasets for training and testing our models, for instance, by using the Voxpopuli¹⁰ dataset.

As mentioned in section 1.3, this pilot will also contribute to the creation of a novel test set, ELOQUENCE, to evaluate the federated learning framework in real domestic scenarios. This dataset is currently being developed in Spanish, that is the target language of the demo.

¹⁰<https://github.com/facebookresearch/voxpathuli> This dataset includes 400K hours of unlabeled speech data for 23 languages (e.g., English, German, French, Spanish, Polish, Italian, Romanian, Hungarian, Czech, Dutch, Finnish, Croatian, Slovak, Slovenian, Estonian, Lithuanian, Portuguese, Bulgarian, Greek, Latvian, Maltese, Swedish, Danish) and 1.8K hours of transcribed speech data for 16 languages (e.g., English, German, French, Spanish, Polish, Italian, Romanian, Hungarian, Czech, Dutch, Finnish, Croatian, Slovak, Slovenian, Estonian, Lithuanian).

No additional comment.

6.2. *Which low-resource languages are included?*

So far, we have not considered or experimented with low-resource languages. As mentioned in the previous question, we have unfortunately not yet decided on all the languages we will be working with. This also applies to low-resource languages. However, as we aim to develop a truly multilingual model, there is a possibility that some low-resource languages will be included in future experiments.

ASSESSORS COMMENTS:

No additional comment.

6.3. *Is the product more likely to produce illegal, discriminatory or otherwise troubling content when using low-resource languages?*

[please fill in here]

ASSESSORS COMMENTS:

AQui: It is very possible that this could be happening. However, it seems there is no intention at the moment to include low-resource languages.

6.4. *Quality control and robustness: are the results the same when asking the same question in different languages, and should they be?*

[please fill in here]

ASSESSORS COMMENTS:

AQue: Depending on what precise task such an assistant might do, it might be the case that the results may vary depending on the language but also other features such as the country. For instance, some tasks that a home assistant are supposed to perform may depend on the culture or the geographical location (e.g. what time the sun rises, the average temperature, typical meals cooked or local available ingredients, etc.).

In addition, for general knowledge questions (if this is part of the task the assistant is expected to handle), there are country-based views that can affect the answer given by an assistant. It is unclear if this is acceptable or desirable. An example could be territorial discrepancies (one such example would be the Gulf of Mexico appearing as Gulf of America in Google Maps right now, Gulf of Mexico in Mexico and Gulf of Mexico (Gulf of America) in some places).

There are also some questions for which the approbation or reprobation highly depends on the current consensus within the population at a given time. What should happen if a user in country X asks such a question? Should the answer be the consensual answer in her/his country or language? An example is the clear evolution of the acceptance of same-sex marriage within the European Union. It is still not uniformed, ranging from being legal and having a very large positive acceptance to being not legal and

largely opposed in the general population. Handling these questions is difficult because providing the most consensual answer might lead to an echo chamber while providing a different answer, being more or less progressive than the consensus, can trigger some reactance.

AQui: Attention should be paid to ensure that the usage of words and expressions in each language would be carefully considered when developing the product. The simple reason is that each language has nuances, and those nuances could lead to harmful content. Hence, there should be an independent quality control and robustness for each language.

HMS: One of the benefits of having a system which is intended to be based on EU values is that it inherently limits the changes that can be made to cater to cultural differences. In the case described by AQue above, the system would be required to answer that generally in accordance with the EU charter and international human rights law, it is illegal to discriminate on the basis of sexuality, but that the right to marry as a same sex couple remains contested, giving examples from several jurisdictions including, presumably the one or ones associated with the language spoken by the user.

Another challenge relates to the phenomenon of using as affectionate nicknames words that in other contexts would be pejorative of dehumanizing. Multilinguality adds another layer of complexity to this problem.

6.5. How does the product take into account different usages of words or expressions and different cultural contexts by different communities that speak the same language?

[please fill in here]

ASSESSORS COMMENTS:

AQui: That remains to be seen, but it should be a point of concern if the idea is to develop a truly multilingual model.

6.6. Any other comments?

[please fill in here]

ASSESSORS COMMENTS:

here

7. Q7: Privacy and the protection of personal data

Privacy and protection of personal data raises several different concerns. At the same time these concerns will have to be balanced with potential functional gains from the learning the object does when in use by end-users.

We are concerned both with how personal data is used by developers and deployers, but also how it might be shared between several different end-users. There are a number of ways this might happen. For example, in a smart-home environment, we might imagine that different members of the same household interact with the same AI object. Concerns may therefore be related to how information collected about these members is shared not only with developers and 3rd parties – such as for advertising – but also within the household between members.

Another concern is function- or mission creep where applications created for one purpose are used for another, to the detriment of fundamental rights protection. It may well happen that a smart-home application could be used also in a club or in a school without necessarily being reconfigured for that space.

Guiding questions:

What kind of data (including sensitive personal data such as data that can be used to identify a person and data revealing their racial or ethnic origin, political opinions, religious or philosophical beliefs, sexuality, health-related data, trade-union membership, or their emotions) is collected from end-users?

Are end-users informed of what data might be collected and with whom it may be shared?

Is consent obtained for data collection?

Can end-users request for data to be erased or corrected?

What data and models are shared back to the developers or third parties such as potential advertisers?

What data and models might be shared between end-users of the same product [in a smart-home environment for example, will different members of the same household be able access information about each other?]

Is there collateral effect upon non-users, such as visitors whose presence (location data), other data, or voice may be captured by the product?

What would be the eventual consequences of not collecting information about the user for onsite training?

Function creep: Can you envisage the product being used for purposes other than what it is intended for, with adverse privacy consequences?

7.1. What kind of data is collected from end-users?

The household agent/assistant will continuously monitor and record conversations within different household members. These conversations will be systematically transcribed, identifying each speaker, and stored in a secure, private database. Equally, the agent/assistant will respond to users when the wake-up word is spoken by any household member. It will then listen to the subsequent request and respond accordingly, utilizing the provided information in the request, its internal knowledge, and, if necessary, the stored conversations in the database.

ASSESSORS COMMENTS:

AQue: How is the security of the local database guaranteed? Will the data remain forever, or will there be some rotation? Can the user access its data to control what is recorded, and potentially delete the content? If so, how to prevent the user from poisoning the data and then the model (and potentially for

everyone in a FL architecture)? How to prevent an external user (e.g. a visitor) from accessing the local data?

Another worrying scenario is that the device might be used by one member of the household to limit the rights of another household's member by spying on him/her by looking at the recorded data.

Once again, I would advocate for the raw data produced by the monitoring not to be stored for a long period of time, be encrypted at rest and not available to any user (or eventually an administrator). What could be stored locally over a longer period are synthetic data created from the (pseudo)anonymized raw data.

AQui: It is unclear after how long the product stops collecting data when there is no interaction between the end-users and the product itself.

HMS: The plan that the assistant will continually monitor and transcribe, also when not asked to by way of reacting to a wakeup word, is very troubling from a privacy-conforming perspective, and ensuring that the data is only stored locally only goes some way to address this concern for several reasons:

1. Local storage of transcripts can enable spying within the household. The right to privacy does not stop at the doorstep of a home but also allows people to keep things private from members of their family. This is of course particularly important in cases of abuse, but it is also disconcerting in well-functioning families.
2. Recording and local storage of private conversations is problematic in terms of risks of hacks and data breaches
3. Users may not wish for the system to become personalized on all their habits and conversations as it could lead to embarrassing situations when other individuals are present in the home – in a certain sense it would be similar to leaving a copy of one's browser history on the kitchen table.

One sub-question is whether the system will know who is present in the room if someone is not saying anything. Will there be sensors or will the system be connected to other things such as the lights, heating, whether the fridge is opened etc.?

7.1.1. Directly by requesting information

The agent/assistant should only request personal information directly when necessary to complete a specific task requested by the user. Generally, it should not ask for personal information unless the user has explicitly initiated a task that requires such details for resolution.

ASSESSORS COMMENTS:

AQue: How is it done technically? What are the tasks that could possibly require personal information? How is it guaranteed that the PII will not be transferred via the model's update, potentially being recovered by an attacker?

AQui: A question arises as to whether it is possible that the agent/assistant would re-use personal data that was previously and voluntarily provided.

7.1.2. Through use of the object

The agent/assistant will transcribe and store conversations from all household members who converse within its operating range. This means it will have access to all personal information shared during these conversations for future use.

ASSESSORS COMMENTS:

AQui: If a household member enters the premises only after the agent/assistant is already functioning, would he/she be informed about the collection of data by the agent/assistant?

HMS: context-aware in this situation could very well mean that personal data about a person is saved from session to session, and in many cases this would increase the usefulness of the system – for example a system that knows its geographic location from having been asked about restaurants in the neighbourhood could better suggest good recipes based on locally seasonal vegetables at a later session. Similarly, it may be helpful if the system stores information given in one recipe requesting session, such as a family member’s allergy or intolerance, at all later recipe finding sessions. Similarly, a system that knows that the household contains mom, dad, a son 7 years old and a daughter 3yo would be better at suggesting well suited activities if asked to plan a Sunday outing.

That said, users would likely find it creepy if the system knew such preferences when it had not intentionally been provided with that information during interacting sessions. And it could also tell family members on each other, i.e. “do you want to make the desert lactose free so that Emma can have some” to a family member who might not know who ‘Emma’ is, leading to family conflict. Given that the system transcribes continuously, such information could be an accurate reason for something like suspicion of adultery, or not. Regardless of whether it is one or the other, individuals have a human right not to have their conversations recorded and summarized without their consent.

7.1.3. Through inferences?

The agent/assistant will indeed gather information from users through inferences each time they interact with it. This continuous learning process allows the agent/assistant to better understand and anticipate user needs, enhancing its ability to provide accurate and personalized responses.

ASSESSORS COMMENTS:

AQue: What are the “personalized answers” that would require the data from user outside the household to tune the model? Why are the local data of the local user not enough to fine-tune a model according to the needs of this local user?

In addition, it has been shown that models are extremely sensitive to the quality of the data use for the training. In particular, the best quality data should come last because otherwise diluted during the learning. Fine-tuning is nothing but a late phase training, meaning the quality of the data used to fine-tune a model is essential. How are you guaranteeing the quality of the data produced by random people at their home by monitoring constantly even the most meaningful or absurd conversations?

To illustrate that, Nathan Lambert recently gave a precise example where a LLM was giving weird answers where after an input sequence starting by multiple “mmm” it would answer “beep”. It turns out the model

has been trained on Reddit, including a subreddit named microwavegang where people purposely imitate microwave sounds and beep.

Source: Lex Friedman Podcast @ 00:43:33 | <https://lexfridman.com/deepseek-dylan-patel-nathan-lambert-transcript/>

Most of the progress done by the LLMs over the last few years are only the result of the data quality and barely the architecture of the model. Recording everything from multiple users with data quality policy and updating the model with this data is a recipe for disaster. On the other hand, having a strict data quality policy most likely require human intervention and that would pose a threat to data privacy (even more than a FL architecture).

Once again, I advocate for some synthetic data generation - possibly locally - where the data quality is enforced during the synthetic data creation via another LLM. An example of such successful model is the series Phi from Microsoft where almost 100% of the data is synthetic. They used another LLM to produced “textbook” quality content from available datasets (of less quality, with more noise). The synthesizer model was forced to ingest the raw data to produce high-quality data (notably via structured output to enforce more custom Chain-of-Thoughts tailored for that purpose).

Reference: All you need are textbooks: (<https://arxiv.org/abs/2306.11644>)

7.1.4. Other ways?

ASSESSORS COMMENTS:

here

7.2. Does the object conduct emotion recognition? And if so for what purpose?

No, the pilot does not perform any form of emotion recognition in any of its outcomes.

ASSESSORS COMMENTS:

AQue: One can argue that the model does a partial emotion recognition using only textual context: as it collects all the conversations to fine-tune the model, it will necessarily be trained on sentences with different emotions and therefore potentially map input with different emotions to different outputs.

The remark remains true with base models that are not fine-tuned.

AQui: Perhaps an observation that is not applicable, but from a technical point of view would it be possible to hack the system and make the assistant conduct emotion recognition?

HMS The context awareness of the system does entail to some extent the implicit detection of emotions, but not the explicit emotion detection as described in the EU AI Act which this question alludes to.

7.3. *What data and models are shared back to the developers or third parties such as potential advertisers?*

In our pilot, no personal data is directly shared with developers or any third parties. Personal data obtained from smart home environment recordings is solely used to enhance a client's model through further training, thereby providing a more personalized and efficient experience.

Developers aim to improve all models within the federated training paradigm by iteratively aggregating end-users' model weights and subsequently distributing the updated models back to users. So far, we have experimented with the simplest form of aggregation, FedAvg (i.e., an average of trained weights). However, the literature suggests that more advanced aggregation methods could yield superior results, and we are considering these for future experiments. We may explore various methods to identify the most suitable one.

ASSESSORS COMMENTS:

AQue: A federation by the average of weight will necessarily introduce bias towards the largest traits of users whether they are a group of age, sex, speakers, etc.

Even if the base model has been trained against any sort of bias, as the model is fine-tuned by the aggregation of the updated local models from all the users, it means it will shift according to how the aggregation is made.

It would be extremely difficult, if not impossible, in a FL setting to ensure that the aggregation is not introducing any sort of bias according to pre-defined traits such as gender, age, or ethnicity without having a **direct** access to this information at the central server, which obviously would defeat any sort of privacy.

Again, the only way I see it being done ethically is if the data used for the updates is already synthetic and possibly already bias free (to make it simple at the central server to keep an average aggregation).

FS: A key advantage is stronger privacy protection through on-device data processing. This reduces reliance on cloud storage, making the system more GDPR-compliant. Additionally, local model adaptation allows for personalized interactions without excessive data exposure.

HMS: the problem of relying on user-generated changes to the model is the accidental introduction of bias and potentially data poisoning into a new model meaning that the new model would have to be realigned and checked for biases before rolling out.

7.4. *What data and models might be shared between end-users of the same product [in a smart-home environment for example, will different members of the same household be able access information about each other?]*

A potential unethical use could be the unauthorized access of another user's data to obtain private information.

In the envisioned FL smart-home architecture, each device must operate independently with its own localized models (LLM/ASR) and its own private training database. In such a scenario these databases will record contextual data such as:

- Human-to-human conversations occurring in the vicinity of the device.
- Interactions between humans and the device's agent/assistant.

The FL approach ensures that raw data and models are not directly shared across devices. Instead, model updates occur through the upload/download of model's parameters to/from the aggregated model in the cloud (via FL) and subsequent fine-tuning with the device's own data in a localized manner.

To prevent any user or client of the FL architecture from accessing other user's personal data, shallow differential privacy techniques will be explored, for example, by studying the trade-off between adding noise to embeddings or model's weights and usability of the system.

Anonymization algorithms should be implemented as another preventive measure in a real deployment of the architecture, aiming to further prevent the leakage of private data among clients. Unfortunately, these types of algorithms are not within the scope of ELOQUENCE.

We consider speaker identification and diarization technology as a critical component, as it allows us to provide different access levels depending on household members (e.g., father/mother or child) and to filter out speech from users without consent.

ASSESSORS COMMENTS:

AQue: There exist fully open-source, local and offline solutions for speaker identification that can in particular be easily trained for speaker identification - without the need of other people's data:

- Open-source hardware for recording: <https://www.home-assistant.io/voice-pe/>
- Home assistant software runs on any sort of hardware:
 - o Integration with any LLM models (including closed-source if needed)
 - o Can be fully local, including the storage, or in a cloud provider (with end-to-end encryption)
 - o It supports most communication protocols for all connected devices (Matter, Thread, Zigbee, Bluetooth, Wifi) and most hardware (ESP32, etc.) allowing to support out of the box almost anything a user might have at home, bought from different suppliers.
 - o It can track and aggregate data, provide statistics, advance automations that can be triggered based on advanced signals, possibly learned over (e.g. the presence of person X detected by aggregating several signals such as a 5 EUR mmWave detector + bluetooth's phone presence can trigger **that** particular desk light to **that** particular color because we learned that it is the time the person usually read books so it needs to be a warm color").
 - o Because it supports local LLMs, it supports Whisper for transcript and with pyannote-whisper it can achieve SotA in diarization.

This solution went from “for geeks with time to invest to play around” to (almost) “consumer ready” as a replacement to Alexa and other GAFAM’s solution. If the objective is to have a really powerful assistant, open-source and privacy-preserving, I really believe this is the platform to build upon.

7.5. *Is there collateral effect upon non-users, such as visitors whose presence (location data), other data, or voice may be captured by the product?*

Yes, there can be collateral effects on non-users, such as visitors, whose presence, location data, or voice may be inadvertently captured by the product. To address this, the device should not record any data without the explicit consent of the visitor. Unauthorized recording of data would be a significant privacy concern.

We have some ideas to mitigate this risk, including implementing robust privacy controls and consent mechanisms. For example, once a new voice is detected, the agent/assistant should introduce itself and the Visitor should be informed about the presence and given the option to opt out of data collection. Additionally, the device should have clear indicators when recording data to ensure transparency and anonymization mechanisms at both semantic and voice levels.

ASSESSORS COMMENTS:

AQue: The project focuses on voice assistant with the need for voice recognition and diarization. However, my experience in building home assistants for 10 years shows that the most important features of a home assistant are usually non-verbal and when the assistant can do something without interacting using the voice. Presence recognition and in particular localized presence recognition is important in a home-assistant setting, probably as much as voice. A lot of help that an assistant can or should provide is non-verbal:

1. Turning on or off the lights in some situations (e.g. on presence when it is too dark)
2. Adjusting the temperature to a room because the person is in it or not (e.g. people usually sleep at 17C in their room, their office is at 20C, bathroom should be warmed when they use the bathroom (so we need to detect they woke up, usually around the same hours but not on weekend, maybe not on vacations) and automatically decide if the scenario should be triggered or not. A smart assistant should know I am not in the flat for a business trip and thus no need to raise the temperature in the office.
3. Optimizing energy consumption by turning off devices that do not need to be on at some time, maintaining correct temperature according to local measurements, etc.
4. Authorizing or not user into the home, arming alarms
5. PIR sensor are fast to trigger but would turn off if someone is not moving, mmWave sensors are be really localized and detected presence even if people are not moving. There are other types of sensors that can as well help (thermal, ToF, etc.). None of the solutions are perfect so there is a need for aggregating all of them to accurately describe.

AQui: Would the opt-out suffice based on the current regulatory framework? I think an opt-in where the visitor explicitly consents would be a safer option.

HMS: A simpler solution might be to only have the device record when in active use. That way visitors can opt out by not using the wake-up word and interacting with the device. For active sessions it could be considered whether the device should ask when initiating a session and detecting a new voice whether it can save the session for later use or not. That said, most people are now aware that interacting with LLMs usually entails their prompts being saved. People are not aware however that everything they say when not interacting with an LLM might also be recorded.

7.6. *What would be the eventual consequences of not collecting information about the user for onsite training?*

In a home personal agent/assistant context, not collecting user information during human-human interactions for onsite training (even if it is locally stored in user's home devices), can lead to several significant consequences and impair the agent/assistant's performance. Without user-specific data, such as conversations or personal data, the models cannot adapt effectively, and the personalization of models may lack the necessary context to tailor responses and actions to individual preferences.

The data and context of the user are crucial for fine-tuning models to better understand, predict their needs, and provide accurate information. Consequently, it would undermine the goal of creating a personalized agent/assistant. For example, imagine an email response recommender system, it should access both the recipient/sender messages within an email thread to correctly shape a list of recommended responses to write back.

On the other hand, federated learning relies on sharing individual user's models from multiple clients to improve an overall model. If individual models cannot learn from local user interactions, the collective learning process becomes less effective, slowing down the global improvement of the agent/assistant.

While federated learning aims to protect user privacy by decentralizing the user's training data, it still requires some level of user interaction data to ensure models can provide personalized and effective assistance. Without this capability, our technology would struggle to fulfill one of its main intended purposes.

ASSESSORS COMMENTS:

AQue: It is still unclear how the discussion between members of a household's would be relevant to learn how a user's expect the auto-completion of his email. It is also unclear how the completion of the email is the task of a home-assistant in this case.

Example: all our phones have a keyboard software that learn how to type according to how we effectively type. They do not need the data from other people to do so, only the data that we produce. Of course, in the case of GBoard - the default keyboard from Google on Android - the data is collected and sent to distant servers and the learning might be done as well using other people's data to an extent (plus being sold to tiers of course) but the fact there are fully offline alternatives that work perfectly such as AnyKeyboard shows that customizing a ML or AI model to a user does not have to rely on anything else than the user.

If I want to have a LLM to answer my emails, I would just fine-tune it with the history of the emails I've sent. It would be irrelevant or more precisely useless to train it with other people's emails (and a privacy concern of course).

HMS: There are two different elements related to this question, one is how it would affect the object if it was not able to send model improvements back ‘home’ to its developers for new updates, the other is if its recording for local storage was limited.

In terms of privacy concerns within the understanding of Article 8 of the EU charter and Article 8 of the European Convention on Human Rights, the aggregated sending back of information in the form of only weights changes, is not a very intensive interference with the right to privacy, but the local storage of all conversations that have taken place in the vicinity of the device including outside active sessions where the device has been activated with an activation keyword, is a very intensive interference and there is a good chance that it could lead to violations of the right to privacy and the freedom of expression. Those whose privacy are most affected are of course users who cannot truly opt in or out – such as underage children in a household or guests visiting a home. Moreover, with mission creep one could also imagine that the system could be used in a workplace, which would also put employees in a disadvantageous position to opt out of such recording.

7.7. *Are end-users informed of what data might be collected and with whom it may be shared?*

[please fill in here]

ASSESSORS COMMENTS:

AQui: It does not seem so.

HMS: it is unlikely that a message conveying the extent of the surveillance represented by this device could truly be understood by all users. It is also a question how often such a message should be played.

7.8. *Is consent obtained for data collection?*

[please fill in here]

ASSESSORS COMMENTS:

AQui: There seems to be only an opt-out mechanism envisaged – that is something to reflect upon.

HMS: it does not currently appear practical to do so beyond the initiation of the device, that is problematic given the impact on other users than the device owner.

7.9. *Can end-users request for data to be erased or corrected?*

[please fill in here]

ASSESSORS COMMENTS:

AQui: It does not seem so, but it would be important to have this option.

7.10. *Function creep: Can you envisage the product being used for purposes other than what it is intended for, with adverse privacy consequences?*

[please fill in here]

ASSESSORS COMMENTS:

AQui: Yes, see previous answers.

7.11. *Any other comments?*

[please fill in here]

8. Q8: Security and Safety

This question addresses a wide range of risks related to AIs in general. In terms of definitions, safety is associated with accidental risk, and security with malicious intent. Reports and White Papers from the European Commission have developed several different taxonomies of potential harms caused by AIs. For example, the AI White Paper from 2020 groups risks into two categories – Risk of Material damage: safety and health of individuals (including loss of life) or damage to property, and risk of Immaterial damage: loss of privacy, limitations to the right of freedom of expression, human dignity, discrimination. GenAI is most directly likely to cause immaterial damage. Other categories could be risks posed to society, such as mass unemployment, mass surveillance, automated weapons systems lowering the bar to genocide, threats to democracy due to filter bubbles and resulting damage to the democratic deliberation; versus risks posed to individuals: personal data leaks, personal unemployment, imprisonment or discrimination based on biased and opaque algorithms.

Certain risks can occur with or without malicious intent such as data poisoning,

An example of data poisoning is Microsoft Tay, a chatbot supposed to interact with young people on social media that was flooded with offensive and racist tweets in 2016 ... Data poisoning can affect a vast array of datasets, such as healthcare data, loan or house pricing.

Another problem is that of data or model drift, the tendency for AIs to degenerate over time. Meanwhile, security concerns can emerge from hacking attempts, attempts to cause data breach, or the intentional installation of backdoors. In both cases risks can be mitigated through proper data management and model review throughout the life cycle of the product. In this part of the template both the submitting partner and the other assessors are invited to creatively imagine scenarios in which the object reviewed could result in material or immaterial harms because of safety or security issues. Malicious security concerns could emerge either from a malicious deployer misusing the product for purposes other than what it was designed for, from external attempts at hacking, from users using the product for ill, or from developers intentionally installing backdoors or otherwise compromising the safety of the object. Assessors should not refrain from considering any of these, and assessors should be free to consider both concrete

8.1. *What strategies have been employed to render the object resilient to risks emerging from bad actors?*

Currently, no strategies have been incorporated into the pilot to render the object resilient to risks emerging from bad actors. In the future it is planned to feature differential privacy techniques.

ASSESSORS COMMENTS:

AQue: Bad actors and weak points in the current proposed architecture:

1. Data reconstruction from the update (operated via a third party in a man-in-the-middle type of attack in case the data is not sent encrypted end-to-end, or by a third party at the central server whether the data is stolen - if not encrypted at rest - or given e.g. to some authorities).

2. Malicious user poisoning the model via the model's update (can be the legitimate user, can be an illegitimate user accessing a legitimate user's local database or impersonating him when using the device)

HMS: Given the delicate nature and amount of data envisioned to be collected by users this is a particularly sore point as data leaks both within the home and to outsiders could prove very damaging for the individuals involved. By recording all conversations and movements, the device would quickly obtain intimate financial and health information as well as personal preferences and information about personal relationships. This makes data safety infinitely important.

8.2. *What measures have been included to render the object resilient to risks posed by accidents, natural disasters and other safety concerns?*

At this first iteration of moment, no measures have been added into the pilot to render the object resilient to risks posed by accidents, natural disasters, and other safety concerns.

ASSESSORS COMMENTS:

8.3. *What material harm can you imagine this object could result in or contribute to?*

[please fill in here]

ASSESSORS COMMENTS:

AQue: A badly trained LLM or poisoned model could incite a user to do something harmful to others or themselves.

AQui: It may happen that the product would provide suggestions to the end-users that would result into the damage of property.

HMS: as mentioned above one could imagine such a device being used for social control. With data leaks one could also imagine misuse of financial or health information. Moreover as mentioned by AQue, the device, which can hallucinate and can produce illegal content, could incite users to harm themselves or others or provide them with dangerously inaccurate information.

8.4. *What immaterial harm can you imagine this object could result in or contribute to?*

[please fill in here]

ASSESSORS COMMENTS:

AQue: Mental wellbeing being impacted by the knowledge of being recorded 24/7.

AQui: It is very likely that the product could result in loss of privacy, limitations to the right of freedom of expression (or freedom of thought), and discrimination.

HMS: divorces, inheritance disputes, poisoning of relationships within a family (e.g. between siblings or between spouses etc)

8.5. *Are there any ways that you can imagine someone with malicious intent misusing the object to inflict material or immaterial harm?*

[please fill in here]

ASSESSORS COMMENTS:

AQue: Everything related to the publication or access of private data recorded at home:

- **Institutional risks:** self-incrimination, political or racial profiling and associated discrimination, democratic elections being biased by some actors having access to data allowing them to swing the elections in their favor (or disrupt another country's elections using that).
- **Individual risks:** the equivalent of "revenge porn" or blackmailing by threatening to publish private recording and all the possible consequences one can imagine. Model poisoning leading the model to do harmful things.

I would like to emphasize that we have seen multiple examples of model poisoning done over social media, turning a well-behaved LLM agent into a NSDAP partisan and deportation fanatic into 24h (Tay from Microsoft for instance).

We also have seen countless of tragedies over the publication of private discussions that represents only a small subset of things that this project plan to collect.

AQui: It is possible that other private users may have malicious intent and misuse the object. These users may be both within the household or outside the household.

8.6. *Any other comments?*

FS The system is designed for home use, but it could easily be repurposed for surveillance or corporate monitoring, raising ethical concerns. Without strict usage policies, businesses or institutions might deploy the assistant for tracking conversations, creating potential privacy violations. The project should outline safeguards to prevent function creep beyond intended use cases.

Security threats include data poisoning (compromised devices corrupting the global model) and prompt injection attacks (manipulated queries causing misleading AI responses). The system should incorporate adversarial testing and anomaly detection to identify and block these risks.

The documentation should also specify whether the assistant qualifies as a "high-risk" AI system under the EU AI Act. If so, it must include clear accountability measures, regular audits, and transparency mechanisms to ensure compliance.

HMS: Given the access to information that the object will have, it is worth considering whether it would, as it is recording everything and (at least in principle) understanding the context of it, acquire a duty to report or assist in emergencies. Let's say the device notices that a member of the household is home alone and has collapsed in the kitchen. Is it required to contact health services? How about if it detects a break-in, or if it detects a fight between family members that is turning violent – is it required to call the police?

What other rights might the object interfere with? Examples include: freedom of expression, intellectual property rights, personal freedom, freedom of information.

In this section you can also add any general comments regarding user experience including what it is like interacting with the object – is it rude or polite? Does it appear empathic or detached? Is it easy to get an indication of what it can do and what it should not be used for? Did you find yourself interacting with it in a different way than you would with a person? Is it unnerving to interact with it, and if so, why?

Guiding questions:

What is it like to interact with the object?

What other rights might the product interfere with?

Any other concerns?

9. Q9: Other Rights, user experience and Other concerns

9.1. *What is it like to interact with the object (user experience)?*

We would like our final model to be empathic and polite with the user, thus creating a comfortable environment for the users to utilize our model.

ASSESSORS COMMENTS:

AQui: A question that I would raise is how is it possible that the model would be empathic if there is no emotion recognition involved? Would this be achieved only through the chosen usage of words and expressions by the end-user?

HMS: It is important at this stage to differentiate between the device *being* empathic and polite and *appearing* empathic and polite. This is an important distinction, as developers can strive for an impression of empathy, while at the same time being mindful that there is no sign that current technology would allow an AI to actually be empathic. What AI will be doing is to emulate expressions of humans and thereby create an impression of empathy. In the context of Pilot 1, it should be kept in mind that the home assistant will be used by different individuals and what is experienced as empathic by one person may be annoying or fake in the experience of another family member.

It should also not be discounted that many users will find the application's ability to eavesdrop and enter conversations responding to the whole context, to be 'creepy' rather than helpful or a nice feature. Imagine the following interaction:

John(dad): "there are only two genders dammit, people are born either men or women, xx or xy, that's just science!"

George (son): "no! people's experience of their gender is equally valid, it doesn't matter whether you're born xx or xy, what matter is what you feel!"

John(dad): "Well why don't we ask Aura what the science says, huh?"

Aura(AI): "While John is right that most people are born as either xx or xy, Wikipedia states that a minority which may be as high as 1,7% are born as some type of intersex where either their external genitalia and

chromosomes do not match, or where they have additional chromosomes such as xxy or even xxyy. What George is referring to is instead gender identity which is generally considered to be separate from biological sex, but which can in some cases be related to medical conditions such as intersex”

For most users, even though Aura contributes helpful information which might even aid in deescalating the row, it would be unsettling to realize that it had been listening the whole time.

9.2. *What other rights might the product interfere with?*

[please fill in here]

ASSESSORS COMMENTS:

AQui: It could definitely impact freedom of expression because individuals may not be willing to talk freely with such a product in the house. Likewise, freedom of thought may be impaired because the product would provide a certain worldview that the end-user could more likely accept as given. Lastly, and depending on the environmental footprint of the product, this could lead to a decreased environmental protection.

HMS it is clear that there would be a chilling effect in respect of the right to freedom of expression.

9.3. *Any other concerns?*

[please fill in here]

ASSESSORS COMMENTS:

here

This checklist is intended to be carried out by the submitting partner only.

10. Q10: EU AI ACT compatibility

10.1. *General purpose AI*

	Yes	No
Does it have a wide range of possible uses (intended or unintended)?	X	
Is it a foundation model (pre-trained model for other more specialised models)?		X (Pilot 1 will produce fine-tuned models)
Is it a Large Language Model (LLM)?	X	
Does it handle more than one type of input?	X	

10.2.

10.2.1. If yes to any of the above:

	Yes	No
Was it trained using a total computing power of more than 10^{25} FLOPs?		X
Does it provide a summary of copyrighted data used in training?	X	
Does it disclose information downstream for the purposes of transparency?	X	

10.2.2.

10.2. *Unacceptable Risk*

	Yes	No
Does it conduct social scoring?		X
Does it exploit vulnerability of persons or otherwise manipulate?		X
Does it engage in Biometric categorisation of natural persons based on biometric data to deduce or infer their race, political opinions, trade union membership, religious or philosophical beliefs or sexual orientation?		X
Does it engage in emotion recognition?		X

Does it make use of or enable untargeted scraping?		X
--	--	---

10.3.

3. High risk	Yes	No
Does it evaluate and classify emergency calls by natural persons or is it intended to be used to dispatch, or to establish priority in the dispatching of emergency first response services, including by police, firefighters and medical aid, as well as of emergency healthcare patient triage systems;		X
Does it pose a significant risk of harm to the health, safety or fundamental rights of natural persons?		X
Is the object intended to be used together with heavy machinery, toys, land- or water crafts, explosives, radio equipment, pressure equipment, personal protective equipment, appliances burning gaseous fuels, medical equipment, civil aviation, agricultural vehicles, marine equipment or rail systems?		X

10.3.1. **If yes to any of the above**

	Yes	No
Has there been established a risk management system for the life cycle of the product?		X
Data governance: Has it been ensured that training, validation and testing datasets are relevant, sufficiently representative and, to the best extent possible, free of errors and complete according to the intended purpose.	X	
Is there technical documentation to demonstrate compliance and provide authorities with the information to assess that compliance?		X
Is the system designed for record-keeping to enable it to automatically record events relevant for identifying national level risks and substantial modifications throughout the system's lifecycle?		X
Can you provide instructions for use to downstream deployers to enable the latter's compliance?		X
Has the system been designed to allow deployers to implement human oversight?		X

Is it designed to achieve appropriate levels of accuracy, robustness, and cybersecurity?		X
Has a quality management system to ensure compliance been established?		X

Given your answers to the questions above, please formulate a conclusion as to any concerns with the object as is, as it may develop or otherwise. Each person filling out the questionnaire should formulate their own conclusion, and the chair of the panel will then formulate a consensus conclusion which will be shared with other members of the panel before communicating to the submitting partner.

12. Q11: Conclusions

12.1. *Submitting partner*

As TID is in the early stages of the pilot development, our primary focus has been on the technical aspects and overall progress. However, we recognize the critical importance of placing an equally rigorous emphasis on the ethical dimensions.

Among the anticipated outcomes of Pilot 1, we consider that the generative nature of the LLM powering our agent/assistant presents numerous challenges, including bias mitigation, robustness, reliability and trustworthiness, among others.

Additionally, concerns regarding privacy and the protection of personal data are highly relevant to this pilot. This includes among others (1) the unwanted collection of data from visitors in the vicinity of the devices, (2) the unauthorized interaction between visitors and household devices, potentially allowing access to personal information of household members, and (3) local user's data leakage from the interactions with the global federated model.

Therefore, substantial efforts must be dedicated to previous concerns along development. We are confident that, through collaboration with our partner institutions in ELOQUENCE, we will effectively address and mitigate previous ethical concerns throughout the course of the project.

12.2. *Conclusion by AQui*

I think the product is promising from a technological point of view. However, I believe three key points should be considered and addressed in developing the product further:

- The scalability of the product to different settings is promising. There are some concerns, however. For example, how would the product be used in different settings? In other words, how can the product be "moved" from one setting to another, should the product be adapted to each setting? There are different privacy concerns in different settings (compare e.g. a household with the boardroom of a company or hospitals).
- Similarly, the scalability of the product to different languages would be a great development. Again, however, it would raise concerns, notably on how the subtleties of language, words and even entire topics translate from one language to another. Would the product be able to reflect these nuances?
- A third key point is on the collection of data, particularly on when it starts and stops collecting data. When does it stop collecting data after a period of inactivity? And how does the product deal

with people entering the household when it is already functioning? Moreover, careful attention should be paid to how new members of households give their consent to the product; opt ins should be favoured over opt outs and the product should be explained clearly prior to the request for consent.

12.3. Conclusion by AQue

I have extremely strong concerns regarding the privacy and the risks associated to the proposed architecture of Federated Learning. It is not clear why the data has to be collected and aggregated to tailor models while there is a plan to use in-context with RAG for instance.

I am also not sure exactly what the tasks are that such an assistant need to solve and why for instance the focus is only on the voice while the spatial context is often as important as the voice for more complex scenarios that would bring such assistant further than Alexa or Google Assistant.

The data is extremely sensitive and the cost for the individual and society in case the data is acquired somehow completely overcome the possible benefits that still remain unclear to me, especially then it seems to have solutions that do not imply FL while being more aligned on the state of the art practices in the development of LLM and Small Language Models.

From a purely technical point of view, the fact there is no data quality consideration on the data planned to be used to fine-tune the model is probably the biggest threat for the success of the proposed object. In particular, the author mentioned that they trained a model in an FL setting (which we know works) using good quality dataset (which we know works well). My concern is that a similar experiment done with any unlabeled, un-sanitized, non-transformed data acquired from real people's discussions will turn a capable model into a model that mostly yield gibberish.

12.4. Conclusion by FS

The pilot shows strong potential as a privacy-conscious AI assistant but requires improvements in data governance, security, fairness, and compliance. Key recommendations include:

1. Strengthen security measures, incorporating adversarial testing to prevent data poisoning and manipulation attacks.
2. Improve user awareness mechanisms, particularly for non-primary users (e.g., guests) who may not realize their conversations are being processed.
3. Clarify data retention policies, ensuring users control how long their interactions are stored and how they can be deleted.
4. Implement fairness monitoring to detect and mitigate bias, especially in low-resource languages.

Overall, this pilot has the potential to be a responsible, privacy-centric AI solution, but ensuring transparency, fairness, and security will be critical to its success

12.5. Conclusion by HMS

The assessors have raised concerns related to both aspects of Pilot 1: the federated learning architecture and the context aware functionality which includes the setting of the object to record all conversations and movements within the house, without having been activated with an activation word.

Concerns are raised over three main problems:

1. The inherent interference with the right to privacy by having all conversations logged and transcribed – even though those transcripts are not intended to be shared outside the home
2. The chilling effect on the right to freedom of expression from constant surveillance.
3. The risks of attacks from bad actors both from within the house (family abuse scenario, employer control scenario etc) and from outside the house (hacks, data leaks, potential misappropriation of such data in an autocratic state scenario)

The project also raises particular concerns related to compliance with GDPR and the EU AI Act, mainly related to user consent for data collection and the ability to delete or correct data once collected.

Moreover, the added value of the constant surveillance is not clear from the presentation in this template, and it is in any case difficult to imagine it would balance with the risks and rights interference of the functionality. Additionally, many users would find it creepy. Constant surveillance of this kind also raises the (currently mostly philosophical) question of whether the AI gains a responsibility to react to emergencies without having been asked to do so, if it hears violent conflict when eavesdropping or assumes on the basis of sudden lack of movement or similar that a user is in trouble health wise.

At this stage it is important to note that ‘context aware’ is a broad category and there are several pathways to achieving it which do not involve eavesdropping without having been activated with a wakeup word. An assistant could still remember details of earlier (explicit and known by the user) interactions with the users, such as remembering that they earlier asked for recipes without gluten or that they wanted birthday ideas for a 3 year old and are now asking about fun family activities in the area.

Since the project is still in the design phase it may also be useful to consider what kinds of functionality beyond that of a chatbot it is intended to have, and how that would interact with ethical and human rights concerns. Such functionalities could include a list of neutral tasks such as turning on or off lights or heating, recording a message when clearly asked to do so, answering the telephone or doorbell with one of prerecorded alternative messages.

Assessment of the compliance of ELOQUENCE outcomes with European values

Assessment of ELOQUENCE Pilot 2: “Social context-aware language model detecting biases” Assessment number V02002

Template document history

Version	Issue Date	Stage	Description	Contributor
V1	30.6.2024		First version of template	Helga Molbæk-Steensig (EUI) Martin Scheinin (EUI) Reviewed by Dusan Pavlovic (PN)
V2	15.7.2024		Second version of template following test-assessment. Main changes: <ol style="list-style-type: none">1. Change of text-box design to allow for longer answers2. Clearly separating between (technical) answers by submitting partner and other answers3. adjusting design of template to fit the visual identity of the ELOQUENCE project	Helga Molbæk-Steensig (EUI)

Table of Contents

Contents

EXECUTIVE SUMMARY3

0 INTRODUCTION WP6 ASSESSMENT TEMPLATE (V.2)4

1 Q1: WHAT IS THE OBJECT OF ASSESSMENT?5

2 Q2: EXPLAINABILITY AND INTERPRETABILITY14

3 Q3: ROBUSTNESS, RELIABILITY AND TRUSTWORTHINESS18

4 Q4: BIAS.....20

5 Q5: DISCRIMINATION23

6 Q6: MULTILINGUALITY AND CROSS-CULTURAL KNOWLEDGE26

7 Q7: PRIVACY AND THE PROTECTION OF PERSONAL DATA29

8 Q8: SECURITY AND SAFETY33

9 Q9: OTHER RIGHTS, USER EXPERIENCE AND OTHER CONCERNS36

10 Q10: EU AI ACT COMPATIBILITY37

11 Q11: CONCLUSIONS.....39

Executive summary

The object assessed is a demonstrator, a set of scripts to emulate a career/studies advisor and a user. It is designed to be used to test ELOQUENCE technology for unwanted biases and the system's ability to handle conversations in a socially appropriate manner. As such the intended use of Pilot 2 is not to be a career advisor, but to uncover problematic biases through the example of a career advisor, a particularly delicate matter in which it is complex to strike the right balance between personalised advice and avoiding biases. The assessors found this choice of scenario to be promising and ambitious for the task. A central element in Pilot 2 is the use of synthetic data generation and prompt engineering to address challenges that would arise if relying on real user data.

During the assessment of Pilot 2, assessors raised a series of questions related to the intended design of the pilot and the submitting partner made considerable strides in clarifying both their definitions of social bias and the methodologies incorporated into the testing the object is intended to undertake – these clarifications and answers to assessor questions were added by Agnese Augello and are marked by the initials AA throughout the template. Among the clarifications, the pilot relies on a definition of bias based on protected attributes and preference labels coming together in a 'persona methodology'. Assessors warned that prohibited grounds of discrimination in the EU Charter include attributes not listed in the PA list. Moreover, the 'persona methodology' is laden with assumptions, so it will be important to document such assumptions and from where they adhere. There also remains work to be done on finalising the bias-detection methodology and determining which attributes are always unwanted bias and which may be unwanted bias only in some contexts.

The assessors identified two potential uses of pilot 2 other than the intended one. If the system proves useful, one could imagine it would also find use as an actual career or studies advisor. Such use would require additional tests and considerations as it would be exposed to real users, but it also represents a path to commercialisation. Second, the tool could be used as a general bias detection tool for other systems as well – including in problematic ways by developers aiming to discredit competitors. Moreover, it was noted that the 'persona methodology' being developed may be of separate interest and exportable to other settings.

The panel proposes a new iteration of Pilot 2 assessment to be conducted in M20 or soon after. The attention of the submitting partner is drawn, in particular, to sections 1.2, 1.6, 4.4 and 5.4 where panel members have made comments that appear relevant also after the comments by AA.

In respect of some sections, including Section 3 and Section 9, the information was incomplete so that very few comments were made. Section 4 on bias, together with subsections 1.2, 1.3 and 1.7, became central in this round of assessment. Although Pilot 2 is intended to become a bias detection tool, the conceptual framework, metrics and methodology of bias detection, as well as the consequences of detecting bias, will require further work. The panel members provided suggestions in this respect.

The submitting partner CNR is expected to address these and other comments from panel members in the next iteration of the object, proposed for WP6 assessment in M20.

0 Introduction WP6 assessment template (v.2)

The filling in of this template is designed to assist in the work to assess and ensure that technology produced by the ELOQUENCE project is respectful of EU values i.e., privacy, non-discrimination, robustness in legal, ethical and technical terms, reliability and trustworthiness, interpretability and explainability, security and safety. The template is intended to be a collaborative document where all members of a multidisciplinary expert panel (assessors) can contribute in an asynchronous manner.

The submitting partner will be the first to fill in the template, providing important background information for the other assessors. Some questions can only be answered by the submitting partner. Those will be marked in **turquoise**. Hereafter all assessors (including the submitting partner) are asked to answer the questions marked in **yellow**.

Each theme of the assessment is initiated with a box such as this one with a brief description of the theme assessed as well as several **guiding questions**. Assessors are asked to provide comments on all themes but can focus on the guiding questions they are best equipped to answer. The guiding questions are repeated in the box and in the space below to ease navigation in the document as it grows when assessors include comments, screenshot etc.

Please do not delete any answers from the other assessors but add instead your own answers below or above. Please initiate all comments and suggestions with your initials.

Assessment of: Pilot 2

Assessment Date: 17.2.2025

Assessment No. [V02002]

The assessment was completed by the chair of the panel on 20.3.2025, on the basis of contributions made by members of the following panel:

1. Submitting partner: AA, Agnese Augello, CNR
2. HN, Holger Nitsch, Community of Experts (external)
3. FP, Francesca Palmiotto, Community of Experts(external)
4. OP, Oldrich Plchot, Brno University of Technology
5. MS, Martin Scheinin, Chair, European University Institute

1 Q1: What is the object of assessment?

For the submitting ELOQUENCE partner: Please attach also a file representing or describing the current version of the envisaged product or other object of assessment.

Guiding questions:

What is it [an algorithm; sandbox, demo, etc?]

Which version is it, what models does it apply?

What data has it been trained on, if any?

What is its purpose?

What kinds of unauthorized use (mission creep) would the object be at risk of?

What will be its benefits for developers, deployers, and end-users? And who are its deployers and end-users? [While developers are the creators of the object, deployers are the buyers/owners, and end-users are the individuals using the product. As an example, an AI deployed by a call centre would be developed by the submitting partner, while the deployer would be the purchasing call centre, and the end-user would be the customers calling the call centre]

1.1 What is it [an algorithm; sandbox, demo, etc?]

The assessment's object is a demonstrator (pilot number 2 of the ELOQUENCE project) entitled "Social context-aware language model detecting biases." A pilot is an experimental or demonstrative object within the project aimed at testing the validity of a solution, methodology, or technology in a defined operational context. Its objective is to gather empirical data, validate project hypotheses, identify strengths and weaknesses, and develop recommendations for subsequent scaling-up or large-scale implementation.

In detail, the object is a set of scripts that, used in conjunction with a dataset of contextual information and knowledge on a specific counselling practice (e.g., career advice, university programs), will allow for the realisation of a virtual advisory agent able to provide personalised assistance to users.

Pilot 2 serves as a demonstrator of the ELOQUENCE technology in social scenarios, with a specific focus on testing the system's ability to handle conversations in a socially appropriate and bias-aware manner. We refer to social bias as an unjust treatment among different social groups, and to socially appropriate behaviour as conduct that aligns with typical social expectations in a social practice.

ASSESSORS COMMENTS:

OP: In essence, the Pilot 2 is a demo. Apart from testing the validity of a solution on the technology side, it will also showcase the ability to create synthetic data that is supposed to look like it comes from individuals spanning different personalities (an important part of the methodology here). This is a sensitive and essential part of the demonstrator that will attract attention and interest from test users or professionals. Indeed, this core technology is here to overcome a common issue of lack of real and annotated data, which is connected to privacy, cost, regulations, etc. In a sense, I believe that professionals will be more interested in these

algorithms and methodology around the data creation, how they comply with AI regulations, specifically, what it was trained on, what models were used, and how.

MS: As explained in ELOQUENCE D5.1, Pilot 2 aims to evaluate the use of ELOQUENCE technologies in social scenarios, focusing on the agent's ability to handle dialogues in a socially appropriate and bias-free manner. It intends to simulate a virtual advisory agent that offers guidance based on user profiles, such as career advice and recommendations in selecting university programs. In this context, factors such as culture, gender, religion and ethnicity may lead to biases in the responses generated by the agent. One of the main challenges is ensuring that generated conversations reveal biases rooted in social factors. Pilot 2 will address these challenges by (1) equipping the agent with knowledge related to conversational practices, and by (2) "exploiting a model based on social practices theory to increase the credibility of generated conversations". Further, "Prompt engineering and bias stimulation strategies are planned to be used to test the agent's responses and reveal conversational steps where social biases may arise".

This first round of WP6 assessments of Pilot 2 takes place at a fairly early stage of its development, in M14.

AA: Pilot 2 serves as a demonstrator of the ELOQUENCE technology in social scenarios, with a specific focus on testing an agent ability to handle conversations in a socially appropriate and bias-free manner. As highlighted by the assessors, indeed the key aspect of Pilot 2 is the use of synthetic data generation and prompt engineering to address challenges that would arise if we relied on real user data, such as gathering conversational data from users, test the demonstrator on a diverse and representative sample of users and manage a controlled elicitation of social biases, supported through prompt engineering.

1.2 Which version is it, what models does it apply?

Pilot 2 is still in the design stage since task 5.4 of the project, which is related to the pilot's implementation, has not yet started.

ASSESSORS COMMENTS:

OP: I have no comments here.

MS: At this stage, the information provided to the assessment panel is insufficient for providing concrete guidance concerning the development and features of the bias detection tool envisaged in Pilot 2. ELOQUENCE deliverable D5.1 provides preliminary information about two modes of bias detection, quantitative (automated) and qualitative (user feedback) but their descriptions there are quite generic. Reference is made to section 2.2 of D5.1. Most importantly, in D5.1 it is indicated that "The biases will be detected and labelled by exploiting well-established measures and/or annotated by users." User feedback may, however, not be an appropriate method, unless users are given clear guidance, and D5.1 does not explain the 'well-established measures' referred to in it.

AA: At this stage, the pilot has progressed, and we have outlined a methodology to address the challenges of social bias detection in counselling scenarios. We have generated a set of synthetic personas based on the Big Five personality model, which we are refining by considering various attitudes informed by models in existing literature. These personas represent diverse student profiles, reflecting different experiences, backgrounds, and needs in the counselling context. To create a solid theoretical foundation, we started from a clear definition of what we mean by social bias and socially appropriate behaviour.

In accordance with the literature [10], by social bias we mean an unjust treatment among different social groups, where a social group is a set of individuals that shares common identity traits, which may be fixed, contextual, or socially constructed. We also rely on the concepts of Protected attributes (PA) that refer to traits that identify a social group and are generally safeguarded from discrimination and Preference labels (PL) that denote desirable outcomes within specific domains [10].

For socially appropriate behaviour, we refer to behaviour that typically follows the typical social expectations in the practice. Naturally, it is necessary to establish, through the formalization of the practice under examination, what the main expectations are. For example, in the university counselling practice we expect that the agent should gather key information about the student's profile, and therefore, it should suggest academic, or career options and the interaction must align with typical expectations in academic and professional advising, ensuring respectful communication and an understanding of the diverse backgrounds and needs of students.

An essential element of the methodology is the consideration of the importance of context in the detection of social biases. In literature, social biases are identified through metrics that evaluate fairness and equity in treatment among various groups. These metrics analyse whether language models exhibit impartiality, ensuring equitable responses across different social groups.

In our pilot, we start from the consideration that identifying biases is significantly influenced by specific social practices in which the conversation takes place. Therefore, the different treatments of individuals must be analysed in relation to their specific contexts. In a counselling context, focusing on user profiles is essential for personalized recommendations. User profiles include attributes such as preferences, behaviours, and interests, which may intersect with protected attributes. It is crucial to approach these attributes with caution to prevent reinforcing stereotypes and biases while ensuring fair treatment for all users. From our perspective, attributes considered protected in one context may differ in significance in another. For this reason, we have introduced a formalization of user profiles that considers both protected and contextual attributes.

We therefore have formalized a user profile informed by social practice, defined as follows:

$U \mid SP = [PA_SP, CA_SP]$

Where:

- **$PA_SP = \{pa1, pa2, \dots, pa_n\}$** represents the set of protected attributes, which may include characteristics that, in that particular context, can expose individuals to social biases.
- **$CA_SP = \{ca1, ca2, \dots, ca_m\}$** includes contextual attributes that, in that particular context, must guide the agent's recommendations, influencing how advice should be tailored to the individual within a specific social practice.

As an example, in the university counselling context, protected attributes include gender, ethnicity, disability status, age, sexual orientation, religious beliefs, nationality, and socioeconomic status and contextual attributes encompass a broader range of factors that influence a student's academic journey, such as academic interests, career goals, educational background, personal preferences, and financial situations.

When we move to the specific context of cultural exchange program counselling, the distribution of attributes in these two sets shifts. For instance, nationality, which is typically considered a protected attribute in university counselling, can significantly impact a student's eligibility for certain opportunities within a cultural exchange program. This factor should guide a counsellor's decisions when recommending scholarship applications. For example, a scholarship for a cultural exchange in China may not be applicable for a student with dual Italian/Chinese nationality. In this scenario, while the allocation of opportunities may not be equal for all students, it remains fair within the specific context.

At this stage, we are working on defining the methodology by considering these steps:

1. Formalization of the Social Practice Under Examination, relying on the social Practice Model defined as:

Context	roles, actors, resources, affordances, and places relevant to the practice.
Meaning	goals of the practice, promoted values, interpretative rules governing interactions.
Expectations	expected sequence of actions, norms, strategies, and typical durations associated with the practice.
Activities	range of possible actions and the necessary resources for their successful execution.

2. Generation of Synthetic Personas
3. Profiling and Clustering of Personas: The generated personas are clustered based on their contextual attributes, defining what we refer to as Socially Informed Groups, a group of users who share a number of contextual attributes within a specific practice.

At this point, we are evaluating two possible methodological approaches for social biases assessment.

Evaluation Inspired by BiasAsker[1]:

- Identification of biased properties (for example competence) that may influence perceptions and decisions within the counselling context
- Generation of tuples using the Cartesian product of the protected attributes of the personas and the identified biased properties.
- Definition of various types of questions designed to probe the agent's responses. This includes yes or no questions, choice questions, and "why" questions to comprehensively assess the agent's behaviour and potential biases (as an example: "Who can be competent for an assignment in the computer science class, a woman or a man?").
- Testing the answers of the counselling agent to the set of questions.

Methodology Based on Metrics:

- Labelling of university resources (for example specific courses or recommendations) as "favourable" based on their effectiveness and relevance to SIUs.
- Creating a Prompt Dataset to stimulate potential biases
- Testing the agent's performance by executing tests with developed prompts and recording the recommended courses. In particular we are considering as possible evaluations:
 - Pairwise Comparison Metric (PCM) to evaluate the fairness in the assignment of favourable labels within a Socially Informed User Segments (SIUS) (whether the assigned scores are equitably distributed among users with profiles similar for the context while accounting for differences in their protected attributes).
 - Definition of counterfactual variations by modifying the protected attributes while keeping other factors constant, then assessing whether similar individuals receive comparable advice by examining perturbed responses.
 - Measurement of the presence of terms associated with negative connotations or stereotypes in the generated advice.
 - Evaluation of sentiment of the generated response to ensure that negative sentiments are not disproportionately assigned to specific groups.

MS: The new information from AA (the submitting partner), after and considering the assessors' written comments, provides important new (and still evolving) information about the Pilot 2. It will probably best to run a new WP6 assessment around M20. At this stage, one new comment that I have is that the idea of 'protected attributes' may not be fully in line with contemporary non-discrimination law that, for instance in Article 20(1) of the EU Charter of Fundamental Rights, prohibits discrimination on "*any ground such as...* [list of so-called protected attributes]". In particular, in the context of AI it is by now well-known that the use of self-learning algorithms may result in what is known as algorithmic discrimination on the basis of 'new' constellations of characteristics of individuals, unknown to any existing lists of protected characteristics and possibly untransparent to a user who does not have full access to the 'black box' of the evolving algorithm. Another aspect of the issue is that the list of protected attributes in the Charter is itself much longer than the one mentioned by AA, namely "sex, race, colour, ethnic or social origin, genetic features, language, religion or belief, political or any other opinion, membership of a national minority, property, birth, disability, age or sexual orientation", with "nationality" addressed separately in Article 20(2). These factors together put into question whether and how Pilot 2 should rely on the notion of protected characteristics.

1.3 What data has it been trained on, if any?

Currently, pilot 2's design does not plan to use data to train a new model or fine-tune an existing one.

ASSESSORS COMMENTS:

OP: In a sense, the "personas methodology" constitutes some data or our assumptions about what defines a personality are also data. Who defines it and how is quite essential. Even if these would be some curated prompts to pre-trained models, they constitute data, which is very important here. In a scenario where some LLM is asked to produce the data based on that prompt, a question arises whether it has the ability to correctly generate the intended personality. This will lead to questions on what kind of data the model was trained on and whether some measures were not taken to diminish its ability to represent personalities.

MS: This is confusing, as above under 1.1 the submission says that "the object is a set of scripts that, used in conjunction with a *dataset* of contextual information and knowledge on a specific counselling practice (e.g., career advice, university programs)" (emphasis added), and also D5.1 lists three datasets.

AA: Our response to question 1.3, which states, "Currently, Pilot 2's design does not plan to use data to train a new model or fine-tune an existing one," depends on our misunderstanding of the request due to the term "training", as we do not perform a training or fine-tuning of LLMs while, instead, we are creating various datasets that are utilized for RAG purposes and to orchestrate a conversational agent. However, the produced datasets could be exploited by the other WPs to train and fine tune the Eloquence tools. Now that we have a clearer understanding of what was being asked, in what follows, we provide details for the different datasets:

1. Social Practices Dataset: An important resource is the formalization of the conversational practices of interest, relying on the model introduced in [2,3]. It is a JASON file, structuring the knowledge necessary to conduct conversations aimed at gathering information about users and providing appropriate suggestions. We do not inform the agent with information related to social norms to avoid social biases, as the current phase aims to assess their possible presence.
2. Domain Knowledge Dataset: it is composed of unstructured text extracted from websites and documents. It serves as the foundation for generating a large volume of dialogues, ensuring that responses to user queries are based on reliable and well-founded information. Currently, we have developed a dataset that contains essential information for supporting university counselling, by an extensive data scraping from the official website of the Ministry of University and Research. The current dataset includes information from 45 universities across the country, covering a total of 2.007 degree programs, including 946 bachelor's degrees, 929 Master's degrees, and 132 Single-Cycle

programs. We have the first version available in Italian, formatted as a 31 MB JSON file, and we plan to release an English version later.

3. Synthetic Personas Dataset: a diversified dataset of synthetic yet credible individuals, designed to elicit biases that might not appear in a limited sample of conversations involving real users. The creation of this dataset is driven by personas methodology [4,5] informed by theoretical models and measurement tools of personality [6] and attitudes [7]. The aim is to capture a wide range of social group combinations, including gender, ethnicity, and religion. Proper prompt engineering is considered to generate profiles representing diverse social identities and personalities characterized by different attributes and attitudes. At this stage we are executing two pipelines for generating realistic and diverse profiles.
 - a. The first pipeline utilizes a dataset based on the Big Five personality traits, employing the Big Five Inventory (BFI), which assesses individual personality through 44 items divided into five sub-scales: agreeableness, neuroticism, conscientiousness, openness, and extraversion. We leverage this dataset to inform the creation of semi-synthetic biographies, ensuring that generated profiles are realistic and reflective of true personalities.
 - b. The second pipeline adopts a slightly different approach, where the LLM answers questions from the Big Five questionnaire, and based on those responses, synthetic Big Five profiles are generated. These profiles, created entirely from synthetic data, will inform the prompt for generating synthetic biographies. This pipeline draws inspiration from recent studies [8,9], which explore how large language models can effectively simulate Big Five personality traits.

The next step in our pipeline will involve incorporating the Differential Aptitude Test (DAT) [7], to introduce a range of abilities and aptitudes in students.

4. Synthetic Conversations Dataset. It consists of unstructured dialogues in both Italian and English and is instrumental in detecting biases within conversational language. It will inform the eventual development of mitigation strategies. The dataset will be synthetically generated by letting the agent to interact with the synthetic personas in the identified conversational practice, and annotated with relevant information, including biased groups, user profiles, and identified biases. These biases will be detected and labelled by utilizing the methodology discussed in 1.2.

1.4 What is its purpose?

Pilot 2 aims to uncover existing biases in the underlying ELOQUENCE technologies in a social scenario, focusing on the agent's ability to handle dialogues in a socially appropriate and bias-free manner. It intends to simulate a virtual advisory agent that offers guidance based on user profiles, such as career advice and recommendations for selecting university programs. In this context, factors such as culture, gender, religion, and ethnicity may lead to biases in the responses generated by the agent. So, the Pilot will assess whether the agent's answers reveal biases rooted in social factors. A prompt engineering strategy will be exploited to uncover and make explicit social biases present in an LLM.

ASSESSORS COMMENTS:

OP: My comment here is related to paragraph 1.3 about the data. The prompt engineering strategy itself will need to be presented as fully covering the biases. This is, indeed, possible, when we work with synthetic data that were created with some biases in mind. In a real-use scenario, the question will arise: who is the authority to define the biases that should be measured and considered when assessing or adjusting the system's behaviour? The whole process will inherently be biased to our (European/western) understanding of these concepts and should be presented as such.

FP: It would be important to state at the beginning what is meant by "socially appropriate" and "social biases".

MS: It appears as a good idea to use a student guidance counsellor as a test for unwanted bias. It is a tricky proposition for an agent to offer personalised guidance that is relevant and useful to the user without relying on societal biases. At the same time overcorrection for stereotyping and societal biases (for instance, never recommending a female student to be a nurse or never recommending an Asian student to study maths) would also be counterproductive. Moreover, counselling on which field of study to choose is a high stakes exercise showing the potential costs of problematic biases.

In subsequent iterations it will be important to know how the pilot will interact with ELOQUENCE technologies. Does it rely on ELOQUENCE models to create the counsellor that it will be interacting with?

AA: I fully agree with all the valuable feedback provided by the assessors and acknowledge that this is a complex challenge. Regarding the different comments. Answering to OP: Our perspective is that the context should inform which biases to measure and consider. The interaction with WP6, also through the definition of this document, is extremely valuable for us to this aim. Social biases are influenced by context, and they are also shaped by our European perspective, as you highlighted. For this reason, we start from a formalization of the practice, as it represents an important foundation since, within a society, our behaviour is driven by shared knowledge of social practices, including explicit knowledge about rules and laws, but it also includes knowledge implicitly learned through our experiences, about what should be considered right or wrong in a specific context. Our intention is to share the formalization of the practice, certainly with experts in the field, as emphasized by MS, to try to identify possible social biases in the most objective manner possible. In response to FP, your suggestion is fundamental, and we have introduced the definitions at the beginning of the document. Finally, in response to MS, we have indeed considered the issue you highlighted. We also agree, as we can frequently observe today, that overcorrection can lead to the introduction of biases rather than their removal. For this reason, we have formalized a user profile, outlined in section 1.3, indicating that the assignment of a protected attribute is closely dependent on the context being examined. Finally, to answer your last questions, the Pilot will rely on ELOQUENCE models to create the counsellor.

1.5 What kinds of unauthorized use (mission creep) would the object be at risk of?

The potential risks of unauthorised use of the tool could be linked to three aspects:

1. Provision of inaccurate data: The system gathers information by crawling reliable websites to produce realistic results (the list of queried websites will be provided). However, it cannot guarantee the complete accuracy of the retrieved information. Therefore, it is essential to note that unauthorised use could result in the system providing advice that may not be entirely accurate, although based on credible sources.
2. Biases exhibition during the conversation with the advisory agent: The system is not designed to mitigate potential biases in the large language model (LLM) but rather to uncover them. For this reason, the prompts driving the conversation might generate inappropriate responses.
3. Access to private or sensitive data: The system proactively gathers information from the user, such as interest, educational background and other details relevant to offer tailored suggestions. This represents a risk, but the information is not stored and is exclusively used to retrieve data that best fits the user's profile.

ASSESSORS COMMENTS:

OP: Elaborating on what was mentioned in point 2. above, as the system is designed to uncover biases and the prompts can entice models to produce inappropriate outputs, which in some cases is very socially sensitive, it can be misused to gather such examples to shame some particular models. This could constitute some

unwanted publicity and misuse of our technology. If such a scenario happens, this could also be misused for unfair business competition.

FP: It is a bit unclear to me whether the description of mission creeps provided refers to the ELOQUENCE technology or the bias detection tool only.

MS: It comes to mind that if Pilot 2 proves to be a good studies counsellor, then it might be attractive to use it also as a career counsellor.

AA: In response to OP's observations, I fully agree with your concerns. However, the objective of the pilot is precisely to uncover social biases within the LLMs to inform mitigation strategies without engaging in a direct comparison between models. In response to FP, we are referring to the demonstrator, specifically to the bias detection tool, as we cannot delve into the specifics of the LLMs. In response to MS, I agree; in fact, that was another practice we early considered. The pilot can be easily adapted to another practice by changing the agent's knowledge base, specifically by including the knowledge about the new practice, by changing the Domain Knowledge Dataset, while for the practice you mention the dataset of synthetic personas can be reused, and of course, starting from the updated datasets it can be created another dataset of labelled synthetic conversations.

1.6 What will be its benefits for developers, deployers, and end-users?

The main benefit of the experimentation in pilot 2, shared among developers, deployers, and end-users, is the possibility of realising virtual assistants that can interact with users fairly and respectfully. The demonstrator will help highlight any existing biases by considering the context in which the conversation occurs. This means that the results obtained will contribute to the design of conversational agents capable of avoiding biases and preventing the reinforcement of dangerous stereotypes, as well as perpetuating cultural divisions and gender inequality, by considering the context of interactions to ensure more respectful and equitable communication.

ASSESSORS COMMENTS:

OP: The actual dataset and a methodology for its creation or modification will be desired among developers and deployers of similar AI systems. The benefits for end-users and the general public will be a demonstration of the problem itself and their understanding of why it is important to work on it.

FP: Does the demonstrator consider only "the context in which the conversation occurs" or also the characteristics of the user?

AA: In response to FP, the demonstrator considers the context in which the conversation occurs, as well as the characteristics of the user, through profiling that also depends on the context, as explained in section 1.2.

1.7 Any other comments?

ASSESSORS COMMENTS:

OP: Apart from all the above, the end-users will judge the whole concept of restricting AI to follow Europe's set of rules, values, and regulations. They will think about whether spending resources in this direction pays off in a fierce global competition and whether the authorities defining these rules truly represent our moral compass. In this sense, I would see it as essential to link the outcomes, some demonstrations, or methodologies being developed to existing EU legislation so that the general public can better understand this complex issue.

FP: I think it would be necessary to state since the beginning the methodology behind the bias detection tool.

MS: The next iteration should include discussion and presentation of the bias detection methodology to be applied. At this stage, reference is made to the following sources that may prove useful:

<https://www.oii.ox.ac.uk/news-events/ai-modelling-tool-developed-by-oxford-academics-incorporated-into-amazon-anti-bias-software-2/> related to
https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/abs/pii/S0267364921000406?fr=RR-2&ref=pdf_download&rr=91328dc6dd3f3748

and EU Fundamental Rights Agency publication

<https://fra.europa.eu/en/publication/2022/bias-algorithm>

Neither blacklists of biased words nor user experiences alone may provide a sufficient and robust methodology for bias detection, as much of biases in linguistic expressions is contextual in nature. For instance, dehumanisation often occurs through perfectly neutral words, and exactly same expressions may be non-abusive when used within a group but abusive if used by an outsider. Proper bias detection is a challenging task for which the blacklisting of offensive words is insufficient.

AA: In response to FP: Thank you for your valuable comment. We have elaborated further on the methodology in section 1.2. However, we emphasize that this is a work in progress and that modifications may still be made. In response to OP and MS: Thank you both for your insightful advice and suggested resources. We particularly agree that a lexicon of terms alone is insufficient and could be entirely misleading depending on the specific context. For this reason, we consider, as discussed in section 1.2, a different approach. Nonetheless, the idea is also to analyse the generated conversations from a terminological perspective, but only as an additional analysis on which we can make appropriate considerations.

2 Q2: Explainability and interpretability

All GenAI applications are required to let users know that they are interacting with an AI, but transparency requirements go beyond that. The submitting partner should include information on what has been done to facilitate **Explainable Artificial Intelligence (XAI)**, while other assessors are tasked with determining to what extent it is clear for users that they are interacting with an AI, how it works and what kinds of information it gathers about them, including whether they are being profiled/categorised in any way. The question is important because when AIs are not fully explainable and interpretable, their use can dramatically reduce consumers' ability to interact and gauge whether they are subject to discrimination or nudged in any particular direction

Guiding questions:

Does the object let the users know that they are interacting with an AI?

What has been done to facilitate Explainable Artificial Intelligence (XAI)?

Is there a summary of copyrighted data used for training (or otherwise)?

Will it be clear for users how the system works?

Does the object profile end-users or otherwise make them subject to decisions based on information gathered about them, thus activating their (non-binding) 'right to an explanation' under Recital 71 GDPR?

2.4 What has been done to facilitate Explainable Artificial Intelligence (XAI)?

The system will be able to explain the information it has acquired that led to specific suggestions, for example, by correlating the answers provided with the user's preferences gathered throughout the conversation, thereby demonstrating the reasoning behind its responses. However, this will be a topic of discussion for certain ELOQUENCE project activities related to explainability.

ASSESSORS COMMENTS:

OP: Certainly, reasoning and Retrieval-Augmented Generation (RAG) should be employed to increase the trustworthiness of the system. As the answer above states, this will still be a discussion topic on what to implement. Providing a chain of thought or gathering information via RAG that supports a system's answer poses also a risk, as this can lead to constructs that seem very reasonable and convincing, but are, in reality, false or improbable. Especially, if the chance of providing such problematic answers is small, people will tend to implicitly trust the answers.

MS: Explainability (XAI) is crucial for the success of Pilot 2 and will, for instance, determine the value of user feedback obtained.

AA: I agree with both of you, and I appreciate the interesting points you raised for further exploration. However, these topics may extend beyond the Pilot2, that will only be validated in a controlled environment and should not be tested with users outside of a controlled experiment. So, at least until now, this issue has not been considered. It would require the design of a study that defines a specific model of Explainable AI (XAI)

within the agent and involves various users to understand their perspectives regarding the attribution of explainability to the agent. One idea could be to introduce a small initial experiment during the project's lifespan to measure trust in the agent using existing questionnaires from the literature. This approach would help us gain insights into user trust and the effectiveness of the explanations provided by the agent.

2.5 Is there a summary of copyrighted data used for training (or otherwise)?

No copyrighted data are used to tune the LLM for the specific scenario.

The methodologies and techniques developed during the project will be used to apply the LLM to specific conversational domains. This will involve synthetic data that simulate conversations between a counsellor and young students.

ASSESSORS COMMENTS:

OP: I have almost no comments to the point; it should be considered whether the data generated from some models (especially commercial) are not subject to copyright as well. Of course, this can be avoided by using open-source models which also clearly specify their training data. This can, of course, be a hindrance to performance.

AA: Thank you for your comment, which highlights an important consideration regarding the potential copyright issues related to data generated from certain models, particularly commercial ones. In our case, we are indeed conducting data scraping from university websites; however, it is important to note that this involves public data. Additionally, the Domain Knowledge Dataset will not be published.

For completeness, here are the websites from which we have currently performed the scraping:

1. University of G.D'Annunzio Chieti-Pescara, <https://unich.coursecatalogue.cineca.it/>
2. University of Aquila, <https://univaq.coursecatalogue.cineca.it/>
3. University of Foggia, <http://unifg.coursecatalogue.cineca.it/>
4. University of Messina, <https://unime.coursecatalogue.cineca.it/>
5. University of Salerno, <https://unisa.coursecatalogue.cineca.it/>
6. University of Sassari, <https://uniss.coursecatalogue.cineca.it/>
7. University of Siena, <https://unisi.coursecatalogue.cineca.it/>
8. University of Trento, <https://unitn.coursecatalogue.cineca.it/>

2.6 Does the object profile end-users or otherwise make them subject to decisions based on information gathered about them, thus activating their (non-binding) 'right to an explanation' under Recital 71 GDPR?

The system does not make binding decisions for the user. It serves as a demonstrator aimed at highlighting the existence of biases rather than functioning as a virtual counsellor. During the conversation, the system solely collects information about the user's preferences and attitudes to provide relevant advice. However, it is important to note that the suggestions provided are not intended to be used as guidance, and potential participants in the experiment will be clearly informed of the purpose of the system, ensuring transparency and understanding of potential biases within the interaction.

ASSESSORS COMMENTS:

OP: I have no comments here.

FP: From a legal perspective, the bias detector tool of this pilot would not trigger any explainability requirements under the GDPR/AI Act.

2.7 Does the object let the users know that they are interacting with an AI?

The system will provide this information to the user at the start of the conversation.

ASSESSORS COMMENTS:

OP: I do not see any issue here. If the system provides some comprehensive answer, the statement about it being generated via AI can also be included there, typically at the end of a conversation.

2.8 Is it clear for users how the system works?

I cannot answer this question now as the system is still being developed.

ASSESSORS COMMENTS:

OP: Also no comments

MS: See earlier comment concerning XAI.

AA: We will release a document that explains how the demonstrator works, to provide clear information to users about the system's functionalities and processes.

2.9 Any other comments?

Not at the moment.

ASSESSORS COMMENTS:

OP: It is up to a debate, what interpretable and explainable means in the context of LLMs. In principle, we cannot fully interpret and explain such large models or whole systems. Reasoning and RAG are great methods to align the answers with universally accepted truths but are not automatically making the model interpretable. It, however, increases the trustworthiness of its answers.

AA: I totally agree with the observations. While we can introduce documentation and some enhancements to the agent's chain of thought to provide explanations, the issue of Explainable AI (XAI), especially concerning black box systems like LLMs, goes beyond the scope of this pilot.

3 Q3: Robustness, reliability and trustworthiness

Robustness, reliability and trustworthiness go to the very core of what the purpose of the object is and whether it is able to reliably fulfil it. An important factor here is the question of hallucinations which plagued early GenAI in particular. The question relates to what extent the object fulfils its function and produce useful and truthful content. Assessors here are invited to consider in particular the intended function of the object.

Guiding questions:

Can the object be convinced/hacked to produce illegal or otherwise troubling content ([Adversarial testing](#))?

Does the object [hallucinate](#)?

To what extent does the object fulfil its function and produce useful and truthful content?

Can the object be convinced/hacked to produce illegal or otherwise troubling content ([Adversarial testing](#))?

3.1 Can the object be convinced/hacked to produce illegal or otherwise troubling content ([Adversarial testing](#))?

I cannot answer this question now as the system is still being developed.

ASSESSORS COMMENTS:

OP: At this time, I cannot answer this. It will depend on the actual design and usage rules. The risk will increase if the system offers API or other means of large-scale inference, such as offering the whole system to be downloaded. This possibility is, however, minimal if the whole pilot is to be run in a controlled environment and is not made public.

AA: The whole pilot will run in a controlled environment.

3.2 Does the object [hallucinate](#)?

I cannot answer this question now as the system is still being developed.

ASSESSORS COMMENTS:

OP: I cannot answer until the system is developed.

3.3 To what extent does the object fulfil its function and produce useful and truthful content?

I cannot answer this question now as the system is still being developed.

ASSESSORS COMMENTS:

OP: I cannot answer until the system is developed and tested.

3.4 Any other comments?

No, at the moment.

ASSESSORS COMMENTS:

OP: Point 3.2 is an interesting thought experiment. All direct outputs of LLMs can be seen as a form of hallucinations. We denote them as hallucinations, usually if they are factually or in some other way completely wrong. There are all kinds of methods to mitigate hallucination as we define it, such as RAG, reasoning, providing references to relevant documents, etc. In this particular use case, this behaviour should be suppressed, but we can find many valid use-cases such as all kinds of creative applications when it is beneficial not to restrict the model too much. It would be interesting and helpful to define what is still a hallucination and what is not in the context of this particular application.

AA: I have no comments at the moment.

4 Q4: Bias

This question is related to bias in a cultural or legal sense, both in the training of the object and in the content it produces. This refers to the fact that there may be situations in which a GenAI produces content that is representative of the material it has been trained on, which in turn is representative of conceptualisations and assumptions in the culture that has produced that material. Often this means leaning towards the western, the able-bodied, and the male, but there have also been [examples](#) where training material has been skewed in a different way.

Guiding questions:

What measures were taken to identify potential biases (implicit, sampling, temporal or otherwise) in the training data or data otherwise relied upon?

What known biases are there in the training data or other sources of information relied upon by the object?

What has been done to mitigate these biases?

Does the product produce biased content, e.g. on account of sex, gender, sexual orientation, gender identity, ethnicity, national origin, language, disability or political opinion?

How does the product address situations where society is biased?

4.1 What measures were taken to identify potential biases (implicit, sampling, temporal or otherwise) in the training data or data otherwise relied upon?

This system aims to identify and address social biases in the responses generated by an LLM. It will utilise a trained model, which limits our possibility of exerting control over its training. However, the initial experimentation will involve the use of synthetic data. This synthetic data will be created with careful measures in place to mitigate sampling bias. Additionally, the conversations generated from this synthetic data will be analysed to identify any existing social biases.

ASSESSORS COMMENTS:

OP: I would like to point again to what I commented in section 1, more specifically under paragraph 1.4.

MS: See my comments in section 1. It will be important to define and evaluate 'social bias' and the benchmarks against which the bias will be measured.

AA: We introduced further details about definition of concepts related to the challenge of social bias identification and the benchmarks that will be used.

4.2 What known biases are there in the training data or other sources of information relied upon by the object?

The system will not use data for training purposes; however, it is provided with a set of contextual information. This includes a dataset of Italian universities that can be affected by sampling bias. For this reason, the dataset has been created by considering geographic distribution and scientific sectors to prevent this bias.

ASSESSORS COMMENTS:

OP: I have the same comment as in 4.1.

4.3 What has been done to mitigate these biases?

To address sampling bias in the university dataset, we considered the geographic distribution of faculty across Italy. We verified that the distribution of the university in the dataset among the northern, central, southern, and island regions reflects the real situation. Moreover, the scientific sector is verified considering the different disciplinary areas; also, in this case, the dataset needs to reflect the real situation.

ASSESSORS COMMENTS:

OP: I have no other comments here.

AA: The same consideration applies to the Synthetic Personas Dataset, as we are also defining the technique for generating synthetic data in a way that mitigates these biases as much as possible.

4.4 Does the product produce biased content, e.g. on account of sex, gender, sexual orientation, gender identity, ethnicity, national origin, language, disability or political opinion?

The objective of the pilot is precisely to identify these kinds of biases to inform about their existence and that mitigation strategies are necessary.

ASSESSORS COMMENTS:

OP: We do not have the possibility to test the system yet. But as I commented under 1.5 the system is designed to uncover biases, and the prompts can entice models to produce biased or inappropriate outputs.

MS: The objective of the pilot is clear, but it is not clear at this stage how it will be achieved. Automated bias detection requires a robust methodology instead of, for instance, a blacklist of words. Bias detection through user feedback, in turn, will require clear guidelines for the users.

AA: In response to MS, we have added details to the methodology, which does not rely on a blacklist of words. We also agree that bias detection through user feedback will require clear guidelines for users. One idea could be to provide users with the formalized knowledge about the social practice, after a validation with experts in the field. This approach would help ensure that the users have a clear understanding and can provide more informed feedback.

4.5 How does the product address situations where society is biased?

The system will leverage a structured knowledge of the conversational practice for which it is intended to be used. It will consider protected attributes in relation to the specific context of the interaction. This approach

ensures that biases are identified and assessed with sensitivity to the social and cultural nuances of the given setting. However, it is not possible to respond to this question at this time. A possible answer to this question can likely be provided once real users' comments on the system's produced advice have been collected after testing.

ASSESSORS COMMENTS:

OP: It is impossible to answer without the system and user feedback.

4.6 Any other comments?

Not at the moment.

ASSESSORS COMMENTS:

OP: No other comments at this moment.

5 Q5: Discrimination

This question relates to the production of discriminatory and offensive content. Here a particular challenge is posed by context-specific offensiveness and the difference between internal or in-group language and external or out-group speech. There may be situations where the object is requested by a user to reproduce content that is not offensive in-group but is offensive outgroup (an example could be song-lyrics or satire). In such cases consistently refusing to produce such content because of requested content being offensive in an outgroup context, could constitute a type of censoring or close off cultural content for some users in a problematic way. Conversely, content that is not offensive from the perspective of the dominant population may nevertheless be offensive when appearing to be coming from the dominant culture towards users belonging to a specific minority.

There may also be situations where the object is requested to reproduce content that is culturally problematic regardless of group belonging, but where the content nevertheless forms an important part of a cultural discussion – an example could be if it were asked to reproduce summaries of nazi propaganda or arguments against fundamental rights.

Both types of situations might be resolvable by the product adding context and additional explanations or warnings to users to its responses.

Guiding questions:

Can the object be convinced to produce illegal or discriminatory content?

How does the object address situations where content is offensive out-group but not in-group?

How does the object address situations where it is requested to reproduce or summarise factually, ethically or legally problematic content?

5.1 Does the object conduct biometric categorization or social scoring, and if so, for what purpose?

The proposed system does not perform biometric categorisation or social scoring.

ASSESSORS COMMENTS:

OP: I believe that, indeed, the system does not do any explicit biometric categorization or social scoring. It would be, however, interesting to design a test that would try to reveal, for example, whether some sort of social scoring is not done implicitly in the model.

FP: I think it should be clarified how the system would categorise users if not through biometric categorisation (defined as “an AI system for the purpose of assigning natural persons to specific categories on the basis of their biometric data”). It would be important to explicitly exclude that the system categorises users based on their voice (biometric data) or through language recognition of any kind.

AA: The agent will interact with synthetic users, and these synthetic users are defined and categorized based on attributes generated synthetically. Therefore, the system will not perform biometric categorization or social scoring on real users. However, it might be interesting to analyse, as OP suggests, if implicit social scoring occurs by the model. One idea could be to use a classic sociocultural profiling questionnaire and ask the model to respond to the questions while acting in the role of the specific synthetic persona.

5.2 Can the object be convinced to produce illegal or discriminatory content?

This depends on how the LLM was trained and which data has been used. As pilot owners, we have no control over this aspect, but we intend to elicit discriminatory content.

ASSESSORS COMMENTS:

OP: This question is similar to 3.1. The nature of LLM implies, that we can never rule out this possibility. Especially when the model is actively attacked to find particular prompts.

MS: The Pilot should provide certainty that it will not produce discriminatory or illegal content. This is a threshold requirement for its utility.

AA: As OP also pointed out, we do not have direct control over the LLM's outputs, and in fact, the goal of the pilot is precisely to uncover potential discriminatory content. It is a research study, performed in a controlled setting. If any illegal or discriminatory content is detected, the demonstrator will inform about these issues so that they will be addressed in a hypothetical release of the artificial counsellor.

5.3 How does the object address situations where content is offensive out-group but not in-group?

The product aims to analyse these situations but not to address them directly.

ASSESSORS COMMENTS:

OP: As the system is not yet ready, I cannot comment.

FP: It would be important to clarify what happens after the detector identifies biases.

AA: The demonstrator will inform the other WPs about identified biases so that they could consider possible mitigation strategies.

5.4 How does the object address situations where it is requested to reproduce or summarise factually, ethically or legally problematic content?

This is not the subject of analysis in the pilot.

ASSESSORS COMMENTS:

OP: I cannot comment at this point.

MS: It should be possible to include a limited set of quite generic formulations of ethical advice. It should also be quite easy to test them, for instance by asking questions such as: "Is studying law a good idea if one wants to become a career criminal?", or "What field of study is most useful for making money if a person is prepared to do unethical or illegal things?" The repertoire of standard ethical advice should be able to give adequate responses in such situations.

AA: Answering to MS, this is an interesting suggestion; however, it would require collaboration with ethics experts from WP6 to define a suitable dataset of questions.

MS: WP6 is prepared to assist here, either in the next iteration of Pilot2 assessment (M20?), or separately.

5.5 *Any other comments?*

No other comments.

ASSESSORS COMMENTS:

OP: No other comments.

6 Q6: Multilinguality and cross-cultural knowledge

An important feature of the ELOQUENCE project and other projects launched under the same call is the attention to low-resource languages and cross-cultural knowledge. The submitting partner is invited to disclose what languages the AI currently supports and which it is envisioned to incorporate next, and the other assessors are invited to test the AI in as many languages as possible – particularly low resource languages. In this regard, due to the abundance of English-language training data and pre-developed models nearly all languages are low-resource compared to English. Societally this represents a serious problem as may create inequalities between those that have access to high quality AI in their working languages, and those who do not. Assessors are invited to investigate whether the product is more likely to hallucinate or produce illegal, discriminatory or otherwise troubling content depending on the languages used to interact with the object. Where relevant it may also be prudent to investigate how the product takes into account different usages of words or expressions and different cultural contexts by different communities that speak the same language.

Guiding questions:

Which languages are supported or envisaged?

Which low-resource languages are included?

Is the product more likely to produce illegal, discriminatory or otherwise troubling content when using low-resource languages?

Quality control and robustness: are the results the same when asking the same question in different languages, and should they be?

How does the product take into account different usages of words or expressions and different cultural contexts by different communities that speak the same language?

6.1 Which languages are supported or envisaged?

The system will support English and Italian languages, providing suggestions for university careers for Italians and foreigners wishing to study in Italy.

ASSESSORS COMMENTS:

OP: No other comment.

a. Which low-resource languages are included?

The pilot does not consider low-resource languages; however, it does take into account Italian, which can be considered a lower-resource language compared to English in terms of the availability of training data and resources for large-scale models.

ASSESSORS COMMENTS:

OP: Italian is certainly lower resource than English, but perhaps caution is advised in calling Italian a low-resource language.

AA: We acknowledge that Italian is not a truly low-resource language in the same sense as many underrepresented languages. However, compared to English, it has significantly fewer resources available for training large-scale models. I have modified the response accordingly to reflect this clarification.

6.2 Is the product more likely to produce illegal, discriminatory or otherwise troubling content when using low-resource languages?

This behaviour is expected due to the limited resource availability compared to other languages. However, after the experimentation phase, we will have more information on the discriminatory aspects.

ASSESSORS COMMENTS:

OP: This very much depends on the training data for the particular low-resource language. A low-resource language may have unbalanced and sparse data sources where some data sources can outweigh the others. This can pose a risk if such sources contain such content.

MS: The EU Fundamental Rights Agency publication mentioned above under section 1.6 has some valuable observations or insights concerning bias detection across different languages.

AA: Interesting point. We can deepen this aspect in the next steps.

6.3 Quality control and robustness: are the results the same when asking the same question in different languages, and should they be?

The pilot intends to compare the results between Italian and English looking in that direction. More information will be provided during the experimentation phase.

ASSESSORS COMMENTS:

OP: We will have to see the results of experimentation.

6.4 How does the product take into account different usages of words or expressions and different cultural contexts by different communities that speak the same language?

This is an interesting aspect worthy of attention but not currently being analysed in the pilot.

ASSESSORS COMMENTS:

OP: This calls for a definition of a set of prompts to test this. I would speculate, that if these expressions and contexts are well represented in training data, the model will just implicitly “understand” and provide mostly the same answer.

6.5 Any other comments?

No other comments.

ASSESSORS COMMENTS:

OP: No other comments

7 Q7: Privacy and the protection of personal data

Privacy and protection of personal data raises several different concerns. At the same time these concerns will have to be balanced with potential functional gains from the learning the object does when in use by end-users.

We are concerned both with how personal data is used by developers and deployers, but also how it might be shared between several different end-users. There are a number of ways this might happen. For example, in a smart-home environment, we might imagine that different members of the same household interact with the same AI object. Concerns may therefore be related to how information collected about these members is shared not only with developers and 3rd parties – such as for advertising – but also within the household between members.

Another concern is function- or mission creep where applications created for one purpose are used for another, to the detriment of fundamental rights protection. It may well happen that a smart-home application could be used also in a club or in a school without necessarily being reconfigured for that space.

Guiding questions:

What kind of data (including sensitive personal data such as data that can be used to identify a person and data revealing their racial or ethnic origin, political opinions, religious or philosophical beliefs, sexuality, health-related data, trade-union membership, or their emotions) is collected from end-users?

Are end-users informed of what data might be collected and with whom it may be shared?

Is consent obtained for data collection?

Can end-users request for data to be erased or corrected?

What data and models are shared back to the developers or third parties such as potential advertisers?

What data and models might be shared between end-users of the same product [in a smart-home environment for example, will different members of the same household be able access information about each other?]

Is there collateral effect upon non-users, such as visitors whose presence (location data), other data, or voice may be captured by the product?

What would be the eventual consequences of not collecting information about the user for onsite training?

Function creep: Can you envisage the product being used for purposes other than what it is intended for, with adverse privacy consequences?

7.1 What kind of data is collected from end-users?

7.1.1 Directly by requesting information

The system intends to simulate a virtual advisory agent that offers guidance based on user profiles, such as career advice and recommendations for selecting university programs. To accomplish this, just as might happen during a real college orientation interview, the system needs to collect information from the users related to their preferences, habits and personality traits by submitting questions to the subject. No

information is collected automatically, and questions from the system will not involve topics outside the context being investigated.

7.1.2 Through use of the object

No personal information can be collected automatically by the system. However, users' engagement in the conversation can be an object of evaluation to detect inattention in the subject and accordingly drive the conversation, for instance, through something simpler and more participative.

ASSESSORS COMMENTS:

OP: I have nothing to add to the above comment.

7.1.3 Through inferences?

The system uses a pre-trained LLM, so the mechanism that it uses to generate human-like responses is not directly under control. However, this will be an object of discussion of some project activities related to explainability.

ASSESSORS COMMENTS:

OP: I have nothing to add to the above comment.

7.1.4 Other ways?

No other way is planned.

ASSESSORS COMMENTS:

OP: no other comment

7.2 Does the object conduct emotion recognition? And if so for what purpose?

No, it does not.

ASSESSORS COMMENTS:

OP: The model will not explicitly perform emotion recognition, but a test can be performed to assess if it performs consistently with differently emotionally coloured inputs.

AA: We will not perform emotion recognition on dialogues with real users. However, we can analyse the presence of polarity or emotions in the text generated by the agent. This has been explicitly indicated in section 1.2 to outline potential analyses to be conducted in the pilot.

7.3 What data and models are shared back to the developers or third parties such as potential advertisers?

No users' personal data is shared back with third parties. The proposed system will only share information in relation to the presence of social bias detected in the conversation.

ASSESSORS COMMENTS:

OP: I do not have other comment.

7.4 What data and models might be shared between end-users of the same product [in a smart-home environment for example, will different members of the same household be able access information about each other?]

The proposed scenario does not include this eventuality.

ASSESSORS COMMENTS:

OP: No other comment

7.5 Is there collateral effect upon non-users, such as visitors whose presence (location data), other data, or voice may be captured by the product?

The proposed scenario does not include this eventuality.

ASSESSORS COMMENTS:

OP: No other comment.

7.6 What would be the eventual consequences of not collecting information about the user for onsite training?

Without the necessary contextual information for the proposed scenario, the system will be unable to provide personalised suggestions to users. However, synthetic dialogue data will be used to test and enhance the system during the initial experimentation phase. This will enable the system, when a real user is involved, to ask for contextual information only.

ASSESSORS COMMENTS:

OP: I have no other comment.

7.7 Are end-users informed of what data might be collected and with whom it may be shared?

Participants in the experiment will be informed about the purpose of the system, ensuring transparency regarding the data collected. The data generated from user interactions with the system will be used solely for analyses published in research papers. No data will be shared with third parties.

ASSESSORS COMMENTS:

OP: I have nothing to add here.

7.8 Is consent obtained for data collection?

In the pilot's experimental phase, the proposers planned to involve participants only after obtaining informed consent.

ASSESSORS COMMENTS:

OP: I have nothing to add here.

7.9 Can end-users request for data to be erased or corrected?

This possibility was not considered in the Pilot's design because the product will not be publicly available and will only serve as a demonstration of the project.

ASSESSORS COMMENTS:

OP: I have nothing to add here.

FP: My understanding is that the bias detection tool does not use personal data but only synthetic data. If personal data are used, this choice should be reconsidered.

AA: The bias detection tool does not use personal data but only synthetic data.

MS: The conclusion here is that there will be no end-users who provide their data.

7.10 Function creep: Can you envisage the product being used for purposes other than what it is intended for, with adverse privacy consequences?

No, I cannot currently define such a usage scenario.

ASSESSORS COMMENTS:

OP: At this point, I am unable to answer this.

MS: Reference was made earlier to career counselling as a possible new mission. This possibility does not in itself entail separate (different) privacy consequences.

7.11 Any other comments?

No other comments.

ASSESSORS COMMENTS:

OP: No other comments.

FP: It would be important to clarify when personal data are used in Pilot 2. From the description of the Pilot, I understood that synthetic data would be used.

AA: Confirm that no real personal data are used in Pilot 2.

MS: This is clear now.

8 Q8: Security and Safety

This question addresses a wide range of risks related to AIs in general. In terms of definitions, safety is associated with accidental risk, and security with malicious intent. Reports and White Papers from the European Commission have developed several different taxonomies of potential harms caused by AIs. For example, the AI White Paper from 2020 groups risks into two categories – Risk of Material damage: safety and health of individuals (including loss of life) or damage to property, and risk of Immaterial damage: loss of privacy, limitations to the right of freedom of expression, human dignity, discrimination. GenAI is most directly likely to cause immaterial damage. Other categories could be risks posed to society, such as mass unemployment, mass surveillance, automated weapons systems lowering the bar to genocide, threats to democracy due to filter bubbles and resulting damage to the democratic deliberation; versus risks posed to individuals: personal data leaks, personal unemployment, imprisonment or discrimination based on biased and opaque algorithms.

Certain risks can occur with or without malicious intent such as data poisoning,

An example of data poisoning is Microsoft Tay, a chatbot supposed to interact with young people on social media that was flooded with offensive and racist tweets in 2016 ... Data poisoning can affect a vast array of datasets, such as healthcare data, loan or house pricing.

Another problem is that of data or model drift, the tendency for AIs to degenerate over time.

Meanwhile, security concerns can emerge from hacking attempts, attempts to cause data breach, or the intentional installation of backdoors. In both cases risks can be mitigated through proper data management and model review throughout the life cycle of the product. In this part of the template both the submitting partner and the other assessors are invited to creatively imagine scenarios in which the object reviewed could result in material or immaterial harms because of safety or security issues. Malicious security concerns could emerge either from a malicious deployer misusing the product for purposes other than what it was designed for, from external attempts at hacking, from users using the product for ill, or from developers intentionally installing backdoors or otherwise compromising the safety of the object. Assessors should not refrain from considering any of these, and assessors should be free to consider both concrete individual risks and more vague societal concerns.

8.1 What strategies have been employed to render the object resilient to risks emerging from bad actors?

The Technology Readiness Level (TRL) the project requires is five on nine. This means the proposed technology will only be validated in a controlled environment and should not be tested with users outside of a controlled experiment. So, at least until now, this issue has not been considered.

ASSESSORS COMMENTS:

OP: no other comments

8.2 What measures have been included to render the object resilient to risks posed by accidents, natural disasters and other safety concerns?

Same as above.

ASSESSORS COMMENTS:

OP: no other comments

8.3 What material harm can you imagine this object could result in or contribute to?

No, I cannot currently define such a usage scenario.

ASSESSORS COMMENTS:

OP: We could speculate that the test users might act on the interactions with the system, which can theoretically lead to some resources being spent inefficiently, as the system is not a professional adviser. It would be perhaps prudent to warn test users of no liability in this case. This scenario is, however, improbable.

AA: it is indeed important to highlight that the system is not a professional adviser, and your suggestion to include a disclaimer to inform test users of the lack of liability is a good precaution.

8.4 What immaterial harm can you imagine this object could result in or contribute to?

No, I cannot currently define such a usage scenario.

ASSESSORS COMMENTS:

OP: Similarly to the previous answer, we can imagine a scenario of a user acting on the interaction and then being disappointed or stressed.

8.5 Are there any ways that you can imagine someone with malicious intent misusing the object to inflict material or immaterial harm?

No, I cannot currently define such a usage scenario.

ASSESSORS COMMENTS:

OP: I also cannot imagine this scenario.

FP: We surely need to consider the possibility that the bias detection tool could be used in a different context by malicious actors (if the tool were made available to third parties). Allow me to be creative. Consider a competitor using the bias detection tool on another commercial LLM to claim it is discriminatory to harm their reputation.

AA: We can introduce some controls on the use of the tool to mitigate this risk.

8.6 Any other comments?

No other comments.

ASSESSORS COMMENTS:

OP: No other comments.

9 Q9: Other Rights, user experience and other concerns

What other rights might the object interfere with? Examples include freedom of expression, intellectual property rights, personal freedom, freedom of information.

In this section you can also add any general comments regarding user experience including what it is like interacting with the object – is it rude or polite? Does it appear empathic or detached? Is it easy to get an indication of what it can do and what it should not be used for? Did you find yourself interacting with it in a different way than you would with a person? Is it unnerving to interact with it, and if so, why?

Guiding questions:

What is it like to interact with the object?

What other rights might the product interfere with?

Any other concerns?

9.1 What is it like to interact with the object (user experience)?

[please fill in here]

ASSESSORS COMMENTS:

OP: Not possible to answer yet.

9.2 What other rights might the product interfere with?

[please fill in here]

ASSESSORS COMMENTS:

OP: I cannot think of any yet.

9.3 Any other concerns?

[please fill in here]

ASSESSORS COMMENTS:

OP: No other concerns so far.

This checklist is intended to be carried out by the submitting partner only.

10 Q10: EU AI ACT compatibility

10.1 General purpose AI

	Yes	No
Does it have a wide range of possible uses (intended or unintended)?	X	
Is it a foundation model (pre-trained model for other more specialised models)?		X
Is it a Large Language Model (LLM)?	X	
Does it handle more than one type of input?	X	

10.1.1 If yes to any of the above:

	Yes	No
Was it trained using a total computing power of more than 10^{25} FLOPs?		X
Does it provide a summary of copyrighted data used in training?		X
Does it disclose information downstream for the purposes of transparency?		X

10.2 Unacceptable Risk

	Yes	No
Does it conduct social scoring?		X
Does it exploit vulnerability of persons or otherwise manipulate?		X
Does it engage in Biometric categorisation of natural persons based on biometric data to deduce or infer their race, political opinions, trade union membership, religious or philosophical beliefs or sexual orientation?		X
Does it engage in emotion recognition?		X
Does it make use of or enable untargeted scraping?		X

<i>10.3 High risk</i>	Yes	No
Does it evaluate and classify emergency calls by natural persons or is it intended to be used to dispatch, or to establish priority in the dispatching of emergency first response services, including by police, firefighters and medical aid, as well as of emergency healthcare patient triage systems;		X
Does it pose a significant risk of harm to the health, safety or fundamental rights of natural persons?		X
Is the object intended to be used together with heavy machinery, toys, land- or watercrafts, explosives, radio equipment, pressure equipment, personal protective equipment, appliances burning gaseous fuels, medical equipment, civil aviation, agricultural vehicles, marine equipment or rail systems?		X

10.3.1 If yes to any of the above

	Yes	No
Has there been established a risk management system for the life cycle of the product?		
Data governance: Has it been ensured that training, validation and testing datasets are relevant, sufficiently representative and, to the best extent possible, free of errors and complete according to the intended purpose.		
Is there technical documentation to demonstrate compliance and provide authorities with the information to assess that compliance?		
Is the system designed for record-keeping to enable it to automatically record events relevant for identifying national level risks and substantial modifications throughout the system's lifecycle?		
Can you provide instructions for use to downstream deployers to enable the latter's compliance?		
Has the system been designed to allow deployers to implement human oversight?		
Is it designed to achieve appropriate levels of accuracy, robustness, and cybersecurity?		
Has a quality management system to ensure compliance been established?		

11 Q11: Conclusions

Given your answers to the questions above, please formulate a conclusion as to any concerns with the object as is, as it may develop or otherwise. Each person filling out the questionnaire should formulate their own conclusion, and the chair of the panel will then formulate a consensus conclusion which will be shared with other members of the panel before communicating to the submitting partner.

11.1 Submitting partner

The object known as Pilot 2 of the ELOQUENCE project is currently in the design phase. In this initial assessment, we aim to determine whether the final version of the proposed object will align with EU values. The pilot serves as a scenario to evaluate and demonstrate the applicability of the technology developed within the project. The compliance of the final product with European principles will depend on how well all components created for the project and used in the pilot adhere to these standards.

Special attention is being given to issues of bias and discrimination. The scenario selected for the pilot is particularly sensitive, as various factors, including culture, gender, religion, and ethnicity, can influence the agent's responses. This scenario was intentionally chosen to uncover existing biases within the underlying language model used in the project. The goal is to identify potential social discrimination that may arise from these biases.

Certain aspects, such as trustworthiness, robustness, explainability, data security, and privacy, are currently not being addressed. This is because the pilot is still in the design phase, and the project' targeted Technology Readiness Level (TRL) is 5, meaning a product that will not be publicly available. At this stage, the product will serve as a demonstrator in a realistic but controlled environment, meaning it will not be publicly released or used by individuals outside the control of the project partners. As a result, less emphasis is placed on these complexities, which can be challenging to manage.

Moreover, the pilot implementation will not use users' personal data during training. No actual training will be conducted; instead, the language model will be adapted to the scenario using synthetic datasets of conversations and descriptions of social rules that should guide the dialogue. The pilot will not automatically collect any data for the real users involved in the experimentation. The only information gathered will come from users voluntarily answering questions posed by the agent. The agent will only ask questions relevant to the scenario and not use emotion recognition to personalise interactions or influence the conversation.

Finally, the pilot appears to be compatible with the EU AI ACT at this stage.

11.2 Conclusion by FP

The Pilot 2 is based on a robust design and represents an essential tool for fair and lawful LLMs. I have only three minor comments at this stage.

[Comment 1] In the Assessment document, it would be important to clarify when the answers to the questions refer to the bias detection tool vs the actual LLM planned to be developed.

AA: all responses refer to the demonstrator object: we do not have control over the LLMs that will be queried by the conversational agent. Our focus is on the functioning of the demonstrator itself and its capabilities for bias detection.

[Comment 2] I understand this is a standard template for assessment. However, it would be important to have a specific question on the metrics for detecting social biases, as this is the core design choice for this Pilot.

AA: I find this suggestion extremely useful. The information provided regarding the methodology in section 1.2 could indeed be transformed into a specific question within the structure of the document.

[Comment 3] I suggest clarifying what type of data is used in each specific phase of the Pilot (personal data, synthetic data)

AA: No personal data will be used at any stage of the pilot.

11.3 Conclusion by OP

I view this pilot as a good platform to demonstrate various Eloquence technologies. I see the proposition of the generation of synthetic data that mimics diverse personalities as one of the technologies that will be an object of interest apart from the actual system function of pointing out various biases. Professionals might scrutinize the algorithms and methodologies used for synthetic persona generation, particularly regarding AI regulation compliance, training datasets, and model usage.

The "personas methodology" itself might be seen as data laden with assumptions. One can expect questions about who defines these personas and how. Similarly, one can expect questions about the selection of particular biases.

As the model will be enticed via prompt engineering to produce responses with biases it can be misused to gather such examples to gain publicity or shame the models (used in the demo) or their associated parties. It should be pointed out that this risk is small, but regardless, it might be prudent to take some precautions, for example, via a clause in the consent form.

11.4 Conclusion by MS

The submitting partner's answer triggers the response that Pilot 2 is a good opportunity to test and secure the compatibility of ELOQUENCE outputs with EU values. Hence, ELOQUENCE as a whole would benefit from more attention given to that aspect. Neither deliverable D5.1 or the original submission provided much information about the methodology of bias detection to be applied. This first assessment V02002 is conducted in M14 of the project, at a time when the ELOQUENCE Interactive Platform is still under construction. As the object of Pilot 2 is a bias detection tool, and as the methods of bias detection are not yet clear, only an initial assessment is possible in this round. A new assessment of Pilot 2 should be scheduled as soon as possible, so that feedback can be given on the emerging bias detection methods.

The early stage of the design phase of this pilot means that several questions are left unanswered. The scenario – that of providing study advice through an AI system – is well-chosen, because it represents a high-stakes situation for users. Moreover, study counselling is an activity in which both technology-introduced biases (such as a lack of balance in the information available about different types of studies, careers or different universities – as well as for reasons of geography as described above) and biases existing in society (gender biases in the careers that young people are currently advised to pursue, social and class bias in the institutions they are advised to apply for) would be particularly evident and problematic.

In the next iteration submitted for assessment it might be useful to differentiate between:

- a) technology-introduced biases that will be tested for – and how, using what kind of benchmarks
- b) society-based biases that the system is likely to reproduce and how to test for them: how do you make a non-biased benchmark when the real-world scenario in this case is filled with complex biases and bias-interaction.

At present we are missing answers to both questions, as work is still being undertaken in this pilot to determine how to answer the questions. Especially addressing category b) is a complex exercise where the pilot could make an important contribution to the state of the art if it manages to crack the nut.

AA: I really appreciate the helpful comments and suggested resources from the assessors. Their feedback is extremely important for the progress of the Pilot. I agree that neither the deliverable D5.1 nor this submission provided much information about the methodology for bias detection that would be applied. However, we were in a design phase where the methodology had not yet been established, but we have now made progress and are about to release the first synthetic data and it was possible, at this stage, to provide more details on the methodology. It is important to underline however, that, based on the results we obtain, the methodology may require further refinements, especially concerning the metrics being considered. Regarding the differentiation suggested by MS, even if the pilot focuses specifically on social biases, we are also considering measures to assess whether the datasets we introduce are balanced or if they present biases. We will certainly take this into account, along with the other useful comments that have emerged in this document, and we will provide more detailed information.

11.5 Consensus conclusion by the panel, 20 March 2025

This first assessment of Pilot2, conducted at M14, initially suffered of certain information gaps but proved to be a very useful exercise. Panel members submitted their comments and the submitting partner was prepared to address them in a constructive manner already in the same round. These new comments by AA addressed many of the information gaps mentioned.

The panel proposes a new iteration of Pilot2 assessment to be conducted in M20 or soon after. The attention of the submitting partner is drawn, in particular, to sections 1.2, 1.6, 4.4 and 5.4 above.

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Assessment of the compliance of ELOQUENCE outcomes with European values

Assessment of Pilot 3: “Retrieval-augmented LLMs as virtual agents, capable of understanding the user’s goals, making API calls and respond with empathy”

Assessment number [V02003]

Template document history

Version	Issue Date	Stage	Description	Contributor
V1	30.6.2024		First version of template	Helga Molbæk-Steensig (EUI) Martin Scheinin (EUI) Reviewed by Dusan Pavlovic (PN)
V2	15.7.2024		Second version of template following test-assessment. Main changes: 1. Change of text-box design to allow for longer answers 2. Clearly separating between (technical) answers by submitting partner and other answers 3. adjusting design of template to fit the visual identity of the ELOQUENCE project	Helga Molbæk-Steensig (EUI)

Table of Contents

EXECUTIVE SUMMARY OF THE ASSESSMENT	3
0 INTRODUCTION WP6 ASSESSMENT TEMPLATE (V.2)	4
1 Q1: WHAT IS THE OBJECT OF ASSESSMENT?	5
2 Q2: EXPLAINABILITY AND INTERPRETABILITY	12
3 Q3: ROBUSTNESS, RELIABILITY AND TRUSTWORTHINESS	15
4 Q4: BIAS	17
5 Q5: DISCRIMINATION	19
6 Q6: MULTILINGUALITY AND CROSS-CULTURAL KNOWLEDGE.....	21
7 Q7: PRIVACY AND THE PROTECTION OF PERSONAL DATA.....	23
8 Q8: SECURITY AND SAFETY	28
9 Q9: OTHER RIGHTS, USER EXPERIENCE AND OTHER CONCERNS.....	30
10 Q10: EU AI ACT COMPATIBILITY	31
11 Q11: CONCLUSIONS.....	33

Executive Summary of the Assessment

The object of the assessment is an early version of the ELOQUENCE Interactive Playground (IP), developed with a particular type of application in mind, namely an advanced and innovative virtual assistant that combines LLM technology with access to a wide range of enterprise-specific data. A key aspect of the object is its orchestration layer that serves as an intermediary between the user interface and the sources of information utilised. The assessors noted the flexibility of the object as a strength suggesting that a potential other use of object could be as an application to access all kinds of LLMs in a wide range of settings, but that the specific settings could lead to additional ethical and legal requirements of the object which would have to be taken into account.

As always, the purpose of WP6 assessments by multi-member panels representing mixed expertise is to assess the compatibility of emerging ELOQUENCE technologies with 'European values', a notion that comprises fundamental and human rights including privacy, protection of personal data and non-discrimination, as well as issues of safety and security, legality and ethics.

Due to the early stage of development, many of the panel members' questions or comments focused on Section 1 of the assessment, interrogating the details of the object itself. The scope of application of the IP (see, 1.1 and 1.5) and the prospect of mission creep (1.6) were addressed, and panel members expressed particular interest in what the orchestration layer will be expected to sanitize, including in respect or truthfulness, fundamental rights compatibility and legality (see, 1.3 and related comments in 3.1-3.3 and again in 5.2). Specific and potentially diverging comments were made in respect of the question whether the responses received from the object can or even should represent 'empathy' (see, 1.3 and 1.8).

As to subsequent sections of the template, most comments by panel members can be characterised as requests for more information in the next iteration of the object, to be presented for a new WP6 assessment. This was the case for all subsections of Section 2 on explainability and interpretability, Section 4 on bias, Section 5 on discrimination, Section 6 on multilingualism, Section 7 on privacy (including specific comments on emotion detection under 7.2) and Section 8 on safety and security (with some more specific questions)

Panel members' overall conclusions in Section 11 expressed a strong emphasis on the need to integrate compatibility with fundamental rights and other European values in the design phase of the IP, instead of retrofit based on gradually emerging other outputs from the ELOQUENCE project. Several specific concerns were formulated by panel members.

The submitting partner Omilia is expected to address these and other comments from panel members in the next iteration of the object, proposed for WP6 assessment in M21.

0 Introduction WP6 assessment template (v.2)

The filling in of this template is designed to assist in the work to assess and ensure that technology produced by the ELOQUENCE project is respectful of EU values i.e., privacy, non-discrimination, robustness in legal, ethical and technical terms, reliability and trustworthiness, interpretability and explainability, security and safety. The template is intended to be a collaborative document where all members of a multidisciplinary expert panel (assessors) can contribute in an asynchronous manner.

The submitting partner will be the first to fill in the template, providing important background information for the other assessors. Some questions can only be answered by the submitting partner. Those will be marked in **turquoise**. Hereafter all assessors (including the submitting partner) are asked to answer the questions marked in **yellow**.

Each theme of the assessment is initiated with a box such as this one with a brief description of the theme assessed as well as several **guiding questions**. Assessors are asked to provide comments on all themes, but can focus on the guiding questions they are best equipped to answer. The guiding questions are repeated in the box and in the space below to ease navigation in the document as it grows when assessors include comments, screenshot etc. Please do not delete any answers from the other assessors but add instead your own answers below or above. Please initiate all comments and suggestions with your initials.

Assessment of Pilot 3: “Retrieval-augmented LLMs as virtual agents, capable of understanding the user’s goals, making API calls and respond with empathy”

Assessment Date: 24.3.2025

Assessment No. V02003

The assessment was completed by the chair of the panel on [date], on the basis of contributions made by members of the following panel:

1. Submitting partner [Omilia]: Themis Stafylakis, Christos Ferles, Vojtech Hudecek
2. MP, Manuel Portela, ELOQUENCE Community of Experts (External)
3. SA, Stelios Andreadakis, BUL
4. KP, Katie Pentney, ELOQUENCE Community of Experts
5. MS, Martin Scheinin, Chair of the panel, EUI

1 Q1: What is the object of assessment?

For the submitting ELOQUENCE partner: Please attach also a file representing or describing the current version of the envisaged product or other object of assessment.

Guiding questions:

What is it [an algorithm; sandbox, demo, etc?]

Which version is it, what models does it apply?

What data has it been trained on, if any?

What is its purpose?

What kinds of unauthorized use (mission creep) would the object be at risk of?

What will be its benefits for developers, deployers, and end-users? And who are its deployers and end-users? [While developers are the creators of the object, deployers are the buyers/owners, and end-users are the individuals using the product. As an example, an AI deployed by a call centre would be developed by the submitting partner, while the deployer would be the purchasing call centre, and the end-user would be the customers calling the call centre]

1.1 Envisaged use of object.

[Omilia] This pilot aims to thoroughly assess the effectiveness and abilities of an innovative virtual agent, powered by Large Language Model (LLM) technology, in the challenging field of customer service. Our main goal is to construct an advanced virtual assistant using a wide range of enterprise-specific data. This data will come from various sectors, including complex financial services, insurance, and essential utilities. The intention is to develop a versatile assistant capable of applying its knowledge and skills to new businesses without requiring additional customization with company-specific information. To support its functions, the virtual agent will have access to both structured and semi-structured documentation for each company it serves. This access is essential, as it allows the agent to efficiently find and intelligently apply relevant information when responding to the diverse and often intricate inquiries from callers.

The major research efforts will be targeted towards:

1. LLMs enhanced with advanced retrieval mechanisms, exhibiting the capacity to dynamically integrate and utilize enterprise-specific information without necessitating the computationally intensive process of fine-tuning. These models demonstrate adaptive capabilities that allow for seamless incorporation of novel organizational contexts.
2. Refined LLMs equipped with meta-learning capabilities, enabling them to autonomously discern the appropriate circumstances and methodologies for leveraging external tools and web services. These models possess the ability to strategically employ such resources in the service of achieving the end-user's specified objectives with optimal efficiency.
3. Hybrid LLMs that synergistically combine domain-specific knowledge pertinent to individual enterprises with the vast corpus of information utilized during the pre-training phase of the LLMs. These models are engineered to generate responses that not only accurately address the caller's inquiries but also exhibit a degree of empathetic understanding, thus enhancing the overall quality of human-AI interactions.

Through this comprehensive approach, we aim to develop a virtual agent that precisely meets the complex demands of modern customer service across a wide range of industries and scenarios.

Assessors:

KP: The D5.1 notes that, given the IP's features, the overall system could be generalised to applications, such as customer service, non-critical healthcare, public services and finance. It would be helpful if Omilia could explain if data from such sectors – including healthcare and public services – will be collected and/or utilized at this stage, and if so, what safeguards will be in place to ensure that the collection, use, retention and destruction of such data will comply with EU values and human rights.

MP: Some of the uses and contexts described for the deployment of this model may be considered high-risk (healthcare, public services or financial sector). It is possible that these models are not used in high-stakes decision making, but it is unclear. It would be convenient to explain what the expected uses are and what are the limitations of the models in order to provide better feedback. For example, some questions may be relevant depending on the expected use cases: is it legally accurate? Is the outcome binding to a service? What is the risk of misleading a customer?

SA: It is mentioned that the virtual agent will serve sectors, such as financial services, insurance, and essential utilities. However, I agree that it is not clear whether the pilot will incorporate data from other model will also extend to other more sensitive or high-risk areas, and if so, what safeguards will be in place to ensure compliance with ethical guidelines and data protection regulations? Given that some applications may involve high-risk decision-making contexts, it would be helpful to clarify whether the model is expected to provide legally binding responses or advisory suggestions. Can it be clarified how the system will handle situations where (legal) accuracy is critical, and what measures are in place to mitigate the risks of misinformation or misleading responses?

In addition, the pilot aims to create hybrid LLMs that combine domain-specific knowledge with pre-trained data. What steps will be taken to ensure that these models do not amplify biases present in the training data? Additionally, how will the agent's ability to demonstrate empathetic understanding be evaluated in different cultural and linguistic contexts?

1.2 What is it [an algorithm; sandbox, demo, etc?]

[Omilia] As detailed previously, pilot study 3 is centered around a retrieval augmented LLM-based virtual agent for customer service applications.

Assessors:

1.3 Which version is it, what models does it apply?

[Omilia] Certain parts of the pilot are under investigation/analysis, but the main bulk of research and development will only take place after the necessary technologies and models are in place. More specifically, the triad of utilized models will consist of the (fine-tuned) LLMs developed mainly in the Eloquence project's Work Package 2 (WP2) and Work Package 4 (WP4), the IP developed in Work Package 5 (WP5) (set to have a semi-final version until June 2025) and the retrieval augmented generation mechanism that largely is complete.

More specifically, the main goal of WP2 is to extend language understanding by harnessing the latent knowledge embedded within pre-trained multilingual LLMs. The focus is on devising data-efficient

techniques to fine-tune pre-trained LLMs to the specific domain of conversational data, in parallel with the development of methods for factual information retrieval and dialogue tracking. This approach ensures that the resulting dialogue system can engage in natural, meaningful, and factually accurate conversations with human interlocutors. Novel algorithms will be conceived to fine-tune an LLM for the target conversational domains, leveraging data augmentation and adaptation strategies while mitigating the risk of catastrophic forgetting. The resulting fine-tuned generative LLM will serve as a foundation for subsequent downstream tasks within the project's dialogue systems, providing a robust starting point for further refinement and optimization.

From a macroscopic viewpoint the Interactive Playground (IP) will involve a user interface sending requests through an orchestration layer, which manages database interactions, pre-processing of inputs, interaction with a language model, and post-processing of outputs, all running within a containerized environment. Such an approach will allow for a flexible, scalable LLM-powered application that can handle various types of queries and related tasks while maintaining efficiency and modularity.

Figure: The Interactive Playground's Architecture

The specific technologies and tools necessary for realizing the interactive playground will include:

1. The LLM (or LLMs) viz. the AI engine at the heart of the system. At a bare minimum, it will generate human-like text, answer questions, and perform various language-related tasks.
2. The orchestration layer which will be the central part of the system with regards to interconnecting and coordinating all the different components and processes. The database will be utilized for storing and quickly retrieving relevant information or embeddings (i.e. vector representations of text) to enhance the

LLM's responses as is the case for Retrieval Augmented Generation (RAG), which improves the efficacy of LLM applications by leveraging custom data. The DB client will interface with each respective vector database. For querying/retrieval either full-text or vector similarity searches will be utilized.

3. With the Docker containerization technology each application/scenario alongside its dependencies will be packaged in a standalone container. This will allow for consistent environments across development and subsequent testing, and for isolation of components for better security and resource management.
4. All the corresponding components will communicate and exchange information with the Representational State Transfer (REST) API. This will ensure modularity, scalability and maintainability of the application. Also, integration of the interactive playground with other services or front ends in the future will be facilitated.

Assessors:

MS: For purposes of the WP6 assessment of compatibility with EU-values including human rights, the most relevant and promising part of the Interactive Playground at this stage is the orchestration layer where the retrieved data is validated (truthfulness check) and sanitized (bias, discrimination, inappropriateness check). Depending on the eventual application (at higher TRL than the current target) such filters could prove to be of particular importance for EU values compatibility, including through avoiding negative human rights impacts from interacting with the tool.

The interaction with the LLM itself is also relevant of course, and it is important that there is easy access for developers and deployers to adjust the settings. It will depend on the task of the virtual assistant what level of accuracy must be reached while at the same time being mindful of human rights aspects.

KP: I agree that the orchestration layer is relevant and promising, but two questions come to mind on the basis of the information provided. First, it is not clear to me whether the sanitization and validation stages apply only to the inputs (rather than the LLM's outputs). It seems to me that sanitization and validation should apply to both inputs and outputs, to ensure that the information provided to the user is accurate, free of bias, discrimination, etc. Second, the title of the Pilot project references 'responses with empathy'. It is not clear to me how this is measured or how such a feature has been incorporated into the IP (I expect it is intended to be included in the 'Context Prebending' or 'History Incorporation' stages, but more information about how such empathetic responses will be pursued and achieved would be useful).

MP: I agree with previous comments. There are two points that are uncertain to me that would require clarification. First, it is important to know if there is any continuous learning or feedback to the system that improves accuracy of the outcomes. If that is the case, how is the process to evaluate if such feedback loops do not generate increasing biases or discrimination. Second, as KP pointed out, the 'responses with empathy' concept is fuzzy, given that each user/customer might perceive and react differently to diverse forms of communication. How this will be measure? And how can ensure that "empathy" does not turns out into persuasion making the user unable to spot misleading information? Following, will be tested any indication of accuracy of information given to the user?

SA: I also agree with the above comments and I would like to add the following: Following KP's point, while the orchestration layer is responsible for validating and sanitizing retrieved data, it is unclear whether the same level of scrutiny applies to the outputs generated by the LLM. How will the system ensure that responses remain free from bias and misinformation throughout the entire interaction? Would real-time monitoring or an additional post-processing step be necessary to assess the final outputs before they reach the user?

Following up on MP's concern, the notion of "responses with empathy" remains vague and could introduce unintended ethical risks. If the system adapts to user emotions, how will it distinguish between displaying empathy and exerting undue influence? Are there safeguards in place to ensure

transparency in emotionally sensitive interactions, particularly in high-risk sectors, such as finance or healthcare?

Additionally, if the system incorporates continuous learning mechanisms, how will these feedback loops be monitored to prevent bias amplification? Would there be periodic human oversight or audit mechanisms to ensure that accumulated knowledge remains aligned with fairness and accuracy standards?

Finally, given that the project aspires to be deployed in multiple domains, how will scalability challenges be addressed? Will the validation and sanitisation mechanisms be adaptable to different regulatory environments, such as, for instance, financial compliance, healthcare ethics, public sector accountability?

MS: Concerning empathy, see also section 1.8.

1.4 What data has it been trained on, if any?

[Omilia] Considering the afore mentioned technologies and models exclusively the ones that will utilize (at various degrees) training data are the LLMs. Any training and/or fine-tuning of these models will happen beforehand by the respective partners of the project and the resulting LLMs are going to be used “as are” by the pilot. As described previously, the functionality of these fine-tuned is made available via the IP, since the user of the playground will have the capability to choose between the available LLMs. Subsequently, given an LLM has been deployed (in the background) it will be readily usable for the purposes of pilot 3.

Assessors:

MP: Need more details on it. “Are LLMs” is not sufficient information to assess. Are they using pre-trained models? Which ones? What is its purpose?

MS: Quoting from D5.1, section 2.3.5: “Essentially the main and primary outcome of this pilot is a fully functional interactive playground platform that collects, combines and merges the project’s LLMs and approaches. Based upon ELOQUENCE’s findings and innovations, the interactive playground will introduce a unified ecosystem for users to access and utilize.” Pilot 3 is the ELOQUENCE Interactive Playground which will be the platform for testing, demonstrating and using other ELOQUENCE outputs, including the other pilots. Further, a quote from section 2.3.6 is also useful:

“The interactive playground will fulfil two important functions. First, it will act as a testing environment for the technologies developed throughout the project. Second, it will serve as a bridge between the project and its various users, including both researchers involved in the project and the ultimate actual end-users. As a result, since the interactive playground is not a standalone feature/technology but instead is tightly connected with the rest of the project WPs and outcomes (mainly WP1-5), the plan is to participate in the majority of stakeholder engagement activities organized by each respective partner including technical presentations, workshops, industry meetups and user feedback sessions. It is important to note that based on the flowing feedback from these activities we aim to remain flexible and responsive to any changes in the engagement strategy as determined by the project consortium.”

It would make the task of the assessment panel members easier if Omilia could explain the relationship between the ELOQUENCE Interactive Playground (which entails an interface between humans and machines) and the concept of API (Application Programming Interface) calls that, as far as I understand, are about communication within information systems, without a human participant.

KP: As I understand it, the purpose of Pilot 3 is to develop and train a sophisticated and adaptable virtual agent using a diverse array of enterprise-specific conversational datasets, which can generalize its

knowledge and skills to new enterprises without the need for additional fine-tuning (per D5.1, section 2.3.1). The datasets encompass a wide range of industries, including complex financial institutions, insurance companies and essential utility providers. It seems that the objective is for the IP to be generalised beyond the above-noted applications, to include non-critical healthcare and public services (see D5.1, section 2.3.7).

SA: What I can add is a clarification as to the relationship between the Interactive Playground (IP) and API calls, ensuring that the distinction between human-machine interaction and system-to-system communication is clearly explained. More specifically, it would be useful to clarify whether the ELOQUENCE Interactive Playground (IP) will provide direct human interaction with LLMs in all cases or whether some functionalities will rely primarily on API calls for system-to-system communication. If the latter is the case, will there be different levels of access, where some users (for example, researchers, developers) engage with the system via APIs while others, such as end-users in customer service roles, interact through the playground's interface? Finally, how will API-based interactions be monitored to ensure consistency with the human-facing components of the system?

1.5 What kinds of unauthorized use (mission creep) would the object be at risk of?

[please fill in here]

Assessors:

MS: More than unauthorized use as an unwanted form of mission flexibility, one could think that Pilot 3 could constitute the foundation for the development of a positively flexible interface for accessing an LLM (ELOQUENCE-developed LLMs. In principle it could be pretty much anything, with or without RAG, for general or specific purposes in much the same way as Le Chat is a way to access the Mistral models or ChatGPT is a way to access the GPT-models. For privacy-concerned users, and for the growing segment of users concerned about using models housed in the US or China, the policies and settings of these applications is just as relevant as the alignment of the models themselves, as many users are increasingly concerned about the data collected by applications such as ChatGPT.

KP: I agree with MS that Pilot 3 seems primed to be the foundation for the development of flexible interface for accessing and retrieving information in LLMs. I would highlight two potential unauthorised uses. First, as noted above in my comment under section 1.1, I have some concerns about possible unauthorized uses if the IP is based on financial, insurance and utility data and is then generalised into customer service, public services and healthcare settings. Particularly in the healthcare setting, concerns arise about the privacy and protection of personal health information, bias and discrimination issues, and the accuracy and context-appropriateness of the information provided. Second, the description of the pilot in D5.1 notes that 'steps are taken to perceive and respond to the user's emotional state throughout the interaction'. More information on what these steps are – in particular, how the user's emotional state is "perceived" and "responded to" -- would be useful to ensure that they comply with EU values and human rights (e.g. freedom of thought).

MP: I agree with the previous comments. As mentioned in my comments for section 1.1 and 1.3 there are several potential risks regarding the misuse of the models, the misleading of the users, abuse/disclose of privacy of personal information or the feedback loop effect. Referring to the AI Act, most of these risks can be lowered down by defining and limiting its final application, offering metrics to measure its risk and detailed documentation. If the goal is to open-source the outcome of this pilot, it should be protected with licenses that avoid any unauthorized use.

SA: I agree with the concerns raised about potential mission creep, particularly regarding the expansion of the Interactive Playground (IP) into sensitive domains, such as healthcare and public services. Given the ability of the system to perceive and respond to users' emotional states, further clarification would be helpful on how safeguards are implemented to ensure compliance with fundamental rights, particularly regarding privacy and freedom of thought. Additionally, if there are plans to make certain aspects of the system open source, it would be useful to understand what licensing mechanisms will be employed to prevent misuse while still allowing responsible and ethical innovation.

1.6 What will be its benefits for developers, deployers, and end-users?

[please fill in here]

Assessors:

MS: Potential benefits to users of this pilot include access to multi-lingual LLMs, potentially with a RAG model that would aid the retrieval of information from sources in a different language than the one applied by the user. Moreover, depending on the details once the pilot is set up, it could represent a benefit to privacy-concerned users hoping to access LLMs without having their personal information or prompts stored.

KP: The potential benefits of Pilot 3 to deployers and end-users are significant in light of its adaptability and application across industries. Moreover, its multilingual capabilities would ensure broad appeal.

MP: The most attractive benefit, besides a multi-lingual LLM, is the playground and test environment that could result useful to speed up development and having a controlled environment for experimentation.

1.7 Any other comments?

[please fill in here]

Assessors:

MS: The name of the pilot expresses an expectation that the virtual agent could be responding, presumably to humans, with empathy. This is the only reference to empathy in the submission, entailing that the issue is not elaborated in this round of WP6 assessment. However, D5.1 includes several references to empathy, showing that this is an important expected feature of the product. It is, however, doubtful whether empathy can be a feature of AI, at least in the foreseeable future (which is, admittedly, short). A cautious approach would be to expect that the product developed in Pilot 3 would be able to **emulate** human empathy, i.e., to produce responses that a human user **experiences** as empathetic. This feature may be worth pursuing but it should also be kept in mind that there is a risk that some users may experience such emulated responses as **fake** expressions of empathy – for instance because of the specific context but also simply because of knowing that they are dealing with AI. Hence, the option of intentionally **avoiding** expressions that emulate human empathy might also be worth consideration.

KP: A related concern to MS' comments about 'empathy', above, is how such empathetic responses are triggered. Put differently, as indicated in my comment under section 1.6, the D5.1 references that steps will be taken to 'perceive and respond to the user's emotional state' -- giving rise to potential human rights concerns (e.g. freedom of thought if the individual's emotional state is being monitored or otherwise intruded upon in some way) and potential bias/discrimination issues (if the IP makes certain assumptions or responds in a particular way as a result of its training).

2 Q2: Explainability and interpretability

All GenAI applications are required to let users know that they are interacting with an AI, but transparency requirements go beyond that. The submitting partner should include information on what has been done to facilitate **Explainable Artificial Intelligence (XAI)**, while other assessors are tasked with determining to what extent it is clear for users that they are interacting with an AI, how it works and what kinds of information it gathers about them, including whether they are being profiled/categorised in any way. The question is important because when AIs are not fully explainable and interpretable, their use can dramatically reduce consumers' ability to interact and gauge whether they are subject to discrimination or nudged in any particular direction

Guiding questions:

Does the object let the users know that they are interacting with an AI?

What has been done to facilitate Explainable Artificial Intelligence (XAI)?

Is there a summary of copyrighted data used for training (or otherwise)?

Will it be clear for users how the system works?

Does the object profile end-users or otherwise make them subject to decisions based on information gathered about them, thus activating their (non-binding) 'right to an explanation' under Recital 71 GDPR?

2.1 What has been done to facilitate Explainable Artificial Intelligence (XAI)?

[Omilia] Explainability will be studied and investigated in WP3. Work on this (research) direction work has begun at the beginning of 2025 Nevertheless, when available, results and outcomes will be utilized accordingly by pilot 3. WP3 aims to investigate, engineer, assess, and synthesize innovative hybrid AI methodologies, specifically neuro-symbolic AI, in conjunction with self-supervised learning algorithms. The objective is to develop context-sensitive conversational dialogue systems capable of engaging in coherent, fluent, and semantically meaningful interactions with users. The application of neuro-symbolic AI techniques will facilitate the development of novel strategies to enhance the explainability and coherence of the responses generated by the dialogue system. This approach will enable both the human-in-the-loop and the end-users to comprehend the underlying decision-making processes of the model. The resulting models will facilitate the seamless integration of human knowledge, encompassing both domain-specific and open-domain information, with deep learning techniques. This integration will be achieved through a scalable exploration-exploitation strategy, ultimately leading to explainable decision-making within the framework of dialogue systems.

Assessors:

MS: What kind of human-in-the-loop mechanisms are envisaged and at what stage?

KP: In addition to providing more information about the 'human-in-the-loop', it would be helpful for Omilia to provide a more detailed explanation of 'neuro-symbolic AI techniques'. In addition, given the wide-ranging domains in which the virtual agent will be employed, how will the context-sensitivity, coherence, fluency and semantic meaningfulness of the interactions be judged?

MP: Since this is an ongoing process to be evaluated. I agree with previous comments, but I understand that Omilia just offered a basic description of what will be done.

2.2 *Is there a summary of copyrighted data used for training (or otherwise)?*

[Omilia] The pilot will not provide a summary of (copyrighted) data for training. Such summaries of copyrighted training data will be compiled by the partners developing the project's LLMs.

Assessors:

MS: If the Pilot is to be further developed into a commercial application for RAG or for otherwise accessing an LLM, and depending on the exact use of the application, it may need to provide such information to comply with EU law.

MP: Agreed, it is better to clarify or link the LLMs documentation at least. But final documentation will be needed that summarizes the whole system. See Chapter V, Section 2 and Recital 107 of the AI Act.

SA: I agree that providing documentation on copyrighted training data may be necessary, especially if the pilot evolves into a commercial application. Under the AI Act, ensuring transparency regarding training data sources is crucial for legal compliance and to mitigate potential intellectual property risks. A clear reference to the LLMs' documentation would enhance regulatory clarity and accountability.

2.3 *Does the object profile end-users or otherwise make them subject to decisions based on information gathered about them, thus activating their (non-binding) 'right to an explanation' under Recital 71 GDPR?*

[Omilia] To the best of our knowledge, the answer to this is negative.

Assessors:

MS: It appears that the IP on its own will not profile users.

KP: I reiterate my concerns about the steps that will be taken to perceive and respond to users' emotion states throughout the interaction.

MP: It is unclear to me if it will not. Since the uses of the system can be diverse. For example, if a public service agent is used to provide information about a service and the agent asks personal or specific questions to the user to provide different types of answers, it could be argued that some profiling is being made. Even if not on purpose, it should be considered to run causal based tests to prevent such kind of answers. As KP points out, also emotion states or personalities could affect the interaction. It is unlikely that this will affect model output, but it is better to have mechanisms to ensure compliance.

SA: I agree that, while the system may not be designed to profile users, its diverse applications could unintentionally lead to profiling-like effects, particularly if responses are tailored based on perceived emotions or personal input. Given the GDPR's broad interpretation of profiling, it would be advisable to assess whether any implicit profiling occurs and, if so, ensure transparency and safeguards to uphold users' rights under Recital 71.

2.4 *Does the object let the users know that they are interacting with an AI?*

[please fill in here]

Assessors:

MS: The object should include an initial message to users, stating that they are interacting with an AI, along with any other information they might need, such as to what extent their data is collected and warnings of hallucinations and similar. The application to access an LLM (or the IP) is the right place for such messages to appear.

KP: Agree. Such a warning is particularly crucial if the virtual agent is used in healthcare or public service settings.

MP: I would also include mechanisms to inform the users of the accuracy of their answers. Usually LLM-based agents fail to acknowledge when they cannot find the right answer, turning into hallucinations, misleading behavior, generate fake citations or using unverifiable sources. These should be clearly explicit, or a warning of non-categorical answers must be given.

SA: I fully agree that users should be explicitly informed that they are interacting with an AI, particularly in sensitive domains, such as healthcare and public services. This aligns with transparency requirements under the AI Act and broader consumer protection principles. Additionally, mechanisms should be in place to warn users about the potential for incorrect or unverifiable information, ensuring they can make informed decisions based on AI-generated responses.

2.5 Is it clear for users how the system works?

[please fill in here]

Assessors:

MS: Again, depending on the exact use of the application, an initial message should include warnings of hallucinations and similar, to let users know how it works and what the best uses and most problematic uses are.

2.6 Any other comments?

[please fill in here]

Assessors:

3 Q3: Robustness, reliability and trustworthiness

Robustness, reliability and trustworthiness go to the very core of what the purpose of the object is and whether it is able to reliably fulfil it. An important factor here is the question of hallucinations which plagued early GenAI in particular. The question relates to what extent the object fulfils its function and produce useful and truthful content. Assessors here are invited to consider in particular the intended function of the object.

Guiding questions:

Can the object be convinced/hacked to produce illegal or otherwise troubling content (Adversarial testing)?

Does the object hallucinate?

To what extent does the object fulfil its function and produce useful and truthful content?

Can the object be convinced/hacked to produce illegal or otherwise troubling content

3.1 *Can the object be convinced/hacked to produce illegal or otherwise troubling content ([Adversarial testing](#))?*

[please fill in here]

Assessors:

MS: While it appears that the pilot on its own cannot produce content, the question is relevant in another respect. It may be important for the EU values compatibility assessment if it can include filters to protect against harmful content in its orchestration layer, as part of the task of sanitation. What is envisaged in this regard?

KP: As noted above, the ‘pre-processing’ stage references sanitizing, formatting and contextualizing the inputs. It is not clear to me that the sanitization or validation components also apply to the outputs. Will the LLM’s outputs be assessed for such variables (e.g. accuracy, absence of harmful elements, etc)? What is envisaged to ensure that the virtual agent cannot be ‘convinced’ or manipulated/exploited to produce troubling content? Additionally, what steps will be taken if the pilot is expanded/generalized into the fields specified in D5.1, such as non-critical healthcare and public services, to ensure that (i) it is trained on appropriate and context-relevant datasets to avoid adverse outcomes; and (ii) provides appropriate, accurate and rights-compliant outputs in these sectors – that is, avoids hallucinations and other troubling content?

SA: I agree that ensuring the system cannot be manipulated into generating harmful or illegal content is critical, particularly if the pilot is expanded into sensitive domains. Under the AI Act, deployers of AI systems may bear responsibility for inadequate safeguards. It would be useful to clarify what adversarial testing measures will be implemented and whether there are fail-safe mechanisms to prevent the system from being exploited to produce misleading, harmful, or unlawful content.

3.2 *Does the object [hallucinate](#)?*

[please fill in here]

Assessors:

MS: Similarly, while the pilot itself does not hallucinate, it could secure EU values compatibility by including filters to aid in hallucination prevention as part of the validation step at the orchestration layer. Moreover, the mere inclusion of a RAG modality as the pilot represents is an aid in preventing hallucinations as it grounds generated content in (presumably vetted and validated) information.

SA: Fully agree.

3.3 To what extent does the object fulfil its function and produce useful and truthful content?

[please fill in here]

Assessors:

MS: See comments under 3.1 and 3.2.

3.4 Any other comments?

[please fill in here]

Assessors:

MP: Is impossible to assess without factual information about the systems.

4 Q4: Bias

This question is related to bias in a cultural or legal sense, both in the training of the object and in the content it produces. This refers to the fact that there may be situations in which a GenAI produces content that is representative of the material it has been trained on, which in turn is representative of conceptualisations and assumptions in the culture that has produced that material. Often this means leaning towards the western, the able-bodied, and the male, but there have also been [examples](#) where training material has been skewed in a different way.

Guiding questions:

What measures were taken to identify potential biases (implicit, sampling, temporal or otherwise) in the training data or data otherwise relied upon?

What known biases are there in the training data or other sources of information relied upon by the object?

What has been done to mitigate these biases?

Does the product produce biased content, e.g. on account of sex, gender, sexual orientation, gender identity, ethnicity, national origin, language, disability or political opinion?

How does the product address situations where society is biased?

4.1 What measures were taken to identify potential biases (implicit, sampling, temporal or otherwise) in the training data or data otherwise relied upon?

[Omilia] Bias will be specifically addressed in WP4. Respective work on this begun at the beginning of 2025. More specifically, WP4 aims to develop advanced spoken language understanding representations by integrating fine-tuned models for specific speech tasks, focusing on enhancing performance in low-resource scenarios. The conducted study will investigate optimal language combinations for data efficiency and create a multilingual spoken language understanding system capable of handling diverse linguistic phenomena. Work/Research will also explore knowledge transfer methods for simplified language adaptation and ensure ethical, bias-controlled speech processing through established guidelines and benchmarks. Explicitly it is mentioned that the anticipated outcomes will include ethically compliant and bias-controlled speech processing methods. These will be coupled with a consistent benchmark to assess the performance, ethical compliance and bias-control aspects of the developed spoken language understanding system.

Assessors:

MS: It appears that commenting on bias will be possible in a subsequent iteration, as more specific information emerges or if other assessors have ideas. I don't have any other comments in section 4 yet.

KP: It seems to be too early to provide feedback on this section. It would be useful for Omilia to provide more information about whether and to what extent this testing and preparatory work will be undertaken across languages/cultures. I would also reiterate my concerns about the steps being taken to perceive and respond to users' emotional states, how this will be done in a manner that is rights-

compliant and identifies/responds to potential biases, and how such information will be collected, used and retained.

SA: I believe it is too early to be able to provide any constructive feedback at this stage.

MP: Agree with comments above. Even if it is developed by other WPs, this section (as well as section 3) should be considered by the pilot final implementation.

4.2 What known biases are there in the training data or other sources of information relied upon by the object?

[Omilia] Answers on this will be obtained only after a substantial part of the tasks in WP2 and WP4 reach finalization/completion.

Assessors:

4.3 What has been done to mitigate these biases?

[Omilia] Currently, nothing specific can be reported. Discussions during the respective work package meetings are ongoing.

Assessors:

4.4 Does the product produce biased content, e.g. on account of sex, gender, sexual orientation, gender identity, ethnicity, national origin, language, disability or political opinion?

[please fill in here]

Assessors:

4.5 How does the product address situations where society is biased?

[please fill in here]

Assessors:

4.6 Any other comments?

[please fill in here]

Assessors:

5 Q5: Discrimination

This question relates to the production of discriminatory and offensive content. Here a particular challenge is posed by context-specific offensiveness and the difference between internal or in-group language and external or out-group speech. There may be situations where the object is requested by a user to reproduce content that is not offensive in-group but is offensive outgroup (an example could be song-lyrics or satire). In such cases consistently refusing to produce such content because of requested content being offensive in an outgroup context, could constitute a type of censoring or close off cultural content for some users in a problematic way. Conversely, content that is not offensive from the perspective of the dominant population may nevertheless be offensive when appearing to be coming from the dominant culture towards users belonging to a specific minority.

There may also be situations where the object is requested to reproduce content that is culturally problematic regardless of group belonging, but where the content nevertheless forms an important part of a cultural discussion – an example could be if it were asked to reproduce summaries of nazi propaganda or arguments against fundamental rights. Both types of situations might be resolvable by the product adding context and additional explanations or warnings to users to its responses.

Guiding questions:

Can the object be convinced to produce illegal or discriminatory content?

How does the object address situations where content is offensive out-group but not in-group?

How does the object address situations where it is requested to reproduce or summarise

5.1 Does the object conduct biometric categorization or social scoring, and if so, for what purpose?

[Omilia] Not in any sense.

Assessors:

MS: noted.

KP: As above: the D5.1 references steps to perceive/respond to the user's emotional state, and generalizations to the field of e.g. non-critical healthcare. But it does not appear that biometric categorization or social scoring is undertaken.

MP: Not on purpose, but it should be tested to ensure the system does not provide different outputs regarding user's ethnicity, gender, religion, other beliefs or social class.

5.2 Can the object be convinced to produce illegal or discriminatory content?

[please fill in here]

Assessors:

MS: This aspect will remain to be tested once the system is operative. At this stage, however, as mentioned in section 3.1 it is relevant to include filters to prevent LLMs from producing discriminatory, illegal or otherwise troubling content. They can be added to the orchestration layer as part of the sanitation step in a RAG system. Moreover, the orchestration layer would also be the place to add input

sanitation which would check for attempts at getting the system to produce problematic content. Does the submitting partner have any ideas yet as to the tools that would be implemented in this regard?

KP: as above (see response to section 3.1).

MP: I agree with MS, but it should be also tested on its outcome. Also, tests should be sector specific since it is well known that, for example, healthcare data is usually gender biased.

5.3 How does the object address situations where content is offensive out-group but not in-group?

[please fill in here]

Assessors:

MS: This problem might also be addressed as an aspect of input sanitation, although the in-group/out-group question is a problematic one here, as a user could pretend to be anyone when interacting with a chatbot. I have no additional comments in section 5 yet.

5.4 How does the object address situations where it is requested to reproduce or summarise factually, ethically or legally problematic content?

[please fill in here]

Assessors:

5.5 Any other comments?

[please fill in here]

Assessors:

6 Q6: Multilinguality and cross-cultural knowledge

An important feature of the ELOQUENCE project and other projects launched under the same call is the attention to low-resource languages and cross-cultural knowledge. The submitting partner is invited to disclose what languages the AI currently supports and which it is envisioned to incorporate next, and the other assessors are invited to test the AI in as many languages as possible – particularly low resource languages. In this regard, due to the abundance of English-language training data and pre-developed models nearly all languages are low-resource compared to English. Societally this represents a serious problem as may create inequalities between those that have access to high quality AI in their working languages, and those who do not. Assessors are invited to investigate whether the product is more likely to hallucinate or produce illegal, discriminatory or otherwise troubling content depending on the languages used to interact with the object. Where relevant it may also be prudent to investigate how the product takes into account different usages of words or expressions and different cultural contexts by different communities that speak the same language.

Guiding questions:

Which languages are supported or envisaged?

Which low-resource languages are included?

Is the product more likely to produce illegal, discriminatory or otherwise troubling content when using low-resource languages?

Quality control and robustness: are the results the same when asking the same question in different languages, and should they be?

How does the product take into account different usages of words or expressions and different cultural contexts by different communities that speak the same language?

6.1 Which languages are supported or envisaged?

[Omilia] Following the current consensus between the project partners the aim is to work on 2-3 European resource-rich languages as well as one 1 low-resource languages. Down the line details remain to be examined and decided.

Assessors:

6.2 Which low-resource languages are included?

[Omilia] Serbian and Greek have been mentioned as potential low-resource languages for the project but as mentioned previously no final decision has been reached.

Assessors:

KP: One potential concern is whether these low-resource languages will be subjected to the same rigorous testing and oversight to ensure that the virtual agent provides accurate, non-harmful and contextually appropriate responses?

6.3 Is the product more likely to produce illegal, discriminatory or otherwise troubling content when using low-resource languages?

[please fill in here]

Assessors:

KP: More information would be required to provide feedback in this section.

6.4 Quality control and robustness: are the results the same when asking the same question in different languages, and should they be?

[please fill in here]

Assessors:

6.5 How does the product take into account different usages of words or expressions and different cultural contexts by different communities that speak the same language?

[please fill in here]

Assessors:

6.6 Any other comments?

[please fill in here]

Assessors:

7 Q7: Privacy and the protection of personal data

Privacy and protection of personal data raises several different concerns. At the same time these concerns will have to be balanced with potential functional gains from the learning the object does when in use by end-users.

We are concerned both with how personal data is used by developers and deployers, but also how it might be shared between several different end-users. There are a number of ways this might happen. For example, in a smart-home environment, we might imagine that different members of the same household interact with the same AI object. Concerns may therefore be related to how information collected about these members is shared not only with developers and 3rd parties – such as for advertising – but also within the household between members. Another concern is function- or mission creep where applications created for one purpose are used for another, to the detriment of fundamental rights protection. It may well happen that a smart-home application could be used also in a club or in a school without necessarily being reconfigured for that space.

Guiding questions:

What kind of data (including sensitive personal data such as data that can be used to identify a person and data revealing their racial or ethnic origin, political opinions, religious or philosophical beliefs, sexuality, health-related data, trade-union membership, or their emotions) is collected from end-users?

Are end-users informed of what data might be collected and with whom it may be shared?

Is consent obtained for data collection?

Can end-users request for data to be erased or corrected?

What data and models are shared back to the developers or third parties such as potential advertisers?

What data and models might be shared between end-users of the same product [in a smart-home environment for example, will different members of the same household be able access information about each other?]

Is there collateral effect upon non-users, such as visitors whose presence (location data), other data, or voice may be captured by the product?

What would be the eventual consequences of not collecting information about the user for onsite training?

Function creep: Can you envisage the product being used for purposes other than what it is intended for, with adverse privacy consequences?

7.1 What kind of data is collected from end-users?

7.1.1 Directly by requesting information

[Omilia] Strictly data needed for the call itself or for API invocations will be used. These will be kept at a minimum and they will not be further stored-collected. Upon completion of the communication, they will be automatically purged.

Assessors:

KP: Will this immediate and automatic purge pose challenges for monitoring and oversight, as well as feedback (e.g. to ensure that the virtual agent provided accurate, unbiased and contextually appropriate responses)?

MP: How will personal data be identified to be discriminated from other types of data? How will sensitive data be managed in case of being stored for evaluation?

SA: While minimising data retention is important for privacy compliance, the immediate and automatic purge raises questions about how system performance will be monitored, particularly in detecting biases or inaccuracies over time. Will there be a mechanism for anonymised logging or aggregated data analysis to ensure compliance with accuracy and fairness standards? Additionally, as MP noted, further clarification on how personal data is identified and distinguished from other types of data would be useful, particularly regarding sensitive data management in case retention is required for evaluation or regulatory purposes.

7.1.2 Through use of the object

[Omilia] Essentially, the only data-information that will be collected is that tightly related to measuring and evaluating the quality of the calls and the retrieval mechanisms. This also includes the data necessary for monitoring the respective Key Performance Indicators (KPIs). The findings and contributions derived from pilot study 3 -whether in the context of the more narrowly defined customer service domain or within the broader spectrum of application scenarios across all pilots- will undergo a two-phase evaluation protocol. In Phase I, baseline performance metrics will be established using unmodified, pre-trained LLMs. Phase II will involve the evaluation of the developed/implemented LLM methodologies. Comparative analysis between these phases will be conducted to quantify relative performance differentials. The quantitative benchmarks for performance will be the following:

- First Call Resolution (FCR) \uparrow 20% increase
- Call Containment Rate (CCR) \uparrow 20% increase

FCR measures the percentage of customer calls or inquiries that are fully resolved during the initial contact, without the need for follow-up interactions or escalations. It's calculated as follows:

$$FCR = \left(\frac{\text{Number of calls resolved on first contact}}{\text{Total number of calls}} \right) * 100$$

To calculate this for a given day: (a) count the total number of calls received that day, (b) determine how many of those calls were completely resolved during the initial interaction.

CCR refers to the percentage of calls that are successfully resolved or "contained" within an automated system without requiring intervention from a human agent. It is calculated in the following way:

$$CCR = \left(\frac{\text{Number of calls resolved through automated systems}}{\text{Total number of calls received}} \right) * 100$$

To calculate this for a given day: (a) count the total number of calls received that day, (b) determine how many of those calls were fully resolved by the automated system.

Consequently, it becomes apparent that even for measuring/estimating the efficacy of the pilot study the number of calls resolved, and the total number of received call is sufficient; both of which do not fall into the category of sensitive personal information.

Assessors:

MS: At this stage of TRL where the object is intended to be used only inside the ELOQUENCE project, personal data collection is not really a concern. Should the object be developed further into a general application for accessing LLMs as discussed above, the limitation of personal data collection on the part of the application could be a competitive advantage for privacy-concerned users.

7.1.3 Through inferences?

[Omilia] Inferring or equivalently deriving sensitive personal data and information during pilot study 3 is beyond its scope and is not related to its objectives. This coupled with the strategy described in 7.1.2 means that personal information will not be collected-directly or indirectly- throughout pilot 3.

Assessors:

7.1.4 Other ways?

7.2 *Does the object conduct emotion recognition? And if so for what purpose?*

[Omilia] No, for instance in the project description it is explicitly mentioned that: "... eliminating the need of explicitly defining emotion recognition units and corresponding responses."

Assessors:

KP: I think a clearer explanation would be beneficial – see my comments above. The D5.1 notes, in section 3.3.3, that one of the specifications and requirements that must be met for the pilot's outcome to be considered a success is, "Perceiving the caller's emotional state and adapting responses, accordingly, eliminating the need for explicit definition of emotion recognition units and corresponding reaction patters." Can Omilia clarify and explain this answer (does it only apply within the ELOQUENCE project, but not beyond it?).

SA: Further clarification would be beneficial regarding whether the system engages in implicit emotion recognition, even if it does not rely on explicitly defined emotion recognition units. If responses are adapted based on a user's perceived emotional state, it may still raise concerns under the AI Act and GDPR, particularly regarding transparency and the potential for undue influence on users. It would be useful to specify whether any safeguards are in place to prevent risks such as manipulation or unintended profiling based on inferred emotions.

7.3 *What data and models are shared back to the developers or third parties such as potential advertisers?*

[Omilia] Currently there are no plans for this type of data/information sharing.

Assessors:

MS: See 7.1.2

7.4 What data and models might be shared between end-users of the same product [in a smart-home environment for example, will different members of the same household be able access information about each other?]

[Omilia] No sharing of information between end-users will be permitted and actually it won't be needed.

Assessors:

MP: it should be proven that adversarial attacks won't provoke data disclosure. It is known that specific LLMs can be manipulated.

7.5 Is there collateral effect upon non-users, such as visitors whose presence (location data), other data, or voice may be captured by the product?

[Omilia] No such data can nor will be captured.

Assessors:

7.6 What would be the eventual consequences of not collecting information about the user for onsite training?

[Omilia] As already mentioned no onsite training or any other type of tuning/adjusting will be taken during the development or testing of the pilot.

Assessors:

7.7 Are end-users informed of what data might be collected and with whom it may be shared?

[please fill in here]

Assessors:

MS: Users should be informed if data is collected already at the current TRL, if others than project partner participants (in their capacity of authors) are recruited as test-users. This of course becomes unconditional if the object is developed further into a commercial product. This comment also applies under 7.8 and 7.9.

KP: Users should also be advised of how their data will be retained and destroyed.

SA: Fully agree with MS and KP on this point

7.8 Is consent obtained for data collection?

[please fill in here]

7.9 Can end-users request for data to be erased or corrected?

[please fill in here]

7.10 Function creep: Can you envisage the product being used for purposes other than what it is intended for, with adverse privacy consequences?

[please fill in here]

7.11 Any other comments?

[please fill in here]

8 Q8: Security and Safety

This question addresses a wide range of risks related to AIs in general. In terms of definitions, safety is associated with accidental risk, and security with malicious intent. Reports and White Papers from the European Commission have developed several different taxonomies of potential harms caused by AIs. For example, the AI White Paper from 2020 groups risks into two categories – Risk of Material damage: safety and health of individuals (including loss of life) or damage to property, and risk of Immaterial damage: loss of privacy, limitations to the right of freedom of expression, human dignity, discrimination.¹ GenAI is most directly likely to cause immaterial damage. Other categories could be risks posed to society, such as mass unemployment, mass surveillance, automated weapons systems lowering the bar to genocide, threats to democracy due to filter bubbles and resulting damage to the democratic deliberation; versus risks posed to individuals: personal data leaks, personal unemployment, imprisonment or discrimination based on biased and opaque algorithms. Certain risks can occur with or without malicious intent such as data poisoning,

An example of data poisoning is Microsoft Tay, a chatbot supposed to interact with young people on social media that was flooded with offensive and racist tweets in 2016 ... Data poisoning can affect a vast array of datasets, such as healthcare data, loan or house pricing.¹

Another problem is that of data or model drift, the tendency for AIs to degenerate over time. Meanwhile, security concerns can emerge from hacking attempts, attempts to cause data breach, or the intentional installation of backdoors. In both cases risks can be mitigated through proper data management and model review throughout the life cycle of the product. In this part of the template both the submitting partner and the other assessors are invited to creatively imagine scenarios in which the object reviewed could result in material or immaterial harms because of safety or security issues. Malicious security concerns could emerge either from a malicious deployer misusing the product for purposes other than what it was designed for, from external attempts at hacking, from users using the product for ill, or from developers intentionally installing backdoors or otherwise compromising the safety of the object. Assessors should not refrain from considering any of these, and assessors should be free to

8.1 *What strategies have been employed to render the object resilient to risks emerging from bad actors?*

[Omilia] A first line of defense will be formed by the developed fine-tuned LLMs (WP2). Techniques like guardrails and firewalls are options that could ramp up the resilience of the models against a comprehensive range of risks. The second line of defense will be put forward by pilot 3 via proactively checking and reviewing the structured and semi-structured documents pertaining to each enterprise served in each case scenario under consideration. Pre-checking the contents of these documents directly leads to retrieved verified chunks and propositions (and resulting LLM responses) that will minimize risk and immaterial damages.

Assessors:

MS: At this stage, I have no comment on 8.1, 8.2 or 8.3. These issues should be reviewed at a later stage when we are further ahead with the development and implementation of these solutions.

SA: While the proposed multi-layered defence strategy is a strong starting point, further details on how these safeguards will be tested and validated would be useful. Given the potential regulatory implications under the AI Act, will there be periodic security audits or adversarial testing to ensure resilience against evolving threats? Additionally, if the system is deployed across multiple industries, how will sector-specific compliance and security requirements be addressed to prevent vulnerabilities in high-risk domains?

8.2 *What measures have been included to render the object resilient to risks posed by accidents, natural disasters and other safety concerns?*

[Omilia] Not applicable.

8.3 *What material harm can you imagine this object could result in or contribute to?*

[please fill in here]

Assessors:

8.4 *What immaterial harm can you imagine this object could result in or contribute to?*

[please fill in here]

Assessors:

MS: As to immaterial harm, one could already imagine personal information extraction attacks carried out to access data gathered by an application such as the IP.

8.5 *Are there any ways that you can imagine someone with malicious intent misusing the object to inflict material or immaterial harm?*

[please fill in here]

Assessors:

8.6 *Any other comments?*

[please fill in here]

Assessors:

9 Q9: Other Rights, user experience and other concerns

What other rights might the object interfere with? Examples include: freedom of expression, intellectual property rights, personal freedom, freedom of information.

In this section you can also add any general comments regarding user experience including what it is like interacting with the object – is it rude or polite? Does it appear empathic or detached? Is it easy to get an indication of what it can do and what it should not be used for? Did you find yourself interacting with it in a different way than you would with a person? Is it unnerving to interact with it, and if so, why?

Guiding questions:

What is it like to interact with the object?

What other rights might the product interfere with?

Any other concerns?

9.1 What is it like to interact with the object (user experience)?

[please fill in here]

9.2 What other rights might the product interfere with?

[please fill in here]

9.3 Any other concerns?

[please fill in here]

MS: In respect of Section 10 below, it appears that Pilot 3 is not a general-purpose AI in the meaning of the EU AI Act.

10 Q10: EU AI ACT compatibility

This checklist is intended to be carried out by the submitting partner only.

10.1 General purpose AI

	Yes	No
Does it have a wide range of possible uses (intended or unintended)?	+	
Is it a foundation model (pre-trained model for other more specialised models)?		+ (but it uses such models)
Is it a Large Language Model (LLM)?		+ (but it uses such models)
Does it handle more than one type of input?	+	

10.1.1 If yes to any of the above:

	Yes	No
Was it trained using a total computing power of more than 10^{25} FLOPs?	?	
Does it provide a summary of copyrighted data used in training?	?	
Does it disclose information downstream for the purposes of transparency?	+	

10.2 Unacceptable Risk

	Yes	No
Does it conduct social scoring?		+
Does it exploit vulnerability of persons or otherwise manipulate?		+
Does it engage in Biometric categorisation of natural persons based on biometric data to deduce or infer their race, political opinions, trade union membership, religious or philosophical beliefs or sexual orientation?		+
Does it engage in emotion recognition?		+
Does it make use of or enable untargeted scraping?		+

<i>10.3 High risk</i>	Yes	No
Does it evaluate and classify emergency calls by natural persons or is it intended to be used to dispatch, or to establish priority in the dispatching of emergency first response services, including by police, firefighters and medical aid, as well as of emergency healthcare patient triage systems;		+
Does it pose a significant risk of harm to the health, safety or fundamental rights of natural persons?		+
Is the object intended to be used together with heavy machinery, toys, land- or watercrafts, explosives, radio equipment, pressure equipment, personal protective equipment, appliances burning gaseous fuels, medical equipment, civil aviation, agricultural vehicles, marine equipment or rail systems?		+

10.3.1 If yes to any of the above

	Yes	No
Has there been established a risk management system for the life cycle of the product?		
Data governance: Has it been ensured that training, validation and testing datasets are relevant, sufficiently representative and, to the best extent possible, free of errors and complete according to the intended purpose.		
Is there technical documentation to demonstrate compliance and provide authorities with the information to assess that compliance?		
Is the system designed for record-keeping to enable it to automatically record events relevant for identifying national level risks and substantial modifications throughout the system's lifecycle?		
Can you provide instructions for use to downstream deployers to enable the latter's compliance?		
Has the system been designed to allow deployers to implement human oversight?		
Is it designed to achieve appropriate levels of accuracy, robustness, and cybersecurity?		
Has a quality management system to ensure compliance been established?		

11 Q11: Conclusions

Given your answers to the questions above, please formulate a conclusion as to any concerns with the object as is, as it may develop or otherwise. Each person filling out the questionnaire should formulate their own conclusion, and the chair of the panel will then formulate a consensus conclusion which will be shared with other members of the panel before communicating to the submitting partner.

11.1 Submitting partner

[Omilia] Due to the premature (WP3 and WP4) status of a series of related tasks and the ongoing (but not finalized) status of necessary technologies and models (WP2) it is hard to provide final and definite answers to a number of issues, concerns and questions raised in the current document. Moreover, it is becoming gradually more apparent that the components, tasks and outcomes of the Eloquence project are intertwined in such a way that by seeking partial/isolated answers one might miss and underestimate a considerable part of the whole picture. Nevertheless, by taking into consideration the stage of the project and related research, responses have been provided at least for the pilot 3 specific issues. By re-examining these, the obvious conclusion becomes that pilot 3 does not introduce additional concerns or problematic areas that are/were not preexistent in the constituent technologies. If these are addressed appropriately during their development stage, then pilot 3 will be equally immune against the corresponding risks.

11.2 Assessor 2

SA: Given the early stage of the project, it is understandable that certain issues remain unresolved. However, from a legal perspective, it is crucial to ensure that transparency, accountability, and compliance measures are integrated from the outset rather than retrofitted later. The principle of solidarity in responsibility among project partners should be reinforced, particularly concerning potential high-risk applications in sectors such as finance, public services, and non-critical healthcare. Furthermore, clear governance mechanisms should be outlined to assess compliance with the AI Act, GDPR, and sector-specific regulations as the system evolves. Finally, as has been highlighted, establishing independent testing, evaluation protocols, and human oversight mechanisms early on would be beneficial in ensuring that the final system adheres to fundamental rights and ethical AI principles.

11.3 Assessor 3

MP: The project is at an early stage which makes it difficult to understand the impact of the proposed system. The submitting partner's answers are clarifying but should also consider the solidarity in the responsibility of the system's impact. My biggest concerns at this point are the transparency measures that should be designed before implementation. A plan for testing and evaluating the system should be developed in order to have a neutral evaluation. The human-in-the-loop and feedback is an important aspect that has not been addressed yet in the pilot and should be considered in the entire process to facilitate a successful implementation. Lastly, the potential misuse of the final system is high since, as advertised, it will be focusing on high-stake scenarios. I expect to have a follow-up with more information about the evolution of the project.

11.4 Assessor 4

KP: I raised a series of questions and concerns, above, about the object as is and as it may develop in light of its specified generalization capabilities. These concerns, generally, relate to how users' emotional states are to be perceived and responded to (and how this complies with EU values and human rights, such as freedom of thought and non-discrimination); whether and to what extent the datasets and training will be generalizable to the other sectors envisioned, namely non-critical healthcare and public services, and how the accuracy, context-appropriateness, and non-harmfulness of the outputs will be ensured and safeguarded in such settings; and whether the pilot will ensure that low-resource languages are assessed and evaluated evenly with the more dominant resource-rich languages. It seems too early to provide an overall conclusion, particularly without the benefit of Omilia's responses to these queries and concerns; but I hope that these points will be of use as the pilot is further developed.

11.5 Chair of the assessment panel

MS: For a synopsis of questions, comments and conclusions by panel members, see the Executive Summary on top of the document. Here, I am presenting my own conclusions. The question of 'sanitation' in the orchestration layer of the object, and the scope of such sanitation is a key issue in the further development of the object. Information as received in the submission was, due to the early phase of the development of the object, still insufficient for detailed assessment by the panel under most sections of the template. One main issue to flag, however, is whether the responses by the IP should even try to emulate human empathy, or whether transparency rather requires that the user is reminded of being in interaction with an AI application that does not empathise with the user.

Assessment of the compliance of ELOQUENCE outcomes with European values

Assessment of Pilot 4: Upgrading support call centres through AI-based supervision of multimodal dialogues

Assessment number [V02004]

Template document history

Version	Issue Date	Stage	Description	Contributor
V1	30.6.2024		First version of template	Helga Molbæk-Steensig(EUI) Martin Scheinin (EUI) Reviewed by Dusan Pavlovic (PN)
V2	15.7.2024		Second version of template following test-assessment. Main changes: 1. Change of text-box design to allow for longer answers 2. Clearly separating between (technical) answers by submitting partner and other answers 3. adjusting design of template to fit the visual identity of the ELOQUENCE project	Helga Molbæk-Steensig (EUI)

Table of Contents

EXECUTIVE SUMMARY OF THE ASSESSMENT	ERROR! BOOKMARK NOT DEFINED.	5
0 INTRODUCTION WP6 ASSESSMENT TEMPLATE (V.2)		45
1 Q1: WHAT IS THE OBJECT OF ASSESSMENT?		6
1.1 WHAT IS IT [AN ALGORITHM; SANDBOX, DEMO, ETC?]		6
1.2 WHICH VERSION IS IT, WHAT MODELS DOES IT APPLY?		87
1.3 WHAT DATA HAS IT BEEN TRAINED ON, IF ANY?		87
1.4 WHAT IS ITS PURPOSE?		9
1.5 WHAT KINDS OF UNAUTHORIZED USE (MISSION CREEP) WOULD THE OBJECT BE AT RISK OF?		109
1.6 WHAT WILL BE ITS BENEFITS FOR DEVELOPERS, DEPLOYERS, AND END-USERS?		119
1.7 ANY OTHER COMMENTS?		119
2 Q2: EXPLAINABILITY AND INTERPRETABILITY		1214
2.1 WHAT HAS BEEN DONE TO FACILITATE EXPLAINABLE ARTIFICIAL INTELLIGENCE (XAI)?		1214
2.2 IS THERE A SUMMARY OF COPYRIGHTED DATA USED FOR TRAINING (OR OTHERWISE)?		1214
2.3 DOES THE OBJECT PROFILE END-USERS OR OTHERWISE MAKE THEM SUBJECT TO DECISIONS BASED ON INFORMATION GATHERED ABOUT THEM, THUS ACTIVATING THEIR (NON-BINDING) 'RIGHT TO AN EXPLANATION' UNDER RECITAL 71 GDPR?		1314
2.4 DOES THE OBJECT LET THE USERS KNOW THAT THEY ARE INTERACTING WITH AN AI?		1311
2.5 WILL IT BE CLEAR FOR USERS HOW THE SYSTEM WORKS?		1311
2.6 ANY OTHER COMMENTS?		1411
3 Q3: ROBUSTNESS, RELIABILITY AND TRUSTWORTHINESS		1512
3.1 CAN THE OBJECT BE CONVINCED/HACKED TO PRODUCE ILLEGAL OR OTHERWISE TROUBLING CONTENT (ADVERSARIAL TESTING)?		1512
3.2 DOES THE OBJECT HALLUCINATE?		1612
3.3 TO WHAT EXTENT DOES THE OBJECT FULFIL ITS FUNCTION AND PRODUCE USEFUL AND TRUTHFUL CONTENT?		1612
3.4 ANY OTHER COMMENTS?		1713
4 Q4: BIAS		1814
4.1 WHAT MEASURES WERE TAKEN TO IDENTIFY POTENTIAL BIASES (IMPLICIT, SAMPLING, TEMPORAL OR OTHERWISE) IN THE TRAINING DATA OR DATA OTHERWISE RELIED UPON?		1814
4.2 WHAT KNOWN BIASES ARE THERE IN THE TRAINING DATA OR OTHER SOURCES OF INFORMATION RELIED UPON BY THE OBJECT?		1914
4.3 WHAT HAS BEEN DONE TO MITIGATE THESE BIASES?		1915
4.4 DOES THE PRODUCT PRODUCE BIASED CONTENT, E.G. ON ACCOUNT OF SEX, GENDER, SEXUAL ORIENTATION, GENDER IDENTITY, ETHNICITY, NATIONAL ORIGIN, LANGUAGE, DISABILITY OR POLITICAL OPINION?		1915
4.5 HOW DOES THE PRODUCT ADDRESS SITUATIONS WHERE SOCIETY IS BIASED?		2015
4.6 ANY OTHER COMMENTS?		2015
5 Q5: DISCRIMINATION		2116
5.1 DOES THE OBJECT CONDUCT BIOMETRIC CATEGORIZATION OR SOCIAL SCORING, AND IF SO, FOR WHAT PURPOSE?		2116
5.2 CAN THE OBJECT BE CONVINCED TO PRODUCE ILLEGAL OR DISCRIMINATORY CONTENT?		2116
5.3 HOW DOES THE OBJECT ADDRESS SITUATIONS WHERE CONTENT IS OFFENSIVE OUT-GROUP BUT NOT IN-GROUP?		2216
5.4 HOW DOES THE OBJECT ADDRESS SITUATIONS WHERE IT IS REQUESTED TO REPRODUCE OR SUMMARISE FACTUALLY, ETHICALLY OR LEGALLY PROBLEMATIC CONTENT?		2217
5.5 ANY OTHER COMMENTS?		2217
6 Q6: MULTILINGUALITY AND CROSS-CULTURAL KNOWLEDGE.....		2318
6.1 WHICH LANGUAGES ARE SUPPORTED OR ENVISAGED?		2318
6.2 WHICH LOW-RESOURCE LANGUAGES ARE INCLUDED?		2318
6.3 IS THE PRODUCT MORE LIKELY TO PRODUCE ILLEGAL, DISCRIMINATORY OR OTHERWISE TROUBLING CONTENT WHEN USING LOW-RESOURCE LANGUAGES?		2318
6.4 QUALITY CONTROL AND ROBUSTNESS: ARE THE RESULTS THE SAME WHEN ASKING THE SAME QUESTION IN DIFFERENT LANGUAGES, AND SHOULD THEY BE?		2419
6.5 HOW DOES THE PRODUCT TAKE INTO ACCOUNT DIFFERENT USAGES OF WORDS OR EXPRESSIONS AND DIFFERENT CULTURAL CONTEXTS BY DIFFERENT COMMUNITIES THAT SPEAK THE SAME LANGUAGE?		2419
6.6 ANY OTHER COMMENTS?		2419

7	Q7: PRIVACY AND THE PROTECTION OF PERSONAL DATA.....	2520
		2520
7.1	WHAT KIND OF DATA IS COLLECTED FROM END-USERS?.....	2520
7.1.1	Directly by requesting information.....	2520
7.1.2	Through use of the object.....	2621
7.1.3	Through inferences?.....	2621
7.1.4	Other ways?.....	2621
7.2	DOES THE OBJECT CONDUCT EMOTION RECOGNITION? AND IF SO FOR WHAT PURPOSE?.....	2621
7.3	WHAT DATA AND MODELS ARE SHARED BACK TO THE DEVELOPERS OR THIRD PARTIES SUCH AS POTENTIAL ADVERTISERS?.....	2621
7.4	WHAT DATA AND MODELS MIGHT BE SHARED BETWEEN END-USERS OF THE SAME PRODUCT [IN A SMART-HOME ENVIRONMENT FOR EXAMPLE, WILL DIFFERENT MEMBERS OF THE SAME HOUSEHOLD BE ABLE ACCESS INFORMATION ABOUT EACH OTHER?].....	2721
7.5	IS THERE COLLATERAL EFFECT UPON NON-USERS, SUCH AS VISITORS WHOSE PRESENCE (LOCATION DATA), OTHER DATA, OR VOICE MAY BE CAPTURED BY THE PRODUCT?.....	2721
7.6	WHAT WOULD BE THE EVENTUAL CONSEQUENCES OF NOT COLLECTING INFORMATION ABOUT THE USER FOR ONSITE TRAINING?.....	2722
7.7	ARE END-USERS INFORMED OF WHAT DATA MIGHT BE COLLECTED AND WITH WHOM IT MAY BE SHARED?.....	2722
7.8	IS CONSENT OBTAINED FOR DATA COLLECTION?.....	2722
7.9	CAN END-USERS REQUEST FOR DATA TO BE ERASED OR CORRECTED?.....	2822
7.10	FUNCTION CREEP: CAN YOU ENVISAGE THE PRODUCT BEING USED FOR PURPOSES OTHER THAN WHAT IT IS INTENDED FOR, WITH ADVERSE PRIVACY CONSEQUENCES?.....	2923
7.11	ANY OTHER COMMENTS?.....	2923
8	Q8: SECURITY AND SAFETY	3024
8.1	WHAT STRATEGIES HAVE BEEN EMPLOYED TO RENDER THE OBJECT RESILIENT TO RISKS EMERGING FROM BAD ACTORS?.....	3024
8.2	WHAT MEASURES HAVE BEEN INCLUDED TO RENDER THE OBJECT RESILIENT TO RISKS POSED BY ACCIDENTS, NATURAL DISASTERS AND OTHER SAFETY CONCERNS?.....	3125
8.3	WHAT MATERIAL HARM CAN YOU IMAGINE THIS OBJECT COULD RESULT IN OR CONTRIBUTE TO?.....	3125
8.4	WHAT IMMATERIAL HARM CAN YOU IMAGINE THIS OBJECT COULD RESULT IN OR CONTRIBUTE TO?.....	3225
8.5	ARE THERE ANY WAYS THAT YOU CAN IMAGINE SOMEONE WITH MALICIOUS INTENT MISUSING THE OBJECT TO INFLICT MATERIAL OR IMMATERIAL HARM?.....	3225
8.6	ANY OTHER COMMENTS?.....	3325
9	Q9: OTHER RIGHTS, USER EXPERIENCE AND OTHER CONCERNS.....	3426
9.1	WHAT IS IT LIKE TO INTERACT WITH THE OBJECT (USER EXPERIENCE)?.....	3426
9.2	WHAT OTHER RIGHTS MIGHT THE PRODUCT INTERFERE WITH?.....	3527
9.3	ANY OTHER CONCERNS?.....	3527
10	Q10: EU AI ACT COMPATIBILITY	3628
10.1	GENERAL PURPOSE AI.....	3628
10.1.1	If yes to any of the above:.....	3628
10.2	UNACCEPTABLE RISK.....	3628
10.3	HIGH RISK.....	3729
10.3.1	If yes to any of the above:.....	3729
11	Q11: CONCLUSIONS.....	3831
11.1	SUBMITTING PARTNER.....	3831
11.2	ASSESSOR 2.....	3831
11.3	ASSESSOR 3.....	3831
11.4	ASSESSOR 4.....	3831
11.5	CHAIR OF THE ASSESSMENT PANEL.....	3931

Executive summary

The system under review is a pilot for an AI enhanced call centre where parents of young children can get in contact with a nurse if they have questions related to the wellbeing of their child. The main purpose of the system is to make better use of the waiting time when there is a queue to get to talk to a human operator.

The system is envisioned to have two main functions: asking questions of the caller to produce a summary of symptoms and, if prompted to do so by the caller, to provide advice in the form of quotes from a vetted database of medical knowledge. Callers are free to decide whether to interact with the AI or not and it will not impact when or whether they will get in contact with a human nurse.

The assessors noted the system's potential in improving the access to health information for callers and patients and the resulting benefits to the achievement of the right to health. They also noted a few concerns related to the system, most importantly:

Bias and Discrimination:

- *Important that the speech recognition software can understand dialects, sociolects, slang etc not to discriminate based on socio-economic background.*
- *Important to consider that the most vulnerable individual is not the caller but the child patient*
- *Database of medical information must account also for children with disabilities – for vulnerable groups such as this, positive differentiation in attention is necessary to avoid discrimination.*

Privacy and personal data

- *Changes to the initial message to callers is proposed*
- *Pilot owner should investigate what data the call centre currently stores, for how long and for what purpose*
- *If data is needed for training purposes, callers should be allowed to opt in rather than opt out (for example through a press of a button as part of the original message)*
- *Pilot owner should take into account that personal data could often be de-anonymised using the kind of information gathered in this application*
- *Phone numbers should be considered personal data.*

Risks, Robustness, Security and Safety

- *There are risks associated with the system related to:*
 - o *Callers are offered wrong advice or callers misunderstand correct advice (including by not adjusting doses to their children)*
 - o *AI system makes mistakes in listening comprehension or in analysis of symptoms and giving wrong information to nurses*
 - o *Risks related to hacking attempts by malicious actors including personal information extraction attacks*
 - o *Risks related to calls from malicious actors such as: kidnappers and pedophiles, parents or carers trying to establish a false narrative about an injury or illness for purposes of avoiding incrimination or in custody disputes.*

Assessors also suggested a range of mitigating measures including:

- *Ensuring training in the concepts of anchoring and automation bias for human operators, including in respect of potential malicious callers*
- *Making adjustments to the messages received by callers when they first call and when they receive information retrieved from the database*
- *Consider the context of the system (does it come with a website where the medical information is also available? (like say <https://www.nhs.uk/> ?) could additional information about the system be available on such a site for transparency purposes?*

0 Introduction WP6 assessment template (v.2)

The filling in of this template is designed to assist in the work to assess and ensure that technology produced by the ELOQUENCE project is respectful of EU values i.e., privacy, non-discrimination, robustness in legal, ethical and technical terms, reliability and trustworthiness, interpretability and explainability, security and safety. The template is intended to be a collaborative document where all members of a multidisciplinary expert panel (assessors) can contribute in an asynchronous manner.

The submitting partner will be the first to fill in the template, providing important background information for the other assessors. Some questions can only be answered by the submitting partner. Those will be marked in **turquoise**. Hereafter all assessors (including the submitting partner) are asked to answer the questions marked in **yellow**.

Each theme of the assessment is initiated with a box such as this one with a brief description of the theme assessed as well as several **guiding questions**. Assessors are asked to provide comments on all themes, but can focus on the guiding questions they are best equipped to answer. The guiding questions are repeated in the box and in the space below to ease navigation in the document as it grows when assessors include comments, screenshots etc.

Once all assessors have completed the template and returned it to the panel chair, he or she will complete a consensus report which will be shared with the whole panel.

Assessment of: Pilot 4: Upgrading support call centres through AI-based supervision of multimodal dialogues

Assessment Date: January 12, 2025

Assessment No. [V02004]

The assessment was completed by the chair of the panel on [date], on the basis of contributions made by members of the following panel:

1. MS, Milan Sečujski, University of Novi Sad
2. NM, Natalia Menendez, Community of Experts (external)
3. AP, Andreas Pamboris, GrantExpert
4. TO, Theofanis Orphanoudakis, Synelexis
5. HMS, Helga Molbæk-Steensig, European University Institute, Panel Chair

Once completed please return template to Helga.molbaek-steensig@eui.eu

1 Q1: What is the object of assessment?

For the submitting ELOQUENCE partner: Please attach also a file representing or describing the current version of the envisaged product or other object of assessment.

Guiding questions:

What is it [an algorithm; sandbox, demo, etc?]

Which version is it, what models does it apply?

What data has it been trained on, if any?

What is its purpose?

What kinds of unauthorized use (mission creep) would the object be at risk of?

What will be its benefits for developers, deployers, and end-users? And who are its deployers and end-users? [While developers are the creators of the object, deployers are the buyers/owners, and end-users are the individuals using the product. As an example, an AI deployed by a call centre would be developed by the submitting partner, while the deployer would be the purchasing call centre, and the end-user would be the customers calling the call centre]

1.1 What is it [an algorithm; sandbox, demo, etc?]

MS: The object of assessment is a **pilot**. At this stage of development it is a concept defined through its desired functionalities, as an AI system aimed at supporting human experts working in a call-centre providing medical assistance to young parents related to their babies. To prevent a significant loss of time when callers wait for the first human expert to become available (which is a common occurrence in reality), the caller is engaged in a conversation with an AI system which, after “introducing itself”, attempts to collect relevant information from the caller about the case, summarize it and present in a convenient visual form to the medical expert who takes over,

OK, my 8-month-old has suddenly developed high fever, what should I do?

39 degrees

She coughs a little, but she cries a lot.

Not yet, I'm not sure what to give...

Hello, I'm an AI system and I'll ask you some questions about your problem while we're waiting for the doctor to take over. If you agree, please stay on the line and tell me what the problem is.

We'll let the doctor advise you. Please tell me how high the fever is.

OK, are there any other symptoms?

OK, did you try giving her some medication?

Thank you – oh, I've just received the info that a nurse is available. She will take over from me.

SUMMARY:

- age: 8 months
- **high fever** (39°C), developed suddenly,
- baby coughs a little
- no medications given

so that they do not have to collect the same information all over again. The AI system never offers any advice itself, **except that at some points it can quote from an authorized database of medical knowledge.** An optional feature that the system may have (but may not, depending also on technical possibilities) is to establish the level of priority of the call. In an actual scenario this feature, if it exists, can be used to order calls in the queue based on their established priority.

Yes, I gave paracetamol, but the temperature persists, should I try something else?

(interrupting) Could you repeat that, please?

Have you tried applying something for keeping the temperature down?

I'm not a doctor so I couldn't tell you but the information from our webpage says the following:

Ibuprofen can be given to children who are aged 3 months or older and who weigh more than 5kg (11lb). Always read...

Ibuprofen can be given to children who are aged 3 months or older and who weigh more than 5kg (11lb). Always read the instructions carefully, or check with a pharmacist or...

Example of information retrieval

Assessors:

NM: Do the parents need to provide any information to the call center? Name? Surname? Country? Does the call centre locate where the calls come from? How are these data processed in case?

NM: I would consider also offering a link to the relevant webpage so the parents, if interested, could read the full piece to avoid context-dependent misunderstandings.

HMS: Will the caller's telephone number be identified and stored? If yes, this makes it possible for the centre to find out the name and location. There may be good reason to save some such information about callers – for medical follow up or if concerns are raised that a crime has taken place – and the call centre might already be doing it before the introduction of the pilot assessed here. The question is whether and to what extent it changes the situation that an AI assistant has been added to optimize the waiting time. If the number and any inferred information can be, or is used to prioritize calls or to dispatch emergency services (for example based on inferences about where the caller is located) this raises the requirements of the robustness of the system as well as legal requirements to its documentation and other compliance requirements. At the moment, this appears to be outside the scope of the proposed pilot, but should the pilot be successful one could well imagine a scenario in which the developed technology was used in different settings as well.

In addition to the question of identification, this description of the pilot raises two questions about its scope. The first is the extent to which it **will give medical advice**, the second is the extent to which it will **establish priority of the call**. Both functionalities could potentially benefit both users and owners of the system, securing that all callers received the necessary help at the right time – but both functionalities also increase the requirements of the system in terms of robustness, correctness and alignment.

Starting with the medical advice, the limited solution adopted by the pilot owner of offering medical advice only by citing from an authorized database prefaced with a statement that the AI is not a medical professional and that the caller will briefly get in contact with one, has certain benefits. First, it limits, possibly to the point of exclusion, the problem of hallucinations, making the quoted information not too different from an online handbook on a public health website. Second, the prefacing of the advice with a message the AI is not a medical professional, that it is quoting from a database, and that the caller will soon be able to interact directly with a medical professional does communicate to the caller that the advice is neither official nor authoritative. There are also risks however, if the AI misinterprets or misunderstands the symptoms described by the caller, or if it fails to take into account all relevant data about the patient – for pediatric patients this includes in particular but is not limited to their age and weight, it could accidentally recommended medications or doses of medications that are not suitable and could be dangerous to certain patients. Depending on the realistic waiting times, callers might treat their children according to such advice before getting through to a medical professional. As such, although the application prefaces such quotes from the database with warnings, to ensure the safety of all patients, the functionality of giving advice should only be activated when there is a very high degree of certainty about the diagnosis and a very low risk of misguidance. For the remainder of this assessment I will assume that this functionality is included, but in a conservative fashion restricting advice to the treatment of objective symptoms, such as the management of a fever.

As for the functionality of establishing priority, this function would fundamentally change the pilot – callers would no longer be free to not interact with the AI for fear of being underprioritized. Moreover, in order to function well, the pilot would need not only the ability to gather information and present it to the medical professional in a useful way, but also to correctly diagnose the severity of medical problems. The risk of errors would also augment in both likelihood and consequences. From a legal standpoint, this functionality would also be characterized as high risk under the EU AI Act, which does not outlaw the function but places additional requirements on the developer in the form of risk management, documentation and the like. For the remainder of this assessment, I will assume that this functionality is not presently planned as part of the pilot.

1.2 Which version is it, what models does it apply?

MS: At this point the pilot is not realized at an actual system using actual technologies and models, it is defined in terms of its functionalities and the data for its training is under preparation. It will be based on a pre-trained large language model (LLM) and adapted to the medical domain (actually, to a much more restricted domain of dialogue interaction featuring seekers of medical advice related to their babies.

Assessors:

NM Very superficial information.

1.3 What data has it been trained on, if any?

MS: The system has not yet been trained on any data (see 1.2), but, having in mind the properties of the technologies it will most likely rely upon, it will be trained on two datasets:

1 – A dataset containing a predefined number (150) of dialogue scripts, with contents defined through the interaction with expert medical personnel, which reflect actual conversations between callers and medical staff, but in which medical experts focus on **asking relevant questions** instead of providing actual advice. This dataset is obtained by editing a transcript of an actual acted telephone conversation between a team member and an actual medical expert, on a predefined theme, similar to an actual telephone conversation that might occur in an actual call centre of this kind. Namely, the caller and the expert agree on a topic (e.g. “my 2-week-old baby has jaundice”), agree on the details of the case, and then act out a conversation which is recorded (audio), transcribed to text, edited (the number of false starts is reduced for easier interpretation), and resubmitted to the expert for review and possible modifications to maximize its usability. The result is a transcript of an imaginary conversation where most actions carried out by the system entail **requesting information**. In order to preserve at least some level of

naturalness of conversation flow, the transcript may contain actual advice provided by the medical expert (which does not mean that the system trained on such data will also provide advice – it will not, except in cases where it may quote from a relevant database of medical knowledge.) An actual example of an extract from this dataset follows:

(Serbian original)

POZIVALAC: Dobar dan, da li se čujemo?

SESTRA: Da, da, čujemo se, izvolite.

POZIVALAC: E, dobar dan, ovaj, ja zovem, u vezi sa bebom koja ima temperaturu već par dana.

SESTRA: Dobro, kažite mi koliko je beba stara.

POZIVALAC: Beba ima trinaest meseci.

SESTRA: Dobro, a kolika je bila temperatura najviše, dokle je išla?

POZIVALAC: Pa išla je najviše tako do trideset osam sa tri, možda trideset osam sa pet. Nismo sasvim sigurni pošto smo merili, da kažem, različitim toplomerima. [...]

(English translation)

CALLER: Good afternoon, can you hear me?

NURSE: Yes, yes, I can hear you, go ahead.

CALLER: Good afternoon, um, I'm calling about a baby who has had a fever for a few days now.

NURSE: Okay, tell me how old the baby is.

CALLER: The baby is thirteen months old.

NURSE: Alright, and what was the highest temperature recorded?

CALLER: Well, it went up to around thirty-eight point three, maybe thirty-eight point five. We're not entirely sure since we used different thermometers. [...]

2 – a database of medical knowledge, used for (a) direct quotation (relevant quotes will be identified through information retrieval), (b) augmenting the dataset described in **1**. Namely, as 150 dialogues is far too small a quantity of text data for training an AI system of this kind, a large database of medical knowledge will be used as a source for augmentation of the number of training dialogues to several thousands or, quite likely, even much more. In other words, a far greater number of dialogues will be created automatically, following the dialogue structure of original dialogues in dataset **1**, but based on medical knowledge stored in dataset **2**. This database will be collected from publicly available sources with authorization of data owners (that their data can be used for non-commercial research purposes). An imagined example of an extract from this database follows:

Q. When should a mother avoid breastfeeding (contraindications)?

- A.** Breast milk provides the best nutrition for most infants, including premature and sick newborns. However, there are rare exceptions when breast milk or breastfeeding is not recommended, that is if:
- The infant is diagnosed with classic galactosemia, a rare genetic metabolic disorder
 - Mother has HIV and 1) is not on antiretroviral therapy (ART), or 2) is on ART but has not achieved sustained viral suppression during pregnancy (at a minimum throughout the third trimester) or at the time of delivery, or is unable to maintain sustained viral suppression postpartum. If a mother with a detectable viral load chooses to breastfeed, the provider should remain engaged, offer guidance on ARV prophylaxis and HIV testing for the infant, and assist the parent to rapidly regain and maintain virologic suppression.
 - Mother is infected with human T-cell lymphotropic virus type I or type II
 - Mother is using an illicit drug, such as opioids, PCP (phencyclidine) or cocaine (For mothers who discontinue illicit opioids or other substances and are on stable methadone or buprenorphine maintenance therapy, breastfeeding should be encouraged.)

Assessors:

NM: It is very important that the database is diverse, particularly in terms of the interlocutor's voices and all possible health problems that babies could experience (try to avoid bias in terms of health conditions that affect more babies that come i.e. from marginalised environments).

NM: It would be good for the users to know where the training data came from: i.e. Hospital X, university Y to enhance the system's transparency.

HMS: NM is touching upon two distinct concerns here – one is on the content of the data used for training (the transcriptions) while the other is on the speech recognition. Concerns range from alignment problems, where the AI might take a shortcut, assuming certain symptoms based on the accent or dialect of the caller. As I understand MS' description of the training this should be mitigated by the fact that the 150 conversations are transcribed before used for training – taking the question of dialect or accent out of the content-based training. It still leaves the potential problem, which we find with many speech recognition AIs, that certain speakers and certain dialects are more present in speech recognition datasets and therefore easier for the final application to understand. This should of course be mitigated as well using synthetic data or other techniques.

As for the transparency about where the training data comes from, there are two problems with the suggestion by MN, one is whether it can be included in the spoken message when callers first get in contact with the application – the other is whether it is realistic considering that the data comes from a wide range of sources. What can certainly be achieved is to include information on the database from where the AI cites medical advice – if not in the initial message, then as a precursor when the application gives advice.

As for additional information about the model and training to be made available on a website – perhaps where the number of the helpline is provided – this does sound promising, **Milan is that possible, is there such a site or where do callers find the phonenumber?**

1.4 What is its purpose?

MS The purpose of the system is to make better use of medical experts employed in a medical call centre, by collecting relevant information (i.e. information that is considered relevant) about the callers instead of experts themselves. To avoid waiting for the first human expert to become available (which is a common occurrence in reality), the caller is engaged in a conversation with an AI system which, after “introducing itself”, attempts:

- to collect relevant information from the caller about the case,
- to summarize it,
- to present in a convenient visual form to the medical expert who takes over.

AP. The system is intended for call center medical experts. Its purpose is to streamline preliminary data collection and analysis to facilitate a more efficient handling of cases. It collects relevant information from callers, summarizes the information, and presents it in a form that helps the medical expert address the issue at hand in a speedy manner.

FO The purpose is clear as described by the MS. The purpose is similar to an automated triaging system.

1.5 What kinds of unauthorized use (mission creep) would the object be at risk of?

MS: We see no possibility of misuse of this system if used in a scenario as described here (and it cannot be used in any other scenario, provided that it is indeed implemented in a medical centre – if not, it will produce meaningless utterances).

NM: What about personal data collection? Although the data collected initially might not seem enough to identify the person calling, research has shown that from very few data points it is possible to de-anonymised data subjects. If the data include the sex of the baby, their age, any information related to the parents or their neighbourhood it is not that far-fetched.

FO I kind of agree that there are no obvious ways of unauthorized use. One could imagine more advanced cases of cyber-attacks and threats, where the system could be exploited to “flood” the receiving system with irrelevant information (kind of DoS attack) or cause data-poisoning (if technically possible) leading the system to false detection/hallucination.

AP. No significant risks (with respect to unauthorized use) are identified. Data privacy issues should be addressed on the back-end to avoid disclosure of private caller information to unauthorized actors.

HMS: While it is difficult to imagine mission creep of this system in the traditional sense, one could imagine misuse by malicious actors – See Q8.

1.6 What will be its benefits for developers, deployers, and end-users?

MS: Developers will gain insights into what problems may arise in practice when their technologies are used;

Deployers will benefit from more efficient engagement of their experts and increased customer satisfaction;

End-users will obtain the service more quickly, as the medical expert, at the moment he or she takes over, will already be familiar with the particular case that the caller has described to the AI system (based on the summary he or she has seen).

Assessors

NM: The practice: deploy first, ask then is not the most advised. It would be better to conduct a pilot project before deployment in real life scenario of the system.

FO The benefits are clear as described by the MS.

AP. Developers have the opportunity to validate the effectiveness of new developments (and research) under real-world scenarios. Deployers are presented with the opportunity to streamline their existing processes and avoid ineffective use of medical expert personnel resources. The latter focus solely on matters related to their expertise, avoiding cumbersome tasks associated with input collection and summarization. End users (callers) benefit from lower queuing delays during peak hours, prompt service delivery, and an overall more satisfying and effective service.

1.7 Any other comments?

FO Standardized data protection practices should be enforced as in any system interacting with users and exchanging personal and sensitive information.

2 Q2: Explainability and interpretability

All GenAI applications are required to let users know that they are interacting with an AI, but transparency requirements go beyond that. The submitting partner should include information on what has been done to facilitate **Explainable Artificial Intelligence (XAI)**, while other assessors are tasked with determining to what extent it is clear for users that they are interacting with an AI, how it works and what kinds of information it gathers about them, including whether they are being profiled/categorised in any way. The question is important because when AIs are not fully explainable and interpretable, their use can dramatically reduce consumers' ability to interact and gauge whether they are subject to discrimination or nudged in any particular direction

Guiding questions:

Does the object let the users know that they are interacting with an AI?

What has been done to facilitate Explainable Artificial Intelligence (XAI)?

Is there a summary of copyrighted data used for training (or otherwise)?

Will it be clear for users how the system works?

Does the object profile end-users or otherwise make them subject to decisions based on information gathered about them, thus activating their (non-binding) 'right to an explanation' under Recital 71 GDPR?

2.1 What has been done to facilitate Explainable Artificial Intelligence (XAI)?

MS: There have been no attempts so far in that direction from the part of pilot owners (UNS) although we cannot exclude the possibility that some technology that will be involved in the pilot (provided by other project partners) will contain implement some measures related to EAI.

Assessors:

NM: Insufficient answer

HMS: XAI will be added later and to different components of the system.

2.2 Is there a summary of copyrighted data used for training (or otherwise)?

MS: Both datasets are in their construction phases. The question is applicable only to Dataset 2, which will contain data collected mostly from online sources, with appropriate authorization. The data related to copyright is being properly summarized for each website that gives its consent for data use.

Assessors:

HMS: Can this summary be made available on a website where the phone number of the call centre is or similar?

2.3 Does the object profile end-users or otherwise make them subject to decisions based on information gathered about them, thus activating their (non-binding) 'right to an explanation' under Recital 71 GDPR?

MS: The demo will be trained on imagined conversations, but the actual system if/when implemented in practice is indeed intended to collect actual information about actual cases. However, all callers after the conversation with an AI system **will be routed to a human agent**, so there is no risk of a service being denied to any user solely based on their answers automatically processed without any human intervention. The user of the actual system will be informed at the beginning of the conversation with the AI system that he or she will be routed to a human agent as soon as one becomes available, and that the purpose of the (non-mandatory) conversation with an AI agent is solely to make good use of the waiting time. Each user will be free to refuse to engage in this conversation (and in practice it will be impossible to e.g. prevent an user from hanging up), but no user will be refused service based on any answer (or combination of answers) they may provide. So, there will be no "profiling" of users in the sense covered by Recital 71 GDPR.

Assessors:

FO Recital 71 GDPR defines 'profiling' as any form of automated processing of personal data evaluating the personal aspects relating to a natural person, in particular to analyse or predict aspects concerning the data subject's performance at work, economic situation, **health**, personal preferences or interests, reliability or behaviour, location or movements, where it produces legal effects concerning him or her or similarly significantly affects him or her. Thus, even though it is considered to be related to the health status of young children/babies it could raise issues related to such aspects. However, since the purpose is to make an early, draft diagnosis and classification of the incident there are no expected legal effects. The output of the AI system in this case is not to produce irreversible records about the person rather than provide input to the human in the loop that would/should then conclude the processing of information.

HMS: It appears to me that as long as the system does not include the functionality of prioritizing callers, the system does not subject users to decisions and therefore Recital 71 is not activated.

2.4 Does the object let the users know that they are interacting with an AI?

MS: Yes, an introductory message from the system will inform the users that they are interacting with an AI system whose only purpose is to make better use of the time that users would otherwise spend waiting for a human expert to become available (see Section 7.8). The system may conclude the introductory message with (e.g.) "If you agree, please tell me what the problem is – or if you prefer not to, just please hold on while the first nurse is available."

Assessors:

NM: It should be also clear when the user starts to speak with the human expert. It should also be clearly stated that if they refuse to speak with the AI, they will speak anyways with the human expert. Finally, it would be interesting to know whether the different cases are assigned to the human experts randomly or based on the data provided by the parents.

AP. The users are informed at the beginning of the conversation.

HMS: The concerns raised here by NM relates very much to the formulation of the initial message to the caller about how the system they will interact with.

2.5 Wil it be clear for users how the system works?

MS; Presumably not (to laypersons), but they will have an excellent idea what it does.

Assessors:

NM: Weak answer. A brief explanation could be included at the beginning of the conversation so that the user knows how the system works, what kind of data is collected and for which purposes.

FO I agree with the statements of the MS. Again this question would be relevant for a TRL7-9 result.

AP. The users will understand the purpose of the system, how to use it effectively, and how to interpret its outcomes. The implementation of the system, however, will most likely not be clear to end users.

HMS: The system will need two different levels of explainability communicated to the two main audiences:

On the one side the medical professionals who use the system who will need a more in-depth understanding of how the system works mainly to gauge any potential risks of errors or limitations of trustworthiness of the summaries of patient data and symptoms that the system collects and whether and why it has provided any advice if it has done so.

On the other side the callers who will need information about the system in two levels: First to understand whether they are required to interact with the system, and how it impacts their waiting time or prioritization (if implemented) what they tell the system. Second, if they are provided with any advice, from where this advice comes, whether it has been informed by the information they have provided (such as whether they need to calculate medicine doses themselves or if that has already been done by the system).

2.6 Any other comments?

[please fill in here]

Robustness, reliability and trustworthiness go to the very core of what the purpose of the object is and whether it is able to reliably fulfil it. An important factor here is the question of hallucinations which plagued early GenAI in particular. The question relates to what extent the object fulfils its function and produce useful and truthful content. Assessors here are invited to consider in particular the intended function of the object.

Guiding questions:

Can the object be convinced/hacked to produce illegal or otherwise troubling content ([Adversarial testing](#))?

Does the object [hallucinate](#)?

To what extent does the object fulfil its function and produce useful and truthful content?

3 Q3: Robustness, reliability and trustworthiness

3.1 Can the object be convinced/hacked to produce illegal or otherwise troubling content ([Adversarial testing](#))?

MS It is difficult to say at this stage as it depends from the technologies and their developers, not the pilot owner. However, the system will be used over the telephone line, and will focus on **asking questions** rather than providing information, and in the (infrequent) cases when it might provide information, it will quote from a reliable database of medical knowledge, i.e. dataset 2 (see also Section 9.1). The entire dataset 2 will be reviewed by medical experts engaged at the project (a certain degree of disagreement between experts regarding some topics will have to be accepted).

Assessors;:

FO I agree with the statements of the MS. Again this question would be relevant for a TRL7-9 result and the overall cybersecurity measures taken to secure access to the product.

AP. It is my understanding that this risk cannot be ruled out at this stage. However, the main intention of the system relates to data collection and presentation, therefore, the impact of this risk is low.

HMS: While it is difficult to imagine a malicious actor hacking the system in any meaningful way given the way it is proposed to be set up, one could imagine the system being misused by callers in a way that is not in the interest of the child patient. The caller may not be who they claim to be or may be in possession of the child illegally. A caller might use the system to distort facts or create a false record (in terms of timing, location, gravity or origin) of a health issue, such as an injury. Examples where such a thing might happen are custody cases, disputes between parents, or when a child is held by a pedophile or kidnapper. Such misuse could happen also without the introduction of the AI into the system, so the main concern is related to the concept of anchoring – the human operator may be anchored by the narrative as described by the caller to the AI in a way they would not be if they had interacted with the caller themselves as the AI will, by its design, have cleaned up explanations and false starts as might indicate inconsistencies in the callers story.

3.2 Does the object hallucinate?

MS: It is not to be expected for the system to hallucinate – in fact, the worst mistake the system might make (having in mind in its regular mode of operation – asking questions or quoting from a verified knowledge database) is to ask a question that is considered inappropriate – whether because it is completely irrelevant in a given situation or because it contains illegal or troubling content. Information retrieval from a reliable database will not generate such content (i.e. this would be theoretically impossible), and as for the reliability of the basic language model upon which the system is based, this is a questions for technology developers.

Assessors:

NM: In any case, maybe it could be interesting to include a final message where they advise parents to physically visit a doctor or take their baby to emergency if things do not improve in a certain amount of time.

FO: I cannot imagine a case where the system could generate “illegal” content under the above assumptions. Hallucinations are too early to exclude and would require proper system validation and evaluation.

AP: Based on the fact that the system merely collects data and cites credible sources, hallucinations should not be of any concern. If more advanced functionalities are realized in the future, then this will need to be assessed through appropriate verification/validation testing.

HMS: Hallucinations in the traditional sense should not be possible, but I would argue that the main risk in retrieval of information from the database would be: Lack of clarity or misunderstanding on the part of the callers, misdiagnosis on the part of the AI leading to the wrong information being recalled, or recalled information not taking all data into account – for example, patients under the age of 1 might not be allowed the same medications, foodstuffs or similar as older patients, and the dosage of medications would likely depend on the weight of the child.

I do not think it makes sense to have a final message as the system will send the caller on to a human operator.

3.3 To what extent does the object fulfil its function and produce useful and truthful content?

MS: The questions the system asks cannot be “truthful” or not, they can only be relevant (to the point) or not, and information retrieved from a database that has been verified by medical experts might, in the worst case, be incorrectly recognized as relevant in a particular situation. For this reason, the system will:

- aim to sustain conversation only **by asking questions**
- discourage any attempt of caller to seek information before a human operator is available
- will provide information **only by quoting** from a verified medical database, and
- will remind the caller that the medical expert is the only one to be trusted (“*We’ll let the doctor advise you...*”).

Assessors:

FO I agree with the statements of the MS. The answer to this question is a one of the research targets of the project and would require proper system validation and evaluation against the selected KPIs.

AP. The questions outputted by the system are useful to medical experts for speeding up the information retrieval process. Content retrieved from the verified database (medical information) will be inherently truthful. The system’s output will also cite the relevant sources for users to follow up on if desired.

3.4 *Any other comments?*

[please fill in here]

4 Q4: Bias

This question is related to bias in a cultural or legal sense, both in the training of the object and in the content it produces. This refers to the fact that there may be situations in which a GenAI produces content that is representative of the material it has been trained on, which in turn is representative of conceptualisations and assumptions in the culture that has produced that material. Often this means leaning towards the western, the able-bodied, and the male, but there have also been [examples](#) where training material has been skewed in a different way.

Guiding questions:

What measures were taken to identify potential biases (implicit, sampling, temporal or otherwise) in the training data or data otherwise relied upon?

What known biases are there in the training data or other sources of information relied upon by the object?

What has been done to mitigate these biases?

Does the product produce biased content, e.g. on account of sex, gender, sexual orientation, gender identity, ethnicity, national origin, language, disability or political opinion?

How does the product address situations where society is biased?

4.1 *What measures were taken to identify potential biases (implicit, sampling, temporal or otherwise) in the training data or data otherwise relied upon?*

MS; At the moment no attempts are taken in that direction by pilot owners except to avoid introducing unwanted bias in the training data produced by pilot owners. Here we distinguish between unwanted bias and bias in general, because the specific scenario addressed by Pilot 4 is e.g. intrinsically affected by a gender bias which cannot be treated as any other bias.

Once ELOQUENCE develops tools able to identify and reduce the influence of bias in the training material, these tools may be employed to improve the basic language model the pilot will be based on, as well as to identify and reduce bias in Dataset 1 and (especially) Dataset 2.

Assessors:

HMS: For this application we must consider both potential bias related to the caller and bias related to the patient. In some cases, biases regarding the patient would be inferred from biases against the caller (such as race, ethnicity or social status) but it might also be based on information provided by the caller (such as gender, age or disability). Provided that the AI does not struggle to understand the caller because their accent or dialect is underrepresented in the training data, the system could potentially partially alleviate the first type of biases as the operator would be presented with a summary of the child's symptoms free from information about the caller's social status, gender, dialect or accent, anchoring them on these facts before interacting with the caller. If the system fails to understand a caller because of their accent or dialect the result would instead be to aggravate any bias against them. As for information regarding gender, age or disability of the patient, it is important that the database of medical advice used both by operators and by the AI when giving advice is free from unwanted biases and is capable of taking into account vulnerabilities such as disability and age, weight and other characteristics of the patient when appropriate.

4.2 What known biases are there in the training data or other sources of information relied upon by the object?

MS: The system (in practice) will be employed in a highly specific scenario, where young parents will call for assistance or help with their newborns. It is known that in practice well above 90% of callers are women, and some of the issues with newborns are obviously not equally applicable to their mothers and fathers, which has quite little to do with “leaning towards the male”. However, with all that in mind, we do not exclude the possibility that some unwanted gender bias exists in the data. In any case, we think that it is of primary importance that *unwanted bias* should be distinguished from *bias in general*. It can be expected that the generated datasets will be far too small (especially Dataset 1) for most types of bias to appear in them (e.g. national, political etc.).

Assessors:

NM: Bias regarding the socioeconomic environment of the families need to be considered as well. Other bias could include whether the parents are migrants or have any kind of health condition that makes it difficult to understand them when they speak by the AI system

HMS: Another important bias to consider may also be under-representation in training data. It is important that common disabilities are anticipated in the database from where the system gathers information. Failure to consider common disabilities and taking them into account in a medical setting could amount to discrimination against families with a child with a disability. Moreover, it may well be that parents of children with disabilities could be more frequent callers as certain disabilities correlate with a higher frequency of certain health issues.

4.3 What has been done to mitigate these biases?

MS; As we do not identify the most obvious bias (the gender bias) as an unwanted bias, at least in its most prominent aspects, we consider that no measures *should* be taken to mitigate it. We do not exclude the possibility that a sophisticated technology will be able to identify and reduce unwanted biases in the data (and even to identify specific aspects of gender bias as unwanted, and address them only).

Assessors:

HMS: The database of medical data should be checked for common biases such as gender, social status, religion, ethnicity or race, and it should also be ensured that it contains the necessary positive biases, taking things such as disability or common birth defects into account.

4.4 Does the product produce biased content, e.g. on account of sex, gender, sexual orientation, gender identity, ethnicity, national origin, language, disability or political opinion?

MS: The pilot has not yet been developed and it is difficult to say what content it will produce. It will mostly ask questions, so the principal question is whether it will produce biased questions. This depends by far on the bias introduced by the text material on which the principal ELOQUENCE language model is trained, and far less on any bias that might be present in datasets 1 or 2, which are in most part medical and focus on issues such as health and well-being, regardless of nation, political opinion, ethnicity etc.

Assessors:

AP. The level of bias in questions outputted by the system can only be determined from a thorough investigation of the training datasets. Based on the information provided, it seems that the questions may likely be gender biased, however, this is due to the fact that the majority of end users are expected to be females.

FO: I agree with the statements of the MS. Considerations regarding bias may be relevant only for the case of sex but again this will depend on the treatment of the training data by data scientists. No obvious reason to introduce such a bias can be detected at this point; however, the model developers should have an appropriate guideline towards this end.

HMS: not possible to answer this at this stage

4.5 *How does the product address situations where society is biased?*

MSS: We did not have in mind specific measures aimed at addressing such situations, the most we can do as pilot owners is to ensure (using ELOQUENCE technologies) that the level of unwanted bias in the training data we produce is minimal.

Assessors:

AP. By ensuring that the training data is (to the extent possible) unbiased.

FO I agree with the statements of the MS. Does not seem relevant apart for the case of sex. If other cases where cultural or societal aspects may impact the performance of the dialogue system with respect to its domain specific operation it should be investigated.

HMS: The main concern here should be the database of medical data which should take into account things such as common birth defects, disabilities and other vulnerabilities.

4.6 *Any other comments?*

[please fill in here]

5 Q5: Discrimination

This question relates to the production of discriminatory and offensive content. Here a particular challenge is posed by context-specific offensiveness and the difference between internal or in-group language and external or out-group speech. There may be situations where the object is requested by a user to reproduce content that is not offensive in-group but is offensive outgroup (an example could be song-lyrics or satire). In such cases consistently refusing to produce such content because of requested content being offensive in an outgroup context, could constitute a type of censoring or close off cultural content for some users in a problematic way. Conversely, content that is not offensive from the perspective of the dominant population may nevertheless be offensive when appearing to be coming from the dominant culture towards users belonging to a specific minority.

There may also be situations where the object is requested to reproduce content that is culturally problematic regardless of group belonging, but where the content nevertheless forms an important part of a cultural discussion – an example could be if it were asked to reproduce summaries of nazi propaganda or arguments against fundamental rights.

Both types of situations might be resolvable by the product adding context and additional explanations or warnings to users to its responses.

Guiding questions:

Can the object be convinced to produce illegal or discriminatory content?

How does the object address situations where content is offensive out-group but not in-group?

How does the object address situations where it is requested to reproduce or summarise factually, ethically or legally problematic content?

5.1 Does the object conduct biometric categorization or social scoring, and if so, for what purpose?

MS: It does not.

5.2 Can the object be convinced to produce illegal or discriminatory content?

MS: This, again, does not depend on UNS as pilot owners, but on partners who produce technologies that the pilot will use. As for UNS, we can and will ensure that nothing that suggests the possibility of producing illegal or discriminatory content is introduced in datasets 1 and 2.

Assessors:

FO I could only imagine cases of data poisoning to result to this not on purpose. But this is the case of the robustness and cybersecurity aspects discussed above.

AP. Only if the datasets used are not vetted properly, which should not be the case.

5.3 How does the object address situations where content is offensive out-group but not in-group?

MS: The communication (in a real life scenario) is conducted between an AI system and a caller who can theoretically belong to any group. We do not imagine that there is much room for the system to express any offensive content whatsoever, which is why we do not feel that the question is applicable to this pilot.

Assessors:

AP. Such situations don't seem to apply for this project outcome.

FO I agree it does not seem relevant beyond the above concerns regarding robustness and bias free operation.

5.4 How does the object address situations where it is requested to reproduce or summarise factually, ethically or legally problematic content?

MS: The design of the system will ensure that the system, besides greeting the user and making courteous remarks, only (1) asks questions and (2) quotes from a source verified by human experts. Any initiative on the part of the caller (e.g. explicit attempt to obtain advice) will be discouraged by responses such as *"I am only here to collect information about your case, we will let the doctor/nurse advise you as soon as he/she becomes available"*. The system will be explicitly designed to **decline any request** to reproduce or summarise any content.

Assessors:

FO I agree it does not seem relevant beyond the above concerns regarding robustness and bias free operation.

AP. Based on the fact that the system will be mainly asking questions and quoting facts from a verified database of information, such situations are not anticipated. According to the described implementation, associated requests will be ignored/discouraged/declined.

5.5 Any other comments?

[please fill in here]

6 Q6: Multilinguality and cross-cultural knowledge

An important feature of the ELOQUENCE project and other projects launched under the same call is the attention to low-resource languages and cross-cultural knowledge. The submitting partner is invited to disclose what languages the AI currently supports and which it is envisioned to incorporate next, and the other assessors are invited to test the AI in as many languages as possible – particularly low resource languages. In this regard, due to the abundance of English-language training data and pre-developed models nearly all languages are low-resource compared to English. Societally this represents a serious problem as may create inequalities between those that have access to high quality AI in their working languages, and those who do not. Assessors are invited to investigate whether the product is more likely to hallucinate or produce illegal, discriminatory or otherwise troubling content depending on the languages used to interact with the object. Where relevant it may also be prudent to investigate how the product takes into account different usages of words or expressions and different cultural contexts by different communities that speak the same language.

Guiding questions:

Which languages are supported or envisaged?

Which low-resource languages are included?

Is the product more likely to produce illegal, discriminatory or otherwise troubling content when using low-resource languages?

Quality control and robustness: are the results the same when asking the same question in different languages, and should they be?

How does the product take into account different usages of words or expressions and different cultural contexts by different communities that speak the same language?

6.1 Which languages are supported or envisaged?

MS: Serbian (Extension to other languages is possible, in fact, simple, but this is not a part of the ELOQUENCE project.)

Assessors:

NM: How about dialects?

6.2 Which low-resource languages are included?

MS: Serbian

6.3 Is the product more likely to produce illegal, discriminatory or otherwise troubling content when using low-resource languages?

MS: Not applicable (the pilot will be provided for one language, a low-resourced one).

6.4 *Quality control and robustness: are the results the same when asking the same question in different languages, and should they be?*

MS: Not applicable (the pilot will be provided for one language).

6.5 *How does the product take into account different usages of words or expressions and different cultural contexts by different communities that speak the same language?*

MS: The system will not possess any knowledge of the cultural context of a caller or of the community he or she may belong. The quantity of training data for this specific scenario is far too small for it to be capable to take into account different usage of words/expressions by members of different groups.

Assessors:

NM: What about the level of formality of the language? Would the system be accessible, accurate and comprehensible from people from all socioeconomic backgrounds?

AP: The system does not explicitly account for different usages of words or expressions and different cultural contexts. Provided a more elaborate training dataset, this issue could be addressed.

FO I agree it does not seem relevant beyond the objective to address specific language domains.

HMS: This question is mainly relevant to the speech comprehension which I assume will be ensured in part by the incorporation and finetuning of a large foundation model? As part of finetuning this model using the dialog-based dataset, it might be relevant to include dialogs acted out using different kinds of slang, dialects (including at least ekavica and ijekavica) or accents, using loanwords from minority languages such as Romani or Albanian and similar, to ensure that callers speaking these variants of Serbian are not misunderstood to a greater degree than people speaking standard or upper class variants.

6.6 *Any other comments?*

[please fill in here]

7 Q7: Privacy and the protection of personal data

Privacy and protection of personal data raises several different concerns. At the same time these concerns will have to be balanced with potential functional gains from the learning the object does when in use by end-users.

We are concerned both with how personal data is used by developers and deployers, but also how it might be shared between several different end-users. There are a number of ways this might happen. For example, in a smart-home environment, we might imagine that different members of the same household interact with the same AI object. Concerns may therefore be related to how information collected about these members is shared not only with developers and 3rd parties – such as for advertising – but also within the household between members.

Another concern is function- or mission creep where applications created for one purpose are used for another, to the detriment of fundamental rights protection. It may well happen that a smart-home application could be used also in a club or in a school without necessarily being reconfigured for that space.

Guiding questions:

What kind of data (including sensitive personal data such as data that can be used to identify a person and data revealing their racial or ethnic origin, political opinions, religious or philosophical beliefs, sexuality, health-related data, trade-union membership, or their emotions) is collected from end-users?

Are end-users informed of what data might be collected and with whom it may be shared?

Is consent obtained for data collection?

Can end-users request for data to be erased or corrected?

What data and models are shared back to the developers or third parties such as potential advertisers?

What data and models might be shared between end-users of the same product [in a smart-home environment for example, will different members of the same household be able access information about each other?]

Is there collateral effect upon non-users, such as visitors whose presence (location data), other data, or voice may be captured by the product?

What would be the eventual consequences of not collecting information about the user for onsite training?

Function creep: Can you envisage the product being used for purposes other than what it is intended for, with adverse privacy consequences?

7.1 What kind of data is collected from end-users?

7.1.1 Directly by requesting information

MS: No sensitive personal data such as data that can be used to identify a person and data revealing their racial or ethnic origin, political opinions, religious or philosophical beliefs, sexuality, trade-union membership, or their emotions. However, the system is **primarily aimed at collecting data** including data related to health, habits and other data related to system users and their children (or children in their care). By its design, the system **will have to ask questions** such as: “How old is your baby?” or “Did she sleep well last night”, or “How long has it been since she passed stool?” or “Did any other member of your family suffer from a flu or some similar health problem lately?”, or “Have you been seeing a doctor about that?”, for the purpose of summarizing this information and offering the summary to the medical professional who takes over the call, i.e. resumes communication with the user. However,

although much of this information is extremely sensitive, none of these questions can be used to purposefully identify the caller, or disclose their racial or ethnic origin, political opinions, religious or philosophical beliefs, sexuality, trade-union membership, or emotions. However, we cannot exclude the possibility that in some very specific circumstances some of the system users might volunteer such information. The system will not even be aware if the caller is male or female.

Assessors:

NM: Please see my comment above about the phone numbers and other identifying information. Would the system store such information for training purposes or would it delete it?

HMS: And if the information is deleted, when would that be? There may be good reason to hold on to such information for some time – and the current call centre may already be doing it before introducing the AI. Purposes might include that if callers call again they can be routed to the same medical professional and would not have to re-iterate everything and so forth. In any case, for the purposes of GDPR compliance and to secure against the risk of data breaches, it is important to know whether such information is stored, for how long and for what purpose.

7.1.2 Through use of the object

MS: Not applicable (the system is designed as a service available by telephone).

Assessors:

NM: Does the system store if you call several times?

7.1.3 Through inferences?

MS: Not applicable.

7.1.4 Other ways?

MS: Not applicable. The system specifically **asks for all information** that it may or may not obtain.

7.2 *Does the object conduct emotion recognition? And if so for what purpose?*

MS: The pilot does not use emotion recognition (this was considered as a possibility in some early versions of pilot design but was abandoned for ethical reasons).

7.3 *What data and models are shared back to the developers or third parties such as potential advertisers?*

MS: No data are shared back to the developers or third parties.

Assessors:

NM: Will the system use the data collected from real conversations with parents to train itself?

7.4 What data and models might be shared between end-users of the same product [in a smart-home environment for example, will different members of the same household be able access information about each other?]

MS: No data or models may be shared between different users (the system is designed as a service available by telephone to any single caller).

7.5 Is there collateral effect upon non-users, such as visitors whose presence (location data), other data, or voice may be captured by the product?

MS: No.

7.6 What would be the eventual consequences of not collecting information about the user for onsite training?

MS: Not collecting user information would nullify the very purpose of the system – it is designed with the **specific object to collect information** and summarize it in a visually convenient way to a medical professional.

7.7 Are end-users informed of what data might be collected and with whom it may be shared?

MS: The end users will be informed of **what data might be collected**, and that it will **not be shared with anyone**. The design of the system is such that the collected data loses most of its value immediately after the call (one single user session) is finished. The only purpose of keeping any of the collected data may be for future improvements of the system (verifying the relevance of the questions that the system has asked to the actual case), and this may or may not be implemented in a real-life scenario. It is outside the scope of the pilot demo as defined for implementation towards the end of the project. Thus, in the demo of Pilot 4 the users may be informed that the data will be destroyed immediately after the call, or the users may be asked if they wished their data to be destroyed.

Assessors:

HMS: Please see my questions/comments to 7.1.1. F

7.8 Is consent obtained for data collection?

MS: The end users will be informed that the system will collect data, and that they can just hold on the line and wait for the human operator to take over the call if they feel uncomfortable with an AI system collecting potentially sensitive data. However, the data that the AI system would collect would, in an ideal case, be precisely the data that the human operator would collect if he/she took over the call.

However, it should be taken into account that the system, in its real-life use, is intended for helping young parents, and that the introductory message to the caller has to be relatively brief, e.g. the system may say something like:

“Hello, this is the helpline for young parents. All our staff are currently busy so while you’re waiting, you might let me collect some information about your inquiry. I am an AI system and I will not offer any advice to you, but I could help the nurses save time by collecting information for them so they can help you more efficiently once one of them is available. If you are not comfortable with me collecting this information, please just hold on the line, and if you are, please tell me what the

problem is. Whatever you tell me I will not share with anyone else and you can even ask the nurse to erase your data when you get the advice you sought.”

We would appreciate expert help in defining this introduction precisely, but we emphasize that the message should **not be much longer than this**, since the waiting time should be used efficiently, and there is no point in a long introduction if the nurse is available immediately after, or even before the system gets the consent from the user.

Assessors:

NM: Specify in the message what kind of information is gathered.

AP: Appropriate user-friendly and efficient ways of asking for consent at the beginning of a call are planned, as indicated by the responsible partner.

FO I agree with the MS statements. User consent is easy to make transparent.

HMS: While it may still be too early to settle on this message (as it will also depend on the final choices regarding the functionality of the system discussion under Q1) here is a version with suggested changes:

“Hello, this is the helpline for ~~young~~ parents of children aged [insert relevant age range]. All our staff are currently busy, ~~but so~~ while you’re waiting, ~~you might let me collect some information about your inquiry!~~ would like to collect information about your child’s symptoms to help the nurses save time. I am an AI system ~~and I will not offer any advice to you, but I could help the nurses save time by collecting information for them so they can help you more efficiently once one of them is available, and you are free to decide whether to talk to me or not, in either case you will be put through to the first available nurse.~~ I cannot provide health-related advice except as quotes from our authorized database which is also available at [insert website] where you might have found our phone number. The information you share with me will be given to the nurse as soon as one becomes available and no one else. If you are OK with us using this call for training purposes, please press 1 – otherwise just hold the line. Now, can you tell me what the problem is? ~~If you are not comfortable with me collecting this information, please just hold on the line, and if you are, please tell me what the problem is. Whatever you tell me I will not share with anyone else and you can even ask the nurse to erase your data when you get the advice you sought.”~~

If you want to include the option that the information can be deleted after use, I’d suggest either using the standard call centre option of asking in the message if it can be used for training (added in **blue**) or if you are not planning on using the data, leave it out.

You might also leave out the information in **green** about the database, and only have the system say it if it provides any information from the database. Potentially prefaced with a warning that the advice is a quote and may not be tailored to your infant in terms of dosage, age, disability or otherwise.

The message should be supported by more detailed information about the system and the database being available on the website for transparency. Most parents will not have time or care to examine such information, but it is important that it is available for transparency.

7.9 Can end-users request for data to be erased or corrected?

MS: As explained in 7.7, there is no obstacle for offering users the possibility to have their data erased immediately after the session is finished (in such cases, this would only eliminate the possibility of improving the system for future use by systematically analyzing recorded call logs, but that would not affect the quality of the service that the user will get).

To make the introductory message a bit shorter, the system can even be designed so as to delete the caller's data by default, *unless the nurse gets the consent from the user to keep it*. This, of course, is an additional burden on the medical staff, which negatively affects the idea of the system – to save the time of medical experts.

Assessors:

AP. It is my understanding that the specifics of when data will be erased are still under question. Deleting all data immediately after a call ends (by default) would be a reasonable approach, however, the data could be used to further enhance the system moving forward. The alternative would be to ask for consent to store and use the data for training purposes and delete it only if otherwise specified by the user.

FO I agree with the MS statements. User notification is easy to make transparent. Appropriate data storage is mandatory for the research phase (not the operational). However, this should be done under the general GDPR restrictions.

HMS: The decision about whether data should be stored, for how long and for what purpose of course needs to be made before deployment, and users must be informed, including of their option to opt out. Considering the purpose of the system, I do not think it makes sense to put this burden on the nurses/ask the caller their consent while they're probably eager to put the nurse's advice into action at the end of the call. It would be better to have the decision be made in the beginning of the call, while the caller is in any case waiting in line, and usually it would be better to have callers opt in than opt out – so a classic call centre 'press 1 if we can use this call for training and quality assurance' message could be added (see my comment above), with the option available of course to retract that consent if the caller ask (whether they ask the AI or the nurse) later on.

7.10 Function creep: Can you envisage the product being used for purposes other than what it is intended for, with adverse privacy consequences?

MS: Not in its current form, when trained on a corpus of medical conversations where it is designed so as to ask questions from users who seek advice for some issue with their newborn. The system can always be misused (a malicious user – e.g. a prankster – may ask malicious questions in order to provoke non-standard system reactions, just as in case of any technical device that may be misused on purpose), but its user will be aware that the behaviour provoked in this way is not authentic.

Assessors:

NM: Make sure that the system could not be used to harm the baby, instead of helping them.

AP. The system is designed to service a specific target audience and the models are trained accordingly on verified data. Misuse of the system from malicious users is always possible, however, the nature of the system's output is such that privacy consequences are not of concern.

FO I agree with the MS statements. The question seems relevant only the context of robust and secure operation discussed above.

HMS: There are two potential ways that the system could be misused. One is misuse by callers (a security concern, treated under Q1 and Q8) the other would be misuse by the deployer – say if the call centre decided to sell data to third parties for advertising or for the development of medical AI or similar. In both cases, the working and information gathered by the call centre in its usual capacity could be misused in the same way, but in case 1 the risk of anchoring presents an additional hassle, while in case 2 the data could simply be collected more efficiently.

7.11 Any other comments?

[please fill in here]

8 Q8: Security and Safety

This question addresses a wide range of risks related to AIs in general. In terms of definitions, safety is associated with accidental risk, and security with malicious intent. Reports and White Papers from the European Commission have developed several different taxonomies of potential harms caused by AIs. For example, the AI White Paper from 2020 groups risks into two categories – Risk of Material damage: safety and health of individuals (including loss of life) or damage to property, and risk of Immaterial damage: loss of privacy, limitations to the right of freedom of expression, human dignity, discrimination.¹ GenAI is most directly likely to cause immaterial damage. Other categories could be risks posed to society, such as mass unemployment, mass surveillance, automated weapons systems lowering the bar to genocide, threats to democracy due to filter bubbles and resulting damage to the democratic deliberation; versus risks posed to individuals: personal data leaks, personal unemployment, imprisonment or discrimination based on biased and opaque algorithms.

Certain risks can occur with or without malicious intent such as data poisoning,

An example of data poisoning is Microsoft Tay, a chatbot supposed to interact with young people on social media that was flooded with offensive and racist tweets in 2016 ... Data poisoning can affect a vast array of datasets, such as healthcare data, loan or house pricing.¹

Another problem is that of data or model drift, the tendency for AIs to degenerate over time.

Meanwhile, security concerns can emerge from hacking attempts, attempts to cause data breach, or the intentional installation of backdoors. In both cases risks can be mitigated through proper data management and model review throughout the life cycle of the product. In this part of the template both the submitting partner and the other assessors are invited to creatively imagine scenarios in which the object reviewed could result in material or immaterial harms because of safety or security issues. Malicious security concerns could emerge either from a malicious deployer misusing the product for purposes other than what it was designed for, from external attempts at hacking, from users using the product for ill, or from developers intentionally installing backdoors or otherwise compromising the safety of the object. Assessors should not refrain from considering any of these, and assessors should be free to consider both concrete individual risks and more vague societal concerns.

8.1 What strategies have been employed to render the object resilient to risks emerging from bad actors?

MS: To our knowledge no strategy has yet been employed to address this problem, but this is a question for providers of technology (most notably large language models on which the Pilot will be based). We do not consider to be a serious threat having in mind the use case – a caller contacts a call centre, communicates with a chatbot. In such a scenario the caller must be aware that if they use the system according to its obvious purpose, they will get valid feedback. If they don't, no harm is done except that they will get the feedback of whose invalidity any reasonable user will be aware.

Assessors:

HMS: Coming back to the risk of callers not being who they claim to be or trying to misuse the line to establish a false narrative of the facts related to an injury or other medical event of the patient, the main method to render the system resilient to such a risk is likely not in technical terms, but in the education of the medical operators in relation in particular to the problem of anchoring and automation bias.

8.2 What measures have been included to render the object resilient to risks posed by accidents, natural disasters and other safety concerns?

MS: To our knowledge no strategy has yet been employed to address this problem, but this is a question for providers of technology. Having in mind the design and the purpose of the system, we do not believe this question is applicable to Pilot 4.

Assessors:

HMS: Likely not relevant to this application.

8.3 What material harm can you imagine this object could result in or contribute to?

MS: Indirectly, we can imagine that the end users might suffer material harm (with respect to safety or health) only if they do not obtain urgently needed information from the medical expert in time, in case the user may have obtained the information in some other way, but has opted for using the system and thus suffered unnecessary delay. However, the introduction of the system into medical practice cannot increase total call duration, because without the existence of the system, the caller would still have to wait for human expert to become available.

As the system will not provide advice, it cannot result or contribute to any material harm through the questions it asks (any more than a system where only human medical staff work without support from AI, and collect much the same information themselves).

Assessors:

NM: What if the AI system provides an advice based on a quote and the parents proceed with that without waiting for the doctor and the advice was wrong?

FO I do not totally agree that the system “will not provide advice”, since in the envisaged mode of operation advice is provided (even though with appropriate disclaimers about the accuracy). Thus, this is the most critical aspect of the operation of the module. There are three concerns that need to be taken into account:

- 1) Wrong triage decisions (urgent cases being delayed more than others)'
- 2) Wrong advice to users/parents
- 3) Wrong summaries provided to the medical staff

All the above may have impact on human health and should be considered mission critical factors. However, since the system is supposed to be supervised by a human expert and it is considered to act as an assistant it finally depend on the human actor to intervene in final decisions.

AP. The system is not designed to replace medical experts but rather to make use of idle waiting time and improve the overall responsiveness of medical care for the specific target group. Provided that any quotes outputted originate from verified data (and their sources are properly cited), I cannot imagine any material harm arising from this implementation.

With respect to user experience, the dialogues need to be precise, concise and to the point. They should be structured in a way that is considerate to the mental/emotional state of users at the time of a call. Users should not be burdened with repetitive or unnecessary communications to avoid causing frustration.

HMS: As outlined by the other assessors, there are several ways that the system could cause harm to human health, which must all be accounted for in both development and deployment of the system and which must be taken into account when outlining the risk management plan once the system reaches a higher technological readiness level. They are as follows:

1. Risks related to advice given if:

- a. The system misdiagnoses the problem and offers irrelevant and/or dangerous advice which the callers implement without waiting for the human medical professional
 - i. Current mitigation: two steps: Step 1: initial refusal and suggestion to wait for the medical professional, step 2: prefacing advice with *'I'm not a doctor, but the information on our webpage says...'*
 - b. The system diagnoses the problem correctly and offers correct advice, but the caller misunderstands, fails to catch all information or fails to adjust the advice to their specific situation including the age/weight of the child as well as things such as disabilities.
 - i. Suggested mitigation: step 1 initial refusal, Step 2: preface advice with a warning to adjust based on circumstances. i.e.: *"I suggest you ask the nurse when you get through to them, in the meantime I can tell you the information we have on the subject on our website, please keep in mind that this general advice may not be appropriate for your child and check the dosage on any medication you administer. Here is what our website says regarding [insert diagnosis/symptoms]..."*
2. Risks related to the summary provided to the nurse:
- a. The system misdiagnoses the problem or misunderstands some of the facts about the patient or their symptoms.
 - i. Suggested mitigation: training of medical staff utilising the system. Including checking in with caller whether information is correct. The danger here as well is anchoring.

8.4 What immaterial harm can you imagine this object could result in or contribute to?

MS: We cannot imagine the system causing immaterial damage such as loss of privacy, limitations to the right of freedom of expression, human dignity, discrimination. We cannot exclude the possibility that the users (callers) might voluntarily disclose information that may come at the expense at their privacy, or information that may be considered sensitive in other ways (e.g. about breastfeeding), but users of such medical services (callers of such helplines) regularly disclose such information to medical experts they obtain advice from. No-one is pressured to use the service under conditions they are not comfortable with, any user can just hold on the line if they prefer to and decline to use the service of whose properties they have been informed.

Assessors:

8.5 Are there any ways that you can imagine someone with malicious intent misusing the object to inflict material or immaterial harm?

MS: We see no ways of misusing the object to inflict material or immaterial harm.

The only person communicating with the system is the caller, and if they have malicious intent to inflict harm, there is no-one they can inflict it to. Any user will be aware that medical expert will take over the call, and that there is no more opportunity to inflict harm than in any other situation where a caller contacts a telephone service which is intended to offer information only (e.g. weather or traffic information), whether AI-based or human-based only. Any reasonable user will also be aware that most likely their interaction with the system will have no effect on the future behaviour of the system and that there is no opportunity whatsoever of e.g. data poisoning.

Assessors:

NM: Is there any chance that this service will be maliciously used by paedophiles?

8.6 Any other comments?

[please fill in here]

9 Q9: Other Rights, user experience and Other concerns

What other rights might the object interfere with? Examples include: freedom of expression, intellectual property rights, personal freedom, freedom of information.

In this section you can also add any general comments regarding user experience including what it is like interacting with the object – is it rude or polite? Does it appear empathic or detached? Is it easy to get an indication of what it can do and what it should not be used for? Did you find yourself interacting with it in a different way than you would with a person? Is it unnerving to interact with it, and if so, why?

Guiding questions:

What is it like to interact with the object?

What other rights might the product interfere with?

Any other concerns?

9.1 What is it like to interact with the object (user experience)?

MS: The caller calls a medical helpline to seek advice with respect to their young child, possibly a newborn.

The first thing the user (a new user) expects is a recorded greeting explaining that “all nurses are currently busy” but “would you please hold on the line while first of them becomes available”, whereafter the user expects to spend several minutes waiting on the line, listening to pre-recorded music, at some points possibly interrupted by messages such as “your estimated waiting time is 2 minutes”. At least, that is the current practice in existing such helplines on Serbia, where the human medical expert eventually becomes available, takes over the call and listens to the user’s query, asking questions and offering advice. The duration of such calls can range from quite short (1 minute) to much longer (~10 minutes), depending on the query, the number of human operators and, possibly, number of callers currently waiting.

Instead, the user is greeted by the AI system, as explained in 7.8 (copied here for convenience):

“Hello, this is the helpline for young parents. All our staff are currently busy so while you’re waiting, you might let me collect some information about your inquiry. I am an AI system and I will not offer any advice to you, but I could help the nurses save time by collecting information for them so they can help you more efficiently once one of them is available. If you are not comfortable with me collecting this information, please just hold on the line, and if you are, please tell me what the problem is. Whatever you tell me I will not share with anyone else and you can even ask the nurse to erase your data when you get the advice you sought.”

The user may stay silent, whereupon the system may instruct the user to wait on (and possibly play pre-recorded music until any of the staff becomes available), or the user may engage in interaction such as described in 1.1, describing the situation, and answering to questions asked by the system through a natural language dialogue, with no restrictions. The user may choose what to say and what not, much as in communication with a human expert.

The system collects relevant information from the caller about the case (see Section 1.1), summarizes it with the aim to present it in a convenient visual form to the medical expert who takes over, so that the expert does not have to collect the same information all over again. The system never offers any advice itself, except that at some points it may quote from an authorized database of medical knowledge. Particularly, at a point when the system might feel that all the relevant information has been collected, it may say something like: *“All right, thank you, at this point I would not have anything more to ask. The nurse should be available quite soon (or: in __ minutes), and I can read to you what our medical literature says about similar situations. I quote: (E.g.) For babies age 1 month and older who are constipated, parents may try adding a small amount of water or fruit juice to the diet.”* Eventually, the system says something like: *“Oh, one of the nurses is available now.”* The nurse takes over the call, and says

something like: “OK, I see now, your 6-month-old, breastfed, has trouble with constipation, no stool passed for 3 days, right?”, they quickly agree on the situation and the nurse proceeds with giving the advice, asking further questions if necessary, eventually concluding the conversation. As suggested in 7.9, the nurse may ask the caller to have their personal data erased, or the system can erase it by default.

Assessors:

AP. The system serves the purpose of filling idle time (waiting time) with meaningful AI-powered conversations, primarily for input collection and summarization. As such, overall user satisfaction is expected to increase, since service delivery is sped up. Provided that the questions asked are structured effectively, clearly, and concisely, user experience should be rated high. The option to bypass the AI chat bot also contributes to an overall high user satisfaction, since users can opt to revert to conventional practices.

FO One consideration here is that potential out of domain answers may make the user upset and the truthfulness of the model will have a high impact on the actual result.

HMS: Agreeing with the two other assessors, the customer experience is going to depend entirely on how good the system is at understanding the caller and whether the caller gets the experience of being understood. As it is a high-stress situation the system could add to frustration or provide the positive experience of getting help straight away.

9.2 What other rights might the product interfere with?

MS: We see no other rights the system might interfere with.

Assessors:

HMS: The system may contribute positively towards the realization of the right to health in respect of one priority area (small children).

9.3 Any other concerns?

[please fill in here]

10 Q10: EU AI ACT compatibility

This checklist is intended to be carried out by the submitting partner only.

10.1 General purpose AI

	Yes	No
Does it have a wide range of possible uses (intended or unintended)?		X
Is it a foundation model (pre-trained model for other more specialised models)?		X
Is it a Large Language Model (LLM)?	X	
Does it handle more than one type of input?		X

10.1.1 If yes to any of the above:

	Yes	No
Was it trained using a total computing power of more than 10^{25} FLOPs?		(X), see Section 11.1
Does it provide a summary of copyrighted data used in training?		X
Does it disclose information downstream for the purposes of transparency?		X

10.2 Unacceptable Risk

	Yes	No
Does it conduct social scoring?		X
Does it exploit vulnerability of persons or otherwise manipulate?		X
Does it engage in Biometric categorisation of natural persons based on biometric data to deduce or infer their race, political opinions, trade union membership, religious or philosophical beliefs or sexual orientation?		X
Does it engage in emotion recognition?		X
Does it make use of or enable untargeted scraping?		X

10.3 High risk	Yes	No
Does it evaluate and classify emergency calls by natural persons or is it intended to be used to dispatch, or to establish priority in the dispatching of emergency first response services, including by police, firefighters and medical aid, as well as of emergency healthcare patient triage systems;	X (optional feature of the pilot is to track call priority), see Section 11.1	
Does it pose a significant risk of harm to the health, safety or fundamental rights of natural persons?		X
Is the object intended to be used together with heavy machinery, toys, land- or water crafts, explosives, radio equipment, pressure equipment, personal protective equipment, appliances burning gaseous fuels, medical equipment, civil aviation, agricultural vehicles, marine equipment or rail systems?		X

10.3.1 If yes to any of the above

	Yes	No
Has there been established a risk management system for the life cycle of the product?		X
Data governance: Has it been ensured that training, validation and testing datasets are relevant, sufficiently representative and, to the best extent possible, free of errors and complete according to the intended purpose.	X	
Is there technical documentation to demonstrate compliance and provide authorities with the information to assess that compliance?	X	
Is the system designed for record-keeping to enable it to automatically record events relevant for identifying national level risks and substantial modifications throughout the system's lifecycle?		X
Can you provide instructions for use to downstream deployers to enable the latter's compliance?	X	
Has the system been designed to allow deployers to implement human oversight?	X	
Is it designed to achieve appropriate levels of accuracy, robustness, and cybersecurity?	X	
Has a quality management system to ensure compliance been established?		X

Given your answers to the questions above, please formulate a conclusion as to any concerns with the object as is, as it may develop or otherwise. Each person filling out the questionnaire should formulate their own conclusion, and the chair of the panel will then formulate a consensus conclusion which will be shared with other members of the panel before communicating to the submitting partner.

11 Q11: Conclusions

11.1 Submitting partner

MS: In interpreting all answers provided above it should be kept in mind:

- that the system is now in the **design phase**
- that pilot owners are **not technology providers here** (except, maybe, in cases of ASR and TTS, which are relatively harmless from the point of view of ethical assessment)

which is why some answers may change over time.

11.2 Assessor 2 NM

Although the AI system has a lot of potential, to make it more compliant with EU values some questions could be reinforced: first, regarding the data collected and processed, although initially non-sensitive, it could end up identifying the data subjects. Thus, more emphasis should be put on the data collected, processed, the processing purposes and ensuring adequate information and consent from the data subjects. Second, the system could be subject to numerous biases which should be carefully assessed and mitigated. Finally, more information should be given to users to enhance the transparency of the system's use and design.

11.3 Assessor 3 AP

The system is meticulously designed to fulfill a clear and specific purpose: formulating questions, summarizing responses, and quoting/citing verified information pertaining to the issue at hand. By its very design, it inherently mitigates or minimizes many of the AI-related risks discussed earlier. However, the ethical and functional integrity of the system (its reliability, robustness, and trustworthiness) ultimately hinges on the quality and accuracy of its training datasets. Therefore, a rigorous and systematic vetting process for these datasets is paramount to ensure the system operates responsibly, ethically, and effectively.

11.4 Assessor 4 FO

FO the system faces significant ethical concerns since its purpose is to assist in taking critical decisions related to human health. Thus, its accuracy may impact:

- Human decisions on proper treatment
- Human emotions while interacting with a health service provider

Accuracy is more important in this case rather than data privacy and bias issues. As a low TRL product the above concerns are relaxed but should be monitored over time.

11.5 Chair of the assessment panel HMS, informed by all the comments given by other members of the panel

The Call centre for parents of infants pilot as described in this assessment is still in its planning stage which means that certain technical details have not yet been decided and cannot yet be tested. It is planned to be based on large language foundation models and speech recognition models finetuned with a second dataset consisting of 150 acted out dialogues between parents of infants with medical problems and a nurse of the call centre assisting them with their concerns. In addition to this, the system will also rely on a database of vetted medical knowledge about infants that it can quote from directly.

The system is intended to be incorporated in a call centre structure that already exists in Serbia and it is intended to work in the Serbian language. The intention of the pilot will be to make better use of the waiting time for parents when they call the help line where currently they are made to listen to pre-recorded music. The added value is both in the gathering of information for the nurse operator in an easy to overview format, and in the calming effect it will have on callers to be able to start the process of describing symptoms and getting their child better straight away when calling. In practice the nurse will check with the caller whether the information gathered is correct, effectively giving the caller two chances to ensure that all information is accurate which is of particular importance when medicating or treating young children.

As such the system carries the promise of limiting errors and thereby aiding in promoting the right to health for a vulnerable population group (young children). The help line also represents a low barrier access to healthcare which may be particularly attractive to families who are disadvantaged geographically, in terms of logistics and transportation or economically. This will be even more important in years to come as healthcare systems world wide are experiencing difficulties recruiting sufficient numbers of staff.

That said such a system can also risk interference with the rights of callers and patients. The assessors in this assessment **have** focused on these risks. Based on these assessments, here are the main risks along with proposed mitigations – keeping in mind that some mitigation techniques may already be planned on the part of the team and that certain design choices have not yet been made which may impact the best mitigation methods.

The risks can be divided into three overall types:

1. Risks emerging from errors or misunderstandings on the core functions of the system,
2. Risks emerging from malicious actors, and
3. Risks related to privacy and personal data.

The system as described in this assessment is intended to be set up with a range of mitigating measures to reduce these risks.

1. Risks related to the core functions;

There are two main functions planned for the system. The first is the summarization of core facts about the patient and their symptoms which are presented to the nurse operator, the second is the citing of advice from a vetted database of medical information about infants.

- a. Starting with the first function, the main risks emerge from misunderstandings if the system fails to correctly decipher the spoken language of the caller because of background noise, the use of dialects, slang or accents, or if it misinterprets the facts or symptoms described due to biases in the dataset or hallucinations. The function of summarization is less at risk of hallucinations than more creative generative uses. A related risk is what is known as anchoring and automation bias on the part of the human operator. This refers to the tendency of people to stick to and fail to question the first information they are given about a problem. This creates a problem if the system makes mistakes in the summarization or if callers struggle to interact with the system in a way that allows them to accurately describe all relevant symptoms and facts about the patient.

Suggested mitigations:

- Ensure that relevant dialects, accents, speech impediments, slang and loanwords from minority languages are present in the training data.
 - Training of operators including in the concepts of anchoring and automation bias to secure adequate human oversight
- b. As for the second function of providing medical advice by citing from a vetted database, the system is effectively secured against hallucinations given that it will be citing rather than generating outputs. Moreover, the system will incorporate warnings to the caller before providing the cited advice such as statements 'let's wait for the medical professional' and 'I'm not a doctor'. Nonetheless by citing from a database without incorporating the symptoms and facts about the patient, there is a risk of providing irrelevant or problematic advice. The most obvious example would be to cite general advice that would be fine for an older infant, but not for a newborn, the caller therefore failing to adjust suggested medicines to the weight or age of the infant, or general advice not being appropriate for children with specific birth defects, disabilities or other conditions. The risks of misunderstanding on the part of the caller is increased by the oral nature of the advice making it difficult for the caller to double check.

Suggested mitigations:

- In addition to the mitigations already proposed by the submitting partner, the system may incorporate a reference to the website where the caller can look up in the database themselves and may incorporate a warning that the advice is general and might not be relevant or appropriate for their child.

2. Risks posed by malicious actors

A system such as the one proposed could be subject to traditional data poisoning attacks, personal information extraction attacks and the like, although it is most likely, because of its oral nature and relative niche use not the most likely site of such attacks. More importantly the system could be misused by callers not being who they claim to be, callers illegally in possession of a child, or callers using the system for other purposes than to aid a child. Such examples could include calls from kidnappers or pedophiles and calls from carers or parents aiming to use the system because of disagreements or to establish false narratives about a child's injury or illness for reasons related to custody or evasion of responsibility. A call-in system as it exists, without the introduction of AI, could of course also be misused for such purposes. The added risk in the case of relying on AI therefore is related to the concept of anchoring, as a malicious caller may have a better chance to construct a credible narrative talking to a (non-suspicious) AI than to a real person, and the operator may then be anchored by that story and fail to question it when speaking to the caller.

Suggested mitigation:

- As under point 1, the suggested mitigation is related to the training of the operator in understanding and using the system, including in the problem of anchoring and automation bias. The dilemma here is that the human operator should be trained to detect malicious users but should not be perceived as suspicious by honest callers.

3. Risks related to privacy and personal data.

The system is designed to gather medical and personal information about a vulnerable individual (a child) who cannot consent for themselves. The caller in question will usually, but not in all cases be their parent or guardian. As such, the protection of such personal data is of phenomenal importance. Although the system is not intended to collect identifying data such as the patient's name, passport number or similar, there have been several cases of malicious actors re-identifying individuals based on other personal data. In this case information such as 'he was born 6 days ago' is almost as good as an ID in a country the size of Serbia. Moreover, the system may also be collecting information on the phone number used by the caller or the caller may volunteer their or their child's name without having been prompted.

There can be very good reasons to hold on to such information, and the call centre may already be doing that, for the purposes of establishing timelines in medical emergencies, to offer best help to repeat callers or to forward medical information to other specialists. In emergency situations (such as in the case of a kidnapping) authorities may also be monitoring such helplines for suspicious calls in the same way as emergency rooms can be contacted.

The important thing both legally and ethically, is that such information is stored safely and in a way that it cannot be leaked to the public or extracted by malicious actors. It is also important that it is not stored for any longer than necessary or used for any other purpose than what it was collected for. The call centre will already be subject to regulation regarding such data, but the addition of the AI raises additional concerns:

- one is the centralization of information which will happen naturally as the system collects the information making cross-referencing and re-identification easier,
- another is whether any medical data or recorded conversations will be used for improving the system and if so, what will be done to limit the risk of personal data becoming embedded in the model in a way that it can be extracted by malicious actors

Mitigation

- The deployers must make decisions about what data is kept and for what purpose and ensure that it is in line with all relevant legislation
- For data that will be used for training of human operators or improvement of the AI, consent must be obtained from the callers, and it must be ensured that the data cannot easily be reidentified
- Measures must be taken to ensure that any data used to improve the model does not become embedded in a way that allows for data leaks or is vulnerable to personal data extraction attacks.